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BUSINESS LOGISTICS IN MODERN MANAGEMENT

**Proceedings of the 24th International
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**JOSIP JURAJ STROSSMAYER
UNIVERSITY IN OSJEK**

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JOSIP JURAJ STROSSMAYER UNIVERSITY OF OSIJEK
FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS IN OSIJEK

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FOREWORD

It is with great pleasure that we present the *Proceedings of the 24th International Scientific Conference Business Logistics in Modern Management 2024 (BLMM2024)*. This conference remains a key platform for scholars and practitioners to explore and debate the challenges and advancements that are shaping the logistics and supply chain sector. The 2024 edition highlights some of the most pressing and transformative issues in logistics, from transportation innovations to sustainability, crisis logistics, and supply chain optimization.

With great honour and enthusiasm, the Faculty of Economics and Business at the Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek proudly continues to serve as the organizer of the international scientific conference BLMM 2024. The Organising Committee has received 31 papers submitted by authors from 10 countries (Czech Republic, Egypt, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, and Croatia). Finally, 25 papers successfully passed the international, double-blind review process and were presented during two days of the Conference. On the 3rd and 4th of October 2024, 54 distinguished researchers and academics assembled at this conference to share their knowledge, exchange ideas, and engage in discussions that seek to advance the boundaries of supply chain discipline. After thorough analysis, four selected papers were sent for potential publication in Springer's monograph titled *Digitalisation of the Greening Supply Chain*, which is going to be a part of the series: EcoProduction. Environmental Issues in Logistics and Manufacturing and one paper was sent to the scientific journal *Economic Thought and Practice/Ekonomska misao i praksa*.

The first chapter, *Transportation*, addresses the strategic role of logistics infrastructure in global trade and regional connectivity. It begins with an analysis of Constanta's hinterland connectivity, focusing on the potential of Ukrainian cereal exports to revitalize the region's transport network. Another paper provides an in-depth analysis of performance indicators for transport and storage in the European Union, which is crucial for measuring the efficiency and competitiveness of logistics operations. The chapter also explores the market potential of air cargo transport in the Czech Republic, offering new insights into opportunities for growth in this field. Lastly, the chapter concludes with a discussion of Romania's intermodal paradox and the role of Constanta Port in reviving rail transportation in the region.

In the second chapter, *Green, Humanitarian, and Crisis Logistics*, sustainability and social responsibility take center stage. The research explores how EU legislation is shaping the battery value chain through recollection, reuse, and recycling initiatives. It also examines the carbon footprint of student mobility, highlighting the environmental impact of commuting. Additionally, the chapter discusses the environmental effectiveness of reverse logistics in the wood biomass supply chain and the application of digital tools in humanitarian logistics management. The final study addresses inventory management challenges in crisis situations, with a focus on food retailers, providing valuable insights for improving supply chain resilience in times of uncertainty.

The third chapter, *Optimization in Supply Chain*, focuses on enhancing the efficiency and adaptability of supply chains. The studies presented here explore

logistics hub location strategies, the organization and operation of data-driven urban mobility, and the evolution of e-commerce warehouse supply chains in the context of Industry 4.0. The chapter also delves into customer demand variability, offering a comprehensive approach to understanding and managing it effectively. Further studies explore agile project management methods, with a specific focus on their application in supply chain contexts, and the challenges, solutions, and opportunities in wood biomass supply chains.

The final chapter, *Technological, Economic, and Social Aspects of Logistics*, examines the broader forces influencing logistics today. The application of digital twins in supply chain management is highlighted as a key innovation, offering new opportunities for efficiency and visibility across supply chains. The role of artificial intelligence in logistics is explored through a case study from the food industry, demonstrating the transformative potential of AI in supply chain operations. Other studies focus on the digitalization of logistics within the European Union and its impact on competitiveness, and the integration of socio-economic indicators to enhance resilience in critical transportation infrastructure. The chapter concludes with a study on the importance of logistics in enterprise development, underlining its strategic significance for business success.

We were honoured to welcome Mr. Peter Corfitsen as the keynote speaker for the BLMM 2024 Conference. In his lecture titled '*RGW as Enabler of Rijeka Becoming the Main Gateway to Central Europe's Logistics HUB*', Mr. Corfitsen provided an in-depth look at the pioneering technologies being integrated into the facility and provided a comprehensive breakdown of how this transformative project will position Rijeka as a leading logistics gateway for Central Europe.

As the logistics landscape continues to evolve, the research presented in these proceedings offers valuable insights and practical approaches to overcoming current challenges and seizing new opportunities. We extend our gratitude to all the contributors, researchers, and participants who have shared their expertise, to the reviewers for their remarkable efforts in ensuring the quality of the submissions, and to the organizing committee for making this event possible.

We hope that the proceedings of this conference will inspire further research and innovation in the field of logistics, helping both academia and industry to move forward together.

In Osijek, October 3rd, 2024.

Davor Dujak,
Editor

I. TRANSPORTATION

CONSTANTA'S GOLDEN HARVEST: LEVERAGING UKRAINIAN CEREALS TO REDESIGN ITS HINTERLAND CONNECTIVITY

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to investigate the accelerated modernization of Romania's Black Sea port of Constanta, triggered by the surge of Ukrainian cereal transit for export. Cargo volume dynamics (tonnage, TEU containers and ships) and the share of bulk cargo types (mainly cereals) at the ports of Constanta and Galati in the last 5 years (2019-2023) are analysed using descriptive statistics. The study uses actual datasets and examines the port's hinterland connectivity, providing a comprehensive overview of Constanta's pivotal role as a transshipment hub in conjunction with the Danube River port of Galati. The port of Constanta handled over 90 million tonnes of cargo in 2023, 44% more cereals than its volumes in 2021 and 53% more freight than its annual throughput 3 years ago. Findings are related to a very specific geopolitical context where cereal handling operations are highly prioritized, making study replicability its major limitation. The paper highlights the compound effect of targeted synergic public-private investments in strategic hubs (Constanta seaport terminals) and their hinterland connectivity (main railway lines and road sectors) to process increased freight volumes in a timely manner. Future research could seek to quantify correlations between the port's increased operational capacity, port operators' business metrics and potential further investments by logistics companies in managing expected additional cargo flows.

Keywords: Black Sea, dry bulk, port logistics, port infrastructure, Danube

1. INTRODUCTION

Constanta is one of the largest European multiproduct seaports, has one of the most capacious single-site cereal handling facilities and stands out as a major cereal transit hub at the Black Sea after Russia's invasion of Ukraine. The port's cargo traffic volumes are leveraged by its strategic location on the western coast of the Black Sea and logistics hub status for the surrounding region: it connects Europe with the South Caucasus, Central Asia and the Far East via the TRACECA corridor. Constanta Port is also a terminus point on the Pan-European transport corridors IV and VII, having main road, rail and river connections (Danube-Black Sea Canal). Rerouting cereals

from Ukraine since 2022 surged dry bulk cargo handling operations, the port is operating at full tilt ever since and is heavily congested, underlining the need for upgraded infrastructure investments.

Despite being a recurring challenge, Constanta Port's cargo handling throughput limitations were never addressed before being included on Romania and the EU's political agendas. Fast pace public investments within the port area and its hinterland to manage Ukrainian cereal inflows prompted a similar response from its terminal operators. The unexpected strategic importance of the issue translated into a major opportunity for the port's logistics service providers to generate substantial revenue growth and undertake long-delayed investment projects with their associated stakeholders.

The Danube indirectly connects the Black Sea to the North Sea and Atlantic Ocean through the Danube–Black Sea Canal and Rhine–Main–Danube Canal, an important inland waterway and river freight connection alternative between Eastern and Western Europe. Cargo volumes on the Danube only have a 9% share of freight traffic on European rivers, while the Rhine has 4 times more cargo volumes (2023), despite being more than 3 times shorter. Romania (25.1%) and Bulgaria (24.4%) also have the highest inland waterway modal shares within transport performance among Danube countries, significantly higher than Croatia (6.7%) or Hungary (5%).

Over a third (37%) of the Danube's navigable waterway (1,075 km) lies within Romania's borders and its 20 river ports. In addition to Constanta, partially unloaded maritime vessels can also be operated in 4 river ports in Eastern Romania: Galati (second largest Romanian port and largest river and seaport on the Danube), Braila (limit of the maritime sector of the Danube), Tulcea (riverine port) and Sulina (free port on the Sulina branch of the Danube) which also flows into the Black Sea. In 2021 the most important trade partners for Romania through the Danube River were: Serbia (41% of volumes), Bulgaria (18%) and Hungary (17%). In 2022 Ukraine ranked first (43%) with its unloading volumes accounting for 39%, more than Serbia's (26%) and Bulgaria's (10%) overall trade combined. This trend continued in 2023: Ukraine increased its share to 59% while its unloading volumes through the Danube-Black Sea Canal (52%) represent more than double those of Serbia (20%) and Austria's (6%) overall trade combined. Moldova's trade also reached 5%, mostly due to incoming cereals from the Ukraine (59%), exceeding Hungary's trade volumes and narrowly coming behind Austria.

The paper's objectives are to provide a comprehensive overview upon the scale of recent infrastructure development at Constanta Port and to give recommendations for improvement regarding its hinterland transportation network and connection to Galati, Romania's main Danube River port, spurred on by the inflow of Ukrainian cereals. This case study delves into the following research questions (RQ): How has the increase in Ukrainian cereal traffic at Constanta and Galati ports impacted their operational capacity and hinterland connections? (RQ1); can Constanta and Galati diversify their port operations to mitigate the risks of over-reliance on Ukrainian cargo and ensure long-term sustainability? (RQ2).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Constanta is ranked 7th by annual cargo tonnage volumes (2023) in Europe and is the most important Eastern European port. Bulk cargo and TEUs transit and distribution between CEE countries and Asia (Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, and China) leverages its role in supporting intermodal terminals (Tadic et al., 2021) and a more sustainable mix of hinterland connectivity alternatives (Notteboom et al., 2020).

A 51% year-on-year increase in cereal volumes (2023) meant Constanta's dry bulk terminals are bottlenecked, showcasing its shortcomings (Behdani et al., 2020), challenges of using available capacity to full extent (Li et al., 2023) and to design investment projects in improved cargo flows to increase future throughput (Kovac et al., 2023).

The Danube's recent increase in traffic volumes was spurred on additionally by the transit and export of Ukrainian cereals, especially through the Romanian section (Pourakbar & Zuidwijk, 2018). In 2021 overall cargo volumes on the river's network just exceeded 60 million tonnes, with the following years bringing new records: over 70 million tonnes (12% increase year-on-year, 2022) and over 80 million tonnes (15% increase year-on-year, 2023), according to preliminary data reports. The Ukraine's share in these volumes increased significantly after Russia's invasion, more than 5 times in volume and almost 4 times in share: from 5.51 million tonnes (8.7%, 2021), to 16.49 million tonnes (22.3%, 2022) and 29 million tonnes (33.5%, 2023). Only small vessels, up to 25,000 DWT, can transit Danube ports around Galati, while Sulina could only be partially operational in 2023, being a seaport with daytime navigation, adding further challenges (Backalic et al., 2015). Computerization, beaconing and signalling works were completed in 2023, allowing for round-the-clock navigation and doubling ship capacity (up to 10,000-12,000 tonnes/ship) in the Sulina port (a 60% increase in freight traffic is expected by the end of 2024). These figures confirm the complexity of issues that prevent cargo shifting from road to river (Mircetic et al., 2017), thus limiting development of inland waterway transport in Romania.

The EU's solidarity corridors for transit of Ukrainian cereals caused problems for farmers in Eastern Europe during the 2023 summer season, confirming the need for a more functional IWW network across its member states (Qasseer et al., 2023). Lower domestic harvest in Romania already decreased farmers' cost-competitiveness, no and/or low storage capacities meant selling at lower prices or at a loss, in addition to the issue of price volatility (Sternberg et al., 2022). Excess market supply decreased regular demand for own harvested raw materials, both domestically and on export markets, as a result of the imports from Ukraine. From marginal imports, the non-EU compliant, duty-free, dumping prices of Ukrainian cereals started to significantly distort internal market prices, validating the role of transparent data sharing within the sector and its LSPs (Szander et al., 2023).

Romania's landlocked neighbours, Hungary and Serbia, and Bulgaria saw their quantities shipped through the Port of Constanta steeply decline in the last 2 years (by 66%, compared to 2021) due to this fraught context, only partially confirming seaport-hinterland traffic correlations (Nguyen & Notteboom, 2019). Similar issues prompted more violent protests from farmers in Spain, Italy, Belgium or France at the end of 2023-beginning of 2024.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research uses secondary data on freight traffic (containers, tonnes, ships), most relevant cargo types (cereals, oil products and metal materials) and their shares in overall cargo volumes handled at Romania's Black Sea port in Constanta. Similar data is presented for the port of Galati, Romania's second largest seaport and largest port on the Danube River. Raw data was obtained from official European statistics databases, the National Institute of Statistics, port authorities' and sector-specific associations' reports and terminal operators' records, analysed, processed and compiled in the form presented in the current paper.

Descriptive statistics was used to examine dynamics, trends and patterns in time series analysis for the 2 ports' freight traffic data across the last 5 years (2019-2023). Year-to-year percentage variations, multi-year averages and relative share in total traffic of relevant cargo types were calculated to understand central tendency and variability of absolute cargo volumes. Initial data originally provided by some reports and records was not always congruent therefore additional research, adjustments and data cleaning were required to correct inconsistencies, source missing values (record matching, data retrieval, imputation and integration) and standardize units of measurement. Relevant other empirical data was aggregated (qualitative and quantitative mixed methods) to enable a broader understanding of the issues, challenges and shortcomings faced by the ports in light of the Ukraine-Russia context.

This study mainly employs descriptive statistics to analyse trends and patterns of freight traffic in the 2 analysed ports. By adding reliable data for validation, real-world metrics and inputs from both freight terminal operators and public authorities, further insights and additional added value were provided in this research. These datasets also allowed establishing causal relationships between variables, making it possible for most limitations of descriptive statistics to be mitigated. The research design itself might still have limitations, as it focuses only on specific types of cargo traffic and its related aspects, possibly neglecting other potentially relevant factors. Study replicability is improbable as current findings are related to a very specific geopolitical context where EU policies, governments and port authorities (Ukraine, Romania, Moldova), as well as freight forwarders (port terminal and rail freight operators, logistics service providers) have all synchronized to rapidly carry out investments and allocate resources to handle an unprecedented inflow of Ukrainian goods during peak season. The ever-changing political situation, availability of transportation alternatives, price volatility and interdependency of routing options further add to the complexity of the endeavour carried out in these 2 years (2022-2024).

4. RESULTS

The port achieved its third consecutive record yearly throughput (92.6 million tonnes, 2023), outlining a significant 22% year-on-year increase and 39% growth compared to 2019 as shown in Table 1. Cereals comprised 40% of the total cargo volume (36.3 million tonnes), which reflects a substantial rise of 51% compared to

the previous year. A significant portion of these cereals (14 million tonnes, 38%) originated from Ukraine. An average of 65 million tonnes of cargo were handled by the port between 2019-2021, with an important surge in the last 2 years: 11% in 2022 and 22% in 2023, increasing this average to over 72 million (2019-2023) and an overall growth of 39% in the last 5 years. TEU container (884,598 units in 2023, an overall 32% growth in the last 5 years) and ship traffic (4,705 units in 2023, an overall 12% growth in the last 5 years) had a similar dynamic after more static 2019-2021 levels.

Table 1 Port of Constanta – freight traffic volumes

year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	5-year average
ktonnes	66,603	60,375	67,483	75,537	92,693	72,538
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	<i>8,65</i>	<i>-9,35</i>	<i>11,77</i>	<i>11,93</i>	<i>22,71</i>	<i>+39.17</i>
TEU	666,036	643,725	631,946	776,590	884,598	720,579
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	<i>-0,30</i>	<i>-3,35</i>	<i>-1,83</i>	<i>22,89</i>	<i>13,91</i>	<i>+32.82</i>
ship traffic	4,176	4,031	3,985	4,498	4,705	4,279
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	<i>0.89</i>	<i>-3.47</i>	<i>-1.14</i>	<i>12.87</i>	<i>4.60</i>	<i>+12.67</i>

Source: Port of Constanta – Annual report, own processing

The Port of Constanța primarily handles bulk cargo, such as cereals and oil, which together make up over half (55.51%) of the total cargo tonnage (see Table 2). Cereals have increased their share of traffic by 7 percentage points (to 39.08%) over the last five years, reflecting its tonnage growth (+14.89 million tonnes) and 69.84% spike in 2023. Oil products average 15 million tonnes, except for the pandemic years, with a decreasing share (16.43%) in 2023, but an overall 6.31% upswing over the past five years. Iron and metal products also source a significant portion of cargo traffic (over 10 million tonnes/year in 2022-2023), averaging over 10% in share and experiencing a substantial growth of 36.91% since 2019.

The increase in cargo volumes at the Port of Constanta was also driven by the sudden surge of cereals from the Ukraine. Prior to Russia's invasion there were no exports of cereals from the Ukraine passing through the Romanian Black Sea port. Since 2022 the port's cereal terminals handled over 20 million tonnes: 8.6 million tonnes (35% share of total, 2022) and 14 million tonnes (40% share of total, 2023) from Ukraine, the equivalent of almost 1 million trucks, if hauled by road. 75% of Ukrainian cereals were exported to Asia and Africa in 2021 with China, Egypt and Turkey being the top 3 destinations. Last year however 70% were shipped towards the EU through Romania, Poland and Hungary (for Eastern Europe), Spain, Italy and Portugal (for Southern Europe) and The Netherlands (for Northern Europe).

Table 2 Port of Constanta – main cargo types handled

year/cargo [ktonnes]	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	average dynamic (2019-2023)
cereals	21,329	21,893	25,174	24,010	36,227	25,727
<i>share [%]</i>	<i>32.02</i>	<i>36.26</i>	<i>37.30</i>	<i>31.79</i>	<i>39.08</i>	<i>+69.84</i>
crude oil & oil products	14,323	11,680	12,153	16,714	15,228	14,020
<i>share [%]</i>	<i>21.51</i>	<i>19.35</i>	<i>18.01</i>	<i>22.13</i>	<i>16.43</i>	<i>+6.31</i>
iron ores, scrap & metal products	7,718	5,822	7,268	10,227	10,568	8,321
<i>share [%]</i>	<i>11.59</i>	<i>9.64</i>	<i>10.77</i>	<i>13.54</i>	<i>11.40</i>	<i>+36.91</i>
<i>top 3 share [%]</i>	65.12	65.25	66.09	67.45	66.91	+43.00

Source: Port of Constanta – Annual report, own processing

The sudden soar in handling Ukrainian cereals increased the dedicated terminal area's usual throughput, but queuing became constant and waiting times increased exponentially. Clogging up access roads to the cereal terminals (see Figure 1) brought about congestion issues and idling times at other cargo terminals as well, outlining the need for port infrastructure to be extended to further handle the upcoming traffic. Figure 1 shows a map of the port's cargo terminals, with cereals being handled on both sides, North and South, similar to TEU containers. Oil, iron and metal products are only handled in the Constanta North area, whereas Midia (oil products) and Mangalia (general cargo) provide additional terminals.

Total cereal storage capacity is at around 1.8-2 million tonnes, but the storage silos are not meant for more than short-term storage (temporary). This means that cereal handling operations are constant, loading-unloading of trucks and ships is continuous. Loading a cargo ship of 50,000-65,000 tonnes requires 40 trains (1,500 tonnes/train), 50 inland waterway barges of 1,200-1,500 tonnes/barge or 1,000 trucks (25-28 tonnes/truck), on average. Dry bulk cargo terminals have a maximum loading/unloading capacity of 3,200-4,200 tonnes/hour (silos-ship), cereal storage buffer with a maximum capacity ranging 100,000-300,000 tonnes and can fully load a ship in under 4 days. One of the port's cereal terminals, with road, rail and sea inflows, has an average throughput of 90,000 tonnes/month and loads 30,000 tonne ships with 15 barges (2,000 tonnes/barge) for the Port of Rotterdam. During peak season however up to 600 barges loaded with cereals were waiting to be unloaded in the Constanta port area (up to 30-40 days, 2023), exceeding terminals' capacities. The berth's capacity was recently increased (up to 200,000-250,000 tonnes/month) to improve handling and reduce unloading/loading waiting times.

Figure 1 Port of Constanta – map of cargo terminals

Source: Port of Constanta, own processing

According to the Constanta Port Business Association its 20 cereal terminals (North and South) are operated by 13 port operators and can accommodate up to 40 million tonnes/year, as of 2024. Half of them are using a digital system for customs statements (processing time: 30 minutes, from 48 hours previously) and traffic management controlled access software systems that can process around 100-200 trucks/day per terminal. Some terminal operators have a maximum standard processing time of 35 seconds/incoming truck. Simultaneous unloading capacity ranges between 1-3 trucks for smaller terminals to 4-6 trucks for modern terminals with handling usually taking, on average, under 30 minutes/truck for unloading and 15 minutes/truck for waiting and queueing. Bad weather (wind) can increase unloading time (up to 2 hours), congestion can delay incoming trucks (up to 1 hour of waiting time), lowering actual processed cargo volumes. Port security and its related operational efficiency are still lenient, posing risks for transit cargo and the EU's Schengen Area requirements. The Black Sea coast surveillance system lacks proper maintenance despite Romania's admission to the maritime Schengen zone in March 2024. The securing of the Black Sea border technology is not functional at its intended full capacity and ongoing filed appeals are delaying its re-engineering process. Cargo scanning is not modern (Constanta South-Agigea), only risk-prone containers are duly checked (around 12,000 TEUs, 2023) and customs clearance authorities' offices are not organized as a one-stop shop, increasing handling time for freight forwarders. An overview of the port's features is provided in Table 3.

Truck access through the A4 is struggling to keep up with demand, sometimes causing delays (over 300 trucks), long queues (up to 10 km of blocked lane) and excessive idling times (up to 4 days) upon entry in the port. In less than 6 months incoming volumes quadrupled from 822,000 tonnes in April to over 3 million tonnes in August 2023. The average lead time for unloading cereals has increased exponentially (up to 12 hours, 2023) in the last 2 years (from 2 hours, 2021). This

backlog is due to the truck throughput not being able to match the surge in incoming cereal shipments from Ukraine (39% of all cargo operations, 2023). Specialized terminal operators invested in extending their own facilities with more silos, whilst the port also built a new unloading area and storage facility (in months), increasing overall cereal handling capacity. During the peak season, on average, between 450-600 trucks deliver cereals from Ukraine, via Sighetu Marmatiei and Siret borders, to Constanta. These same trucks then have to collect locally harvested quantities and deliver them to the port. For most regular delivery routes this means transportation costs/tonne increased by 60-70%, on average, during summer months with Romanian producers struggling to ship their harvest quickly to prevent further price increases. With the cheaper agricultural imports with lower quality from Ukraine (estimates show 40% of grain harvest escapes taxation through fraudulent schemes) competing on the same market and swaying market shares, farmers started protesting in Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia. Around 45,000 trucks, only with Ukrainian cereals, arrived in 2023 in Constanta, but most facilities and utilities are not modernized or even inadequate. The port's infrastructure is not primarily designed to handle such an intense traffic flow via road, especially since most incoming cargo shipments, not only for cereals, arrive by truck. In addition, general port access is not done via an automated software system, creating confusion, traders' trucks arrive without having prior scheduled ships available for loading and with storage capacities already full, they wait in the port area (no parking area is available), further congesting traffic flow. Despite shortcomings, all cereals harvested from Romania (22 million tonnes) were processed at Constanta Port by the end of 2023, albeit with lower profit margins for local producers during the summer season. Starting summer 2024 Romanian harvested cereals will have separate handling flows following completion of cargo operator's terminal extension projects. The port's road connectivity is thus operational, but in need of investments to improve current inflow of trucks and in-house traffic management.

Table 3 Port of Constanta – infrastructure and intermodal features

Port infrastructure	Operations management
<u>Port facilities:</u> Constanta terminal: sea and river port 15 km of breakwater (North and South) South breakwater: needs extension investment in Pier III and IV (for oil, containers and cereals) 140/156 operational berths (89%) 32km of quay length (depth: 7-19m) Midia terminal: oil products Mangalia terminal: general cargo Tomis terminal: passengers	<u>Port facilities:</u> cargo (multiproduct), operating at full tilt (congested) cereal storage capacity: 2 million tonnes dry bulk terminals (cereals): 20 loading capacity: 3,200-4,200 tonnes per hour and a cargo ship in under 4 days (per terminal) traffic management: 200 trucks/day with automated AI software with RFID (owned by terminal operator), but no operational port-owned software
<u>Road connectivity:</u>	<u>Road connectivity:</u> heavily congested (high waiting times) occasionally

<p>100 km of road (within port premises) and connections: Bucharest-Constanta (A2, 203 km) and Constanta By-Pass (A4, 22 km) Port Community System: not functional, manually issued order entry tickets, lack of automated systems</p>	<p>A4 highway: heavy congestion during summer season and peak hours (truck queue: 300+ trucks, 10+ km or 2-3 days of waiting prior to port access) Parking & services (trucks): not functional yet (only public toilets)</p>
<p><u>Railway connectivity:</u> 326 km of railway (59 km own, 18%) 367 railway lines (45 private, 12%) 72/99 modernized railway lines (72%) 110/126 switch machines were modernized (2023) 7 level crossings modernized (2024) 2 marshalling yards (Palas, Valu lui Traian) for traffic management with 25 railway lines (MOD due 2027)</p>	<p><u>Railway connectivity:</u> underutilized 256 km of railway (owned by CFR) 97 railway line heavily degraded (30%) 35 railway lines (14 km) need MOD 75 switch machines need MOD 780 stationary train cars (300 beyond repair, 38%): blocked on railway marshalling yards: only 5/25 functional lines (20%), all others are currently useless (closed since 2011)</p>
<p><u>Other:</u> formalized Black Sea port security: present cargo scanning: outdated (1 fixed scanner, used since 2006, only risk-prone containers verified: 12,000 such units in 2023) coast surveillance system: security requirements (currently non-compliant)</p>	<p><u>Other:</u> operational risks port security: lax and neglectful (due to under capacity) cargo scanning: current scanner is in breakwater South, none in breakwater North (convoy needed) customs: clearance/control authorities' offices: spread across port</p>

Source: Port of Constanta, own processing

Constanta is mainly designed as a seaport with railway access, but only 1 railway line (3% of total) was operational before rerouting cereals from the Ukraine. Rusty wagons were blocking the port's tracks in 2022 and railway works were stalled, highly doubting its reduced overall logistics capacity could handle the estimated 50% increase in dry bulk cargo volumes and be used as an alternative route for Ukrainian grain transit. Aggregate data for 2022 showed 2-3% of GDP was lost due to the Port of Constanta's inability to handle a higher amount of incoming traffic flows from Ukraine. Only 18% of railway is owned by the port and 12% by the port operators, the rest is owned by the national railways company (CFR). 256 km of railway and most railway lines (97/322) owned by CFR are heavily degraded (30%) and need important investments. Since 2023 however some investments were made, part of a project, to improve rail infrastructure within the port area and help reduce intense road congestion caused by excessive truck inflows: modernized railway lines, switch machines and level crossings. All railway lines and switch machines need modernization for the railway system to partially start diverting traffic away from road. In the first months of re-routing cereals on railway, private railway operator GFR shipped 250,000 tonnes of cereals with 1,000 wagons to the Black Sea Port. Transit time from Dornești to Constanța was 50 hours, but queueing at port entry was even longer (waiting time: 60 hours) until the wagons could be unloaded (within 24

hours maximum), on average. Transit to Curtici Cargo Center intermodal terminal at border with Hungary takes at least 20-34 hours running time, with most freight trains needing up to 3 days. During high season (summer months) when priority is given to passenger trains and/or when railway line repairs are scheduled freight trains could even need 7-12 days, depending on carried tonnage, to complete the full journey due to the many restrictions (hundreds) limiting overall speed to below 5 km/h and several stopping times (taking the siding and waiting) along the way. This is one of the main reasons why road freight (68%) is still largely preferred over rail freight (12%). 35 railway lines were urgently rehabilitated (total duration: 5 months), other 64 lines (28 km of tracks) are still under execution, 112 operate with restrictions whilst 100 are closed down (2023). Half of the wagons are moved out, the other half is rusted to the lines, awaiting to be temporarily moved out of the way for the railways lines to be cleared of abundant weeds and then repaired. Ongoing projects sometimes require dismantling old tracks, reconstructing the embankment, moving track switches and installing new tracks, but progress is slow because of 144 wagons blocking the tracks and reconstruction works. A modernization project for Valu lui Traian marshalling yard (35 km of railway, including 32 electrified reception and dispatch tracks and the connection to M800 Bucharest-Constanta) has been approved and is due by 2027. A record number of 300 km of railway modernizations (delayed, 70-80% already executed) is due by the end of the year (2024). Increased cargo volumes at Constanta Port have triggered railway investment projects with private port and logistics operators being already prepared to offer rail freight intermodal alternatives (2024), but limited modernization of state-owned railway tracks is still insufficient to handle and operate even current cargo flows at a competitive operational level.

More than half of Ukraine's cereal production was exported in the last 2 years: 48.4 million tonnes (of 87 million harvest, 55%) in 2022 and 49 million tonnes (of 80 million harvest, 61%) in 2023. A third of these exports are shipped through the Port of Constanta, mostly by barges and ships (over 90%), being a 4 times cheaper alternative than the Black Sea Grain Initiative (BSGI), meant as a temporary deal (2022-2023) for the safe export of Ukrainian grain and other foodstuffs through the Black Sea, despite the ongoing war. Almost 80% of Ukrainian cereal shipments and freight arrive by sea, whereas 15% of cargo volumes transit through the Danube River. An overview of the cargo flows on the Danube River in Romania is provided in Table 4.

Table 4 Romanian ports on the Danube River – overall cargo volumes

year	2021	2022	dynamic [%]	2023	dynamic [%]	2023/2021 dynamic [%]
tonnes on [millions]	32.120	28.620	-10.9	32.102	+12.2	-0.05
tkm [billions]	13.52	10.75	-20.4	11.94	+11.1	-11.6
tonnes through [millions]	17.289	17.265	-0.1	23.364	+35.3	+35.1
international, o/w [millions]	12.324	14.541	+17.9	20.467	+40.7	+66.1
share [%]	71.2	84.2	+13.0 pp	87.6	+3.4 pp	+16.4 pp
international, tkm [billions]	7.48	6.50	-13.1	8.55	+31.5	+14.3
share [%]	55.3	60.4	+5.1 pp	71.6	+11.2 pp	+16.3 pp
total ships	25,088	25,739	+2.6	32,696	+27.0	+30.3
international, o/w	8,395	9,749	+16.1	15,334	+57.3	+82.6
share [%]	33.4	37.8	+4.4 pp	46.9	+9.1 pp	+13.5 pp

Source: Maritime and River Danube Ports Administration, own processing

Traffic on the Romanian Danube in the last 2 years has been increasing, despite its overall state not being fully prepared to handle such an abrupt surge in activity. Cargo volumes through the river have increased by over 35% since 2021 to 23.3 million tonnes with more than 87% international traffic (2023), an increase of over 16 percentage points over the last 2 years on the Danube-Black Sea Canal. More than half of cargo and almost two thirds of all handled cereals come from Ukraine. The number of ships on the river has also increased by over 30% (32,696 ships, 2023) since the invasion of Ukraine, as a result of increased international traffic and foreign ship operators on the Danube (82.6%, 2023). Since Russia's invasion of Ukraine ships transporting goods on the Danube more than doubled in Sulina: from 1,823 ships in 2021 to 4,285 ships, similar to aggregate volumes (2,003 ships (2021) to 3,815 ships (+90% in 2022) and 4,523 ships (+18% in 2023) on Chilia and Sulina Canals. Cargo volumes more than tripled on the Sulina Canal: from 5 million tonnes in 2021 to almost 16.5 million tonnes in 2023 with 47% being cereals, of which 78% originating from Ukraine. Loading a larger ship of 100,000 tonnes could take up to 2 months (2022) since it required 11 convoys of 6 inland waterway barges of 1,500 tonnes/barge or 9,000 tonnes/convoy and an operating time of 6-8 days/convoy, on average. Ukrainian cereal shipments compete with those from the lower Danube countries (Bulgaria, Serbia, Hungary and/or Croatia), in addition to Romania, for dispatch slots at Port of Constanta.

Galati, Braila and Tulcea ports accounted for more than 10 million tonnes of cargo handled in the last 2 years, but after 7.35 million (2022), their activity was rerouted and decreased by 48% to only 3.8 million tonnes (2023). High ship traffic exceeded port handling capacity creating congestion on the Sulina Canal, waiting times increased and so did shipping and freight insurance costs. The lack of capacity

at the 3 main Danube ports thus shifted cereal volumes such as corn, wheat and sunflower towards trains and trucks. Freight traffic in Romania's main ports on the Danube (Galati, Braila and Tulcea) is nevertheless expected to increase by around 15-20% by the end of 2024. Drobeta-Turnu Severin, Giurgiu, Oltenita and Medgidia are the other 4 main ports located on the European TEN-T railway network corridor (RFC Rhine-Danube (RDN) corridor/CORR 9), but their use is limited. A map with an overview of the location of these ports is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Danube River – main seaports (blue) and river ports (red) in Romania

Source: Maritime and River Danube Ports Administration, own processing

Cargo traffic on the Danube has increased to over 32 million tonnes (+12.2%, 2022), but only has a 6.80% share in overall freight volumes (2023). This is mainly due to the state of the Danube's poor infrastructure or lack of proper maintenance, reducing its annual capacity availability in Romania, as only 25% of cargo volumes are destined for its inland river ports. Widening and, especially, deepening the navigable channel (depth: too low for navigating 40-70 days/year) to allow large tonnage ships to transport goods from Constanta Port to Austria or Germany would increase traffic and make the Danube a more competitive freight alternative. A convoy of 4 barges carrying 7,000 tonnes of cargo by river is equivalent to transporting the same load with 280 trucks by road or 170 train cars by railway. Low depth (droughts

in summer) and/or the risk of floods (more common in recent years), polluted waters (littering) and/or even large-scale industrial pollution make Romania's section of the Danube the dirtiest (Everwave report, 2022) as well as scarce interconnected railway lines at its river ports, including limited intermodal transportation options, are some of the Danube's main issues in Romania.

The main ports on the Danube River have invested in increased operational capacity with new terminals and berths as well as improved handling and processing capability, reducing waiting times for loading/unloading ships and barges. Some sections (12) are in need of dredging for a minimum depth of 2.5m, with 3 of these being capital because alluvium is constantly being deposited close to the ports of Bechet between Calafat and Corabia, Belene and Popina on the Bulgarian side. Works are also needed on the maritime Danube (Braila-Sulina) to ensure a navigation depth of at least 7m all year round. The Fast Danube project to increase depth, improve navigation conditions and traffic safety, funded by the EU's CEF (Connecting Europe Facility) transport program could increase navigability by at least 60 days/year and more than 20% compared to current standards, making the river effective for around 340 days/year.

According to the Ukrainian Sea Ports Authority (USPA), 21% more goods were handled last year in all ports (62 million tonnes), whilst over 29 million tonnes of cargo (46% share of total) were handled only in Ukraine's Danube ports in 2023, a second consecutive record freight volumes. Most of the 14,031 ships on the Danube were operated in the port of Izmail (20 million tonnes and 9,324 vessels, 66%), Reni (3,858 vessels and almost 30% of cargo volumes) and Ust-Dunaisk (849 vessels and almost 5% of total cargo) handling the difference. Danube traffic almost doubled compared to 2022, with 16.49 million tonnes, an overall 75% year-on-year increase, with more than 56 million tonnes of overall traffic being exported (90% of total), of which cereals account for 45.5 million tonnes and 81% share (2023). Almost 12 million tonnes of cargo from the Ukraine was handled through Romanian river ports (11.83 million tonnes), while over 75% of its 8,171 ships hauled cereals (6,165 ships, 2023). Ukrainian cargo volumes shipped via seaports, on the other hand, decreased: Odessa (8.41 million tonnes, +9.3% compared to 2022), Yuzhny (10.08 million tonnes, -34%) and Chernomorsk (11.41 million tonnes, -0.3%). Nevertheless, a total of 23 new transshipment points are operational and 15 investment projects are currently underway in Ukrainian ports, as of 2023.

Cereals from Ukraine have also been subject to complex tax-avoiding schemes through dubious shell firms (liquidated companies, unclear ownership, proxies and multinational corporations) and Ukrainian customs service suspicions of corruption. Unusually low prices (40-80% lower than regular market price) and farmers' protests lead to a temporary import ban from the EU in summer of 2023, which was lifted in autumn. During the import ban, official data from Romania showed 0.3% of Ukrainian cereals still entered the country. Unofficial data suggests around 2.5-3.5% more smuggled cereals transited Romania during the peak months of 2022 and 2023 or a combined yearly average of up to 1.5%. An increased flow of grain ships through ports in the Odesa region (Chornomorsk, Odesa and Yuzhny/Pivdennyi) and new tax avoidance (undeclared harvest, falsified documents, fictitious intermediary companies, barter and cash payments) prevention mechanisms in the first trimester of

2024 also meant slightly lower volumes through Constanta Port (-44%). This backlog was compensated after spring as April had record export levels, an increase of 24% year-on-year, regular shipments resumed, with an extra inflow redirected from Poland after farmers blocked border crossings. Overall traffic is nearing last year's record levels, as estimates show a 15% increase in harvest and export volumes is expected by end of 2024.

Cargo traffic through the main Danube ports (Galati, Braila, Tulcea) decreased by 26% to 7.34 million tonnes (2022) from 9.93 million tonnes of goods a year before, with the port of Galati having almost two-thirds of the share (62.81%) in overall volumes (see Table 5).

Table 5 Romania's main sea ports on the Danube – overall cargo volumes

year	2021	2022	dynamic [%]	2023	dynamic [%]	2023/2021 dynamic [%]
total tonnes [millions]	9.93	7.34	-26.1	3.86	-47.41	-61.12
Port of Galati	6.18	4.61	-25.4	2.38	-48.37	-61.48
share [%]	62.23	62.81	+0.58 pp	61.65	-1.16 pp	-0.58 pp
maritime [%]	41.31	45.99	+4.68 pp	60.17	+14.18 pp	+18.86 pp
river [%]	58.69	54.01	-4.68 pp	39.83	-14.18 pp	-18.86 pp
total ships [units]	3,773	3,943	+4.51	2,796	-29.08	-25.89
Port of Galati	2,473	1,972	-20.25	1,804	-8.51	-27.05
share [%]	65.54	50.01	-15.53 pp	64.52	+14.52 pp	-1.02 pp

Source: Maritime and River Danube Ports Administration, own processing

The inland waterway transit volumes are more severely impacted (-41.3%) than maritime traffic (-34%) in all three ports due to the Russia-Ukraine conflict disrupting regular supply chain flows through the Sulina Canal and reconfiguring routes by road and/or rail due to the rising shipping costs: increase in fuel prices and maritime insurance premiums. Liberty (former ArcelorMittal) Galati is the largest integrated steel producer in Romania with a maximum capacity of 3 million tonnes of steel/year for the construction, shipbuilding, oil and gas, automotive industry, transportation and renewable energy sectors. With 5,000 employees, the steel mill is the second largest energy consumer in Romania and produced a record 2.35 million tonnes of liquid steel in 2021 (78% of its maximum capacity and 38% more than its average yearly levels) with 60% of its volumes being exported.

The activity of the Liberty steel mill in Galati experiences major disruptions in its supply of raw materials and finished product shipments. Hindered supply of raw materials like iron ore and/or coal to the steel mill lead to several production slowdowns, shutdowns and even shortages, affecting export of finished goods (3.06 million tonnes and -38.6%, 2022) to its customers through its dedicated terminal in the port of Galati. Steel production capacity at Liberty plunged following the ban on raw material imports and exports from Russia. Rising energy costs, from 8% to 40%

per tonne of steel, also lead to an increase in the prices of its finished products and to the repeated shutdown of a blast furnace for various maintenance and repair works, impacting output. Due to recent inflation and rising costs for raw materials, services and GHG statements, the steel mill's current production levels are well below 2 million tonnes. The ore terminal with a maximum capacity of 20 million tonnes/year is operated by Romportmet, accounts for most (66-80%) of Galati's volumes (4.99 million tonnes, 2021) and is Liberty's dedicated import-export handling hub. The Mineralier ore terminal was thus heavily impacted by the reduced activity of Liberty Steel Galati and only handled 1.18 million tonnes (61.4% decrease, 2023) and traffic volumes plummeted: 70% decline on inland waterways and 50% on maritime.

The other 2 terminals, Bazinul Nou and Docuri, increased their volumes by an aggregated 13.1% in 2022 and then decreased by 40.4% in 2023, but their contribution in overall port dynamics is marginal compared to the Mineralier ore terminal. These terminals handle cereal imports from Ukraine, in addition to rolled steel, scrap metal and quarry product exports (Turkey, Bulgaria, Ukraine). Unicom Oil Terminal tripled its volumes to 431,108 tonnes of diesel fuel and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) handled from Ukraine, Turkey, Greece and Egypt (2022) and also increased its cargo traffic by 6% to 457,746 tonnes in 2023. Works for modernizing dock 32 meant lower output in 2023 for the port, but the higher handling capacity which will increase operational activity by 2024. In the first trimester of 2024 overall handling volumes increased by 14% year-on-year, driven by the steel mill's higher production (20% increase for the first 3 months).

5. DISCUSSION

Rerouting Ukrainian cereals through Constanta has forced overdue public and private investments in Romania's Black Sea port. Mainly dry bulk handling capacity has increased, but intra-port and hinterland upgrades benefit all terminal operators. The inflow of cereals also lead to oil and TEUs positive dynamic, overall liquid bulk and intermodal shipment growth being due to improved operational flow. Fast pace road and railway works enabled Constanta's streamlined operations to support growing cargo volumes by better leveraging its idle resources. Excess influx was directed to Galati, where the port also struggled to handle the unexpected surge. Its alternative route through the Danube diverted a part of traffic from Constanta and accelerated some of its overdue public hinterland investments.

Danube ports around Galati encounter the risks induced by the war, including higher transportation costs and compounded waiting times for transiting the Sulina Canal (other freight traffic), as well as a shift towards trucking for cereal distribution from Ukraine. Currently, the number of large ships is low due to the limited number of specialized berths located at deep water, such is the number of companies with technical equipment capable of handling large quantities of goods in a short time. Ukrainian cereal inflow thus had an indirect impact on Constanta and Galati ports (RQ1): their increased operational capacity and improved hinterland connections is a result of recent public and private investments, triggered nevertheless by the geopolitical context. This also aligns with takeaways from some of other authors'

relevant work, related to the role of public authorities (Pourakbar & Zuidwijk, 2018) in working through industry-specific challenges (Mircetic et al., 2017) and providing indirect support for terminal operators (Li et al., 2023). Both Romanian seaports can leverage the current context to increase their strategic role in trade relations between the EU and Asia by increasing their port throughput (Behdani et al., 2020), while also concurring to EU's sustainable transportation targets (Notteboom et al., 2020).

Attracting new trade flows would avoid the ports' risk of being over-reliant on these goods, but requires further infrastructure modernizing, digitizing operations and reducing the fees charged by their administration body. Building new port terminals, expanding berths, deepening navigation channels, and improving port facilities for cargo handling are main target areas in Galati. A dedicated barge terminal would increase the traffic of cereals, fertilizers, oilseeds and solid mineral fuels, goods that are typically transported by barge. Digitizing port operations and activities, implementing cargo flow automation solutions and connecting the public and private port community are essential in Constanta, as also indicated by similar other works (Szander et al., 2023). An implemented Port Community System (PCS) streamlines activities and processes and reduces turnaround times, integrating companies along the supply chain faster. Computerized road traffic management solutions, coupled with creating parking spaces adjacent to ports would significantly decongest road traffic within both ports. The extent to which Constanta and Galati will diversify their port operations depends on intra-port, terminal and hinterland investment projects (RQ2): on-time project completion and public-private collaboration to continue current momentum will ensure long-term sustainability. This is in accord with similar other authors' views (Qasseer et al., 2023) on how inland ports from Eastern Europe should develop more resilient and sustainable transportation systems.

Highly prioritized cereal traffic from Ukraine in current geopolitical context is the paper's major limitation, as study replicability is unlikely. In addition, the compound effect of targeted synergic public-private investments in strategic logistic hubs has a broader implication in practice, exceeding the paper's outlined short-term gains.

6. CONCLUSION

Water transportation is a strategic sector in the EU, especially in view of a more sustainable modern transport mix and its current status quo: more than 80% of the EU's external trade and 40% of the EU's internal trade is performed via waterways. One of the EU policy's objectives is to transfer 25% of the cargo volumes from road transport to inland waterways by 2030. IWW competitiveness and share in total transportation will increase through improved connectivity projects across the EU by integrating railway infrastructure and providing efficient intermodal transportation alternatives.

Constanta Port had record cargo traffic in 2023, its third consecutive year of record throughput being enabled by capacity extensions in its Black Sea terminals and hinterland connections (37% increase since 2021) boosted by incoming transit of Ukrainian cereals (44% increase since 2021), similar projects being started along the

Danube River and its main port of Galati. Romania has taken over for transit approximately 45 million tonnes of freight, mostly cereals (25.5 million tonnes, 63%) exported through Constanta Port (40 million tonnes, 88% of total), the main gateway for Ukrainian cargo after Russia's aggression in 2022. Sea traffic at the port of Constanta increased by 18% to around 70 million tonnes (76% of total cargo, 2023) with river traffic through the Danube spiking at over 23 million (40% increase in cargo freight handled). Around 95% of cereals arrive and are further shipped through maritime transportation on the Black Sea, the rest is routed via road, rail or the Danube River. In 2021 river transportation via the Danube was used for only 6% of the total cargo transported at EU level, from a share of 9% in 2011. Romania's stretch of the Danube had very low competitiveness prior to the war in Ukraine, as the port fees for operating in Galati, largest port on the Danube, were 46% higher than in Odessa (Ukraine) and 54% higher than in Bulgarian ports of Burgas and Varna.

Recent public and private investments in the ports, terminals and berths of Galati, Braila and Constanta have doubled Romania's cereal handling capacity to around 4 million tonnes/month (as of 2024). Other port investments are under way or planned for Giurgiu (cargo capacity increase by 75,000 tonnes/year, operational since 2024), Ovidiu (new port, due 2025) and Galati (new multimodal platform with a 150,000 TEU/year capacity, due 2025). Despite shifting flows of Ukrainian imports between different transportation modes (sea, river, road and/or rail) in the last 2 years, port operators and freight forwarders have had record profit figures. The geopolitical context means that public and private sectors in Romania are finally working together in a coordinated and sustained manner for the first time in more than 30 years: investing in capacity extensions, infrastructure development and modernizing strategic transportation hubs in order to support Constanta Port's inbound and outbound logistics. Current efforts are focused on handling transit of Ukrainian cereals, but the modernized seaport (Constanta, Galati) and inland waterway (Giurgiu, Drobeta-Turnu Severin) terminals and main railway lines (M200, M300, M500) will contribute to an improved and more sustainable modal split of the transportation sector in the upcoming years.

Future research topics could investigate the ports' intra-logistics metrics, port operators' handled cargo volumes and financial performance and further investments in terminals. Hinterland traffic dynamics, correlated with railway connectivity, could also be studied in medium and/or long-term horizons.

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ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF TRANSPORT AND STORAGE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

Transport and storage performance research is challenging, current, significant, and complex. Based on that, this study assesses the performance of transport and storage in the European Union. The conducted research on the positioning of the transport and storage performance of the countries of the European Union using the LMAW-DNMA method in this study showed that Italy is in the first place, and Malta is in the last place. The top five countries of the European Union in terms of transport and storage performance are, in order: Italy, France, Poland, Spain, and the Netherlands. Germany ranks sixth in terms of transport and storage performance in the European Union. The leading countries of the European Union have positioned themselves well in terms of transport and storage performance. In the European Union, in terms of transport and storage performance, Croatia is in twenty-first place, and Slovenia is in twenty-second place. Slovenia is worse positioned than Croatia. The key performance factors of transport and storage are economic and political climate, economic activity, number and size of companies, number of employees, turnover, added value, employee costs, investments, coronavirus pandemic COVID-19, logistics costs, types of transport and storage, integrated models transport, energy crisis, and others. An efficient control system of critical factors significantly contributes to the achievement of the target performance of transport and storage in the European Union. A significant role in this is undoubtedly played by the digitization of the entire transport and storage business.

Keywords: performance, transport and storage, European Union, LMAW-DNMA method

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of evaluating transport and storage performance is challenging, continuously current, important, and complex (Kara, 2022; Zhang & Wei, 2023;

Zavadskas et al., 2012; Hadžikadunić et al., 2023). Because the performance of transport and storage is maintained on the performance of all other sectors, and the entire economy. Bearing that in mind, the subject of research in this study is the analysis of factors of performance positioning of transport and storage in the countries of the European Union. The goal and purpose of this is to investigate the given problem as complex as possible to improve the performance positioning of the transport and storage of the European Union countries in the future by taking adequate measures. Recently, to assess the performance of all sectors as precisely as possible, which includes transport and storage, various multi-criteria decision-making methods are increasingly being applied in the literature (Lukić & Hadrović, 2021, 2022, 2023; Tadić et al., 2021; Ulutas et al., 2021; Osintsev, 2021; Saaty, 2008; Popović et al., 2022; Iao et al., 2022; Đalić et al., 2020; Kovač et al., 2021; Miškić et al., 2021; Puska et al., 2021; Stević & Brković, 2020; Stević et al., 2020; Stanković et al., 2020; Trung, 2021; Mešić et al., 2022; Jafarzadeh Ghouschi et al., 2023; Chakraborty & Zavadskas, 2014; Zavadskas et al., 2013; Kutlu Gundogdu & Cengiz Kahraman, 2019; Urosevic et al., 2017). This includes both the LMAW and DNMA methods. The multi-criteria analysis provides, compared to the classical methodology, a more accurate assessment of the transport and storage performance as a basis for improvement in the future of taking adequate measures (Thanh, 2022; Do Duc Trung, 2022; Aytekin & Korucuk, 2023; Stević et al, 2023). Continuous analysis of transport and storage performance factors, in the specific case of the European Union, is a key assumption for improvement in the future by taking adequate measures (Lukić, 2022a,b,c,2023a,b,c,d,e,f). This manifests the primary research hypothesis in this study. In the methodological sense of the word, as a result of the defined research hypothesis, the application of LMAW and DNMA methods plays a significant role in the most realistic assessment of transport and storage performance in the countries of the European Union (Özekenci, 2023). The necessary statistical empirical data for researching the problem addressed in this study were collected from Eurostat. They are "produced" by all relevant standards so that there are no limitations regarding the international comparison of the empirical results obtained in this study.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the research methodology of the analyzed problem is based on the application of the LMAW-DNMA method. Statistical analysis was also used to some extent. Below we will present the characteristics of the LMAW-DNMA method.

The **LMAW** (Logarithm Methodology of Additive Weights) method is the latest method used to calculate criteria weights and rank alternatives (Liao, & Wu, 2020; Demir, 2022). It takes place through the following steps: m alternatives $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$ are evaluated in comparison with n criteria $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ with the participation of k experts $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k\}$ and according to a predefined linguistic scale (Pamučar *et al.*, 2021). Diagram 1 shows the process of applying the LMAW method.

Diagram 1 Steps of the LMAW method application process

Source: Author's diagram

Step 1: Determination of weight coefficients of criteria

Experts $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k\}$ determine priorities with criteria $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ about previously defined values of the linguistic scale. At the same time, they assign a higher value to the criterion of greater importance and a lower value to the criterion of less importance on the linguistic scale. By the way, the priority vector is obtained. The label γ_{cn}^e represents the value of the linguistic scale that the expert e ($1 \leq e \leq k$) assigns to the criterion C_t ($1 \leq t \leq n$).

Step 1.1: Defining the absolute anti-ideal point γ_{AIP}

The absolute ideal point should be less than the smallest value in the priority vector. It is calculated according to the equation:

$$\gamma_{AIP} = \frac{\gamma_{min}^e}{S} \quad (1)$$

Where is γ_{min}^e the minimum value of the priority vector and S should be greater than the base logarithmic function. In the case of using the function Ln, the value of S can be chosen as 3.

Step 1.2: Determining the relationship between the priority vector and the absolute anti-ideal point

The relationship between the priority vector and the absolute anti-ideal point is calculated using the following equation:

$$n_{cn}^e = \frac{\gamma_{cn}^e}{\gamma_{AIP}} \quad (2)$$

So the relational vector $R^e = (n_{c_1}^e, n_{c_2}^e, \dots, n_{c_n}^e)$ is obtained. Where $n_{c_n}^e$ represents the value of the relation vector derived from the previous equation, and R^e represents the relational vector $e(1 \leq e \leq k)$.

Step 1.3: Determination of the vector of weight coefficients

The vector of weighting coefficients $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is calculated by the expert $e(1 \leq e \leq k)$ using the following equation:

$$w_j^e = \frac{\log_A(n_{c_n}^e)}{\log_A(\prod_{j=1}^n n_{c_n}^e)}, A > 1 \quad (3)$$

where w_j^e it represents the weighting coefficients obtained according to expert evaluations e^{th} and the $n_{c_n}^e$ elements of the realization vector R . The obtained values for the weighting coefficients must meet the condition that $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j^e = 1$.

By applying the Bonferroni aggregator shown in the following equation, the aggregated vector of weight coefficients is determined $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$:

$$W_j = \left(\frac{1}{k \cdot (k-1)} \cdot \sum_{x=1}^k (w_j^{(x)})^p \cdot \sum_{\substack{y=1 \\ y \neq x}}^k (w_{ij}^{(y)})^q \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \quad (4)$$

The values of p and q are stabilization parameters and $p, q \geq 0$. The resulting weight coefficients should fulfill the condition that $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

The **DNMA** (Double Normalization-based Multiple Aggregation) method is a newer method for showing alternatives (Demir, 2022). Two different normalized (linear and vector) techniques are used, as well as three different coupling functions (Complete Compensatory Model – CCM, Uncompensatory Model – UCM, and Incomplete Compensatory Model – ICM). The steps for applying this method are as follows (Liao & Wu, 2020; Ecer, 2020) (Diagram 2 shows the steps of the DNMA method application process):

Diagram 2 Steps of the DNMA method application process

Source: Author's diagram

Step 1: Normalized decision matrix

The elements of the decision matrix are normalized with linear (\hat{x}_{ij}^{1N}) normalization using the following equation:

$$\hat{x}_{ij}^{1N} = 1 - \frac{|x^{ij} - r_j|}{\max\{\max_i x^{ij}, r_j\} - \min\{\min_i x^{ij}, r_j\}} \quad (5)$$

The vector (\hat{x}_{ij}^{2N}) is normalized using the following equation:

$$\hat{x}_{ij}^{2N} = 1 - \frac{|x^{ij} - r_j|}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (x^{ij})^2 + (r_j)^2}} \quad (6)$$

The value r_j is the target value for c_j the criterion and is considered $\max_i x^{ij}$ for both utility and $\min_i x^{ij}$ cost criteria.

Step 2: Determining the weight of the criteria

This step consists of three phases:

Step 2.1: In this phase, the standard deviation (σ_j) for the criterion c_j is determined with the following equation where m is the number of alternatives:

$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{x^{ij}}{\max_i x^{ij}} - \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{x^{ij}}{\max_i x^{ij}} \right) \right)^2}{m}} \quad (7)$$

Step 2.2: Standard deviation values calculated for the criteria are normalized with the following equation:

$$w_j^\sigma = \frac{\sigma_j}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_j} \quad (8)$$

Step 2.3: Finally, the weights are adjusted with the following equation:

$$\hat{w}_j = \frac{\sqrt{w_j^\sigma \cdot w_j}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{w_j^\sigma \cdot w_j}} \quad (9)$$

Step 3: Calculating the aggregation model

Three aggregation functions (CCM, UCM, and ICM) are calculated separately for each alternative.

The CCM (Complete Compensation Model) is calculated using the following equation:

$$u_1(a_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\hat{w}_j \cdot \hat{x}_{ij}^{1N}}{\max_i \hat{x}_{ij}^{1N}} \quad (10)$$

The UCM (Uncompensatory Model) is calculated using the following equation:

$$u_2(a_i) = \max_j \hat{w}_j \left(\frac{1 - \hat{x}_{ij}^{1N}}{\max_i \hat{x}_{ij}^{1N}} \right) \quad (11)$$

The ICM (Incomplete Compensation Model) is calculated using the following equation:

$$u_3(a_i) = \prod_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\hat{x}_{ij}^{2N}}{\max_i \hat{x}_{ij}^{2N}} \right)^{\hat{w}_j} \quad (12)$$

Step 4: Integration of utility values

The calculated utility functions are integrated with the following equation using the Euclidean distance principle:

$$DN_i = w_1 \sqrt{\varphi \left(\frac{u_1(a_i)}{\max_i u_1(a_i)} \right)^2 + (1 - \varphi) \left(\frac{m - r_{1(a_i)+1}}{m} \right)^2} \\
- w_2 \sqrt{\varphi \left(\frac{u_2(a_i)}{\max_i u_2(a_i)} \right)^2 + (1 - \varphi) \left(\frac{r_2(a_i)}{m} \right)^2} \\
+ w_3 \sqrt{\varphi \left(\frac{u_3(a_i)}{\max_i u_3(a_i)} \right)^2 + (1 - \varphi) \left(\frac{m - r_3(a_i) + 1}{m} \right)^2} \quad (13)$$

In this case, the means $r_1(a_i)$ and $r_3(a_i)$ represent the ordinal number of the alternative a_i sorted according to the functions CCM and ICM in descending value (higher value first). On the other hand, $r_2(a_i)$ shows the sequence number in the obtained order according to the increasing value (smaller value first) for the UCM function used. The label φ is the relative importance of the child value used and is in the range [0.1]. It is considered that it can be taken as $\varphi = 0.5$. The coefficients w_1, w_2, w_3 are the obtained weights of the used functions CCM, UCM, and ICM, respectively. The sum should be equal to $w_1 + w_2 + w_3 = 1$. When determining the weights, if the decision maker attaches importance to a wider range of performance alternatives, he can set a higher value for w_1 . In case the decision maker is not ready to take risks, i.e. to choose a poor alternative according to some criterion, he can assign a higher weight to w_2 . However, the decision maker may assign a greater weight to w_3 if he simultaneously considers overall performance and risk. Finally, the DN values are sorted in descending order, with alternatives with a higher value being the best.

3. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the framework of the discussion and results, we will point out the importance of the transport and storage sector in the European Union to process the problem analyzed in this study as complex as possible. Likewise, the results of the performance positioning of the transport and storage of the countries of the European Union were obtained by applying the LMAW-DNMA method.

3.1. Importance of transport and storage in the European Union

The role of transport and storage in creating the overall performance of the European Union is significant. Thus, for example, in 2021, transport and storage accounted for 4.5% of the total number of companies within the business economy of the European Union (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). In the structure of transport and storage companies of the European Union, by size, SMEs (0-245 persons employed) participate with 65%, and large (250+persons employed) with 35% (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). In a way, this is reflected in the overall performance of the transport and storage of the European Union. The rate of added value of transport and storage in the European Union in 2021 was 5.7% (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). In 2021, the transport and storage employment rate of the European Union was 6.7% (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). Labor productivity adjusted according to transport and storage wages of the European Union in 2021 was 179% (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). In 2021, the gross operating rate of transport and storage of the European Union was 13.36% (Eurostat (sbs_sc_ovw)). Concentration is one of the important factors in the performance positioning of the transport and storage of the countries of the European Union. Figure 1 shows the concentration of employment and added value of transport and storage in the countries of the European Union for 2021.

Figure 1 Concentration of value added and employment, Transportation, and storage, (% of the EU total)

Source: Author's work

The five countries in terms of concentration of added value of transport and storage of the European Union are Germany (26.21%), France (17.89%), Italy (11.41%), Spain (8.01%), and the Netherlands (6.72%). The five countries in terms of concentration of employment in transport and storage in the European Union include Germany (22.51%), France (13.99%), Italy (11.27%), Spain (8.91%), and Poland

(8.87%). Croatia participates in the total added value of transport and storage of the European Union with 0.35%, and in the total number of employees with 0.73%. Slovenia participates in the total added value of transport and storage of the European Union with 0.47%, and in the total number of employees with 0.53%. Therefore, the share of Slovenia in the total added value of transport and storage in the European Union is greater than that of Croatia. The share of Slovenia in the total number of transport and warehousing employees of the European Union is less than that of Croatia. In its way, this was reflected in their performance positioning within the European Union.

The types of transport and storage in their way influence the performance positioning of the countries of the European Union. In the total added value and the total number of employees of transport and storage in the countries of the European Union, according to Eurostat statistics, the participation of land transport and pipeline transport is predominant. Average employee costs and labor productivity adjusted for wages are different for individual types of transport and storage in European Union countries. In the USA: United States in 2019, transport and storage participated in the total added value with 3.4%, and in the total number of employees with 4.1%. In Japan, in the same year, transport and storage participated in the total added value with 5.4%, and in the total number of employees with 6.2% (OECD Statistics). So in these statistical parameters, the participation of transport and storage in the European Union is higher than in the United States and Japan.

All the statistical performance parameters presented above speak for themselves that transport and storage play a significant role in determining the overall performance of the European Union. Hence, the continuous analysis of key statistical performance indicators of transport and warehousing in the European Union (number of companies, number of employees, added value, employee earnings, investments, turnover) is significant to improve in the future by applying relevant measures, such as efficient management of the number and size of companies, human resources, employee costs, added value, traffic, investments, sustainable development, energy crisis, integrated transport, digitization of the entire business, etc. In addition to classical analysis, the application of multi-criteria decision-making methods, including the LMAW-DNMA method, plays a significant role in this. This contributes to a more realistic view of the performance situation of transport and storage in the European Union, as a basis for improvement in the future by applying key relevant measures.

3.2. Selection and ranking of transport and storage of European Union countries

In this study, the selection of transport and storage of European Union countries will be carried out using the LMAW-DNMA method. The key issue when applying the LMAW-DNMA method in the selection (performance evaluation) of transport and storage of the European Union is the choice of appropriate criteria. They must fully correspond to the nature of the business of the transport and storage sector. Accordingly, in this study, the selected criteria for the analysis of the transport and storage performance of the European Union are C1 - Enterprises - number, C2 - Persons employed - number, C3 - Value added, C4 - Wages and salaries, C5 -

Purchases of goods and services, and C6 – Net turnover. According to Eurostat statistics, they are key indicators of transport and storage performance.

Alternatives are the countries of the European Union: A1 – Belgium, A2 – Bulgaria, A3 – Czechia, A4 – Denmark, A5 – Germany, A6 – Estonia, A7 – Ireland, A8 – Greece, A9 – Spain, A10 – France, A11 – Croatia, A12 – Italia, A13 – Cyprus, A14 – Latvia, A15 – Lithuania, A16 – Luxembourg, A17 – Hungary, A18 – Malta, A19 – Netherlands, A20 – Austria, A21 – Poland, A22 – Portugal, A23 – Romania, A24 – Slovenia, A25 – Slovakia, A26 – Finland, and A27 – Sweden.

Table 1 shows the key statistical performance indicators of transport and storage in the European Union for 2021. (In this study, all calculations and results are the authors' work.)

Table 1 Key Statistical Performance Indicators of Transport and Storage of the European Union, 2021

	Enterprises - number	Persons employed - number	Value added – one million euros	Wages and salaries – one million euros	Purchases of goods and services – one million euros	Net turnover – one million euros
European Union - 27 countries (from 2020)	1,380,703	10,182,339	527,493.47	254,732.97	1,033,185.18	1,506,681.40
Belgium	21,306	220,221	17,933.98	8,475.85	38,273.16	54,419.95
Bulgaria	22,222	152,321	2,161.66	1,064.27	7,285.78	9,336.24
Czechia	44,113	288,661	8,311.01	3,842.91	20,518.45	26,197.41
Denmark	11,766	145,817	24,748.87	7,180.05	52,456.79	75,504.09
Germany	100,517	2,292,208	138,233.61	67,845.18	242,251.86	372,864.34
Estonia	6,513	39,496	1,408.17	613.05	4,014.61	5,396.92
Ireland	24,052	105,690	4,692.61	3,178.80	14,662.78	18,887.55
Greece	60,445	166,127	5,523.35	2,189.12	10,035.29	14,466.31
Spain	224,761	906,970	42,252.94	20,414.40	78,117.82	113,823.20
France	181,815	1,424,343	94,373.23	45,852.66	145,726.10	229,644.44
Croatia	13,228	74,275	1,850.59	901.97	3,175.60	4,871.95
Italy	115,231	1,147,312	60,204.82	30,319.57	116,535.03	169,799.44
Cyprus	3,251	18,378	804.54	420.93	2,899.33	3,697.18
Latvia	8,901	69,040	1,411.43	772.03	3,909.16	5,271.64
Lithuania	28,969	166,765	4,316.97	2,303.10	10,331.93	14,321.23
Luxembourg	1,046	22,906	3,470.33	1,341.45	5,054.15	8,215.28
Hungary	44,149	197,887	4,504.42	2,359.96	12,444.81	16,802.04
Malta	3,346	15,277	653.69	322.82	2,638.21	3,275.64
Netherlands	59,170	429,468	35,465.53	16,558.72	75,376.36	105,192.14
Austria	15,717	213,365	14,623.31	7,787.19	32,819.19	44,271.36

Poland	174,352	902,754	18,611.67	8,387.10	59,416.91	77,679.86
Portugal	36,473	188,481	6,581.83	3,606.57	15,005.01	20,843.71
Romania	92,117	425,421	6,700.88	3,881.67	17,294.70	22,389.11
Slovenia	9,048	53,858	2,464.90	1,112.19	4,809.28	7,177.02
Slovakia	24,513	120,222	3,386.19	1,404.85	7,850.47	11,179.07
Finland	23,343	122,119	6,668.15	4,270.95	14,413.57	20,917.51
Sweden	30,339	272,957	16,134.81	8,325.65	35,868.83	50,236.83
Statistics						
N	Valid	27	27	27	27	27
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	51137.1481	377123.6667	19536.7959	9434.5559	38266.1178	55803.0170
Median	24513.0000	166765.0000	6581.8300	3606.5700	14662.7800	20843.7100
Std. Deviation	59753.84591	527879.13620	31905.92386	15604.62776	54706.08325	83957.27173
Minimum	1046.00	15277.00	653.69	322.82	2638.21	3275.64
Maximum	224761.00	2292208.00	138233.61	67845.18	242251.86	372864.34

Note: Author's statistics

Source: Eurostat

Table 2 shows the correlation between the observed statistical variables.

Table 2 Correlations

Correlations		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	Pearson Correlation	1	.734 **	.597 **	.599 **	.619 **	.606 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001	.001	.001	.001

	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
C2	Pearson Correlation	.734 **	1	.956 **	.960 **	.966 **	.964 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
C3	Pearson Correlation	.597 **	.956 **	1	.998 **	.991 **	.996 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
C4	Pearson Correlation	.599 **	.960 **	.998 **	1	.988 **	.993 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
C5	Pearson Correlation	.619 **	.966 **	.991 **	.988 **	1	.999 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
C6	Pearson Correlation	.606 **	.964 **	.996 **	.993 **	.999 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	27	27	27	27	27	27
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							

Note: Author's statistics

It can be concluded that in the analyzed case there is a strong correlation between net turnover (C6) and other statistical variables (C1, C2, C3, C4, and C5), at the level of statistical significance. The same is the case with the additional value (C3) and other statistical variables (C1, C2, C4, C5 and C6). This means, in other words, that effective management of the given statistical variables, which are nothing but factors, can largely act in the direction of achieving the target performance of transport and storage in the European Union.

Table 3 shows the prioritization scale and evaluation criteria. Figure 2 shows their weighting coefficients to get a more complete picture of the importance of the selected criteria.

Table 3 Prioritization Scale and Evaluation Criteria

Linguistic Variables	Abbreviation	Prioritization
Absolutely Low	AL	1
Very Low	VL	1.5
Low	L	2
Medium	M	2.5
Equal	E	3
Medium High	MH	3.5
High	H	4
Very High	VH	4.5
Absolutely High	AH	5

KIND	1	1	1	-1	-1	1	
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	LN($\Pi\eta$)
E1	H	AH	H	E	MH	MH	12,145
E2	VH	VH	MH	H	H	MH	12,445
E3	E	MH	VH	AH	AH	H	12,620
E4	MH	E	E	VH	AH	E	11,821

Υ AIP	0.5
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Weight Coefficients Vector	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
W1j	0.171	0.190	0.171	0.148	0.160	0.160
W2j	0.177	0.177	0.156	0.167	0.167	0.156
W3j	0.142	0.154	0.174	0.182	0.182	0.165
W4j	0.165	0.152	0.152	0.186	0.195	0.152

Aggregated Fuzzy Vectors	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
W1j	0.007	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006
W2j	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.006

W3j	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.006
W4j	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.008	0.008	0.006
SUM	0.027	0.028	0.027	0.029	0.031	0.025
Aggregated Weight Coefficient Vectors	0.1634	0.1677	0.1632	0.1705	0.1760	0.1582

Note: Author's calculations

Figure 2 Weight coefficients of criteria

Source: Author's picture

In this case, the ranking of the criteria by importance is as follows: C5, C4, C2, C1, C3, and C6. This means, in other words, that the efficient management of criterion C5 (Purchases of goods and services) contributes to the greatest extent to the improvement of transport and storage performance in the European Union.

The calculation and results of the LMAW-DNMA method in this particular case are shown in Tables 4 – 10. Figure 3 shows the ranking of transport and storage of the countries of the European Union to obtain a more complete picture of performance positioning.

Table 4 Initial Matrix

INITIAL MATRIX	KIND	1	1	1	-1	-1	1
	Weight	0.1634	0.1677	0.1632	0.1705	0.1760	0.1582
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
	A1	21,306	220,221	17,933.98	8,475.85	38,273.16	54,419.95
	A2	22,222	152,321	2,161.66	1,064.27	7,285.78	9,336.24
	A3	44,113	288,661	8,311.01	3,842.91	20,518.45	26,197.41
	A4	11,766	145,817	24,748.87	7,180.05	52,456.79	75,504.09
	A5	100,517	2,292,208	138,233.61	67,845.18	242,251.86	372,864.34
	A6	6,513	39,496	1,408.17	613.05	4,014.61	5,396.92
	A7	24,052	105,690	4,692.61	3,178.80	14,662.78	18,887.55
	A8	60,445	166,127	5,523.35	2,189.12	10,035.29	14,466.31
	A9	224,761	906,970	42,252.94	20,414.40	78,117.82	113,823.20
	A10	181,815	1,424,343	94,373.23	45,852.66	145,726.10	229,644.44
	A11	13,228	74,275	1,850.59	901.97	3,175.60	4,871.95
	A12	115,231	1,147,312	60,204.82	30,319.57	116,535.03	169,799.44
	A13	3,251	18,378	804.54	420.93	2,899.33	3,697.18
	A14	8,901	69,040	1,411.43	772.03	3,909.16	5,271.64
	A15	28,969	166,765	4,316.97	2,303.10	10,331.93	14,321.23
	A16	1,046	22,906	3,470.33	1,341.45	5,054.15	8,215.28
	A17	44,149	197,887	4,504.42	2,359.96	12,444.81	16,802.04
	A18	3,346	15,277	653.69	322.82	2,638.21	3,275.64
	A19	59,170	429,468	35,465.53	16,558.72	75,376.36	105,192.14
	A20	15,717	213,365	14,623.31	7,787.19	32,819.19	44,271.36
	A21	174,352	902,754	18,611.67	8,387.10	59,416.91	77,679.86
	A22	36,473	188,481	6,581.83	3,606.57	15,005.01	20,843.71
	A23	92,117	425,421	6,700.88	3,881.67	17,294.70	22,389.11

	A24	9,048	53,858	2,464.90	1,112.19	4,809.28	7,177.02
	A25	24,513	120,222	3,386.19	1,404.85	7,850.47	11,179.07
	A26	23,343	122,119	6,668.15	4,270.95	14,413.57	20,917.51
	A27	30,339	272,957	16,134.81	8,325.65	35,868.83	50,236.83
	MAX	224761.0000	2292208.0000	138233.6100	67845.1800	242251.8600	372864.3400
	MIN	1046.0000	15277.0000	653.6900	322.8200	2638.2100	3275.6400

Note: Author's calculations

Table 5 Linear Normalization Matrix

Linear Normalization MATRIX		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	MAX
	A1	0.0906	0.0900	0.1256	0.8793	0.8513	0.1384	0.8793
A2	0.0947	0.0602	0.0110	0.9890	0.9806	0.0164	0.9890	
A3	0.1925	0.1201	0.0557	0.9479	0.9254	0.0620	0.9479	
A4	0.0479	0.0573	0.1751	0.8984	0.7921	0.1954	0.8984	
A5	0.4446	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000	
A6	0.0244	0.0106	0.0055	0.9957	0.9943	0.0057	0.9957	
A7	0.1028	0.0397	0.0294	0.9577	0.9498	0.0422	0.9577	
A8	0.2655	0.0663	0.0354	0.9724	0.9691	0.0303	0.9724	
A9	1.0000	0.3916	0.3024	0.7024	0.6850	0.2991	1.0000	
A10	0.8080	0.6188	0.6812	0.3257	0.4028	0.6125	0.8080	
A11	0.0545	0.0259	0.0087	0.9914	0.9978	0.0043	0.9978	
A12	0.5104	0.4972	0.4328	0.5558	0.5247	0.4506	0.5558	
A13	0.0099	0.0014	0.0011	0.9985	0.9989	0.0011	0.9989	
A14	0.0351	0.0236	0.0055	0.9933	0.9947	0.0054	0.9947	
A15	0.1248	0.0665	0.0266	0.9707	0.9679	0.0299	0.9707	

	A16	0.0000	0.0034	0.0205	0.9849	0.9899	0.0134	0.9899
	A17	0.1927	0.0802	0.0280	0.9698	0.9591	0.0366	0.9698
	A18	0.0103	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000
	A19	0.2598	0.1819	0.2530	0.7595	0.6964	0.2758	0.7595
	A20	0.0656	0.0870	0.1015	0.8895	0.8740	0.1109	0.8895
	A21	0.7747	0.3898	0.1305	0.8806	0.7630	0.2013	0.8806
	A22	0.1584	0.0761	0.0431	0.9514	0.9484	0.0475	0.9514
	A23	0.4071	0.1801	0.0440	0.9473	0.9388	0.0517	0.9473
	A24	0.0358	0.0169	0.0132	0.9883	0.9909	0.0106	0.9909
	A25	0.1049	0.0461	0.0199	0.9840	0.9782	0.0214	0.9840
	A26	0.0997	0.0469	0.0437	0.9415	0.9509	0.0477	0.9509
	A27	0.1309	0.1132	0.1125	0.8815	0.8613	0.1271	0.8815

Note: Author's calculations

Table 6 Vector Normalization Matrix

Vector Normalization MATRIX		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	MAX
	A1		0.5601	0.4874	0.4911	0.9128	0.8960	0.5005
A2		0.5621	0.4706	0.4244	0.9921	0.9864	0.4297	0.9921
A3		0.6095	0.5043	0.4504	0.9623	0.9478	0.4562	0.9623
A4		0.5395	0.4690	0.5199	0.9266	0.8546	0.5335	0.9266
A5		0.7314	1.0000	1.0000	0.2775	0.3005	1.0000	1.0000
A6		0.5282	0.4427	0.4212	0.9969	0.9960	0.4236	0.9969
A7		0.5661	0.4591	0.4351	0.9694	0.9649	0.4447	0.9694
A8		0.6448	0.4740	0.4386	0.9800	0.9784	0.4378	0.9800
A9		1.0000	0.6573	0.5940	0.7850	0.7797	0.5936	1.0000

	A10	0.9072	0.7853	0.8145	0.5128	0.5823	0.7753	0.9072
	A11	0.5427	0.4513	0.4231	0.9938	0.9984	0.4227	0.9984
	A12	0.7632	0.7168	0.6699	0.6790	0.6675	0.6815	0.7632
	A13	0.5211	0.4375	0.4186	0.9990	0.9992	0.4209	0.9992
	A14	0.5333	0.4500	0.4212	0.9952	0.9963	0.4234	0.9963
	A15	0.5767	0.4742	0.4335	0.9788	0.9775	0.4376	0.9788
	A16	0.5163	0.4386	0.4299	0.9891	0.9929	0.4280	0.9929
	A17	0.6095	0.4819	0.4343	0.9782	0.9714	0.4414	0.9782
	A18	0.5213	0.4367	0.4180	1.0000	1.0000	0.4202	1.0000
	A19	0.6420	0.5392	0.5653	0.8263	0.7877	0.5801	0.8263
	A20	0.5481	0.4857	0.4771	0.9201	0.9119	0.4845	0.9201
	A21	0.8910	0.6563	0.4940	0.9137	0.8343	0.5369	0.9137
	A22	0.5929	0.4796	0.4431	0.9649	0.9639	0.4478	0.9649
	A23	0.7132	0.5382	0.4436	0.9619	0.9572	0.4502	0.9619
	A24	0.5336	0.4463	0.4257	0.9916	0.9937	0.4264	0.9937
	A25	0.5671	0.4627	0.4296	0.9884	0.9848	0.4326	0.9884
	A26	0.5646	0.4631	0.4434	0.9578	0.9656	0.4479	0.9656
	A27	0.5797	0.5005	0.4835	0.9144	0.9030	0.4939	0.9144
	Adj Wj	0.1759	0.1658	0.1638	0.1671	0.1682	0.1593	

Note: Author's calculations

Table 7 CCM (Complete Compensatory Model)

CCM (Complete Compensatory Model)	u1(ai)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	SUM
A1		0.0181	0.0170	0.0234	0.1671	0.1628	0.0251	0.4135
A2		0.0168	0.0101	0.0018	0.1671	0.1668	0.0026	0.3652
A3		0.0357	0.0210	0.0096	0.1671	0.1642	0.0104	0.4081
A4		0.0094	0.0106	0.0319	0.1671	0.1483	0.0346	0.4019
A5		0.0782	0.1658	0.1638	0.0000	0.0000	0.1593	0.5670
A6		0.0043	0.0018	0.0009	0.1671	0.1680	0.0009	0.3430
A7		0.0189	0.0069	0.0050	0.1671	0.1668	0.0070	0.3717
A8		0.0480	0.0113	0.0060	0.1671	0.1676	0.0050	0.4050
A9		0.1759	0.0649	0.0495	0.1174	0.1152	0.0476	0.5705
A10		0.1759	0.1270	0.1381	0.0674	0.0839	0.1207	0.7128
A11		0.0096	0.0043	0.0014	0.1660	0.1682	0.0007	0.3502
A12		0.1615	0.1483	0.1276	0.1671	0.1588	0.1291	0.8924
A13		0.0017	0.0002	0.0002	0.1670	0.1682	0.0002	0.3376
A14		0.0062	0.0039	0.0009	0.1669	0.1682	0.0009	0.3470
A15		0.0226	0.0114	0.0045	0.1671	0.1677	0.0049	0.3782
A16		0.0000	0.0006	0.0034	0.1662	0.1682	0.0022	0.3405
A17		0.0349	0.0137	0.0047	0.1671	0.1663	0.0060	0.3928
A18		0.0018	0.0000	0.0000	0.1671	0.1682	0.0000	0.3371
A19		0.0602	0.0397	0.0546	0.1671	0.1542	0.0578	0.5336
A20		0.0130	0.0162	0.0187	0.1671	0.1653	0.0199	0.4001
A21		0.1547	0.0734	0.0243	0.1671	0.1457	0.0364	0.6016
A22		0.0293	0.0133	0.0074	0.1671	0.1677	0.0080	0.3927
A23		0.0756	0.0315	0.0076	0.1671	0.1667	0.0087	0.4572

	A24	0.0063	0.0028	0.0022	0.1666	0.1682	0.0017	0.3479
	A25	0.0187	0.0078	0.0033	0.1671	0.1672	0.0035	0.3676
	A26	0.0184	0.0082	0.0075	0.1655	0.1682	0.0080	0.3758
	A27	0.0261	0.0213	0.0209	0.1671	0.1643	0.0230	0.4227

Note: Author's calculations

Table 8 UCM (Uncompensatory Model)

UCM (Uncompensatory Model)	u2(ai)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	MAX
	A1	0.1578	0.1489	0.1404	0.0000	0.0054	0.1342	0.1578
	A2	0.1590	0.1557	0.1620	0.0000	0.0014	0.1566	0.1620
	A3	0.1401	0.1448	0.1542	0.0000	0.0040	0.1488	0.1542
	A4	0.1665	0.1552	0.1318	0.0000	0.0199	0.1246	0.1665
	A5	0.0977	0.0000	0.0000	0.1671	0.1682	0.0000	0.1682
	A6	0.1715	0.1641	0.1629	0.0000	0.0002	0.1583	0.1715
	A7	0.1570	0.1590	0.1587	0.0000	0.0014	0.1522	0.1590
	A8	0.1278	0.1545	0.1578	0.0000	0.0006	0.1543	0.1578
	A9	0.0000	0.1009	0.1143	0.0497	0.0530	0.1116	0.1143
	A10	0.0000	0.0388	0.0257	0.0997	0.0843	0.0385	0.0997
	A11	0.1663	0.1615	0.1623	0.0011	0.0000	0.1586	0.1663
	A12	0.0143	0.0175	0.0362	0.0000	0.0094	0.0301	0.0362
	A13	0.1741	0.1656	0.1636	0.0001	0.0000	0.1591	0.1741
	A14	0.1697	0.1619	0.1629	0.0002	0.0000	0.1584	0.1697
	A15	0.1533	0.1545	0.1593	0.0000	0.0005	0.1543	0.1593
	A16	0.1759	0.1653	0.1604	0.0008	0.0000	0.1571	0.1759

	A17	0.1409	0.1521	0.1590	0.0000	0.0019	0.1532	0.1590
	A18	0.1741	0.1658	0.1638	0.0000	0.0000	0.1593	0.1741
	A19	0.1157	0.1261	0.1092	0.0000	0.0140	0.1014	0.1261
	A20	0.1629	0.1496	0.1451	0.0000	0.0029	0.1394	0.1629
	A21	0.0211	0.0924	0.1395	0.0000	0.0224	0.1228	0.1395
	A22	0.1466	0.1526	0.1564	0.0000	0.0005	0.1513	0.1564
	A23	0.1003	0.1343	0.1562	0.0000	0.0015	0.1506	0.1562
	A24	0.1695	0.1630	0.1616	0.0004	0.0000	0.1576	0.1695
	A25	0.1571	0.1581	0.1605	0.0000	0.0010	0.1558	0.1605
	A26	0.1574	0.1576	0.1562	0.0016	0.0000	0.1513	0.1576
	A27	0.1497	0.1445	0.1429	0.0000	0.0038	0.1363	0.1497

Note: Author's calculations

Table 9 ICM (Incomplete Compensatory Model)

ICM (Incomplete Compensatory Model)	u3(ai)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	MAX
	A1		0.9177	0.9012	0.9035	1.0000	0.9969	0.9087
A2		0.9049	0.8837	0.8702	1.0000	0.9990	0.8753	0.6085
A3		0.9228	0.8984	0.8831	1.0000	0.9974	0.8879	0.6484
A4		0.9093	0.8932	0.9097	1.0000	0.9865	0.9158	0.6675
A5		0.9465	1.0000	1.0000	0.8072	0.8169	1.0000	0.6241
A6		0.8943	0.8741	0.8684	1.0000	0.9998	0.8726	0.5922
A7		0.9097	0.8834	0.8770	1.0000	0.9992	0.8833	0.6221
A8		0.9290	0.8865	0.8766	1.0000	0.9997	0.8796	0.6349
A9		1.0000	0.9328	0.9182	0.9604	0.9590	0.9203	0.7260
A10		1.0000	0.9764	0.9825	0.9091	0.9281	0.9753	0.7894

	A11	0.8983	0.8766	0.8688	0.9992	1.0000	0.8721	0.5962
	A12	1.0000	0.9896	0.9789	0.9807	0.9777	0.9821	0.9122
	A13	0.8918	0.8720	0.8672	1.0000	1.0000	0.8714	0.5876
	A14	0.8959	0.8765	0.8685	0.9998	1.0000	0.8726	0.5950
	A15	0.9112	0.8868	0.8751	1.0000	0.9998	0.8797	0.6219
	A16	0.8914	0.8733	0.8719	0.9994	1.0000	0.8746	0.5932
	A17	0.9202	0.8892	0.8755	1.0000	0.9988	0.8810	0.6304
	A18	0.8918	0.8716	0.8669	1.0000	1.0000	0.8710	0.5869
	A19	0.9566	0.9317	0.9397	1.0000	0.9920	0.9452	0.7853
	A20	0.9129	0.8995	0.8980	1.0000	0.9985	0.9029	0.6648
	A21	0.9956	0.9466	0.9042	1.0000	0.9848	0.9188	0.7711
	A22	0.9179	0.8905	0.8803	1.0000	0.9998	0.8849	0.6367
	A23	0.9488	0.9082	0.8809	1.0000	0.9992	0.8861	0.6721
	A24	0.8964	0.8757	0.8704	0.9996	1.0000	0.8739	0.5969
	A25	0.9069	0.8817	0.8724	1.0000	0.9994	0.8767	0.6112
	A26	0.9099	0.8853	0.8803	0.9986	1.0000	0.8849	0.6266
	A27	0.9230	0.9049	0.9009	1.0000	0.9979	0.9066	0.6807

Note: Author's calculations

Table 10 Rank Order

											w1	w2	w3	
											0.6	0.1	0.3	
		CCM		ϕ	UCM		ϕ	ICM		ϕ	Utility Values			Rank Order
		u1(ai)	Rank	0.5	u2(ai)	Rank	0.5	u3(ai)	Rank	0.5				
Belgium	A1	0.4135	9	0.5958	0.1578	11	0.6966	0.6769	7	0.7601	0.6552	0.6552		9
Bulgaria	A2	0.3652	20	0.3573	0.1620	17	0.7888	0.6085	20	0.5161	0.4481	0.4481		20
Czechia	A3	0.4081	10	0.5716	0.1542	7	0.6463	0.6484	11	0.6714	0.6090	0.6090		11
Denmark	A4	0.4019	12	0.5263	0.1665	20	0.8500	0.6675	9	0.7179	0.6161	0.6161		10
Germany	A5	0.5670	5	0.7515	0.1682	21	0.8717	0.6241	16	0.5769	0.7111	0.7111		6
Estonia	A6	0.3430	24	0.2912	0.1715	24	0.9332	0.5922	25	0.4657	0.4078	0.4078		25
Ireland	A7	0.3717	18	0.3941	0.1590	13	0.7241	0.6221	17	0.5617	0.4774	0.4774		18
Greece	A8	0.4050	11	0.5488	0.1578	12	0.7081	0.6349	13	0.6297	0.5890	0.5890		13
Spain	A9	0.5705	4	0.7742	0.1143	3	0.4660	0.7260	5	0.8243	0.7584	0.7584		4
France	A10	0.7128	2	0.8847	0.0997	2	0.4044	0.7894	2	0.9155	0.8459	0.8459		2
Croatia	A11	0.3502	21	0.3326	0.1663	19	0.8334	0.5962	22	0.4881	0.4293	0.4293		21
Italy	A12	0.8924	1	1.0000	0.0362	1	0.1480	0.9122	1	1.0000	0.9148	0.9148		1
Cyprus	A13	0.3376	26	0.2725	0.1741	26	0.9766	0.5876	26	0.4585	0.3987	0.3987		26
Latvia	A14	0.3470	23	0.3045	0.1697	23	0.9100	0.5950	23	0.4795	0.4176	0.4176		23
Lithuania	A15	0.3782	16	0.4342	0.1593	15	0.7513	0.6219	18	0.5486	0.5002	0.5002		16
Luxembourg	A16	0.3405	25	0.2810	0.1759	27	1.0000	0.5932	24	0.4716	0.4101	0.4101		24
Hungary	A17	0.3928	14	0.4809	0.1590	14	0.7371	0.6304	14	0.6109	0.5455	0.5455		14
Malta	A18	0.3371	27	0.2684	0.1741	25	0.9584	0.5869	27	0.4557	0.3936	0.3936		27
Netherlands	A19	0.5336	6	0.7146	0.1261	4	0.5178	0.7853	3	0.8940	0.7487	0.7487		5
Austria	A20	0.4001	13	0.5048	0.1629	18	0.8070	0.6648	10	0.6984	0.5931	0.5931		12
Poland	A21	0.6016	3	0.8099	0.1395	5	0.5759	0.7711	4	0.8673	0.8037	0.8037		3
Portugal	A22	0.3927	15	0.4612	0.1564	9	0.6714	0.6367	12	0.6474	0.5381	0.5381		15

Romania	A23	0.4572	7	0.6586	0.1562	8	0.6619	0.6721	8	0.7387	0.6830	0.6830	7
Slovenia	A24	0.3479	22	0.3173	0.1695	22	0.8925	0.5969	21	0.4977	0.4289	0.4289	22
Slovakia	A25	0.3676	19	0.3747	0.1605	16	0.7693	0.6112	19	0.5292	0.4605	0.4605	19
Finland	A26	0.3758	17	0.4143	0.1576	10	0.6858	0.6266	15	0.5932	0.4951	0.4951	17
Sweden	A27	0.4227	8	0.6217	0.1497	6	0.6222	0.6807	6	0.7813	0.6696	0.6696	8
	MAX	0.8924			0.1759			0.9122					

Note: Author's calculations

Figure 3 Rank Order

Source: Author's work

The research on the positioning of the transport and storage performance of the countries of the European Union using the LMAW-DNMA method in this study showed that Italy took the first place. In the last place is Malta. The top five countries of the European Union in terms of transport and storage performance in order include Italy, France, Poland, Spain, and the Netherlands. Germany ranks sixth in terms of transport and storage performance in the European Union. The leading countries of the European Union are well-positioned in terms of transport and storage performance. In the European Union, Croatia ranks twenty-first in terms of transport and storage performance. Slovenia is in twenty-second place. Croatia is in a better position than Slovenia.

The positioning of the countries of the European Union in terms of transport and storage performance was influenced by numerous controlled and uncontrolled macro and micro factors. These are economic and political climate, economic activity, number of company sizes, number of employees, traffic, added value, employee costs, investments, the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic, logistics costs, integrated models of transport, sustainable development, modes of transport, energy crisis and others. Effective control of critical factors can significantly influence the achievement of the target performance of transport and storage in the European Union. The digitization of the entire transport and storage business plays a significant role in this.

4. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded based on the results of the empirical research of the problem treated in this study that: in five countries by concentration of added value of transport and storage of the European Union, they are: Germany (26.21%), France (17.89%), Italy (11, 41%), Spain (8.01%) and the Netherlands (6.72%). The five countries in terms of concentration of employment in transport and storage in the European Union include Germany (22.51%), France (13.99%), Italy (11.27%), Spain (8.91%), and Poland (8.87%). Croatia participates in the total added value of transport and storage of the European Union with 0.35%, and in the total number of employees with 0.73%. Slovenia participates in the total added value of transport and storage of the European Union with 0.47%, and in the total number of employees with 0.53%. Therefore, the participation of Slovenia in the total added value of transport and storage of the European Union is greater than that of Croatia, and it is less in the total number of employees. By the way, concentration belongs, among others, to very significant factors of the performance positioning of the countries of the European Union.

In this study, the research on the positioning of the transport and storage performance of the countries of the European Union using the LMAW-DNMA method showed that Italy took the first place. In the last place is Malta. The top five countries of the European Union in terms of transport and storage performance in order include Italy, France, Poland, Spain, and the Netherlands. Germany ranks sixth in terms of transport and storage performance in the European Union. The leading countries of the European Union are well-positioned in terms of transport and storage performance. In the European Union, in terms of transport and storage performance,

Croatia is in twenty-first place, and Slovenia is in twenty-second place. Compared to Croatia, Slovenia is therefore in a worse position.

Numerous macro and micro factors have influenced the positioning of European Union countries in terms of transport and storage performance. These are economic and political climate, economic activity, number of company sizes, number of employees, turnover, added value, employee costs, investments, the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic, logistics costs, sustainable development, integrated transport models, modes of transport, energy crisis, and others. Effective control of critical factors significantly affects the achievement of the target performance positioning of transport and storage of the countries of the European Union. There is no doubt that the digitization of the entire transport and storage business plays a significant role in this.

The proposal is that considering the importance, similar research is carried out for countries that are not members of the European Union. This provides a complete picture of a global level of transport and storage performance.

It is recommended that similar research be carried out on a global level. In that case, global comparisons of transport and storage performance can be made to achieve the target profit. There are no restrictions on the quality of available empirical data.

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MARKET POTENTIAL OF AIR CARGO TRANSPORT WITH OPERATIONAL BASE IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

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Abstract

Air cargo holds a significant position in the logistics chain of goods transportation. The sector is stable and not characterised by significant fluctuations in performance. European air cargo transportation accounts for one-fifth of global cargo tonne-kilometres. There is no domestic operator in the Czech Republic providing these services. This article brings a comprehensive analysis of the Czech air cargo market in context. The main objective was to define the market potential from the perspective of a Czech operator based in the country. A questionnaire survey was conducted as the first step to estimate demand from Czech freight forwarders. A comparative method was used to determine market potential, involving the comparison of competing airports. The process included identifying decisive factors, assigning weights to these factors, and finally calculating the overall score for each airport. The results revealed a certain potential for a Czech air cargo operator. This is the first study targeting a small Central European state with undefined or undiscovered cargo base potential. This analysis provides a good basis for future studies, referencing several previous studies but using a unique methodology.

Keywords: air transport, cargo, potential, market

1. INTRODUCTION

Air cargo transport is the fastest way of transporting goods. It is therefore typically used for certain specific types of goods. Although only a small portion of cargo volume by weight is transported by air (around 1%), it accounts for 35% of the total value of all transported goods (IATA, 2024). Typical air cargo shipments are lightweight and high-value items, such as electronics. Other types of goods include perishable items (flowers, fruits and vegetables, meat, and fish), textiles,

pharmaceuticals and medical supplies, jewellery, artwork, and other valuable shipments. Live animals are also frequently transported by air, with horses being the most significant part of animal transport. Up to two hundred racehorses are transported by air each day (IATA, 2024). Animal transportation is subject to special procedures and veterinary inspections. Goods that pose certain safety risks are classified as dangerous goods and are handled and processed specially. Dangerous goods include substances and items that may pose a risk to people, animals, cargo, or the environment (e.g., flammable liquids, dry ice, and lithium batteries) (IATA, 2024). Part of the air cargo is transported as so-called belly cargo on passenger flights in the cargo hold, and part on cargo flights designated exclusively for goods transport. Airports with cargo traffic must be equipped with the necessary infrastructure, cargo terminals, storage areas, handling units, veterinary station, freezer and cooling boxes, container transshipment areas and more.

Since 2004, we have seen mostly stable growth in the volume of air cargo transported (Statista Research Department, 2024). Over the past 20 years, there have been three significant declines. The first was caused by the global economic crisis in 2009, the second by the COVID-19 pandemic. The effect of the pandemic was not to reduce demand. The decrease in cargo transported was due to the loss of belly capacity resulting from the grounding of passenger flights. Third case, 2022 and 2023, the war in Ukraine and the related economic instability, including high inflation, resulted in decreased demand as well as reduced air cargo volumes (IATA Economics, 2022). Despite the continued difficult situation, air cargo is and will continue to be an essential component of global infrastructure (Boeing, 2022).

In the air cargo transport chain, the shipper or recipient can arrange the transport on their own or use the services of forwarders with a door-to-door concept and full services. Air cargo forwarders optimize the shipping process, especially by consolidating shipments (Sales & Scholte, 2023). Most of the air cargo (85%) is arranged through cargo forwarders (ILS Company, 2024). There are also so-called integrators with a strong market share. These are companies that provide complete door-to-door transportation, just like cargo forwarders, but they transport with their own trucks and have their own fleet (Morrell & Klein, 2019). Integrators compete with conventional cargo airlines, which helps to create downward pressure on prices (Doganis, 2019). Thus, the market includes conventional air cargo airlines, combined airlines with passenger and cargo fleets, air integrators with door-to-door concepts, and passenger airlines that use belly capacity as a complementary business to their core business. Air cargo transport generated 13.7 billion cargo tonne-kilometres (CTK) in the European Union in 2022, with the Czech Republic contributing 520 million CTK (Eurostat, 2024). Is there a real possibility of a Czech operator based in the country (economic resident or non-resident) entering the market in this sector? The hypothesis was that there is potential for an air cargo base in the Czechia. Although the hypothesis has not yet been statistically tested and confirmed due to the character of this work, this study has established a possible basis for a start from idea to gradual implementation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

For the purposes of this analysis, market potential is not processed as a function of the dependent variables. The market potential function defines the variables that influence the market (Jacks & Novy, 2016). These are usually GDP, income level, population size, foreign trade and other macroeconomic indicators. Their correlation with the market performance of specific products or the market potential of a particular geographic market(s) is monitored (Lakshmanan & Hansen, 2007; Head & Mayer, 2010). Market potential related papers use different approaches and models for research. They pursue different objectives e.g. timing of market entry (Islam et al., 2022). Market potential can be defined by the quantity demanded. Market size defines the quantity sold. Their difference indicates the degree of market saturation. Market potential and market size can be described by some measurable unit of a specific unit of space – a region or a country (Head & Mayer, 2004). If we quantify the value of demand in some measurable unit and it is higher than the actual value realised in the market, we get the potential.

In this paper, we proceed on the fact that market potential is defined by demand. However, the demand for the services of a Czech air cargo provider has not yet been revealed. The hypothesis is that this market has potential. In such a market there is a set of consumers (Czech firms or shippers) who are interested in the service. Or else: "A market has potential when there is a real and sustainable need and sufficient (size) or growing purchasing power to satisfy those needs" (Gharajedaghi, 2011). Market potential is determined by defined demand. This work reveals the state of demand from Czech freight forwarders, defines a Czech airport suitable for a cargo base and identifies the potential of this airport base by comparing it with competing airports in neighbouring countries.

3. METHODOLOGY

Step-by-step:

- Analysis of the Czech cargo market
 - Comparison with competing markets
- Questionnaire survey
- Comparative method

Analysis of the market is the basis of finding new business opportunities. It is based on information and datasets – Eurostat, websites and Annual Reports of airports and airlines, Transport Yearbooks of the Czech Republic, Flightradar website and other additional sources. The data in the analysis is from the Eurostat database, covering the period from June 2022 to April 2023, i.e. 11 consecutive months. All information presented is valid until April 2023. The limitation of the work is that the data files contain only point-to-point data (cargo from the Czechia to the first airport and cargo from the last stop of the goods to Czechia). This means that goods going to the next subsequent airport/s are not included in the presented data. The analysis is based in part on personal knowledge of the market. It is therefore a combination of

documented facts and professional judgement. Analysis is complemented by a comparison with competing markets. These are countries that are the leaders in volumes of transported cargo in Europe: Germany, Belgium, France, Netherlands; and the neighbouring countries: Slovakia, Poland, Austria (Germany is already included in the leaders).

The questionnaire survey among Czech freight forwarders was a supplementary background. A total of 115 companies were contacted and 25 of them returned the completed questionnaire. Although this is 21.7% of them, but the results give some idea of the existing demand. The companies that responded to the questionnaire do not want to be named. The questionnaire contained 7 questions. The aim was to get an overview of the distribution of demand by region (Czech Republic, Europe, outside Europe). One of the questions was directed to the Czech airport that would be preferred for cargo shipments.

According to IATA, the Air Trade Facilitation Index (ATFI) score for the Czech Republic is 8.1 out of 10. The ATFI tracks a country's level to facilitate air cargo through customs and border processes and regulations. Concept evaluates the set parameters and defines the AFTI level of an individual country. This started the idea of establishing a scoring system for a selected airports in terms of air cargo transport. Based on this scoring system (table 1), the Czech airport was compared with competing cargo airports in neighbouring countries. This defined its potential as a cargo base for air operator. Prague Airport was selected as a suitable airport for the base of the air cargo operator. Although Ostrava Airport is also operationally suitable, a concentration of demand has been defined for Prague and interest in this airport was confirmed by the results of the questionnaire. Procedure of comparative method:

1. Selecting the area to be compared – a radius of 450 km around the Prague airport was determined. This distance corresponds to the distance between Prague and Budapest. It is the shortest scheduled cargo route from Prague.

2. Selection of airports – within the defined area, airports that handle more than 1000 tonnes of cargo per year were selected: Prague (PRG), Bratislava (BTS), Vienna (VIE), Katowice (KTW), Wroclaw (WRO), Budapest (BUD), Leipzig (LEJ), Frankfurt (FRA), Nuremberg (NUE), Munich (MUC) and Berlin (BER).

3. Determination of factors and their weights – by compiling the cited studies and expert judgment, nine factors were determined (table 1). This is also the way the score levels were created.

4. Determination of score levels – for all factors 5 levels were determined, level 1 is the lowest, level 5 is the highest level. The selection of specific parts was influenced by the availability of information. One exception was applied, namely for Frankfurt and Leipzig airports. For these two airports, the “tonnes” factor was rated 10 points due to the enormous differences in tonnes handled compared to other airports. Frankfurt and Leipzig handle over 1.3 million tonnes of cargo per year. Vienna Airport has the next highest number of tonnes handled at 260,000 tonnes.

Factors:

- Infrastructure – cargo airport facilities, cargo terminal(s), airport capacity in thousands of tonnes, level of navigation system, number

of runways and aircraft stands, presence of logistics centres, connection to rail.

- GDP – national GDP per capita.
- Tonnes – annual number of cargo tonnes handled.
- Charges – landing charges, were compared for a Boeing 767-300 aircraft with a maximum take-off weight (MTOW) of 159,000 kg, using 150 tonnes MTOW for the calculation.
- Hub – distance from the nearest hub airport like Leipzig. Bratislava, for example, is near two major airports – Vienna and Budapest. The nearest competing airport is Vienna up to 100 km away. Proximity to such a competitor is not appropriate. With greater hub distance the score increases.
- Restrictions – restrictions on operating hours, e.g. German airports have noise restrictions at night.
- Maintenance – available aircraft maintenance is an important factor for air operators in establishing a base. The assessment was based on the number of type certificates held by airport providers of these services.
- Forwarders – the presence of freight forwarders directly at the airport is an important factor for optimising the transport chain. The evaluation was based on the number of freight forwarders at the airport.
- Growth – average of the annual growth/decline trends in tonnes handled in % over 5 years. The reference period is 2018-2022.

5. Evaluation – to define the potential a weighted average was used, that is, the weight and score of each factor of a given airport was multiplied. The sum of these parameters was divided by the sum of all weights (1). Subsequently, the resulting potential values of the single airport comparisons were compared. Calculation for Prague:

$$CAP_{PRG} = \sum \frac{(w_t * s_{PRG}) + (w_i * s_{PRG}) + \dots + (w_g * s_{PRG})}{w_t + w_i + w_r + w_{ch} + w_f + w_m + w_h + w_{gdp} + w_g} \quad (1)$$

CAP_{PRG} – cargo airport potential Prague

w – weight (*t* tonnes, *i* infrastructure, *ch* charges, *f* forwarders, *m* maintenance, *h* hubs, *gdp* GDP, *g* growth)

s – score level (1-5, tonnes for LEJ and FRA 10)

Table 1 Scoring system for comparing cargo potential of airports

Factors (weight)	Score levels				
	1	2	3	4	5
Infrastructure (5)	Absence of cargo terminals or logistics Absence of special cargo facilities	ILS CAT I Facilities for certain types of special cargo Logistics centres Cargo terminal Annual capacity up to 70,000 tonnes	ILS CAT III A Facilities for all types of special cargos Logistics centres Cargo terminal Annual capacity up to 300,000 tonnes	Annual capacity up to 500 thousand tonnes Connection to railway 2 RWY	Annual capacity over 500 thousand tonnes Extensive logistics centres and freight terminals All facilities
GDP (5) Country, per capita CZK	to 9,700	9,7001 to 19,500	19,501 to 29,300	29,301 to 39,100	39,001 and more
Tonnes (4) Thousands	0 to 10,000	10,001 to 20,000	20,001 to 50,000	50,001 to 100,000	100,001 and more
Charges (4) CZK	56,000 and more	42,001 to 56,000	28,001 to 42,000	14,001 to 28,000	to 14,000
Hub (4) km	0 to 70	71 to 140	131 to 210	211 to 280	281 and more distant
Restrictions (4)	Cargo only by exception	Restricted day traffic	Restricted night traffic	Restricted number of movements at night	No restrictions
Maintenance (3) Number of type certificates	0 to 2	3 to 4	5 to 6	7 to 9	10 and more
Forwarders (2) Number of them	0 to 8	9 to 16	17 to 24	25 to 32	33 and more
Growth (1) %	- 18 to - 10	- 11 to - 1	- 2 to + 6	+ 7 to + 15	+ 16 and more

Source: authors based on Larrodé at al., 2018; Gardiner at al., 2005, Pileček, 2018; Pokloková, 2019

The method is not uniform, there is no fixed set of factors or weights, as it depends on the specific market and the objective being pursued. The development and modification of the method is influenced by the characteristics of the market and the decisions of the authors. The factors and their weights are set individually by the authors according to their own professional judgement. Our model builds on a previous model to quantify the growth potential of air cargo (Larrodé at al., 2018). The system of assigning each weight and two factors (operating hours and presence of forwarders) was taken from the publication that defined factors influencing cargo airlines' choice of airport. (Gardiner at al., 2005). The design of the overall processing is based on two other publications. These are articles that focus on comparisons for the purpose of evaluating tourism potential (Pileček, 2018) (Pokloková, 2019).

4. RESULTS

With a population of over 10.5 million, the Czech Republic is the ninth largest country in the European Union, by GDP it has a ranking of 13 in the EU (Trading Economics, 2023). It is strategically located in the centre of Europe. Short, medium and long-haul flights can be operated from the country. There are 19 countries within a radius of 800 km, including Germany, Austria, France and Switzerland. 800 km is the length from which it is advisable to replace ground transport with air transport. Shorter flights include cargo time to the airport and cargo time from the airport, which reduces the efficiency of using air travel, also in terms of cost. Within Europe, shorter routes are mainly operated by integrators who consolidate and distribute shipments worldwide. From the Czech Republic, it would be possible to operate routes to distant hubs such as Houston (9,000 km) or Hong Kong (8,500 km). For example, by Boeing 777 F, with a range of 9,500 km and a maximum take-off weight of 347 kg.

4.1 Analysis of the Czech Cargo Market

From the Czech Republic, scheduled cargo flights are operated from three airports: Prague, Brno and Ostrava. Prague has three cargo terminals and there are several logistics parks in the vicinity, but there is a lack of a rail connection, which will not be implemented soon. There are 5 scheduled air cargo services and 1 belly cargo service from Prague (flight number/route/frequency/aircraft type/operator): 1. FedEx 3V4006/Paris-Prague-Gdansk-Nuremberg-Paris/4x weekly/Boeing 737-800 BCF/ASL Belgium; 2. FedeEx 3V4563/Paris-Katowice-Kaunas-Prague-Paris/4x-5x weekly/Boeing 737-800 BCF/ASL Belgium; 3. Turkish Airlines TK6296/Istanbul-Prague-Istanbul, occasional stopover in Budapest or Vilnius/1x-2x weekly/Airbus A330-200 F or Airbus A310-300/ULS Airlines Cargo; 4. Qatar Airways QR8232/Doha-Budapest-Prague-Doha/2x weekly/Boeing 777 F or Boeing 747-400 F/AirACT or Compass Air Cargo; 5. UPS 5X294/Cologne-Prague-Budapest-Prague-Cologne/5x weekly/Boeing 757-200 F/UPS); 6. EK140/Prague-Dubai/daily/Boeing 777-300 ER/Emirates. The Emirates passenger line has the largest share of 27.6% of imports to Prague, while it accounts for 20.3% of exports to this country. Although it is not a cargo line, it is significant in terms of cargo volume. Germany accounts for the largest share of exports at 21.8% (imports 25.4%). DHL does not have a line to Prague and transports cargo by road to its hub in Leipzig. The import/export ratio from Prague is comparable 53.4%/46.6% (table 2).

Table 2 Import and export from/to Prague in tonnes handled cargo, June 2022 – October 2023

Country	To Prague	From Prague	
UAE	5,933.7	3,815.7	
Germany	5,463.3	4,106.8	
Hungary	2,968.7	2,090.9	
Turkey	2,396.5	2,185.3	
South Korea Only 3-4/23	210.3	134.7	
Qatar	156.3	1,827.9	
Poland	306.85	818	
Switzerland	291.7	-	
Portugal	155.7	150.4	
Lithuania	332.4	-	
Spain	103.55	252.7	
Israel	63.2	135.6	
France	2,736.6	2,694.5	
UK	34.5	262.8	
USA Only 6-9/22	330.4	309.2	
Total	21,483.7 (53,4%)	18,784.5 (46,6%)	40,268.2 (100%)

Source: Eurostat, 2023

There are 2 cargo routes operating from Brno in the period under review: 1. DHL/Leipzig-Brno-Leipzig/working days/ Airbus A321 P2F/Titan Airways; 2. FedEx 5O4639/Paris-Nurenberg-Katowice-Brno-(Munich)-Paris/Monday-Thursday/Boeing 737 BCF/ASL Airlines. According to Eurostat data, flights from Germany carry an average of 10 tonnes per flight. On average, 13 tonnes are exported to Germany. Poland imports an average of 4 tonnes and France exports 5 tonnes. 87% of the volume goes to Germany and 10% to France. Brno does not have sufficient equipment for efficient cargo operations. There are 2 cargo routes operating from Ostrava and one scheduled charter to Tashkent: 1. DHL QY5571/Ostrava-Leipzig/working days/Boeing 737-400, sometimes Boeing 757 or Boeing 737-800 BCF/Cargo Air or Swiftair; 2. UPS WT1907/Ostrava-Cologne on the Rhine/working days/ATR 42-300 F/Swiftair; 3. Uzbekistan Airways HY3546/Ostrava-Tashkent/two

times a week/Boeing 767-300/EGT Express. The line to Tashkent provides a connection to Asia, with goods also flowing through Tashkent as consolidated goods to and from Europe. According to Eurostat data, 40% of all volumes for the period under review were to Uzbekistan and almost 50% of volumes were to Germany. The remaining 10% are ad hoc flights to other destinations. Ostrava Airport has all the equipment, three cargo terminals and is being modernized rapidly. Compared to Prague Airport, it is equipped with a direct connection to the railway. There are logistics centres and industrial zones in its vicinity. Over the last five years, the volume of air cargo handled at this airport has doubled. In the last two years, 2021 and 2022, it handled around 15,000 tonnes of cargo per year. Ostrava is a suitable airport for base of air cargo in the country and is a competitive airport in terms of cargo with respect to Prague airport – the benefit is the connection to the railway; the handicap is the location outside the effective radius of the capital city/centre of the Czechia. However, its location within Europe is attractive.

The Czech Republic exports engineering and automotive products, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, electronics and animals. Textiles, military goods and biological material are also shipped. Urgent shipments of spare parts for factories or means of transport are often transported. The airports in Prague and Ostrava, where the Czechia's largest industrial zones are located, have the highest volumes of cargo transport. In the Ostrava region, there is a Hyundai automotive factory, which uses Ostrava airport for transporting car parts, using DHL. Considering the location of the Czech Republic, it can be assumed which types of goods are transported by air the most. Textiles, shoes, leather, electronics and machinery parts flow from Asia to Europe. From North America, it is various manufacturing parts and parts for further processing, as well as electronics. Europe exports chemicals, pharmaceuticals, machinery products and parts. Africa imports fruit, vegetables, fresh flowers and seafood, as does Latin America, which imports mainly perishable goods (Boeing, 2022).

4.1.1 Comparison with Competing Markets

Compared to the European market leaders in terms of the highest volumes of handled cargo, air cargo volumes in the Czech Republic are lower. In 2022, 73.300 tonnes of air cargo flowed through the Czech Republic, up from 20 tonnes the year before (Eurostat, 2022), the EU total was 13.8 million tonnes in this year. Europe's cargo giant is neighbouring Germany (4.9 million tonnes in 2022), which transports the largest volumes to South Korea, China and the United States. The main German hubs are Frankfurt, Cologne/Bonn and Leipzig. Much of the product from the Czech Republic travels to German hubs, not only by air but also by road. Germany has several airlines based in Germany that handle cargo transportation - Lufthansa, Aerologic, DHL, UPS, FedEx, Amazon Air and Antonov Airlines. France (2.1 million tonnes in 2022) provides significant connections between Charles De Gaulle Airport and the United States, the United Arab Emirates, Germany and China. Major airlines such as Air France and FedEx are also based here. Belgium (1.7 million tonnes in 2022) operates two major airports, Brussels and Liege, and most flights are to China and the United States of America. It is the home country for ASL Airlines Belgium

(under the brand FedEx). From the Netherlands (1.5 million tonnes in 2022), most flights are to China, the United States of America and the United Arab Emirates. Amsterdam is the base for KLM and Martinair.

The air cargo giants operate connections to countries outside the European Union. In contrast, countries with smaller cargo volumes, like Slovakia or the Czech Republic, transport goods within the European Union. The highest volumes of cargo handled move via the United States, China and Germany. The strongest economic markets are North America, Europe and East Asia, which are also the most lucrative potential markets from the perspective of a Czech-based operator. Other suitable partners are neighbouring countries. None of these countries have any cargo-based airlines. Austria and Poland have strong national airlines, Austrian Airlines and LOT Polish Airlines, which also transport cargo on their long-haul scheduled flights as belly cargo on flights to the USA, South Korea, China, Japan and Thailand. Austria carries the most cargo to Korea, Germany and the UAE, Poland to the USA, UAE and Germany. Both countries ship more cargo outside the EU than within the EU. Slovakia has only one cargo route to Leipzig operated by Bluebird Nordic, which declared in March 2023 that it wanted to obtain a Slovak air operator's certificate to expand in the market. Another Slovak-registered airline is Air Explore, which added a Boeing 737-800 BCF freighter to its fleet in 2022, and currently has two of these aircraft. Like its other aircraft, it leases to other companies by way of ACMI leases. The only airline currently based in the Czech Republic is the national operator Czech Airlines, a member of the Smartwings Group, which operates two passenger Airbus A320 from its home base in Prague. It works closely with its partner Smartwings, which retains cargo capacity specifically for Czech Airlines Cargo clients on its scheduled routes. Czech Airlines (CSA), which recently celebrated its centenary, operates scheduled flights between Prague and Paris and Madrid. Smartwings operates scheduled flights with its Boeing 737 NG/MAX to Dubai, Tel Aviv and the Canary Islands, where it also frequently transports cargo. Thanks to CSA's connection with SkyTeam, it is possible to send goods on the alliance's partner flights to its network. CSA and Smartwings are certified to transport not only mail and cargo, but also dangerous materials including radioactive, animal, pharmaceutical and perishable goods. Currently, both companies provide belly cargo only and have no plans to divert their main revenue to cargo flights.

4.2 Questionnaire Survey

From which region or state do you have the greatest demand? 64% from Prague, 36% together from the Central Bohemia and Moravia-Silesia regions, from South Moravian Region 32%, from USA 16%.

What % of your cargo volumes are transported outside the EU? 29.2% of respondents send between 10% and 20% of their shipments outside the EU. 25% of companies send 60% of their shipments outside EU and 20.8% send 10% of their shipments outside the EU.

Which continents do your non-European orders flow to? The highest demand is confirmed for routes to Asia and North America, between 68% and 80%, and 22% to South America.

Which factors most influence your choice for air cargo? Total price 88% and total transport time 76%.

Which airport would you use for your air destinations? 80% Prague, 20 % Ostrava airport.

How much of your current road transport costs would aviation save you? 68% of respondents reported up to 10% of the cost.

Which country would be lucrative for you to connect by air? 24% of respondents would like a direct link with the USA, 20% with China, followed by minority responses from South America, Australia, Mongolia, Norway, Africa, and Ukraine. 20% of respondents said they would send to any country as needed.

The results suggest that there is demand in the Czechia for direct flights to Asia (specifically China) and to USA. The key factors are price and total transport time. The most suitable airport for the implementation of the concept is Prague, as most customers are from the Central Bohemian Region. A direct line to the destination would save the freight forwarders up to 10% of the road transport costs.

4.3 Comparative Method

The results of the comparison with competing airports are interesting (table 3). Cargo hubs LEJ and FRA are big players with the biggest score. Prague has a higher potential than Bratislava, Katowice, Wroclaw, Nuremberg and Berlin.

Table 3 Potential of selected airports – comparison

Factors (weight)	PRG	BTS	VIE	KTW	WRO	BUD	LEJ	FRA	NUE	MUC	BER
Infrastructure (5)	3	2	4	2	2	4	5	5	2	5	3
GDP (5)	3	3	5	2	2	2	5	5	5	5	5
Tonnes (4)	3	2	5	3	1	5	10	10	1	5	3
Charges (4)	4	1	3	3	2	3	4	4	3	4	4
Hub (4)	3	1	4	4	5	4	5	3	3	5	3
Restrictions (4)	5	5	3	5	5	5	4	2	5	2	2
Maintenance (3)	5	2	3	3	1	3	4	5	1	3	3
Forwarders (2)	4	2	5	2	2	3	4	5	2	5	2
Growth (1)	1	2	2	4	2	4	3	2	1	1	5
Total score	3,56	2,28	3,94	3,03	2,53	3,66	5,16	4,78	2,84	4,19	3,31

Source: authors

Bratislava has the lowest score of all airports. It has high charges. The airport does not try to focus on cargo handling, nor is there sufficient demand from freight forwarding companies. This is probably due to the proximity to Vienna airport (1 hour

drive by highway). Katowice is located near Ostrava, which is a big competitive challenge for both. Katowice Airport is developing rapidly, the number of tonnes handled is growing and the airport infrastructure is being modernised. It has flexible operating hours, but higher charges compared to Czech airports. Its disadvantage is also the low number of freight forwarders in the area. Wrocław has a lower potential due to the low number of forwarders, which corresponds to the slow growth in the volume of tonnes transported. Apart from Ryanair's maintenance centre, it has no aircraft maintenance services. Nuremberg and Berlin share Germany's high GDP per capita. Nuremberg has a lower infrastructure score, relatively high fees, poor maintenance and a low number of forwarders. Berlin has good tonnage growth and favourable charges but has few forwarders and limited operating hours.

In addition to the giants Leipzig and Frankfurt, Vienna, Munich and Budapest airports have higher potential compared to Prague. The infrastructure of Vienna Airport is outstanding. Austria has the highest GDP per capita of all the countries reviewed. This contributes to the development of air transport. Despite higher charges and limited night-time traffic, Vienna handles a high volume of cargo and profits from the presence of many freight forwarders. Munich Airport has excellent infrastructure and growth. However, limited operating hours or average availability of air maintenance reduce its potential.

Hungary's capital Budapest has an airport with good potential, even though GDP per capita is not very high. An airport without traffic restrictions with sufficient facilities shows growth. It has an average availability of maintenance and presence of forwarders. It is the biggest competitor of Prague airport in terms of scores. However, Prague is closer to Germany, which may attract more demand. This is due to the economic maturity of Western Europe and the cargo leadership of Germany.

5. DISCUSSION

This paper has new access compared to the previously cited studies on which it is based - the authors of the previous publications used a weighted sum for the final assessment. The method used in this paper uses a weighted average, which is a more balanced and representative indicator in the case of airport potential. In the case of weighted sum, a high value of the same factor can significantly affect the overall result. This could bias the final comparison of airports. The weighted average considers the importance of each factor through the weights, which allows a better reflection of the factors influencing the evaluation of airports.

A limitation of the work was the availability of information and data. As for the developed method, it may be influenced by the authors' decision. For example, there may be a case where the presence of a hub is positively evaluated, depending on the situation. This is a challenge for follow-up work that can develop or modify the methodology more. From our perspective, it would be very useful to complement this work by quantifying potential as the difference between market size and market potential, as mentioned in the introduction. If the numbers were available - the volumes of shipments that Czech freight forwarders would like to transport by air

compared to the volumes that are transported, it would be possible to quantify the potential using these values.

When we discuss the potential of the Czech freight base, it is necessary mentioning two key facts. The first is the complexity of market entry, both economic and procedural. This certainly has a major influence on why no one has yet launched such a business plan in the Czech Republic. Currently, the Czech airline Smartwings is for sale and one of the possible buyers is the German Lufhansa group or similarly strong companies. Their market power, consolidated services and strong partnerships could be enough to create cargo base in Prague. The second key issue from our point of view is infrastructure: a new parallel runway at Prague airport, which has long been discussed, and connecting the main Czech airport to the railway. These are large and financially challenging projects. However, investment in infrastructure is essential for the prosperity of the country. If Prague had these facilities, its score would be significantly higher.

6. CONCLUSION

Prague and Ostrava airports are suitable for full cargo operations. Based on the results of the questionnaire survey, we have identified Prague as the airport with the greatest potential. Demand is concentrated in the capital city and central Bohemia. The highest number of logistics centres and shippers are in this area. We contacted these companies, and the results of the survey showed an interest in air services. The highest demand is confirmed from Prague, followed by the Central Bohemia and Moravia region. The declared demand from abroad is from the USA. The freight forwarders reported that goods are also shipped outside the European market. The USA, China, South America, Australia, Mongolia, Norway, Africa and Ukraine were identified as markets for which it would be appropriate to use the air routes from Prague.

To determine the potential of Prague as a base for cargo transport, we used a comparative method. Comparisons were made between Prague and competing airports in neighbouring countries. The method is based on the determination of evaluation factors to which weights are assigned. Each factor has levels from 1 to 5, with 5 being the highest level. The method reflects the approach of the authors, and their work is inspired by several analyses. The factors, weights and levels of the factors are based on the authors' decisions. The highest possible score according to the chosen score is 4.2 (4.8 for hub airports). Prague received a score of 3.56. Its potential is higher than that of competing airports Bratislava, Katowice, Wroclaw, Nuremberg and Berlin. Airports in Vienna, Munich and Budapest scored higher. Leipzig and Frankfurt are giants that cannot be competed with as they already handle many times higher volumes than the other airports compared.

Prague has the potential to become a Central European cargo hub because none of the neighbouring countries except Germany has a cargo airline based there. Polish, Slovak and Austrian freight forwarders could be as interested in Prague as domestic companies. Analysis of the current Czech market has shown that some cargo is transported from Europe via other European hubs to more distant countries. This is an

already stabilised part of the Prague market, which could grow once a base is established. A rail link connecting to Prague airport and a new parallel runway at this airport would undoubtedly help. Yet these are factors that are described as 'unnecessary because there is no demand'. Demand would be generated by these constructions. We consider this to be a very important investment in terms of future development.

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ROMANIA'S INTERMODAL PARADOX: THE ROLE OF CONSTANTA PORT IN RAIL TRANSPORTATION REVIVAL

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to investigate the unprecedented and accelerated investments in Romania's railway sector, triggered by the cargo volume overflow at Constanta Port and spike of transiting Ukrainian cereals for export. Secondary data on rail freight dynamics (ITU and TEU containers, tonnage), the share of intermodal transportation and the deterioration of the rail transportation infrastructure in the last 5 years (2019-2023) is analyzed using descriptive statistics. The paper uses primary data obtained from on-site fieldwork (empirical research) to map out and compile datasets for Romania's main intermodal terminals. The case study also provides a comprehensive overview on Constanta Port's paramount role in reviving an idle network of cross-border railway stations and prompting other relevant strategic rail hub investments. Overall cargo volumes handled at intermodal terminals increased (over 700,000 containers and 8 million tonnes, 2023), but further growth is still hindered by uncompetitive transit times on Romanian railways. Findings outline an unprecedented geopolitical context where public railway investments for repairs and modernizations are highly prioritized, in close coordination with private rail freight terminal operators. The paper highlights the compound effect of targeted synergic public-private investments in Constanta's hinterland connections (railway network and intermodal terminals) to increase dry bulk handling capacity and process higher levels of inbound and outbound throughputs. Despite railway shortcomings, new intermodal terminal investments continue to be driven by logistics companies, in anticipation of fully modernized rail freight corridors and potential business growth opportunities. Future research topics could be directed towards quantifying possible correlations between intermodal terminal's connectivity, transit time predictability and cost-competitiveness for distances of 300-450 km.

Keywords: intermodal transportation, rail freight, containerization, transshipment, intermodal terminal

1. INTRODUCTION

Rail freight transported volumes (48.86 million tonnes) in Romania decreased by over 10% in 2023, most (79.3%) being destined for national destinations. Overall share of rail transportation is rather constant in recent years, but private rail freight and logistics companies have continuously increased their share of shipped volumes, while the national railway company's proportion has dropped to only 31.2% (2023). In 2023, freight transport volumes in Romania neared half a billion tonnes, with only a 0.64% year-on-year increase (471.6 million tonnes). Most goods are still transported by road in Romania (68.14% share and 1% decrease since 2022), despite the country having one of the densest railway networks in the EU (10,615 km) and an extensive inland waterway (Danube). Maritime transportation volumes increased by 15% in 2023, with the Black Sea accounting for a similar share (14.68%) in total tonnage, while railway freight decreased by 11.5% and now has a share of only 10.36% of cargo volumes. With a 12% increase in overall volumes transported on the Danube River, inland waterways account for 6.80% share of total freight, while air cargo has only 0.01% contribution to yearly tonnage (2023).

Despite a slight 1% decrease, trucking still has more than two thirds of all freight volumes (over 68%) with more than 321 million tonnes transported (2023). Romania's road transportation sector is driven by trade within the EU, 95% of all shipped goods (94.8% incoming and 94.4% outgoing) are with EU countries (Germany, Italy and Hungary account for almost 50% of volumes). The highest share of long-distance road transport of containers on total road freight transport of containers, based on tonnes, was recorded by Lithuania (44.4%) in 2022, followed by Romania (35.9%), Slovenia (21.0%) and Bulgaria (20.7%). Over 300 million tonnes of goods were transported on Romanian railways (2000), but average volumes are now at around 50 million tonnes/year, only a fraction (15%) of previous capacity. This massive decrease (over 80%) is in direct conjunction with the lack of investment and maintenance of overall railway infrastructure in the past 2 decades. Average freight speed has had a similar plummet (over 70%) from 57 km/h (2000) to 15.86 km/h (2023), outlining major maintenance issues even across main and major rail lines. To cross the country by rail on a main railway line, from Curtici to Constanta (832 km), a regular freight train normally needs at least 22 hours, but delays are common and can increase transit time (scheduling, stoppages, weather) to 3 days or even 7-12 days, especially for longer or heavier trains, challenging predictability.

Prior to the bustle caused by the cereal inflow from the Ukraine, during the summer season Constanta Port was always congested due to its dry bulk activity increase (running at only 60% of its operational capacity). Dry bulk handling capacity in the port's terminals was operational, but its hinterland connections were neglected and sometimes grains and/or other goods could neither enter nor leave the port area, bottlenecking other cargo volumes. Growing volumes in recent years (up to 5% per year, on average) and increasingly extensive blockages were more and more frequent at the port's terminals, underscored in the first year after Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Since Russia's invasion, over 33 million tonnes of Ukrainian cereal exports (35% of total) transited Romania (over 60% of freight that was transported via the EU solidarity corridor). The Black Sea Grain Initiative (BSGI) was as a temporary deal

(2022-2023) to safely export cereals (and other vital foodstuffs) from Ukraine through the Black Sea despite the ongoing war. Ships leaving the port of Odessa (Ukraine) and passing the Russian-Turkish-UN inspection in Istanbul (Turkey) incurred higher insurance premiums and waiting times (4 times higher, on average) than the alternative sea leg of the route through the port of Constanta (Romania). Since around 78% of freight shipments (including Ukrainian cereals) arrive by sea, these cargo volumes shifted towards Romania's Black Sea port, increasing additional influx. Over 45 million tonnes of non-agricultural products (iron ores, steel and others), in addition to cereals are also contributing to Ukrainian exports (2023). EU Solidarity Lanes have a 60% export share of all Ukrainian freight, the remaining 40% transits through the Black Sea (90% of grain, oilseeds and related products) towards Europe, China and Africa.

Since Russia's invasion of Ukraine (2022) railway investments in Romania have surged and modernizations have accelerated at an unprecedented rate, in close coordination with the private sector's logistics companies (Constanta Port and intermodal terminal operators), to shift cargo volumes (at least partially) away from port terminal operations (running at full capacity) and truck haulage (congested).

The paper's objective is to provide a comprehensive overview upon the unexpected dynamic of recent intermodal terminal development spurred on by Constanta Port's recent inflow of Ukrainian cereals. This case study delves into the following research questions (RQ): To what extent have recent public and private investments in Romania's railway sector been effective in addressing the challenges posed by the increased cargo volumes from Ukraine at Constanta Port? (RQ1); what are the most prevalent constraints hindering the development of intermodal transportation in Romania? (RQ2); can the current geopolitical context be leveraged to transition more cargo volumes towards rail on medium-term? (RQ3).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Romania's railroads are deteriorating faster than they are repaired (Haralambides, 2017). There are 473 areas (a total of 930 km of railway, 2024) where trains are forced to run at low speed to avoid derailment while most of the network (65-70% of 10,615 km) is due for major repairs. Trains can operate at over 100 km/h only on about 35% of the total railway network (3,746 km). As of 2022, there are 1,562 mapped areas where speed reductions to 10-15 km/h are mandatory due to the deteriorated and fissured tracks (Saeedi et al., 2017). In 2023 several restrictions were removed (on 555 km), but new ones were introduced, which in total account for 764 kilometers. Around 450 restrictions are planned to be lifted in 2024 through the so-called "quick wins" works (inexpensive and fast-to-implement). The possibility of reaching a maximum speed of 160 km/h is restricted to just two CFR routes: M800 Bucharest-Constanta (225 km) and M200 Sighisoara-Curtici (186 km). This translates to only 411 kilometers (3.87% of the total network length) and is further contingent on railway operators possessing compatible rolling stock (Notteboom et al., 2022).

Shifting more traffic towards rail or IWW, for an improved and more sustainable overall transport mix (Demir et al., 2019) according to EU targets (30% target share

of rail freight transport by 2030) seems unrealistic even in medium-term (Castelein et al., 2019). Extreme weather is also an impeding factor, as higher temperatures impose reduced speeds (summer) and sometimes (during winter) unloading ships in Constanta Port might not be possible if the connecting journey implies rail haulage (Zecevic et al., 2017). Discretionary allocation of public funds mostly towards road infrastructure projects and maintenance works is also coupled with a low priority for the railway sector. A more often implemented cost-cutting policy for rail transportation has constantly reduced passenger traffic, indirectly discouraging the use of trains (Maslaric et al., 2019). High turnover of managers with low industry-relevant professional skills and competence and short-term appointments add to the challenges of drawing up a consistent investment and modernization plan (Kine et al., 2022). Nevertheless, private railway operators have taken over previously cancelled routes by CFR and made them profitable, whilst also competing on other busier passenger routes. Private freight train operators have enjoyed accelerated development (Rozic et al., 2022) and constant market share increases (78.44% in 2022) by serving routes where the national railway company underperformed.

The length of public railway lines in operation totals 10,615 km (2023), of which 10,514 km (99.1%) are standard gauge lines and 91 km (0.9%) broad gauge lines. 85% of railway lines (9,000 kilometers) are in need of rehabilitation due to varying degrees of damage, but only 638 kilometers (7% of the total network) are slated for modernization in 2024. Over the last 35 years Romania has decreased its railway network by more than 700 km (-6.5%), from 11,348 km in 1990. Traffic on railway line 102 Bucharest-Giurgiu (61 km) resumed in June 2024 after almost 20 years since the collapse of the Gradistea Bridge (2005) after works finished on the 12.86 km damaged portion and made the entire section active again. The average speed of freight trains in Romania is almost thrice lower than trucking (40-45 km/h), mostly due to restrictions on degraded stretches and number of necessary stops along the way (single line, passenger trains, scheduling). This makes it even more challenging for shorter hauls (Gruhonjic et al., 2021), where a couple of stops (many hours in certain places) and slow container (TEU) processing times at customs (insufficient capacity) make freight trains uneconomical (Tadic et al., 2021) for distances shorter than 300-450 km (as of 2022).

Another noteworthy challenge, in addition to low average freight train speeds, is the increasing number of accidents, mostly due to poor railway infrastructure. Certain stretches are closed with detours being employed by both regular routes (Roy et al., 2022) and the ones having to change course, this extra traffic volume increasing the likelihood of unexpected issues and higher chance of unreliable transit times for freight trains (Archetti et al., 2022). Despite its shortcomings, some private logistics operators have surprisingly opened intermodal terminals and regularly use freight trains for part of their shipments (Garcia-Alonso et al., 2019), anticipating completion of ongoing projects and due investments in Romania's main railway lines.

Rail freight operators complain that in recent years modernizations resulted in the removal of many lines (used for temporary parking of freight trains) even in larger stations. Curtici currently has only 22/40 lines for parking trains and wagons (55%) and Arad 29/45 lines (64%) after modernization. The border station Episcopia Bihor (near Oradea) has not been modernized by CFR and still has its 17 lines, supporting

the new EBIT terminal. Since 2001 rail freight volumes transported in Romania decreased by 35%, the highest value in Europe, while average commercial speed of freight trains has decreased by almost 50% (from 30 km/h to 15.86 km/h, 2023), making rail haulage even more challenging for logistics companies (Ge et al., 2021).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current research paper uses primary and secondary data on intermodal transportation (ITU and TEU containers, tonnes), dry bulk cargo volumes (mainly Ukrainian cereals) and their share in overall freight traffic. Primary data was sourced by conducting empirical research through intermodal terminal fieldwork, on-site observation, data gathering, including comparing terminal operators' files and databases with practical research, subject to the specific terms of the NDAs signed prior to the private field visits of each intermodal terminal. Raw data (secondary) was obtained from European statistics databases, official releases of the National Institute of Statistics, Constanta Port Annual reports and Pro Infrastructura Association's records. All data and information presented, analyzed and compiled within the current paper was consented for publication and does not contain any reference that might be subject to breaching the agreed terms of the signed NDAs by the authors.

Descriptive statistical methods were applied to investigate the 5 year evolution, tendencies and recurring characteristics within the time-series data (2019-2023) on intermodal freight traffic (ITU and TEU containers). Year-to-year percentage variations, multi-year averages and relative share in total traffic of dry bulk and other cargo types were analyzed to comprehend variability and central tendency of absolute cargo volumes. Data cleaning was required to correct some inconsistencies within preliminary data obtained from certain sources (reports and records). Data retrieval, record matching and standardizing units of measurement were performed to complete the dataset and make compiled data homogenous. A mix of qualitative and quantitative methods was used to underline empirical data gathered throughout the case studies (mapping and compiling data on main rail border crossings, their connectivity to main railway lines and intermodal terminals' handling capacities) in order to provide a comprehensive overview and broader understanding of the topic.

This study's main strong points and added value is related to primary data and practical insights sourced from actual intermodal terminal operators and their freight traffic volumes, enabling pertinent causal relationships. Reliable secondary data was used for validation (intermodal terminal operators, relevant associations and public European and Romanian authorities), adding further inferences and broader context to this research. The research paper's main limitations arise from not being able to present more underlying evidence of its assumptions and claims, due to them not being subject of disclosure, as previously mentioned. Another issue might be access to a similar amount and range of primary data by other researchers, as well as the openness of terminal operator representatives to share such an extensive amount of data for research purposes (study replicability). Finally, current findings are related to a very specific geopolitical context (massive inflow of transiting Ukrainian cereals), where both public authorities and private operators have coordinated efforts in prioritizing

rail and terminal investments for handling excess cargo inflows, a very unique and unusual real-life context.

4. RESULTS

Around 400,000 TEU and over 2,600 tonnes were handled in 2017, but the degrading of the railway network (train breakdowns, derailling incidents and railway accidents) and its lack of maintenance and investment have reduced freight activity and handled throughput. Despite an overall decline in intermodal transportation (11% decrease in tonnage and 40% in TEU containers), the share of private operators' (logistics and rail freight companies) activity has increased, as CFR currently only holds less than a third of volumes. An overview of the declining activity in intermodal terminals is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 Romania – Annual goods transported by rail in intermodal transport units

year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	5-year average (2019-2023)
ktonnes	2,114	2,164	2,154	1,735	1,866	2,006
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	-18.72	2.37	-0.46	-19.45	7.55	-11.73
TEU	344,212	296,830	279,891	227,691	205,445	270,813
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	-15,36	-13,77	-5,71	-18,65	-9,77	-40.31

Source: Eurostat, own processing

25 million tonnes of Constanta Port's cargo volumes (2023) come from the commercial relationship with Ukraine, grains originating in this country representing over 14 million tonnes (56%). Ukraine's cereal exports transiting Romania mainly arrive through the Black Sea and the Danube River. Total share of dry bulk (cereals) shipped via the Constanta Port increased by 8 percentage points (78% in 2023), while 15% of volumes are handled on the Danube's main seaports. Rail (6%) and road volumes (1%) have a smaller proportion of overall hauled tonnage. An overview of cargo volumes shows significant increases were registered in the category of oilseeds, iron ores, petroleum products and fertilizers. Constanta Port's hinterland railway network was stalled in 2022, but recent modernizations are starting to make intermodal transportation a more widespread option, although there is still a lot of work to be done. Only 1% of total network (125 km) was rehabilitated and a third of CFR Marfa's intermodal terminals (9/26) were still active in 2023. Rehabilitating terminals involves modernizing buildings, as well as ITU (intermodal transport units) and TEU storage platforms, crane runways, new access roads to the terminal and other facilities, new and modern equipment and state of the art integrated technologies. Only one marshalling yard (Palas) out of the port's facilities is functional, but its

capacity is restricted to 20% (only 5 out of 25 lines are operational). The remaining marshalling yards and the port's two train ferries have been inactive since 2011, limiting traffic management around the port area. During peak season in the Port of Constanța, waiting times for unloading increased exponentially for all means of transportation: up to 30 days (freight trains), up to 10 days (trucks) and/or up to 60 days for several convoys of barges (400-500 barges, congesting waiting area). Overcapacity in the port's cereal terminals also meant higher costs for transportation services (trucking and railway companies, shipping lines) for certain routes: up to 80-90% per ton (River Danube ports), up to 60-70% per ton (from Curtici Cargo rail terminal) and/or up to 50-70% per ton (short haul by truck). Scheduling was very tight for already planned freight, but new incoming shipments (larger quantities) could be idled for up to 1.5-2 months before delivery. Queuing, congestion and bottlenecks put pressure on Constanta Port's operations and handling capacity and outlined the need for infrastructure investments to better coordinate and consolidate the arrival of cargo volumes.

The conflict in Ukraine urged unprecedented outlays in the bordering regions' railway sector, while repairs and modernizations were executed at a decent speed, which is rare in Romania. Investments focused on increasing cargo handling capacity (mostly for cereals, TEUs and liquid bulk) in the cross-border area by doubling railway lines (Porumbesti-Halmeu (5 km) and Socola-Ungheni (17 km) stretches) and/or by electrifying connecting sections (Nicolina-Ungheni Prut (20 km) stretch). Transport capacity for handling Ukrainian cargo was increased after Romania took over 1200 dry and liquid bulk wagons (1000 for grain transport and 200 for oil products) and 35 locomotives from the EU (2022) and prioritized repairs of existing wagons and locomotives used for the same purpose.

Routing Ukrainian cereals to Constanta Port initially created 2 logistics problems: although entering Romania in freight trains, Ukrainian cereals could only enter the port of Constanta via trucks (no railway entry access), in addition to a different gauge system at the Romanian border. This causes freight trains to be delayed at the border as well, until the changeover is made from one gauge to another (Russian gauge/broad, 1520 mm, to standard gauge, 1435 mm, in Romania). Moreover, once transferred from trains to trucks, the Ukrainian cereals cause blockages in the port, competing for unloading slots with already scheduled incoming shipments and domestic farmers' harvests (also delivered with trucks). Rail carriers needed to allocate additional capacity to take over the new transport flows from Ukraine, as their resources (locomotives, wagons and employees) were already assigned and budgeted for scheduled freight forwarding service contracts (especially towards Western Europe). Short notice efforts were made to assign and deploy rolling stock and rail cargo professionals quickly to take on the growing traffic coming from Romania's neighbor to the north. Challenges included changing bogies from Soviet broad to standard gauge, which depending on the wagons, load and length of freight trains could take up to 1-3 days, compared to passenger trains (1 hour). Cargo transfer type was also important as transferring Russian-type wagons to Romanian bogies (transposition) is a lot more labour intensive than goods being completely transferred from one wagon to another, without changing bogies (transshipment). Transposition also implies having a sufficient fleet of bogies to be available for the transposition of

the goods (border stations) before returned after completing the journey to Constanta Port and back. Moreover, special adapter cars (barrier vehicles) are sometimes needed (2 such wagons/freight train) because Russian-type wagons have a different coupler than the EU wagons. Barrier vehicles (match wagons or translator coaches) are used to convert between non-matching railway coupler types and also have to be taken back to the border station, so they can be reused for further shipments. An overview of the main border crossings (Ukraine-Romania) is shown in Figure 1, their intermodal connections and transit times to Constanta Port is provided in Table 2.

Figure 1 Romania – map of main railway border crossings (Ukraine-Romania)

Source: Pro Infrastructura Association, own processing

The most intense crossing is in the North of Romania, as it concentrates both road and rail inflows and has the Dornesti intermodal terminals (TTD, RTD) at only 15 km to consolidate all cereal and TEU shipments towards Constanta Port or other transit hubs. Terminal operators in Dornesti built 2.4 km of railway and increased handling capacity from 5-8 wagons/train (beginning of 2022) to loading 1.5-1.8 tonnes/train in only 2 days (end of 2022). This region (North) has 4/9 main entry points from the Ukraine within 114 km of border: Vicovu de Sus, Siret, Racovat (road) and Vicsani (rail). Vicsani reopened 13 railway lines (6 standard and 7 broad gauge lines) The railway crossing between Vadu Siret (UA)-Vicsani (RO) benefited from the creation of dedicated customs control points for faster processing of incoming freight trains. The Ukrainian border city's railway station (Vadu Siret) has gauge change facilities (broad-standard). The shortest railway access route (Ukraine-Romania) is from Vadu Siret (UA) through the border crossing at Vicsani (RO). Vadu

Siret (UA) railway station is equipped with gauge change facilities, allowing trains to shift from broad (Ukraine) to standard gauge (Romania). Incoming cereals, from both trains and trucks, are loaded into Romanian dry bulk freight trains (32 wagons/train and 6,400 tonnes/day) at Dornesti (at only 15 km from the border) and transported to Constanta Port, easing truck congestion on the roads from North-East Romania (400 trucks/day pass the Porubne (UA)-Siret (RO) border crossing, on average) and reducing transit time.

Another intense border crossing point is Diakove (UA)-Halmeu (RO) in North-West Romania, as the border towns have both road and railway customs and an intermodal terminal connection in Transylvania (AIP) for further sea export at the Port of Constanta or continued transit towards the EU via the intermodal terminal in Curtici (RAIT) at the Hungarian border. A number of 5 standard gauge lines (1,435 mm) and several other broad gauge lines (1,520 mm) became operational in Halmeu, reopened as part of a modernization program (summer 2022) to increase the railway station's handling capacity, in addition to 16 other lines and 47 railroad switches being modernized. This increased the number of crossings in Halmeu exponentially (from just 10 trucks/month in the early days of the war to 1,600 trucks/month in fall of 2022), all carrying Ukrainian cereals.

Table 2 Ukraine-Romania: main border crossings and intermodal hubs

region	Outbound (Ukraine)	Inbound (Romania)	Distance to Constanta Port [km]	via	Transit time [hours]	Reliability
Satu Mare (North-West)	Diakove (UA)	Halmeu (RO)	Decea (AIP): 866 (road)	A10 A1 A2	16-32	high (or average)
Satu Mare (North-West)	Diakove (UA)	Halmeu (RO)	Decea (AIP): 932 (rail)	M400 M300 M800	62	average (or low)
Maramures (North-West)	Solotvino (UA)	Sighetu Marmatiei (RO)	Decea (AIP): 855 (road)	A10 A1 A2	16-32	high (or average)
Suceava (North)	Porubne (UA)	Siret (RO)	Dornesti (TTD): 572 (road)	E85 A2	10-24	high (or average)
Suceava (North)	Vadu Siret (UA)	Vicsani (RO)	Dornesti (TTD): 705 (rail)	M500 M800	36	average (or low)
Galati (East)	Reni (UA)	Galati (RO)	Giurgiulesti (MD): 256 (rail) 186 nm (Black Sea)	M700 M800 Port (DN-Galati)	12-18	average (or low)

Source: Romanian Border Police, own processing

The Reni (UA)-Galati (RO) railway connection, which also passes through the Republic of Moldova, was rehabilitated in less than a month by CFR employees, making the line operational after 22 years. Within the project 780 wooden sleepers, 246 special wooden sleepers on switches and running lines and over 5,000 tonnes of small fastening material were replaced. First the Ukrainian freight trains pass through a cross-docking hub in Bender (14 km from Tiraspol) where they are consolidated and then exit through Giurgiulesti (MD), before arriving in Romania. Galati also handles rail shipments originating from Chornomorsk (through Reni) since there is a double gauge route between the transshipment area in Galati and the Giurgiulesti Port in Moldova. When demand is much higher than the operational capacity of the Giurgiulesti Port freight trains are re-routed via the Ungheni (MD)-Cristești Jijia (RO) border crossing where they use an alternative main railway line (M600) to reach Constanta (5 railway lines: 3 broad and 2 standard gauge lines). The Republic of Moldova also reopened, after 25 years, the Basarabasca (MD)-Berezine (UA) section, providing a shorter additional alternative for deliveries to Romania through Galati. Old lines are being modernized to allow the transport of grain and other products (especially metallurgical) between Romanian (Galati and Constanta) and Ukrainian ports (Odesa, Izmail, Reni, Chornomorsk or Belgorod-Dnestrovsky). Upon arrival in Galati, freight trains can continue their journey on rail to Constanta (the port's inner railway system has European gauge change facilities) or can be transhipped on the Danube to continue by water towards Romania's Black Sea port. Galati was also part of a rehabilitation program, to connect its railway station to the port with an extended double-gauge railway (3.5 km of broad gauge line and 1.5 km of standard gauge line), operationalizing its cereal storage silo (capacity: 35,000 tonnes) located in the port. Initially freight trains arrived with only 15 wagons/day, then increased load to 30 wagons/train, before a surge of 200 wagons were scheduled for arrival within less than 48 hours (summer 2023). In Galati, cereals can be loaded/unloaded by road (trucks), rail (standard and broad gauge trains) and the Danube River (barges and sea vessels) for further transit to Constanta Port. The 5 km of new railway lines increased transshipment capacity, reducing handling and transit times of freight trains originating from Ukraine.

The Solotvyno (UA)-Sighetu Marmatiei (RO) border crossing through the Tisza Bridge is an alternative road entry point (102 km) that can support Halmeu, in case of congestion, and also routes its incoming shipments towards the AIP intermodal terminal in Decea. 2 other railway border connections (Ukraine-Romania) are located in the North-West region within 102 km of each other, flanking Sighetu Marmatiei (Campulung la Tisa and Valea Viselui), but their practicality is limited, being used only if the main transit routes (Table 99) are congested. The Teresva (UA)-Câmpulung la Tisa (RO) double gauge railway connection (also connecting with Valea Viselui) was taken out of use because a wooden road bridge was opened over the Tisza between Solotvyno and Sighetu Marmatiei (2007). A new bridge, more adapted to modern road traffic is currently being built, execution being already under way in Sighetu Marmatiei (25% of total, as of 2024). Dilove (UA)-Valea Viselui (RO) has only a gauge of 1,520 mm and was taken out of use because it was heavily affected by the floods of 2006. Ukraine rebuilt the railway lines (via Rakhiv-Berlebash) in less than 2 months, but had to wait another 4 months before the works

on the Romanian side were also complete, to be able to actually use the crossing. An additional 6 pairs of trains/day could thus transit through this border crossing point and relieve up to 3.5 million tonnes of cargo/year according to Ukrainian Railways, Ukrzaliznytsia (UZ). Chornomorsk (UA)-Constanta (RO) line (through Albita border crossing) operates on a broad gauge (1520mm),but has European gauge change facilities in the port. Buzau railway station is on the M500 highway and reaches the Constanta port via the 702 Făurei–Fetești–Constanța line (railway distance: 207 km). The last active entry point (road) is Isaccea, on the right bank of the Danube (only 35 km from Tulcea), with a capacity of up to 48 trucks/ferry from the Ukrainian border town of Orlivka (crossing time: 90 minutes). Other former border railway crossings have been closed since almost 20 years, tracks are rusty and/or heavily degraded and their network connectivity is rather marginal. Considerable investments would thus have to be made if long and heavy freight trains were to pass through those areas (50-70km), making them uneconomical.

Average speeds on the Romanian railway network are unacceptably low. Trains sometimes transit a few hundred kilometers in more than 24 hours (2-3 days/outbound leg), making many freight carriers choose road haulage for this section. Freight trains arriving at the intermodal terminal in Curtici (RAIT) from Western European countries (the Netherlands, Belgium and/or Germany) usually have their final station here and their containers (full or empty TEU) are put on trucks, instead of continuing on the railway to Constanta, Pitesti or Craiova. Railport Arad (Curtici Cargo Center) is the first major intermodal transportation investor in Romania, operating a modern inland terminal (close to the Hungarian border), one of the largest in Central and Eastern Europe. Its main cargo volumes are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Freight volumes by rail at Railport Arad Intermodal Terminal (RAIT)

year/cargo handled [TEU]	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Railport Arad – Curtici (corridor VII)	86,012	87,357	96,052	128,379	167,981
<i>dynamic [%]</i>	<i>1.18</i>	<i>1.56</i>	<i>9.95</i>	<i>33.65</i>	<i>30.84</i>

Source: Railport Arad – Annual reports, own processing

With the increasing incoming cereals from the Ukraine taking up a more important part of Constanta Port’s handling activity (reduced Black Sea shipping slots), other goods were re-routed towards trucks and/or freight trains for transit towards customers in Western Europe. TEU container traffic increased 2 years in a row by more than 30% and had a record throughput of 167,981 units in 2023 (84% of the terminal’s maximum capacity). Despite Romania’s major railway network shortcomings, many projects for new intermodal terminals are currently being developed in strategic locations, as logistic hubs for economically developed regions with further growth potential and good infrastructure network access. A map of the operational (blue) and project terminals (red) is provided in Figure 2. Their handling capacity and links to main road, rail and other infrastructure (river, sea and/or airport) is summarized in Table 4.

Figure 2 presents the locations of the intermodal terminals in reference to Romania’s main railway sector (M200 Arad-Brasov, M300 Brasov-Bucharest and

M800 Bucharest-Constanta). Most terminals are located along the depicted railway section, which is part of both the Orient/East-Med (OEM) and Rhine-Danube (RDN) rail corridors and closely follows the A1 motorway. Oradea's 2 terminals are part of the M300 (Oradea-Cluj section is under execution, due 2027), Dornesti is connected to the M500 (Bucharest-Vicsani, planned for modernization), while the multimodal platform in Galati serves Romania's second largest seaport and largest port on the Danube.

Figure 2 Romania – map of intermodal terminals

Source: Pro Infrastructura Association, own processing

Romania's main intermodal terminals currently have an aggregate capacity of over 700,000 TEU (handling), 15,000 TEU (storage/day) and 8 million tonnes (processing/year). By 2030 the handling capacity of these terminals would increase by up to 15% for tonnage and over 35% for TEU containers. The new cereal handling railway terminal in Dornesti (TTD) has a share of over a third (36.59%) of overall tonnage. The terminals in Transylvania (AIP, TIS) cover a third of cargo tonnage (33.54%) and 12% of TEU container handling. The Arad terminals (RAIT, EBIT, IVT) have a share of almost two thirds (60.68%) of TEU handling, whilst Oradea is catching up and currently holds just short of a sixth (13.35%) in overall TEU container volumes.

Railport Arad (RAIT) handles up to 70% of all TEU hauled by rail (ISO containers and other ITU) connecting freight from Western to Eastern Europe through both railway corridors (OEM and RDN). Regular trains (5 round-trips) are scheduled every week for destinations in Central and Western Europe such as Budapest

(Hungary), Lambach (Austria), Hamburg (Germany), Genk (Belgium) or Tekirdag (Turkey). Ro-La operations (freight trains carrying trucks) are also possible on site, but their usage in Romania is very low and is decreasing in recent years. Fitting 4 trailer heads on a wagon also means 2 semitrailers/TEUs less (empty truckload) and extra handling costs involved (loading-unloading times, specialized personnel, height clearance along the railway), making the system less cost-efficient than conventional road haulage which in Romania is still very competitive compared to EU average. Curtici Cargo Center has attracted other intermodal investments nearby, such as Rail Hub Transylvania with connections to Slovenia (port of Koper), Germany (port of Duisburg and Hamburg), Belgium (port of Antwerp) or Turkey (transit through the port of Constanta). Rail Hub Transylvania (RHT) operates its own intermodal terminal in Vladimirescu (near Arad) with rail service connecting Romania to the North Sea Port. The North Sea Port is a multimodal port in the Netherlands, connecting its port areas of Vlissingen and Terneuzen to Ghent (Belgium) with ports in the United Kingdom and Italy. Transit time between Arad and Ghent is 56 hours/each way, departure takes place on the same day within a maximum of 12 hours from the arrival of the train at RHT terminal. A temperature-controlled warehouse (storage capacity: 1,500 tonnes) investment in under way for goods imported from countries such as Turkey, Poland and Germany. Arad South Terminal is a cereal hub for the Banat region, operated by Afluent and has 4 railway lines (350m each) connected to Orient/East Med corridor. At any time 2 trains can be handled at the same time (loading and/or unloading), currently only 10% of cargo volumes are cereals while the rest represent industrial products for export (Switzerland, Germany or Italy). Unreliable scheduling from Constanta Port is still the container terminal's main issue, transit times (via rail) ranging from 22-72 hours, challenging predictability.

Besides the Railport Arad intermodal terminal (RAIT) in Curtici, the Western region of Romania bordering Hungary has a further growing investment area: Oradea. Automotive industry multinational suppliers are based here (most recently Nokian has opened a new tire factory in 2023, after a 650 million euro investment), as well as storage facilities for MOL fuels (Tileagd) with over 160 million euros being invested in Bihor's 6 industrial parks (2022), of which 4 are located in Oradea's outskirts. Episcopia Bihor Intermodal Terminal (EBIT) in Oradea is the newest intermodal terminal in Romania (2023) and is operated by Routier European Transport and Cabooter Intermodal. EBIT offers connections to Germany (Ruhr basin and Benelux ports up North), France and Slovakia. The terminal has 2 railway tracks (700m each) and registered a number of 18,390 handlings (rail-in and rail-out handlings, between April-December 2023), can operate between 8-9 trains/month up to a maximum of 8 trains/day. Currently 4 trains/week (round trips) are operational towards Venlo (the Netherlands) with mostly automotive parts and products. Imported goods (via TEU containers) are currently shipped further with trucks until works on Episcopia-Cluj connecting railway line (166 km) are completed (by 2027). Work at CTPark Cargo Terminal within the International Airport is under way (since 2022), confirming Oradea's position as second largest market for logistics and transport in Romania, after Bucharest. Intermodal Vest Terminal (IVT) in Oradea has container (TEU and ITU), semitrailer and bulk cargo handling facilities. On-site LSPs ship cereals towards

Germany and Benelux countries (30 trains) through the ports of Rotterdam, Antwerp or Hamburg. Loading and unloading a train (up to 42 wagons) takes 8 hours on each line (2 trains/day) with two thirds of the Romanian cereal production (18.9 million tonnes, 2023) being exported, in addition to incoming volumes handled through the port of Constanta. P&O Ferrymasters operates in Oradea with an average of 11 train connections/week towards the UK through the connecting port of Zeebrugge, Belgium (2-3 trains/week), Stuttgart, Germany (5 trains/week), Piacenza, Italy (2 trains/week) and Lodz, Poland (1-2 train/week) with transit times of 48-72 hours. The terminal can handle up to 21 trains/week (rail-in and rail-out), thus is it currently running at only 52% of its maximum capacity, according to Transmec, another terminal LSP.

Table 4 Romania – intermodal terminal’s features (2024)

terminal	location	capacity	connections
RAIT	Curtici (West)	200,000 TEU/year 2,25 million tonnes/year storage: 3,000 TEU/day	A1 (road) M200 (rail)
RHT	Vladimirescu (West)	220,000 tonnes/year storage: 1,300 TEU/day	A1 (road) M200 (rail)
AST	Sagu (West)	10,000 tonnes/year storage capacity: 750 TEU	A1 (road) M200 (rail)
EBIT	Oradea (West)	10,600 TEU/year storage: 2,640 TEU/day	A3 (road) M300 (rail)
IVT	Oradea (West)	84,000 TEU/year 200,000 tonnes/year storage: 675 TEU/day	A3 (road) M200 (rail) OMR (airport)
CIM (new) (2030)	Timisoara (West)	50,000 TEU/year 250,000 tonnes/year storage: 500 TEU/day	A1 (road) M200 (rail) TSR (airport)
AIP	Decea (Center)	50,000 TEU/year storage: 3,000 TEU/day	A1, A3 (road) M300 (rail)
TIS (new) (2026)	Sebes (Center)	35,000 TEU/year 2,75 million tonnes/year (est.) storage: 210 TEU/day (est.)	A1 (road) M200 (rail)
TTD	Dornesti (North)	240,000 tonnes/month (3,000,000 tonnes/year) storage: 1,250 TEU/day	M500 (rail) via R500 (rail) M800 (rail)
RTD	Dornesti (North)	250 TEU/day (90,000 TEU/year) storage: 2,500 TEU/day	M500 (rail) via R500 (rail) M800 (rail)
PMG	Galati (East)	150,000 TEU/year 1,200-3,600 tonnes/day storage: 30,000 tonnes/year	M600,M700 (rail) ROGAL (river) ROCND (sea)
BIT	Bucharest (South)	750 TEU/month (9,000 TEU/year)	A1, A2, A3 (road) M800 (rail)
BIMH	Moara Vlasiei	60,000 TEU/year (est.)	A0, A3 (road)

(new) (2027)	(South)	800,000 tonnes/year (est.) storage: 1,000 TEU/day (est.)	M800 (rail) OTP (airport)
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Source: own processing

Timisoara leverages its location and infrastructure network in the West (A1 motorway, city bypass and international airport) and has a highly developed automotive industry. With its 106 km, the city has the highest amount of highways per county (10% of total highway length), a partial city by-pass (the rest is under execution, due 2025) and a planned investment of connecting the airport (Traian Vuia International Airport) with the main railway line (M200). The logistic Western Area's competitive logistic setting (high concentration of warehouses and storage spaces and LSPs) would most likely use the new intermodal center (CIM) for freight forwarding operations and further increase terminal traffic and handled cargo volumes.

Aiud Intermodal Park (AIP) is DP World's intermodal terminal in Decea/Aiud offering 6 rail connections (50 TEU/train) and operating between 1 freight train/week and 1 freight train/day across Europe and China, through its Black Sea terminal in the Port of Constanta. DP World's terminals enable intermodal transportation both ways, either from Constanta to AIP (via rail) and then truck distribution within a radius of 100 km (for 11 main cities in the Transylvania region) or cargo consolidation at AIP and further transit towards CEE or Western Europe (via rail) or AIP to Constanta (via rail) and then shipping towards the Adriatic (Koper and/or Rijeka ports) or North Sea ports (Antwerpen, Rotterdam, Bremerhaven and/or Hamburg). Road transport has developed a lot in Romania in the last decade due to lack of investments in the railway network and less competitive services. On the other hand, increased competition has also brought about more road congestions and slower overall truck speeds on longer distances. In recent years road freight prices have increased despite slightly lower cargo volumes. A freight train with 50 wagons replaces 120 trucks in traffic. Outbound transportation (on rail) is more efficient (and safer) as waiting times for trucks at the Hungarian border crossing (Nadlac II) may take even 2-3 days. An intermodal shipment from Aiud (by rail) generates 75% less CO2 emissions than by truck and is also cheaper towards Budapest (by 33%) and Rotterdam (by 24%) than by road, whereas towards Constanta costs are similar (11% more expensive for intermodal), but trucks are indeed faster on this shorter segment. Almost 80% of TEUs transported in Romania by trucks cover more than 300 km (79.40%), in line with the 4 times higher amount of cargo hauled by road (61,749 million tkm) than by rail (13,564 million tkm), according to Eurostat (2021). Also nearby (45 km) a new 23 million euro intermodal terminal investment with a processing capacity of 2.8 million tonnes and storage capacity of 210 TEU (due 2026) is under way in Sebes (TIS), connecting with existing road (A1-A10) and rail (M200) network. Alba county (Transylvania region) is among the few areas in Romania that managed to have foreign investments of over 1 billion euros, most notably Star Transmission and Star Assembly (both part of the German Daimler group), mainly due to its well-connected infrastructure (A1 highway).

Northern Romania has the largest transshipment terminal (TTD) for agricultural products in Europe located in Dornesti on the Romanian-Ukrainian border (June 2024). The terminal allows simultaneous transshipment between up to 8 Ukrainian

broad gauge wagons (1,520 mm) and up to 8 Romanian standard gauge wagons (1,435 mm), 4 times more than most similar European terminals. Since 2022 Grampet Group handled more than 1.5 million tonnes of Ukrainian cargo and decided to increase its existing cereal handling capacity with a first major logistics investment (10 million euros) in the Northern area. The terminal is operated by Grup Feroviar Roman (GFR) and enables simultaneous loading/unloading of 8 wagons with 2 conveyor belts, each with a capacity of 250 tonnes/hour (dry bulk: 500 tonnes/hour), similar to volumes operated at sea port terminals. TTD has tripled its initial handling capacity and targets the transit of Ukrainian cereals towards the port of Constanta (via rail) with 4 trains/day. GFR partners with Constanta Port's main cereal operator, Comvex, which doubled its barge unloading capacity in 2022, increased its storage capacity by 25% to 250,000 tonnes and its handling capacity (by an additional 120,000 tonnes/month) in 2023. Doubling its processing capacity was fortunate as Ukrainian cereal transit through Poland was blocked and an extra influx was re-routed through its terminals on short notice (254 freight trains and 2,050 trucks). The railway distance between Dornesti and Constanta is 705 km, passes through the M500 and M800 main railway lines, and takes 36 hours. The TTD transshipment terminal will also benefit from an upcoming approved rehabilitation and modernization project (370 million euros) of the border line section (Darmanesti-Dornesti-Vicsani): 32/35 km of modernized lines will be electrified allowing passenger trains to travel at speeds of up to 160 km/h (freight trains up to 100 km/h) by 2028, from an average of less than 50 km/h currently (2024). The A7 motorway (Ploiesti-Siret, 437 km) is under execution (up to 77% by 2025), but its official due date is after 2026 with only 16 km (4%) being currently open and Pascani-Siret (115 km) is only planned. DP World also operates a railway terminal in Dornesti (RTD) since autumn 2022 (less than 8 km from TTD), but its main focus is on cargo via TEU containers from the Ukraine to be shipped to its own terminal in Constanta Port. RTD was built soon after the sudden influx of Ukrainian goods caused major congestion in Romania's Black Sea port (blocked terminals and full cereal storage capacities), including DP World's own sea terminal. Truck drivers waiting times at port entry increased (2-4 days), in addition to traveling 600 km regularly to deliver goods between Ukraine and Constanta Port (round trips). RTD's rail service operates up to 5 round trips/week (50 TEU containers/train), the facility has a bonded warehouse providing customs services (transit or re-export operations) and can accommodate up to 2,500 TEU/day in storage.

The Multimodal Platform Galati (PMG) project is a public-private partnership for the new intermodal terminal at the port of Galati. PMG handles different types of cargo (bulk, steel, oil), container units (TEU and ITU) and ships with 15,000 tonnes deadweight tonnage (DWT), mostly with dry bulk. The project started in 2016 and its execution deadline of 36 months is already long overdue (currently due 2025), but its outcome should improve current connections towards the EU (Hungary, Austria, Germany and the Netherlands) through the German port of Duisburg and other destinations in Europe (Moldova, Ukraine, Serbia), Turkey and Asia (through Constanta Port). Works for modernizing an existing quay (dock 32), road (remove traffic blockages: new bridge, roundabout and 2.3 km of road) and rail infrastructure (relocate and extend railway line, total: 5 km) are already complete (stages 1 and 2), as of April 2024. Galati is the only port along the Rhine-Danube Corridor that

connects two gauge types (1520 mm and 1435 mm) after reopening its 5 km of unused railway lines in 2022. Freight trains coming from Ukraine via Moldova can unload their grain directly at the Port of Galati without transshipment operations at the border crossing. The new industrial broad-gauge railway line between docks 47-53 (800m long) will mainly be used for loading/unloading of steel products, fertilizers, cereals, scrap metal and TEU containers to/from Moldova and Ukraine. Building a new access (entrance-exit) to the handling and storage area (to be modernized) for TEU containers and the Ro-Ro terminal is the last stage of the project financed by EU funds (85%) and would make Galati the most import intermodal hub on the Romanian stretch of the Danube.

Bucharest Intermodal Terminal (BIT) is operated by SLS Cargo (an LSP owned by FAN Courier) on P3 Logistic Parks and runs 15 two-way trains to Constanta Port per month. BIT offers terminal operations, container freight station (CFS) facility, customs and warehousing with international links to Bulgaria and Turkey. Bucharest-Ilfov Multimodal Hub (BIMH) in Balotesti-Moara Vlasiei (Northern Bucharest) is a new 100 million euro project to build the largest intermodal hub in Romania (annual capacity: 800,000 tonnes). The multimodal hub (railway terminal and logistic park) will include 2 cargo terminals (airport and railway station), rail connection to Henri Coanda (Otopeni) Airport, road connections between terminals, A3 highway (Bucharest-Ploiesti), new Bucharest By-Pass (A0) and incoming roads from Ilfov area. The airport cargo platform in Otopeni will have a storage capacity of 400 tonnes/day with a connecting electric railway of 750 m for cargo transportation in addition to building connections with Caciulati (railway-airport, 5 km) and Moara Vlasiei (railway-cargo terminal, 1 km) and modernizing existent railway near the airport.

2 Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) railway corridors run through Romania: the Orient/East-Med (OEM) and Rhine-Danube (RDN). On the OEM (CORR 4), only 3/5 main railway segments are modernized and suitable for modern railway traffic (including the European Train Control System, ECTS): Simeria-Sighisoara (169 km), Brasov-Bucharest (166 km) and Bucharest-Constanta (225 km). The 2 missing sections, Arad-Simeria (158 km) and Sighisoara-Brasov (128 km), are still under execution, slowing down both passenger and freight traffic. 2 other main projects (total amount: 3 billion euros) that are carried out are Arad-Caransebes (162 km) on the RDN (CORR 9) and Episcopia-Cluj (166 km) that connects Transylvania to the Hungarian border. The projects are due 2026-2027, but they are both behind schedule (minimum: 42 months of execution) and might lose funding. The 128 km of Sighisoara-Brasov include 7 km of tunnels and are funded through the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program, but opening this segment is due only in 2027. Lagging in infrastructure projects in Romania is common due to legislation allowing for countless appeals, lawsuits and institutional blockages, lack of specialized personnel, action-oriented managing directors and overall professionalism, in addition to corruption issues. Figure 3 presents an overview of main, operational and modernized railway lines (red), motorway network (green) and the flow of the Danube River (blue), as well as the main drivers of economic business in the country's regions.

Figure 3 Romania – map of main road, rail and waterway connections (2024)

Source: Pro Infrastructura Association, own processing

Constanta's recent surge in volumes (37% increase in tonnage and 39% in TEUs in the last 2 years), has prompted port operators to build new terminals. DP World's new 70 million euro terminal (Constanta South-Agigea) provides an alternative to regular truck inflows from Turkey (long border waiting times through Bulgaria) or incoming freight from Asia (automotive parts, fruits and vegetables, retail products). The terminal (operational since June 2024) distributes cargo to customers from the CEE (Hungary, Austria, Germany) via its intermodal hub in Transylvania (AIP), in addition to Romania and its neighbouring countries with more predictability. The terminal operates both RoRo and RoPax vessels, has a special cargo warehouse and a modern drive thru scanner for inspection of goods (from TEU containers and trucks), reducing waiting times and allowing fast release of goods due to the scanner being directly connected to the customs authorities database system. Constanta is a port with tax facilities (no customs taxes and/or VAT is due for goods in transit (temporary storage), making it suitable for a distribution center (DC) covering Romania, Bulgaria and Turkey's freight traffic on the Black Sea (Varna, Constanta and Samsun ports). DP World operates a new cargo terminal (for heavy, large and complex cargo) and logistics hub in Constanta Port (since May 2024). Operating capacity is 80,000 vehicles/year (Ro-Ro terminal) for connecting Romania's Black Sea port with Turkey (Karasu), Georgia (Batumi), the Caspian Sea (Azerbaijan), Central (Kazakhstan) and East Asia (China). An additional multi-transport platform (under execution) will open in 2025 and improve DP World's connectivity with Novi Sad (Serbia), Antwerpen (Belgium) and London Gateway (United Kingdom) multipurpose port

terminals. The new terminal has a modern cargo scanner (60-70 scans/hour) for containers (TEU) and trucks, a new warehouse (storage of special goods), as well as dedicated offices for customs clearance authorities' offices (customs, sanitary veterinary and food safety authority, transport police), organized as a one stop shop. It even has a hold room for the detention of traveling clandestine migrants. The other main Ro-Ro terminal is operated by Romcargo Maritim (shipping of Dacia and Ford cars towards Western Europe, Middle East and Africa) and handles up to 250,000-300,000 units/year with storage capacity for 7,500 vehicles (simultaneous storage). Its cargo terminal features a berth (length: 200 m), 3 railway lines handling of up to 2 trains (with 21 wagons/train) simultaneously and an operating capacity of 25,000 vehicles/month (maximum). Romcargo Maritim also handles all major maritime imports of passenger cars and light commercial vehicles to Romania (Ford, Renault-Nissan Alliance and Stellantis brands), in addition to providing services for vehicles in transit, shipped towards other destinations from its terminal.

Automotive industry has a 13% share of Romania's GDP (KPMG report), driven by Renault-owned Dacia (Mioveni) and Ford Otosan (Craiova) plants' exports (more than 90% of production output), in addition to an extensive network of upper tier multinational suppliers for premium brands (Mercedes-Benz, BMW, Volkswagen Group, Stellantis). The Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary and Poland have similar automotive industry settings, contributing to supply chain nearshoring and/or reshoring efforts of major European carmakers. The competitiveness of Romania and the CEE countries' automotive sectors also depends on a reliable logistics infrastructure for predictable deliveries (across surrounding regions), including Ro-Ro terminal's operational performance capabilities. Both Dacia and Ford would like to increase their share of cars shipped via rail, but their target transit time (12-18 hours) to the border crossing is still not feasible.

5. CONCLUSION

Rail freight (48.86 million tonnes) in Romania has an 11.36% share in overall cargo volumes, decreased by 11.5% in 2023 and is only a fraction (15%) of its previous levels (300 million tonnes, 2000). 85% of railway lines are degraded and in need of rehabilitation, but only 7% are planned for modernization. Only 35% of the total railway network (3,746 km) allows average speeds of 100 km/h, while less than a third (28%) of its 1,562 mapped heavily deteriorated areas (with mandatory speed reductions) are planned for "quick wins" works (2024). The M800 (Bucharest-Constanta, 225 km) and 37% of the M200 (Brasov-Curtici, 500 km) are the only modernized sections on the main rail freight corridors. Average commercial speed of freight trains has decreased by almost 50% (from 30 km/h to 15.86 km/h, 2023) and is almost thrice lower than road haulage with trucks (40-45 km/h), making rail cargo and intermodal transportation options less competitive for logistics companies.

A third consecutive year of record cargo volumes (over 90 million tonnes) in the port of Constanta was driven by over 25 million tonnes of transiting Ukrainian cereals (2023). Incoming levels of dry bulk cargo initially sourced high congestion, waiting times and lower port operations' throughput for unloading the surge of arriving trucks,

barges and ships at Romania's Black Sea terminals. Idling, queuing and bottlenecks put pressure on Constanta Port's handling capacity and inspired coordinated public and private outlays to shift volumes, at least in part, towards rail. An unprecedented amount of repairs and modernizations (inbound port, railway border crossings, private rail terminal operators) were executed with high priority and several lines became operational within less than 6 months. Investments focused on increasing dry bulk handling capacity (mostly for incoming Ukrainian cereals) in the cross-border area, but other private intermodal terminal operators also invested in increased freight handling capacity and bulk cargo dedicated flows, anticipating future business growth opportunities. These recent public-private coordinated efforts have been partially effective (RQ1): they have improved Constanta Port's hinterland connection via rail and aided in an improved inbound and outbound flow for Ukrainian cereals, but most of the stretches still require upgrades to reach more modern operational standards.

Intermodal is still a more expensive alternative in the EU (by 56%), while in Romania the gap is even higher due to very competitive trucking prices (despite them increasing since 2023). Romania's operating intermodal terminals currently handle yearly throughputs of over 700,000 containers and over 8 million tonnes of cargo volumes (2023). Over 90% of car production is exported, but intermodal shipments (20% Dacia and 35% Ford) are still limited by uncompetitive transit times on the Romanian railway stretch, despite the 2 carmakers considering rail haulage if shipping to Curtici would decrease to less than 12 hours (Ford) and 18 hours (Dacia). Private rail carriers account for almost 70% of rail freight and their share is increasing at the expense of CFR (only 31.2% share, 2023). Intermodal volumes have increased by 25-50% around major regional hubs, mostly driven by external demand for automotive, industrial and oil products and supported by the terminal operators' modern handling facilities. Intermodal transportation's main constraints are related to a disjointed Romanian railway network with overall low average speeds and resulting low lead time reliability (RQ2). Logistics companies' recent investments in new intermodal terminals to connect to this flawed network are thus rather surprising, if not a paradox.

By 2030 these terminals and other due projects (Galati, Bucharest, Timisoara) would increase overall intermodal handling capacities by an estimated 15-30%. Despite Romanian railway network's major shortcomings, new intermodal terminal projects (additional handling capacities) continue to be opened in strategic regional hubs with connecting infrastructure (main railway lines, motorways, port access). By 2027, the OEM (CORR 4) and RDN (CORR 9) rail freight corridors will be modernized and fully operational (along a total length of 500 km), increasing average speed, cost competitiveness and transit time predictability for already operated connections to the 5 intermodal terminals in Arad and Oradea. An already anticipatory logistics business environment, its network of intermodal hubs (West, Transylvania, North and East) and a supporting modernized railway network could increase rail freight share to 25% of total cargo volumes (2030 estimates), a lot closer to the EU's 30% rail target share for a more sustainable overall transport mix. Shifting more freight towards rail on medium-term and leveraging current geopolitical momentum to continue railway modernization projects requires public authorities to continue synergy with the private sector (RQ3). Discontinued collaboration will mean cargo

volumes and traffic increase on the railway network would only be marginal, with few and less consistent overall economic benefits.

Future research topics could investigate the intermodal terminals' traffic volume dynamics, lead time comparisons between their main distribution centers/hubs and correlation between lead time reliability and cost-competitiveness for a range of distances (300-450 km, on average). Other performance metrics (high-frequency routes, financial, TEUs turnover, capacity utilization) can also be studied separately or in conjunction with other relevant terminal-related data.

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II. GREEN, HUMANITARIAN AND CRISIS LOGISTICS

RECOLLECTING, REUSING AND RECYCLING: THE OBJECTIVES AND IMPACTS OF EU LEGISLATION ON THE BATTERY VALUE CHAIN

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Abstract

To drive sustainability on the policy level, the European Union has a set of directives and regulations to guide the development of the European battery supply development in light of the electrification of vehicles and meeting the needs of battery energy storage systems (BESS). The European Union has several historical legislations revised and renewed to drive and guide the development, but also create a common set of objectives as the end goal. This paper reviews the recent legislation changes concerning the battery supply chain such as the Waste and Recycling Directive, the Battery Act, End of Life Vehicle Management, Alternative Fuel Infrastructure and Waste Management related directives and gives an overview on battery related regulations in the EU with focus on reverse logistics (recycling, remanufacturing, reuse). The paper aims to determine how far policies can harmonize the development of the supply of a new industry? What potential risks can occur in the development of supply of a newly and intensively developing battery supply? The research is based on secondary data with additional insights gained from interviews from economic actors from the industry. In our research we find that the European regulations are among the strictest ones globally and denote both opportunities and challenges for the business actors; however, the legislations are key for the competitiveness of the EU. For the EU to leverage on the benefits and avoid the realization of the challenges the sufficient enforcement of legislation, the involvement of value chain actors, investments, research and development are all needed.

Keywords: EU policies, sustainability, battery supply, circular economy

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, one of the biggest concerns and challenges is climate change thus sustainability and carbon-neutrality have become imperious issues globally. To

support these the European Union is pushing towards digital and green twin transition where sustainability is institutionalized in the European Green Deal. The Green Deal thrives for the creation of a carbon-neutral Europe by setting proposals to make the EU's energy, transport, climate, and taxation policies fit for the new age and by setting specific goals: by 2030 net greenhouse gas emission should be reduced by at least 55% compared to the 1990 level and by 2050 there should be no net greenhouse gas emission (Kastanaki & Giannis, 2023; Pisani-Ferry et al., 2023).

One of the main issues in terms of sustainability is decarbonization and the use of renewable energy. The reduction of greenhouse gases is the most relevant in the transport sector where electric vehicles are becoming more prominent; these vehicles are powered by lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). At the same time, batteries are more and more considerable for energy storage as well. Thus batteries are fundamental for reaching the EU's decarbonization goals (Abdelbaky et al., 2021; ACEA, 2021; ACEA et al., 2022; Latini et al., 2022).

Due to electrification electric vehicle sales are increasing which brings about the growing need for lithium-ion batteries too. According to projections by 2030 globally, therefore, there will be 140 million electric vehicles on the road causing cumulatively 11 million tons of spent batteries. These can either be repurposed for second-life applications or can provide recycling opportunities, especially given the fact that batteries contain hazardous waste which if not recycled poses serious waste management concerns (Abdelbaky et al., 2021; Kampker et al., 2023; Latini et al., 2022). Aside from these, recycling is also a crucial matter in the EU due to the raw materials like lithium, graphite, and cobalt the access to which might be a challenge in the future due to high extraction rates (Lopez et al., 2022) thus these materials are considered as Critical Raw Materials for the EU (EC, 2024b). These Critical Raw Materials are characterized by high economic importance, high risk of low supply and supply disruptions thus recycling them can contribute to the decreased reliance on external suppliers (Sommerville et al., 2021). Moreover, recycling can help in the creation of reduced carbon-dioxide or carbon-neutral battery cell production which contributes to the goals of the European Green Deal (Doose et al., 2021).

Overall, to foster a strong European battery industry, a proper legislative framework is indispensable (ACEA et al., 2022) which was realized by EU decision-makers too. Ms Ribera, Spanish minister for the ecological transition in a press release states that *“batteries are key to the decarbonisation process and the EU's shift towards zero-emission modes of transport. At the same time end-of-life batteries contain many valuable resources and we must be able to reuse those critical raw materials instead of relying on third countries for supplies. The new rules will promote the competitiveness of European industry and ensure new batteries are sustainable and contribute to the green transition”* (EC 2023a, p.1). As the battery industry is increasingly more relevant in the EU and new regulations are being enforced, the main purpose of this research is on one hand to give an organized overview on the battery recycling related regulations in the EU, on the other hand to provide some insight from the businesses' point of view as battery recycling is in most cases analysed through engineering lenses. Our paper aims to answer the following questions by focusing on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs): (1) How far policies can harmonize the development of the supply of a new industry? (2) What potential risks can occur in

the development of supply of a newly and intensively developing battery supply? The research is based on secondary sources with additional insights gained from interviews with economic actors from the industry.

2. LITHIUM-ION BATTERY RECYCLING

Undoubtedly the battery industry flourishes due to electrification and the need for energy storage, yet there is a critical limitation in raw materials sourcing. One EV lithium-ion battery contains several kilograms of lithium, graphite, nickel, copper, and cobalt, thus the growing need for these batteries can easily result in bottlenecks in the supply of these materials as their global reserve is not unlimited (Adelbaky et al., 2021). Moreover, the production of new electric vehicle batteries has high environmental impacts (Kastanaki & Giannis, 2023). This highlights the need for a shift towards a more circular and sustainable battery production in which recycling and second-life strategies are essential (Gianvincenzi et al., 2024; Kampker et al., 2023). When handling batteries, the best circular business model is the combination of remanufacturing, reuse, and recycling (3Rs) (Kastanaki & Giannis, 2023).

Figure 1 depicts the lifecycle of an electric vehicle battery and shows the different stages that the product can go through before recycling (Adelbaky et al., 2020). After the EV battery comes to the end of its first life 80% of its initial capacity could be utilized for other applications thus reuse / second-life application is a viable option, these second-life possibilities include storage of electricity from renewable energy or the use of batteries for street lightning or other mobility vehicles. With extending the batteries' lives recycling can be delayed to a time when the product is more mature.

Figure 1 The lifecycle of an electric vehicle battery

¹ Treatment of manufacturing and processing waste as well as collection and transport can occur between all activities within the value chain

Source: Aschermayr et al., 2023, p. 33.

Remanufacturing of batteries can create closed-loop battery management strategies thus producers can have control over their products (Kastanaki & Giannis, 2023). At the end of the lifetime, recycling should be carried out, yet battery recycling has benefits and costs (Table 1). Yet, both second-life usages and recycling possibilities depend on the amount of returned LIBs thus to plan and successfully carry-out circular economy related strategies and leverage their benefits, the number of batteries leaving their first-life cycle needs to be understood by companies and policymakers too (Kampker et al., 2023).

Table 1 Benefits and costs of lithium-ion battery recycling

Benefits	Costs
reduced use of resources	material collection issues - who collects and stores used batteries
reduced depletion of raw materials	battery removal from vehicles – knowledge, cost and safety of removal
reduced cost of raw materials	transportation costs and logistics – safety issues and specific transport requirements (e.g. special packaging, instructions, labels or restrictions on the weight or number of batteries possible for transportation)
reduced environmental and social impacts of battery production	policy and regulatory issues

Source: own compilation based on (Gaines et al., 2018; Windisch-Kern et al., 2022)

According to projections, by 2030 there will be close to 290,000 tons of spent batteries in the European Union (Figure 2) alone which should be recycled for which recycling capacity expansions are highly needed (Heimes et al., 2024).

Figure 2 Estimated European return rates of lithium-ion batteries and battery production scrap in '000 tonnes

Source: Heimes et al., 2024, p. 15.

The immense growth of end-of-life batteries and the increasing need for recycling is especially concerning as the EU’s recycling capacity is highly limited, especially compared to its global competitors (Figure 3) (Gianvincenzi et al., 2024).

Figure 3 Battery recycling capacity in Europe, the US and China in 2023 in ‘000 tonnes

Source: Statista, 2024.

Overall, in Europe battery production is catching up to the global competitors, yet recycling facilities are still not that widespread and the ones already operating are at a pilot phase and scale only thus their true capacity and progress are yet to be seen. Moreover, there is a visible centralization of recycling facilities as they tend to be located close to the core of the European automotive industry but Northern European countries also emerge which can benefit from their cheap renewable energy, their crucial position in metal processing, and their relatively large mineral reserves (Navarro et al., 2022). In country comparison, Germany has the highest recycling capacity in the EU followed by France and Belgium (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Planned and established lithium-ion battery recycling facilities in Europe

Source: Battery Recycling in Europe (Battery-news 2024)

In the EU, players of the battery value chain contribute to recycling and reuse ambitions to a diverse extent in many cases through forming collaborations with actors at upstream or downstream parts of the supply chain.

3. LEGISLATION FROM OUTSIDE THE EU

To realize the possible benefits of battery recycling, several countries adopted regulations. These legislations play an influential role in the control of battery recycling and waste management but also by setting targets and defining responsibilities, battery-related laws can contribute to the realization of the circular economy. Aside from recycling efficiency or material recovery targets, another important concept in connection with battery regulations is the extended producer responsibility (EPR) for treating end-of-life vehicles by manufacturers. EPR covers both physical and financial responsibilities; while physical responsibilities mean the collection, transportation, sorting, reuse, recycling, and disposal of spent batteries, financial responsibilities are connected to the financing of these activities (Neumann et al., 2022; Tuner & Nugent, 2015).

Before looking at EU-level policies, we discuss regulations in the USA and China due to these countries' relevance for battery production and consumption.

In the United States there is only one federal law for battery recycling, the Battery Act of 1996, which focuses on the recycling of nickel-cadmium and lead-acid batteries (Neumann et al., 2022) thus there is no federal policy directly aiming at LIB recycling/recovery, instead senate bills were proposed which mostly focus on funding infrastructure investments. Thus law does not order battery requirements but funding schemes are provided: 60 million USD to foster battery recycling research, 50 million USD for local governments and 15 million USD to fund retailers' battery recycling programs. Moreover, there are two federal laws that are applicable for LIBs: (1) the Mercury-Containing and Rechargeable Battery Act sets requirements for lead-acid batteries' recycling and introduces EPRs meaning that rechargeable battery producers are required to internalize the costs of recycling while retailers are obligated to take back used batteries – this could serve as a starting point for lithium-ion battery recycling regulations; (2) the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act which serves as the legal framework for the disposal of hazardous solid waste – the components of LIBs fall under this category thus are subjects of this waste regulation (Bird et al., 2022; Neumann et al., 2022).

In contrast, China enacted several regulations and even though earlier laws focused only on lead-acid batteries, as the electric vehicle market and the demand for EV batteries advanced, lithium-ion battery regulations were also adopted in the 2010s. These cover battery manufacturing, collection, recycling and different responsibilities. In 2016 the Policy on Pollution Prevention Techniques of Waste Battery and the Extended Producer Responsibility System were introduced specifying standards for the collection, transportation, storage or disposal of waste EV batteries. Moreover, in China since 2018 car manufacturers are responsible for battery recycling; information is required at all stages of recycling from all the concerned parties to ensure recycling efficiency (Bird et al., 2022; Neumann et al., 2022). Also

by 2025 50% of waste LIBs should be recycled. In 2018 the Interim Measures for the Management of Power Battery Recovery and Utilization of New Energy Vehicles was enacted encouraging battery manufacturers to use designs that allow for easy disassembly, necessitating manufacturers to provide information for end-of-life battery treatment, promoting second-life battery usage, clarifying EV and battery manufacturers' responsibilities regarding waste management and setting material recovery targets for nickel (98%), lithium (85%), cobalt (98%), manganese (98%) and rare earth metals (97%) (Neumann et al., 2022; Skeete et al., 2020). These regulations were further tightened in 2020 in the blueprint of Energy in China's New Era which included guidance on building a sustainable battery supply chain with a focus on recycling to support energy efficiency but also had provision for the reduction of carbon intensity regarding the electricity used in e-vehicles (Melin et al., 2021).

It is clear that while in the US there are no clear and generally applicable lithium-ion battery related requirements, China regulates this sector strictly. The European Union is similar to China in setting high requirements for recycling (Doose et al., 2021).

4. EUROPEAN POLICIES, REGULATIONS AND INITIATIVES REGARDING BATTERIES

Battery regulations and policies are not new in Europe and has gone through several rounds of changes and modernization. The collection, disposal and recycling of lead/acid batteries was for instance already regulated by EC Directive 91/157/EEC (Ahmed, 1996). This required member states to guarantee collection and recovery schemes and the necessary financial measures, to raise public awareness on the dangers of uncontrolled disposal (Ahmed, 1996).

Prior to the new Battery Regulation the EU had an outdated Battery Directive (2006/66/EC) which though set specific targets for recycling efficiency and even defined minimum battery collection rates and EPRs¹ these were inadequate for the batteries powering electric vehicles (Navarro et al., 2022; Skeete et al., 2020; Turner & Nugent, 2015). For instance, collection targets were only defined for portable batteries but they excluded EV batteries (Neumann et al., 2022; Skeete et al., 2020). Thus there was a need for revision to better fit regulations to LIBs and their specificities.

The new Battery Regulation (Regulation 2023/1542 concerning batteries and waste batteries) in the EU entered into force in August 2023 aiming at the revitalization of the battery policy framework and its adaptation to changing technological, economic and social conditions in terms of batteries (EC 2023b). *“EU rules on batteries aim to make batteries sustainable throughout their entire life cycle – from the sourcing of materials to their collection, recycling and repurposing. In the current energy context, the new rules promote the development of a competitive sustainable battery industry, which will support Europe's clean energy transition and independence from fuel imports.”* (EC 2024a p1). Thus, the regulation facilitates the

¹ These EPRs included both physical and financial responsibilities where producers and distributors had to take back batteries, including EV batteries for free (Neumann et al., 2022).

shift toward a circular battery value chain (Lopez et al., 2022). As more and more LIBs are being used due to electrification efforts, this new Battery Regulation set a legal framework for establishing an appropriate collection scheme for LIBs and introduced new policy elements like mandatory requirements for battery design, end-of-life handling, recycling, and reusing thus providing a common and comprehensive framework for battery design, sales, usage and recycling (Bird et al., 2022; EC, 2023b; Neumann et al., 2022). This regulation aims to increase sustainability, safety and circularity of batteries. The scope of this new regulation is a much-enhanced version of the previously in force 2006 Battery Directive as the 2023 regulation focuses on electric vehicle batteries, waste portable batteries, batteries for light means of transport and industrial batteries and also concentrates not only on improving battery waste management but also on social and environmental sustainability at all battery life cycle stages. The Battery Regulation introduces requirements regarding sustainability, labelling, end-of-life management and due diligence which to be applied to every company selling batteries or products containing batteries within the European single market. To ensure sustainability first maximum carbon emission levels will be introduced and the carbon footprint of batteries will be calculated for the whole lifecycle of the products (Bernhart et al., 2023; EC, 2023; Lopez et al., 2022; Rizos & Urban, 2024). Moreover, the regulation sets specific recycled content targets for different materials composing batteries. In addition, material recovery targets were also defined to foster recycling efficiency (Bird et al, 2022; EC, 2023b; Rizos & Urban, 2024). These specific requirements which should be followed from 2030 are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Battery Regulation material requirements

Material	Minimum recycled content target from 2030	Material recovery targets by 2027
Lithium	6% to be increased to 12% from 2036	50% to be increased to 80% by 2031
Nickel	6% to be increased to 15% from 2036	90% to be increased to 95% by 2031
Cobalt	16% to be increased to 26% from 2036	90% to be increased to 95% by 2031
Lead	85%	90% to be increased to 95% by 2031
Copper		90% to be increased to 95% by 2031

Source: own compilation based on EC (2023b)

Aside from recycled content targets, the regulation also has obligations regarding end-of-life management and extended producer responsibility. Battery producers thriving to sell their products in the EU will be subject to extended producer responsibility meaning that they will have to finance separate battery collection and the transportation of waste batteries, will have to arrange for take-back and collection systems but also will be responsible for informing distributors and end-users on waste management. The Regulation introduced collection targets too for diverse battery types – e.g. by 2030 minimum 73% of portable batteries and 61% of LMT (light

means of transport) batteries are to be gathered. These actions will gradually be introduced over the years (Figure 5) (EC, 2023b; Bernhart et al., 2023; Rizos & Urban, 2024).

Figure 5 The timeline of introducing the actions of the Battery Regulation

Source: own construction based on (EC, 2023b; Rizos & Urban, 2024).

As part of the 2023 Battery Regulation, the European Union introduces a digital product passport (DPP)² called the Battery Passport that will be a legal requirement from 2027 for electric vehicle batteries and industrial and LMT batteries with a capacity higher than 2 KWh. This tool supports the collection and sharing of battery-related data across the supply chain thus addressing information gaps regarding the product and its components among the actors of the battery supply chain. The Battery Passport can support battery reuse and recycling by increasing transparency and fostering horizontal requirements for all supply chain actors thus fostering circularity and sustainability. The Battery Passport will contain information for the whole product life-cycle but will have data specifically on the battery model and the individual battery. Shared data include the manufacturer, capacity, material composition, battery category or carbon footprint, share of renewables, recycled content or prevention and management of waste batteries – all these will be publicly available information. For repairers and remanufacturers additional information regarding safety measures, dismantling or battery composition will also be available. The Battery Passport decreases information asymmetries among value chain members as battery related data will be accessible for them based on which circular business models could be enabled and processes and costs could be improved (Aschermayr et al., 2023; Neumann et al., 2022; Rizos & Urban, 2024). These contribute to the efficient monitoring of recycling and reuse as well (Bird et al., 2022). Figure 6. summarizes the main elements of the Battery Regulation with a focus on circularity.

² A DPP is a digital and policy tool that electronically registers, processes and shares information related to the products among authorities and supply chain actors. Data provided by DPP include: material composition and origin, carbon footprint, chemical substances, performance and repairing, recycling and disposal issues.

Figure 6 A circular economy for electric vehicle batteries and the connected articles of the Batteries Regulation

Source: Melin et al., 2021, p. 386.

A similar initiative is the German Battery Pass project launched in 2022 and aiming at the advanced application of the EU-level Battery Passport, also it serves as a guidance for the EU Battery Passport (Aschermayr et al., 2023) This is a tool for supporting the sustainable battery value chain scaling and helping companies to make better decisions regarding their supply chain based on the increasingly available information (Christidis, 2024). Another comparable initiative is the Global Battery Alliance Battery Passport which is a DPP for electric vehicle batteries. Individual companies like Minespider or Circular, also offer battery passport solutions mostly by using blockchain technology to store and share data on responsible sourcing, carbon footprint, and battery origin. These solutions can help in the preparations for ensuring compliance with EU Battery Regulations (Rizos & Urban, 2024). These efforts are even supported by the European Union, for instance, RECIRCULATE is a project Minespider, Iconiq Innovation and Eurecat and some associated partners to develop “blockchain-based battery passports to enable efficient tracking and exchange of information about batteries across the supply chain” (Christidis, 2024) this way

making the assessment of battery components easy when it comes to remanufacturing, reusing or recycling.

Individual European countries might have different policies. The United Kingdom does not have a specific battery regulation but taxes and subsidies for battery recycling have been endorsed. In Germany, a lithium-ion battery recycling regulatory framework already existed prior to the EU-level Battery Regulation. This framework defines the manufacturers', consumers' and recyclers' responsibilities (Bird, et al., 2022).

Moreover, the realization of these objectives is supported by EBA – European Battery Alliance (2024) and a specialized organization too called EUCOBAT (Neumann et al., 2022) - European Association of National Collection Schemes for Batteries. EBA was created in 2017 by the European Commission to establish a competitive European battery value chain. EBA is a project-driven community bringing together more than 800 industry and innovation actors from mining to recycling aiming at securing battery raw material supply (Abdelbaky et al., 2020). EUCOBAT (2024) members strive for the creation of a better environment by collecting more and more used batteries and making better use of them. EUCOBAT ensures that the collection and recycling of used batteries is organized as simply and efficiently as possible and its members encourage sustainable use, collection and recycling of batteries through appropriate and clear communication. The main aims of EUCOBAT include: (1) dealing with matters of general scientific, economic and institutional interest that are relevant for national compliance organizations; (2) representing the interests of national battery compliance organizations in Europe; (3) harmonizing procedures, especially regarding participating companies and the activities of the national compliance organizations that assume the financial and/or organizational responsibility of manufacturers for the management of waste cells and batteries.

Moreover, the EU supports the battery industry and battery recycling-related projects too, one such is the Battery 2030+ project (2024) under the Horizon Europe scheme which focuses on research including possibilities for improved recycling concepts (Neumann et al., 2022).

5. CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES AND RISK RAISED BY LEGISLATION, THE EUROPEAN AND THE GLOBAL BATTERY INDUSTRY ENVIRONMENT

Through interviews with relevant stakeholders, we seek to understand the risks and opportunities of the developing European model. In our review a set of interviews was used to understand the challenges, opportunities and risks concerning the development of the circular business model for the batteries, especially focusing on the reverse logistics components. We had face-to-face (F2F) and online interviews, and inputs were also gathered at events organised by professional organisations. The summary of the business inputs is presented in Table 3. The interviews were carried out between April and June 2024, and lasted for 20-25 minutes.

Table 3 Primary business insight to battery recollecting, reusing and recycling (battery 3R)

Code*	Relation to battery 3R	Relevance for battery 3R
1	Regional lead of battery producer	Role of lead batteries in the industry transformation
2	Executive at battery innovation organization	Opportunities for the growth of lead batteries
3	Director of a European NGO	Building a successful recycling industry in Europe
4	Industry safety expert	Managing industrial waste in LIB manufacturing

Source: own compilation

If applied correctly, the Battery Regulation can benefit the European battery value chain through diverse channels. Table 4 summarizes the possible opportunities and challenges arising due to the European Battery Regulation. By setting clear regulations and with the introduction of the Battery Passport transparency and traceability can be increased across the battery supply and value chains. The established lead acid battery supply fully operates in a circular mode according to a regional lead of battery producer (1) and sets a clear best practices on recollection, reuse and recycling of LIBs. Lead acid battery reuse and recycling demonstrated a 95% recovery rate according to Eurostat, which creates the benchmark for the future realities and exactions on LIBs. Learnings from these established processes drives the design for an expanded operation on all types of batteries. Though an executive at battery innovation organization (2) called out that it will be critical to use the right battery for the appropriate purpose. The set of different recovery targets and recycled material content requirements can ensure the EU's independence on external suppliers and the better safeguarding of critical materials and by having common standards, compliance among different actors of the value chain can more easily be achieved. Increased recovery and recycling efficiency can contribute to circularity which is aligned with the sustainability goals of the EU set in the European Green Deal (Lopez et al., 2022; Melin et al., 2021). It is clear, that end-of-life vehicles will drive the need for increased recycling capacities in the future. As presented in Figure 2, battery production scrap creates an immediate challenge. According to a head of a European NGO (3) current recycling capacities need to be increased by 12 times; in parallel with that Europe must stop the outflow of black mass which is the production of waste material containing precious rare materials which makes an incentive for building the recycling business in Europe. In countries where LIB battery production is ramping up, the intensive recycling capacity expansion is a present pressing challenge according to an industry safety expert (4). Ramping up these capacity expansion projects are strategically critical (3).

Table 4 Possible opportunities and challenges arising due to the European Battery Regulation

Opportunities	Challenges
Increased transparency and traceability	Distorted innovation and competition
Compliance among different actors	Increased barriers to entry to the recycling sector for European companies
Decreased reliance on external suppliers	Outflow of end-of-life batteries from Europe
Better safeguarding battery materials supply	Increased environmental burden
Reduced information asymmetry, better access to information alongside the value chain	False supplying of data

Source: own compilation

On the other hand, the Battery Regulation can create distortions in innovation. Batteries are heavily regulated as manufacturers have to provide information on the battery life cycle, materials sourcing or recycled content. As a result, battery electric vehicles have to face stricter requirements than for instance internal combustion engine-powered vehicles and these requirements can indeed be very burdensome which on one hand might harm smaller producers and on the other hand might motivate companies to opt for raw materials substitutions instead of direct compliance with the rules which in turn can weaken the upstream part of the value chain. These strict requirements can slow down the roll-out of new technologies and hamper research and development. On the one hand, strict regulation can serve as benchmarks for companies operating networks globally, according to a regional head of battery producer (1), but it is also a competitiveness question for Europe as a region. Another issue arising in connection with the Battery Regulation is that according to experts lead times and requirements are unrealistic which could contribute to distorted innovation and might have negative consequences for the competitiveness of the European battery industry so it might even slow down the shift towards electrification. For instance, recycling targets might lead to price volatility of raw materials thus of batteries; or too strict recovery targets could increase battery carbon footprint as they might motivate the use of less environmentally friendly recycling methods and processes just to reach the targets and eliminated the possible benefits of recycling (ACEA, 2021; ACEA et al., 2022; Hoarau & Lorang, 2022). To avoid such negative environmental consequences the growing use of renewable energy in production and recycling and the shift towards more advanced recycling methods is needed (Bernhart et al., 2023; Hoarau & Lorang, 2022; Kurz et al., 2023) which requires investments, capital, research and knowledge.

Moreover, even as recycling is substantial for the European battery value chain and is regulated in Europe, there are aspects where no clear rules can be applied. The Battery Regulation does not entail the European sourcing of recycled materials nor does it restrict the sources of recycled materials to end-of-life batteries. This could put Chinese and South Korean companies in a competitive advantage compared to

European firms resulting in higher barriers to entry in the material recycling sector for non-Chinese and non-South Korean companies. This goes against the EU's ambition to be less reliant on Asian manufacturers. In addition, batteries nearing the end of their life are usually traded on international markets thus leaving the single market making it more difficult for European recycling companies to reach economies of scale putting them in a disadvantageous position and making them less attractive for investments (Melin et al., 2021). There is also a challenge of collecting all end-of-life vehicles which create a gap between the total number of automotive batteries and batteries entering the reusing or recycling channels according to the Evaluation of the Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles (Williams et al., 2020): this must improve in the future. Moreover, the interoperability and compatibility of batteries alongside the value chain is still an issue that needs to be addressed thus enabling reuse and easier remanufacturing and recycling (Lopez et al., 2022). Also, the regulation is deficient in minimum design requirements ensuring battery removability, replaceability and reparability exacerbating effective second-life applications thus the introduction of such standards is needed (Tsougka, 2024; Villagrossi & Dinon, 2023).

Similarly to the whole legislative framework, the implementation of the Battery Passport has several opportunities and challenges too. Benefits mainly stem from recycling and second-life applications. For recycling labelling can give clarity to recyclers regarding product content and can help in determining the optimal recycling time. As for second-life applications, having data on the state of the battery and its cells can make the value calculation of a used battery easier and can promote effective implementation and can facilitate the process. Aside from these advantages several challenges arise, examples include data confidentiality concerns, lack of standards for data interoperability, data reliability and validity concerns and lack of clarity on battery passport responsibilities regarding different end-of-life stages. Companies might be reluctant to report sensitive data which would be available to their competitors (Ashermayr et al., 2023; Rizos & Urban, 2024), moreover, they might even supply false data, especially on battery carbon footprint so that they could enter the European market or could gain bigger market shares and lower the compliance costs associated with data disclosure (Xia et al., 2023)

Lastly, one of the greatest challenges stems from the global perspective. As presented in the previous chapters, the regulatory environment regarding batteries is very diverse across the main global actors meaning that rules and requirements also differ while many actors operate at the global scale thus for them assuring compliance with all these different legislative systems can require a lot of effort and investment. Global standards which then to be enforced in local laws are needed to have unified legislation across regions (Popova, 2022), yet it is expected that the European Battery Regulation will emerge as the global standard (Villagrossi & Dinon, 2023).

6. CONCLUSIONS

In our study we aimed at understanding the battery related regulations in the EU with a special focus on reverse logistics elements and business relations. With this research we shed light on the political economy and business aspects of battery

recycling regulations in the EU which provides a new viewpoint in battery recycling studies and supplements legal, technical and engineering studies of the topic. We synthesized and evaluated the available literature on European battery regulations and their possible consequences and complemented these findings with insights from battery industry experts.

Batteries, specifically lithium-ion batteries are inevitable elements for sustainability, renewable energy and the transition towards zero-emission economies in the European Union. Undoubtedly not only their significance but their sales number also have been growing in the past years. The European Union recognizing the importance of the sector took diverse attempts to improve the innovativeness and competitiveness of the European battery industry. As part of its bigger strategy, in 2023 the EU adopted a new Battery Regulation which on one hand is the strictest battery regulation globally, on the other hand, considers the whole life-cycle of batteries from mining to remanufacturing, reuse, recycling and waste management. The Battery Regulation contains comprehensive requirements from the battery value chain actors like carbon footprint transparency, material recycling content and material recovery targets, supply chain due diligence and extended producer responsibilities or the introduction of the Battery Passport. This regulation is an extensive legislative framework that should be followed by all the actors who market battery-related products in the European single market. Yet, when we critically evaluated the regulation, we found that the possible effects of these rules are mixed, we found both possible benefits and challenges for the European battery value chain actors. In terms of battery recycling, recollecting and reusing the European Battery Regulation could increase transparency and traceability, improve compliance among actors, decrease reliance on external suppliers or reduce information asymmetry. These findings were supported by primary business insights. To realize these benefits for the LIB market, the EU could use the lead battery supply chains' best practices and should increase recycling capacities. Challenges include distorted innovation and competition, outflow of end-of-life batteries from Europe or increased environmental burdens. Overall, the strict European battery regulations, despite the possible negative effects, are key for the competitiveness of the EU, but for the EU to leverage the benefits and avoid the realization of the challenges the sufficient enforcement of legislation, the involvement of value chain actors, investments, research and development are all needed. Moreover, the revision of targets and requirements will be needed as the introduction of the new actions proceed in time.

The main limitation of our research stems from the timeline and novelty of the new European Battery Regulation. Even though the Regulation entered into force in 2023, changes are not expected to be visible in the near future thus specific business reactions and actions cannot yet be studied, we could only gathered some viewpoints from experts and literature. Another limitations of the research is the small sample size for the interviews thus we had to rely mostly on secondary sources.

Regarding the possible directions for future research, our sample could be extended with new interviews with other business actors. Going further in-depth with our research we could undertake a company case study either on a firm specializing in battery recycling or on a battery manufacturer or automotive company to understand how they apply recycling practices and comply with the relevant EU

legislations. Another possibility is to carry out an in-depth analysis comparing Chinese and EU-level or US and European battery recycling legislations and business practices as this research just touches on the global aspects.

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EXPLORING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF STUDENT MOBILITY: CARBON FOOTPRINT OF COMMUTING

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Abstract

Quantifying the impact of students' mobility on their immediate environment – the cities where they live and/or study helps to manage the mobility of the younger generations and create mobility patterns that are in line with the EU vision of a greener and carbon-neutral future. In order to identify the variety of factors that impact student mobility and its sustainability, and in line with the purpose of identifying the measures and actions that could support the shift to a more sustainable student mobility, this paper uses the Carbon Footprint (CF) method to quantify the environmental impact of students. In contrast to the usual focus on trip characteristics or basic socio-demographic elements as part of determining student mobility patterns in previous studies, this research focuses on exploring the mobility determinants whose potential to alter the environmental impact of student mobility patterns for commuting purposes is still under-researched. By calculating the individual CF (per person of a given mobility behaviour), this paper identified several (additional) behavioural determinants that need to be taken into account when planning a more sustainable student mobility that would imply a change in their modal split. Among other, student employment, student status and class attendance, having a car at disposal (unlike car ownership) and affinity to different mode-share options are the factors that differentiate the impact of student mobility related to their compulsory activities. Consequentially, a list of policy implications is given.

Keywords: student mobility, carbon footprint, factors affecting student mobility patterns, policy implications, (sub)urban mobility

1. INTRODUCTION

Bearing in mind the EU's orientation towards reducing traffic emissions, mitigating climate change, encouraging alternative mobility modalities and improving the sustainability of the entire transport system at all levels, as well as the orientation

towards the health of citizens, traffic behaviour of young people is an important part of social orientation towards a more sustainable future. The creation of more sustainable and smarter mobility patterns and the resulting environment with a better quality of life are aligned with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015).

The long-term sustainability of any region is directly impacted by transportation choices (Hossain et al., 2022). Reducing the need for mobility seems challenging, as well as shifting the mobility patterns towards more usage of collective (public) transport and active mobility modes, but the transformation of the existing transport systems to a more sustainable version, able to contribute to reducing the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of urban mobility (EEA, 2023a) seems much needed while transportation generates around one third (29%) of total GHG emissions globally (Zhang et al., 2019), and road transport accounts for half (Apriandy et al., 2023). Mitigating climate changes requires the shift in transportation-related behaviour and reductions in the negative effects of GHGs on the quality of life.

Higher education institutions (HEI) generate large GHG emissions of transport by attracting large numbers of commuters (students, teaching staff, administrative staff). This also puts HEIs in a position to support decarbonisation by encouraging more sustainable mobility (Appleyard et al., 2018). Students tendency to use different modes of transport is determined not only by their 'latent attitudes', but also by objective circumstances (available alternatives, built environment, income, household vehicle ownership, etc.) (Hossain et al., 2022), and their mobility (i.e. transportation) patterns are subject to their habits and routines. Patterns formed at this age are shown to reflect to their future mobility preferences (Hasnine et al., 2018), and that is a reason why student mobility should be "shaped" towards more sustainability. Having in mind the strong negative potential of traffic impacts to the environment and the society, it is important to examine the mobility-related CF of the student population because there are previous studies (European Commission, 2014; European Commission, 2020b; Mrnjavac & Slavić, 2018) whose results suggest that patterns of daily mobility are reflected in patterns of travel on longer distances (for tourism purposes or not), and students are determined as 'very active travel segment ... with low regard for the environmental impact of their travel' (Hergesell & Dickinger, 2013).

Student mobility does not lack research when the general focus is on establishing their behaviour. However, there is only a small number of studies that deal with the GHG emissions of student mobility, and that address the impacts of their functional mobility (i.e. commuting to university) on the environment (Appleyard et al., 2018; Azzali & Sabour, 2018; Barros et al., 2018; Mesarec & Trček, 2024; Pérez-Neira et al., 2020; Ribeiro & Fonseca, 2022; Sobrino & Arce, 2021). Aforementioned studies suggest that university policies aimed at more sustainable mobility (increasing bus, bicycle and walking shares) can noticeably reduce GHG emissions of commuting to campus.

Due to their generational and mobility behavioural specifics, this research focuses only on student population, unlike the number of studies (eg. Daisy et al., 2016; Hamad et al., 2021; Kothval-K, 2024; Mesarec & Trček, 2024; Pérez-Neira et al., 2020; Rotaris & Danielis, 2014) that also include teaching and administrative university/faculty staff and visitors. All these groups demonstrate particular travel

patterns (Hamad et al., 2021), and the student segment of transportation demand should therefore be analysed separately from other segments (Aliari et al., 2020), in order for their behaviour to be adequately represented in travel demand models (Khattak et al., 2011) and transportation planning.

Objectifying the identification of the differences in the level of sustainability of students' mobility based in the CF measurement, and determination of the influencing factors on the mobility patterns of the student population, the purpose of this research is therefore to identify measures and actions that could encourage more sustainable mobility. Unlike many studies, this research avoids a focus on a single commute mode and a single-day perspective in gaining an insight into student mobility patterns, as well as it acknowledges the factors that are under-researched or completely not researched. Another specific of this research is that it measures the GHG emissions of the students' functional mobility, i.e. the carbon footprint of student mobility on local level in relation to their actual commute to the university, unlike travel intent.

After Introduction, this paper is made of three larger sections. Theoretical background offers an overview of previous studies on student mobility and the contextual setting in relation to EU policies and strategic objectives, and the GHG emissions of transportation sector. Methodology section provides information about the study site and sample, as well as the research approach taken in this paper. An insight into the current student mobility patterns (in Results and discussion section) and the identification of factors influencing the size of their carbon footprint should enable theoretical and applied research contributions. Applicable suggestions with potential to change the student modal split are derived from previous research, and this research, and cross-referenced with research participants' attitudes. The Conclusion of the paper lists some of the research limitations and provides direction for future research on the topic of student mobility.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

From approx. 18.5 million tertiary education students in EU in 2021, 161000 study in Croatia (Eurostat, 2023). By accepting the thesis of the low regard for the environmental impact of their travel (Hergesell & Dickinger, 2013) and that the patterns they create at this age will affect their future mobility preferences (Hasnine et al., 2018; Kotval-K et al., 2024) students' mobility patterns need further examination in order to be evaluated, monitored and managed as part of the demand that influences the smart and sustainable mobility EU objectives.

2.1 Transportation sustainability in EU

Strategic documents of EU (European Commission, 2020a; European Commission, 2021; Regulation EU 2021) are largely committed to achieving transportation sustainability objectives, as part of the broader orientation on mitigating climate change and its negative impacts on society. Climate neutrality is a binding goal (Regulation EU 2021). However, the European Green Deal (European

Commission, 2021) acknowledges the climate neutrality objective without disregarding the economy and societal needs that transport sector contributes to.

A variety of improvements in transportation and mobility should result from Sustainable and Smart Mobility strategy, aimed at transforming the EU transport system to a more sustainable and a more resilient version (European Commission, 2020a). Suggested transformation puts forward the usage of public transport (PT) modes and active mobility modes in passenger transportation, thus contributing to reductions of GHG emissions of mobility (EEA, 2023a), as well as the overall reduction in the need for mobility (EEA, 2024b). However, the modal share of collective mobility modes (i.e. PT) in EU, not including the pandemic period, is stagnant around 18% of total inland passenger transport activity (European Commission, 2023).

The EU actions against climate change (primarily, actions aimed at energy efficiency) resulted in a decrease of EU emissions in 2022 (compared to 1990) of almost a third (31%), but even a greater reduction, of 55% or more by 2030, and a climate-neutrality by 2050 require further transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy accompanied by restoring the natural capacity to be able to absorb the GHG emissions (EEA, 2024c). There is an evident lack of sustainability in transport sector, responsible for one fourth of the EU GHG emissions and its share is increasing (EEA, 2024b).

2. Transportation GHG emissions and impacts

Mitigating climate change and its negative impacts is a global issue. Transportation sector generates approx. one third (29%) of total GHG emissions globally (Zhang et al., 2019), and is responsible for an even larger proportion of CO₂ end-use emission (International Energy Agency, 2021) – of which road transportation accounts for half (Apriandy et al., 2023). Road traffic is responsible for around 70% of total transport-related GHG emissions in EU (European Council, 2024). Monitoring transportation GHG emissions is a prerequisite of any actions aimed at reducing its negative effects on climate (Lyu et al., 2021). Climate-neutrality in EU is founded in a 90% reduction in GHG emissions of transport requirement (EEA, 2024a).

CO₂ is the most represented GHG, comprising around 99% of the total emissions. A modal shift to more sustainable modes of personal mobility like active travel, accompanied by demotivating motorized modes usage (Keall et al., 2018; Scheepers et al., 2014), whose CO₂ emissions derive from fossil fuels, has the potential in decreasing the total GHG emissions (Brand et al., 2021). Transportation modes with lower GHG emissions are therefore considered more sustainable than modes with higher emissions. This paper uses carbon footprint calculation in order to quantify the impact of student mobility on the local environment. Measuring carbon footprint of any human activity is important in understanding the environmental impact and finding options to reduce it.

Research on GHG emissions from transport takes different perspectives, like life cycle emissions of transport infrastructure (Guo et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2015; Kalvå, 2015; Trunzo et al., 2019), or the ability of natural areas to absorb traffic

emissions (Grofelnik & Kovačić, 2023), and does not disregard its contribution to economy and society (Magoutas et al. 2022; Prus & Sikora, 2021; Santana et al., 2022). Resident population mobility and economic activities executed by means of road transport are responsible for the majority of the annual CF of road traffic locally (Grofelnik & Kovačić, 2023). There are studies about student mobility showing that students from more polluted areas are more inclined to sustainable modes (Cattaneo et al., 2018).

2.3 Mobility patterns of tertiary education students: variables influencing mode choice

Travel behaviour of university students differs from general population (Khattak et al., 2011; Whalen et al., 2013). Students' mode choices are the outcome of a combination of economic, attitudinal and environmental impacts (Whalen et al., 2013), which is why their mobility patterns need to be assessed before trying to steer them towards greater sustainability (Shannon et al., 2006). There is a variety of variables to be considered – the socio-demographic individual determinants (age, gender, level of education, household automobile availability, driver's license), the aspects of the built environment (the presence of PT stations, cycle paths, sidewalks), trip characteristics, and attitudinal factors (Hossain et al., 2022). The structure of the built environment has a significant impact on the mode choice (Dong et al., 2016; Cattaneo et al., 2018) and is key in implementing policies aimed at transportation sustainability.

Gender is significantly correlated to students' mode choice (Zhan et al., 2016) and found to distinguish the general pro-environmental behaviour of students (Vicente-Molina et al., 2018). Women tend to make more sustainable (PT) mobility choices (Hamad et al., 2021), particularly on shorter urban distances (Hasnine et al., 2018). However, women sometimes demonstrate negative attitudes towards active mobility (Vahedi et al., 2021). Alongside gender, age and income significantly impact mode choice decisions (Nguyen-Phuoc et al., 2018). Marital status, family, and vehicle ownership influence mode choice flexibility and inclination to use collective PT and non-motorized alternatives (Zhou, 2012).

Time distribution of students' mobility patterns (outside peak hours) depends on class schedule (Aliari et al., 2020; Khattak et al., 2011) and their flexibility depends on PT complementary routes and hubs distance, as well as trip duration, weather and topographical conditions (Aliari et al., 2020; Hamad et al., 2021). The year of study, and the aspects of the built environment (educational institution's location, coverage by PT) impact students' travel frequency and mode choice as well (Zhan et al., 2016). Economic reasons often surpass the ecological motivation in mode choice (Hamad et al., 2021). The inclination to use more sustainable modes is related to students informedness (Cattaneo et al., 2018).

Service quality aspects demonstrate significant policy implications (Hasnine et al., 2018), while in some cases considered influential to mobility preferences (Eboli et al., 2013), although in specific circumstances considered insignificant (Allen & Farber, 2018). Trip characteristics, such as travel time (Nguyen-Phuoc et al., 2018) or distance (Allen & Farber, 2018), affect mobility mode choice, and the subjective

travel experience plays an important role in making sustainable mobility choices, as does the cultural outline (Cattaneo et al., 2018). Moreover, students' mobility patterns recognize differences if non-mandatory activities (unlike functional mobility, i.e. commute) are considered and the aspects of their leisure time acknowledged (Loa & Habib, 2024).

University campuses are large generators of transportation demand (Rotaris & Danielis, 2014; Whalen et al., 2013), i.e. there is a multiplication of incoming and outgoing traffic flows to their location(s) during the academic year. However, universities act like a city within the city (Ahlers et al., 2016) or a small city (Ahlers et al., 2016) and therefore have the potential to influence student mobility patterns by taking different approaches and implementing different measures (Meesit et al., 2023; Ribeiro & Fonseca, 2022; Schubert et al., 2020; Sultana et al., 2018; Urmí et al., 2022; Vahedi et al., 2021). By shaping the students' mobility choices, educational institution indirectly influences their health (Kotval-K et al., 2024). Non-motorized mobility preconditions infrastructural and environmental favourable setting [65], and this is the reason why many universities try to influence more sustainable student mobility by creating more sustainable environments (Lo, 2015).

3. METHODOLOGY

This research focuses on understanding the student mobility patterns and quantify their local impact on the environment in an attempt to identify measures and actions that could encourage more sustainable mobility. Unlike the prevailing focus on trip characteristics (i.e. on duration, distance and frequency) and basic sociodemographic determinants (i.e. age, gender, level of education) as part of mode choice and behaviour in previous studies, this research is a first step in exploring the under-researched factors of student mobility and the resulting environmental load of non-leisure time activities (for example, having a family vehicle or a business car at disposal, student employment, place of permanent residence, weekly attendance to lectures, student status, a tendency to share rides, etc.).

3.1 The approach

Previous research identifies students as an important part of current and future transportation demand. Analysing the transportation mode choices of students from large universities should inform policymakers and enable understanding of the factors that could contribute to shaping more sustainable transportation patterns (Cattaneo et al., 2018). This is what this paper attempts to do.

With the purpose of identifying factors that are assumed to influence the sustainability of student mobility, an online questionnaire was designed to collect the data from university students. The similar approach is often found in determining the mobility patterns of student population while a web-based survey is used (Appleyard et al., 2018; Khattak et al., 2011; Hasnine et al., 2018; Kotval-K et al., 2024; Mesarec

& Trček, 2024; Pérez-Neira et al., 2020) due to its potential to reach the targeted population.

The research process started from identifying the purpose and the objectives of this paper (as previously described), based in the gap identified in the existing studies, after which a plan of collecting and interpreting the data was established. The overview of the previous studies supported the research orientation towards broadening the scope of factors that could influence behaviour related to commuting. The population chosen for this research were students of the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Management (FTHM) in Opatija, due to location specifics of the Faculty campus, as well as the large number and variety of students studying there, often living away from permanent residence, and/or dealing with limited commute choices while fulfilling their student tasks. The information about the survey was shared publicly on all study levels through an online learning platform, containing the research objectives, a link to an online survey form, as well as some instruction on how to proceed. The survey was available online from February to May 2024. Three months of data collection resulted in a sample that represents all undergraduate and graduate student groups, and includes around one half of the total number of targeted students. The data was analysed and interpreted in June, followed by reporting the findings in a form of the scientific paper in the following month.

The survey was designed on the basis of several previous studies in the fields of mobility and travel, primarily on the basis of the two Eurobarometer studies in transport and mobility - Special Eurobarometer 422a: Quality of transport (European Commission, 2014) and Special Eurobarometer 495: Urban mobility and transport (European Commission, 2020b), and supplemented with several questions from the Methodology and indicator calculation method for sustainable urban mobility survey (WBCSD, 2015). A couple of questions important for determining the individual carbon footprint (for example, the brand and the model of the car, fuel type, the habit of ride sharing, distances travelled, etc.) were also added to the questionnaire in order to capture all mobility pattern determinants.

Calculating the CF of the student population enables quantifying the students' impact on the environment, while evaluating the impact of individual elements of mobility patterns supports determining the factors that are positively or negatively related to the CF size. CF calculation is distance-based and related to academic schedule, and CF of the actual commutes to the faculty is quantified per trip, per week and per academic year.

Data on student mobility collected through primary research was converted into specific CO₂ emission values based on emission data for motorized (including electric) transportation means (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero and Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, 2020), LPG-fuelled vehicles (Ryskamp, 2017), bicycles and walking (Cycling UK, n.d.; ECF, 2016) and actual commute distance (in km). The determinants of students' mobility behaviour are related to the resulting burden on the environment, expressed as local load generated by student mobility - in the context of functional movement (commuting to educational institution, and work, in cases of the employed students).

This research acknowledges a broader list of alternatives to private car travel, including different vehicle and ride-share options when analysing student mobility

patterns. Collective, i.e. public transportation is considered as an active mobility mode in the context of this research, as in some of the previous studies (Shannon et al., 2006; Mesarec & Trček, 2024), while PT service requires access by bike, or on foot in most cases.

The interpretation of the results explores the contribution of individual determinants of student travel behaviour to the size of their CF. The focus of this research is on functional mobility (commute influenced by compulsory activities), and not on leisure time activity-related behaviour. In line with some previous studies (Hergesell & Dickinger, 2013), when researching the level of sustainability among different mobility options or modes of students' choice this paper focuses on an actual impact (already realized behaviour) rather than basing the findings on researching mobility intention (planned or desired behaviour).

3.2 Study site information

According to biannual projections of GHG data required by the Energy Union and Climate Action Regulation (Regulation EU 2018), Croatia's GHG emissions from transport are not as high as in some other member states in the period 2010-2022. However, transport accounts for the largest part of its total emissions (EEA, 2023b). This research involved students from many large urban centres of the Republic of Croatia and their gravitational areas while the sample is made of students of the only public tourism-oriented faculty in the state, with large enrolment quotas, and that attracts students from all regions nationally. The specific suburban location of the Faculty for Tourism and Hospitality Management in the City of Opatija (its nearby settlement of Ika) makes it an interesting case in relation to mobility patterns, due to its seclusion from the university centre and main campus in Rijeka, and the fact that Opatija is one of the oldest tourism destinations in Croatia, whose transportation options are limited by spatial constraints.

FTHM is accessible by road transportation. Aside by private vehicles, that get parked with no charge on four FTHM designated micro-locations (with an addition of additional parking spaces in the surrounding settlement), the Faculty is accessible by bus. There is only 1 major bus line that operates daily and connects the Faculty to the 20 km distant University centre – Rijeka, where many of the students find accommodation. The PT frequency is from 20 minutes in peak hours, to 50 minutes, and the ride takes approximately 45 minutes (Autotrolej, 2024). If the students live in the region, there are other connecting bus lines to the one that operates towards the Faculty, but it significantly prolongs the trip duration due to bad inter-connections. For students living closer to FTHM, housing is more expensive but short distances allow for more active mobility choices, primarily walking. There is no car-sharing, bike-sharing nor e-scooter sharing or free-floating systems available as a commute alternative on the location of the Faculty.

3.3 Research limitations

The findings of this study are inevitably influenced by the specifics of campus location, while it is suburban and in a settlement economically oriented mostly on

tourism, with a large number of daily migrations to (and from) work/school to the closest large urban centre, lack of alternative mobility options, and expensive housing. Single-campus orientation could also be considered limitative to generalizing the findings and comparing the results with previous studies on student mobility, but it is done in order to capture the particulars of a highly frequented (suburban) location that in itself generates a substantial transportation demand. The context implied by the chosen site (as previously described) and its features that impact student behaviour are found interesting to explore from mobility point of view, while there is a prevailing focus on urban setting in the existing research of students' mobility patterns.

The sample type is convenience while the online survey targeted the FTHM student body, including all levels of study, all study programmes and methods of studying (full- or part-time, mostly onsite). Recognizing its disadvantages, the convenience sample is still found suitable for this research while it enabled equal opportunity to all student groups to participate. Although uneven, gender distribution reflects the actual situation at FTHM, and the age distribution of participants shows that all levels of study were involved.

Using an online survey limits the potential to broaden the research on points that arise during data collection process, however due to the broad scope of research and a large number of specific questions, as well as a large number of students in the researched population, it is considered appropriate, like in many previous studies referenced in this paper.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

This research aimed to explore and determine which of the determinants of students' mobility patterns are resulting in differences of their CF and the environmental burden of student mobility in relation to these factors. In achieving its objective, the research was guided by the hypothesis that sustainable mobility is positively related to students' tendency to use active mobility alternatives (namely, PT, cycling and walking) to a private car in their commute to faculty location (proven by previous research) and that the level of sustainability (quantified as CF) is determined by a set of additional factors that influence mobility patterns (aside usually studied variables) and affect CF of students' commute.

The examined set of mobility pattern determinants is derived on the basis of referenced studies (in theoretical part) with an addition of variables considered valuable to further explore while those emerged in student population profiles in some previous research of the authors. To be precise, the focus is on the following variables, considered influential on mobility behaviour and CF size: drivers licence, car ownership in relation to having a car at disposal, students' employment, residence, regional attachment, attendance to lectures, tendency to share rides, and tendency to use vehicle/different modes' sharing schemes for commuting.

4.1 Sample description and mobility pattern context

A total of 1246 students participated in the survey but the research sample is made of 1014 respondents, whose responses were considered valid. The sample represents more than a half of the total number of FTTHM students (AZVO, n.d.). Descriptive statistics of respondents' characteristics illustrated in Table 1 shows that the average size of the respondents' household is 3,64. The average age is 21,37 with a standard deviation of 2,95, reflecting the fact that most of the respondents are of age between 18 and 24, but 25-year and older respondents are also included in a small share (8%). There are different mobility options/modes included in the survey, but some were barely represented in the split (details in Table 2) and some used solely for leisure, not the commute, and therefore addressed accordingly.

Table 1 Sample characteristics

Variable	Mean	St. Dev.	Max. value	Min. value
Household size	3,64	1,04	5	1
Number of cars in the household	2,03	0,99	4	0
Age of respondents	21,37	2,95	60	18
Driving licence_car (yes=1, no=0)	0,77	0,43	1	0
Car ownership (yes=1, no=0)	0,36	0,48	1	0
Car at disposal (yes=1, no=0)	0,39	0,49	1	0
Carpooling/ridesharing (yes=1, no=0)	0,65	0,48	1	0
Car-sharing scheme usage (yes=1, no=0)	0,1	0,3	1	0
PT pass ownership (yes=1, no=0)	0,44	0,5	1	0
Bicycle ownership (yes=1, no=0)	0,73	0,44	1	0
Bike-share scheme usage (yes=1, no=0)	0,07	0,25	1	0
E-scooter ownership (yes=1, no=0)	0,07	0,26	1	0
E-scooter-share usage (yes=1, no=0)	0,17	0,38	1	0
<i>Trip duration</i>				
Travel time_car (min)_commute	34,38	20,92	105	15
Travel time_PT (min)_commute	40,39	21,38	105	15
Travel time_bike (min)_commute	23,65	10,08	45	15
Travel time_walk (min)_commute	19,16	11,14	105	15
<i>Trip distance</i>				
Trip distance_car (km)_commute	15,76	18,69	75	1
Trip distance_PT (km)_commute	13,14	14,87	75	1
Trip distance_bicycles (km)_commute	3,92	2,52	7,5	1
Trip distance walking (km)_commute	2,4	2,95	15	1

Source: own work.

The results in Table 1 show that 36% of the students own a car (48% of the students with a driving licence), and even more (39%) have a family vehicle or a company car at their disposal to commute to the faculty. It is therefore no surprise that the car is ranked first among mode choice preferences (Table 2). It is followed by PT, whose usage is lower than its potential, according to the total number of students that have PT pass. Aside as a single mode, PT is used in multimodal combinations with motorized (car) and active mobility (walking) modes.

Walking is substantially represented as a single primary mode (Table 2). Walking to university indicates short commute, i.e. that students are living close to the faculty. Bike ownership percentage in Table 1 (73%) is not reflected in the total share of the mode usage in commute (Table 2), and bike share is never used to commute (due to no service). The same is true for scooters, that get used as private means (7%) or through share system (17%) but never for commuting purposes.

Most of commuters by bicycle or on foot live close to the Faculty, mostly in the range of '1 to 5 km'. Distances covered by the motorized means mostly fall in the category of '10 to 20 km' indicating that the students are travelling to the Faculty from the entire gravitational area of Rijeka, and the shorter trips are just as represented as the 'longer than 50 km' in the sample. Average trip duration per mode is proportional to average commute distances, but the data also reveals a broad span between minimal and maximal values.

4.1 Students' CF – exploring the determinants

The respondents' contextual information should also be considered (Table 2). Gender distribution is uneven, but it reflects the actual ratio at FTHM. Women demonstrate mobility patterns that result in more environmental impact than their male counterparts, despite the fact that most women prefer active modes (54,98% in comparison to 51,88% of the men). The difference lies in the higher frequency of weekly attendance, travelling on larger distances, and unlike men, additionally using taxi services.

Regional distribution according to the place of permanent residence, shows that 51% of the sampled students study in the region where they live (Adriatic Croatia), and that almost half of the respondents have to find accommodation while at the faculty and choose between cheaper accommodation and longer commutes from Rijeka (where student dormitories are) and shorter commute but significantly more expensive accommodation.

Our research suggests that people living closer to the faculty (shorter commute, up to 5 km) demonstrate more sustainability in mode choice by preferring walking (and cycling) to campus (42%), and PT (35%). On distances up to 10 km, PT is the primary mode choice (40%), followed by walking and cycling (27%). The data also shows that almost 45% of respondents live in urban surroundings, and that another 41% commute to and from urban centre daily. Specific mode-generated CF per distance (g/km) results in a much smaller footprint of students using active mobility modes (walking, cycling and PT), except when PT is combined with car usage (*Park&Ride*). The *Bike&Ride* option is neglected among students due to the lacking infrastructure and offering.

Earlier studies neglected the fact that some students often work while simultaneously studying. This research noted differences in the size of the environmental load (overall, employed students have a larger CF than general student population) – ranging from individuals working online and living close to the Faculty with the minimal impact, to the ones that commute 7 times a week for work and study, by car, on distances over 50 km per trip.

Predictably, students without driving licence demonstrate less environmental impact while their choices are limited to mostly non-motorized modes, or carpooling, but it is worth noting that students with a licence that chose cars as the primary mode of commute, have substantially smaller CF if they use their family or company vehicle to travel to the faculty, unlike individuals that own a car. Expectedly, students with no ownership or no car at their disposal demonstrate a smaller individual CF than students that use a family car to attend lectures.

Table 2 CF per academic year (in kg), distance-based calculation

Variables	%	Mean	St. Dev.	Max.	Min.	Per person
<i>Gender</i>						
female	68,34	637,12	870,71	6451,20	1,79	637,12
male	31,56	610,04	873,72	6451,20	1,79	610,04
non-binary	0,10	53,76	0,00	0,00	0,00	53,76
<i>Regional distribution_NUTS-2 regions of permanent residence</i>						
Pannonian Croatia	11,44	561,03	999,14	5745,60	1,79	561,03
Adriatic Croatia	51,08	585,84	724,43	6451,20	1,79	585,84
City of Zagreb	17,36	568,26	830,91	4924,80	1,79	537,71
Northern Croatia	20,12	824,68	1113,58	6451,20	1,79	824,68
<i>Student/employment status</i>						
student	62,52	498,72	671,18	4924,80	1,79	498,72
student and employed	30,87	1149,79	35,93	6451,20	1,79	905,69
student and unemployed	6,41	571,17	731,71	32832,00	2,02	571,17
<i>Mode share_1st choice commute</i>						
car (driver)	36,19	1060,11	1091,31	6451,20	6,14	1060,11
car (passenger)	3,55	1169,02	1395,38	6098,40	34,85	1169,02
PT	30,97	393,72	441,01	2520,00	3,36	393,72
bicycle	1,28	23,68	19,05	60,48	2,02	23,68
walking	14,40	43,67	92,99	627,20	1,79	43,67
PT&walk	7,00	324,90	384,14	1932,00	12,88	324,90
PT&bicycle (<i>Bike&Ride</i>)	0,30	97,44	50,73	151,20	50,40	97,44
PT&car (<i>Park&Ride</i>)	6,02	842,65	711,50	3312,00	71,28	842,65
walk and bicycle	0,10	30,80	0,00	30,80	30,80	3,08
other: taxi	0,20	271,44	2670,80	460,80	82,08	271,44
<i>Residence</i>						
The city	44,77	527,13	846,01	6451,20	1,79	527,13
Urban gravitational area _ regular trips to the city	40,93	735,72	892,30	6451,20	1,79	735,72
Urban gravitational area _ occasional trips to the city	13,51	648,10	871,71	4924,80	1,79	648,10
Urban gravitational area _ no trips to the city	0,79	420,06	478,55	1149,12	30,72	420,06
<i>Driving licence</i>						
Yes	76,92	684,19	907,44	6451,20	1,79	684,12
No	23,08	440,95	707,18	6098,40	1,79	440,95
<i>Car ownership OR family car at disposal (students with licence)</i>						

Ownership	46,54	886,55	1032,74	6451,20	1,79	886,55
Family car at disposal	51,15	502,88	727,37	6451,20	1,79	502,87
No ownership, nor disposal	2,31	3443,89	9578,78	3484,80	8,96	425,90
<i>Active mobility mode</i>						
Yes (PT, cycling, walking, and combinations)	54,04	280,48	396,15	2520,00	1,79	280,48
No (car driver, car passenger, taxi, Park&Ride)	41,72	1036,67	1076,42	6451,20	6,14	1036,67
<i>Frequency of commute weekly attendance</i>						
1 or 2 times (part-time students)	8,62	309,46	449,96	1843,20	1,79	309,46
3 or more times (full-time students)	91,38	572,66	740,04	46080,00	2,02	572,66
<i>Ride-sharing/carpooling non-active modes</i>						
Yes (always, often, sometimes)	68,66	459,90	475,78	3225,60	6,84	459,90
No	31,34	956,51	1057,50	5745,60	6,14	956,51
<i>Car-sharing system usage</i>						
Yes	9,86	430,58	624,22	2613,60	1,79	430,58
No	90,14	649,60	891,57	6451,20	1,79	649,60
<i>Bike-sharing system usage</i>						
Yes	7,69	490,09	741,98	3484,80	1,79	490,09
No	92,31	639,49	880,35	6451,20	1,79	639,49

Source: own work.

Sharing rides with other students lowers CF of commute substantially, even if the trip is shared with only one more person, which is true for around 63% of the students prone to carpooling. On the other hand, more than 40% of students that don't share rides cover large distances while mostly being employed in addition to studying. Combining work and class schedules makes carpooling organization challenging. Although used to a small extent, results of analysis suggest that affinity to mode-sharing options results in less environmental impact, due to its inverse proportion to the tendency to use such schemes.

Our research showed that full-time students (attendance of 3 and more times a week) primarily choose PT and PT intermodal options (41%), followed by cars (35,72%) and walking (14,84%). Their average GHG is lower per person per arrival (143 as opposed to 206 kg of CO₂), but inevitably higher per person in total (per week and academic year) than of part-time students (attendance 1 or 2 times a week) whose first choice is also more in favour of active than non-active modes. Due to focusing solely on compulsory activities, attendance in this research is equal to the commute frequency – as presented in Table 3, and indicates that students generate a large number of trips in relation to academic schedule – individually, 147,76 per academic year.

Table 3 Individual student CF (in kg/distance) in relation to established mobility patterns

	car	PT (bus)	walk	PT& walk	PT& car	bicycle	PT& bike	taxi	bike & walk
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commute frequency mean (days/week)	4,7	4,5	4,6	4,8	4,5	4,1	4,3	4	5
commute distance mean (km)	15,8	13,1	2,4	13,3	23,5	4,5	5,8	5	2,5
carbon emission (g/km)	B7=171 E5=192 EL=53 LPG=160	105	56	80,5	B7=138 E5=148,5 LPG=82,5	21	63	B7=171 E5=192	38,5
CF_per trip (kg CO₂)	B7=2,7 E5=3,0 EL=0,8 LPG=2,5	1,4	0,1	1,1	B7=3,3 E5=3,5 LPG=1,9	0,1	0,4	B7=0,9 B5=1	0,1
CF_per week (kg CO₂)	B7=12,7 E5=14,2 EL=3,9 LPG=11,9	6,3	0,6	5,1	B7=14,5 E5=15,3 LPG=8,7	0,4	1,6	B7=3,4 E5=3,8	0,5
CF_per ac. year (kg CO₂)	B7=406,1 E5=456,0 EL=125,9 LPG=380,1	200,0	19,8	162,9	B7=465,3 E5=490,6 LPG=278,2	12,2	50,9	B7=109,4 E5=122,9	15,4

Source: own work.

In the context of EU commitment to more sustainable mobility this research results confirmed that in objectifying the GHG reductions of everyday mobility, the factors that additionally influence the size of the environmental load of students' mobility include: (1) academic schedule / class attendance - that translates to commute frequency; (2) not only car ownership, but also having a family or a company car at disposal for commute purposes - that translates to car-dominant mobility; (3) tendency to share rides (carpooling); (4) affinity to mode-share options (bike-sharing, car-sharing, scooter-sharing); (5) using active mobility modes (walking and cycling) or intermodal combinations of active and collective mobility modes; (6) student employment – that translates to additional trips, aside commuting to faculty; (7) residing in rental accommodation or at a permanent residence; (8) the region of origin that influences the term-time housing choices, but also mobility habits in relation to options at disposal.

Finding no differences in reasons for choosing the primary commute mode (prevalingly speed and convenience) regardless the mode of choice, with ecological reasons being equally unimportant to students already preferring walking or cycling, as to students commuting by cars or PT, indicates that the modal split could be changed if the alternatives to car travel provide competitive services. The actions related to such efforts are addressed in Table 4 and the included policy implications.

5. DISCUSSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS OF CHANGING STUDENT MOBILITY

Unlike previous research (Hamad et al., 2021; Hasnine et al., 2018), women in this study demonstrate mobility patterns that result in more environmental impact than their male counterparts, which is related to larger trip distances and class attendance among female students.

Previous research showed that a high level of car ownership results in cars being the preferred mobility mode (Hamad et al., 2021), like in the studied case in this paper, and demonstrate a strong negative correlation between car and PT use among students (Hossain et al., 2022) which requires additional consideration in managing mobility at FTHM. The ownership of mobility modes influences the modal split (Hasnine et al., 2018), and owning a car also implies less concern about sustainability (Cattaneo et al., 2018).

The results of this study correspond to some previous studies that exhibit students' preference of PT in relation to active mobility modes, like walking (Eboli et al., 2013), more so if PT had acceptable frequency/wait times (Dong, 2020). Subsidising PT could increase students' ridership (Rotaris & Danielis, 2014) as opposed to car travel, but if this is the approach to managing student mobility the attention needs to be given to shortening trip duration while it has the negative effect on PT users (Hasnine et al., 2018) and class attendance (Allen & Farber, 2018).

Our research did not support previous findings that students that walk to campus participate lectures more frequently than students that commute by car (Allen & Farber, 2018), but confirmed that as well as living at the campus or close to campus, not having access to a car influences the non-motorized alternative mode choice to get the campus (Kotval-K et al., 2024). The small share of bicycle commuters is not surprising while there is no dedicated infrastructure in the area and non-motorized mobility modes require infrastructural and environmental suitability (Tuncer & Brown, 2020), while for example, sidewalk density is inversely proportional to likelihood of using motorized modes (Whalen et al., 2013). It must not be disregarded that built environment and the urban surroundings also play an important role in mobility modes availability, and subsequently mode choice (Hasnine et al., 2018; Hossain et al., 2022; Soria-Lara et al., 2017).

FTHM students are limited by suburban location, where there is no formal student accommodation and apartment rental is the only option. It is more expensive than living in student dormitories in Rijeka (and available only outside tourist season), which is why many students live in Rijeka and subsequently make longer commutes, demonstrate higher CF, and are "forced" to use road transportation to get to FTHM location. However, there is still a substantial number of students living in close vicinity of the Faculty, which enables shorter travel times and allows for more alternative modes to be considered (like walking, walking and PT combination, *Bike&Ride*) in efforts to reduce CF. Almost half of the respondents need term-time accommodation during the academic year. Although the previous research highlighted the fact that students with term-time accommodations demonstrate a smaller annual CF in comparison to the students with permanent residence, the smaller impact derives from shorter trip distances in urban surroundings (Mesarec & Trček, 2024) which is not the case in this research. Transportation and housing policies should therefore be integrated (Appleyard et al., 2018; Zhou, 2014) when opting for more sustainable mobility.

Residence location is one of the main factors affecting students' modal choice (Danaf et al., 2014) and the greatest potential for CO₂ savings is observed within 5 km of the faculty (Mesarec & Trček, 2024). Urban surroundings offer more alternative choices to car travel, but suburban trip destinations (like FTHM location) could act as limitation in mode choice. Although students living closer to the campus in the studied case demonstrate more alternative modes orientation, there is also a large share of daily commuters by car. It is worth noting that PT in general, accompanied by its intermodal combinations, has a potential to cover the distances that are now done by car and could serve as an alternative. Additionally, there is the EU regulation 2019/631 that sets a target of 95g CO₂/km for the years 2020-2024 for new passenger cars (EEA, 2024d) so the future student CF could be lower if the trip distances or the frequency of car commutes do not increase.

Being the big generators of transportation demand, universities try to influence more sustainable mobility choices (Assi et al. 2020; Szmelter-Jarosz and Suchanek, 2021) by creating incentive environments. Analysing students' mobility should inform policymakers and stakeholders, and enable understanding of the factors that shape their patterns. Therefore, the measures and actions aimed at more sustainable student mobility in the studied case are associated to identified determinants of their mobility patterns and discussed in context of previous research and this research findings (Table 4).

Table 4 Policy implications in creating more sustainable student mobility

Mobility issue	Measures and actions aimed at more sustainable mobility	Important to acknowledge
Large commute frequency (generating CF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more condensed weekly academic calendar, avoiding scheduling only 1 course a day 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • class schedule is key determinant of time distribution of students' mobility patterns (Aliari et al., 2020; Khattak et al., 2011)
High level of car ownership / Unused potential of PT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • subsidizing PT (Hasnine, 2018; Rotaris & Danielis, 2014; Zhou 2014; Zhou 2016) or offering discounted PT passes to encourage students to use PT (Hossain et al. 2022) • faster bus service (Hamad et al., 2021), i.e. introducing direct PT lines to the faculty from university centre, including entire gravitational area (avoid long connections/wait times) • reorganizing campus parking - introducing parking charges (Hamad et al., 2021) • rewarding students that use PT (Hamad et al., 2021) • removing barriers to other (alternative) commute modes • subsidising short-distance housing, and integrating transportation and housing policies (Appleyard et al., 2018; Zhou, 2014) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high level of car ownership results in car dominance over PT options (Hamad et al., 2021; this research) • number of household cars positively affects the frequency of car usage (Daisy et al., 2018) and negatively the frequency of active modes usage (Wang et al., 2012) • PT frequency/wait times determine its usage (Dong, 2020; Hasnine et al., 2018) • increasing parking cost, decreasing PT travel time and cost influence students to choose PT over cars (Danaf et al., 2014) • fully subsidizing PT deters students from active mobility (Kotval-K et al., 2024) • higher access to PT and decent PT services encourage students to choose this mode (Zhou, 2014; Zhou 2016) • students that choose cars as the primary commute mode have substantially smaller CF if they use their family or company vehicle to travel to the faculty, than individuals that own a car (this research) • increasing the capacity of student housing is beneficiary to changing students modal

		split (Hossain et al., 2022) while people living closer to the faculty demonstrate more sustainability in mode choice (this research)
Low level of ride-sharing (carpooling)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • creating incentives to share rides (e.g. competition system – rewarding) • promoting carpooling apps • assigning parking places for carpooling users (Hamad et al., 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students living further from campus make more trips by car (Daisy et al., 2018; Kelarestaghi et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2012) • using a car is often an outcome of barriers to other commute modes (Hasnine et al., 2018)
No car-sharing scheme in the area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supporting alternatives to car-sharing on short distances (upgrading walking conditions and cycling infrastructure), and longer distances (upgrading PT services, motivating carpooling) • introducing other forms of longer range share-systems like electric bike sharing, or <i>Bike&Ride</i> alternatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • car-sharing requires large demand in order to be profitable and implies a different business model in lower density areas and smaller cities - a more socially oriented one, which requires more involvement of local authorities and PT operators (Rotaris & Danielis, 2018)
Lack of bicycle use in general / No bike-sharing system / No dedicated cycling infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • encouraging active transportation by: (1) enhancing the sidewalk and bicycle infrastructure within 3-5 km of the campus locations (Hossain et al. 2022); (2) improving sidewalks and bike lanes on campus (Hamad et al., 2021); (3) enabling bicycle parking (racks, storage, repair) and charging (e-bikes); (4) designating space to change clothes and leave equipment (helmets, shoes) at the campus; (5) offering bicycle skill training • introducing bike-sharing program (Hamad et al., 2021) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • non-motorized mobility requires favourable setting (Tuncer and Brown, 2020) • bike-sharing supports fuel savings, reduced parking demand, congestion and emissions (Kelarestaghi et al., 2019) • bike-sharing indicates small environmental impact (this research) • cycling GHG emissions are even lower than of walking (ECF, 2016)
Low levels of intermodal choices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • allowing bicycles on board buses • integration of bike-share system and PT with bike share stations next to PT stations to enable fast connections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • adequate facilities and supportive policies are beneficial to students shifting to <i>bike&ride</i> from cars (as driver and passenger) (Hasnine et al., 2018) • bike stations close to main transportation hubs have the highest demand (Aliari et al., 2020)
(E-)scooter mobility not part of the commute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • designated space to park private scooters (combined to bicycle parking, or not) • introducing free-floating electric scooters (FFES) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e-scooters could decrease the modal share of walking (Kopplin et al., 2021) and PT (Christoforou et al., 2021) • e-scooter ownership implies occasional use (Christoforou et al., 2021) • e-scooter share systems are more attractive to users when significantly shortening their travel time (Nikiforiadis et al., 2023)
Lack of dedicated sustainable mobility strategy on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • surveying students on their mobility patterns – determining factors that shape that behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • student segment of transportation demand should be analysed independently from other segments (Aliari et al., 2020) to represent their behaviour adequately in

campus level and on university level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identifying mobility options available in relation to the built environment • planning actions in line with Mobility Management concept (EPOMM, n.d.) but focusing on incentives preferred by student body (surveying) • integrating housing in transportation policy (Appleyard et al., 2018; Zhou, 2014) and ‘eco-friendly’ housing (close to campus living) subsidies • introducing mobility education and information 	travel demand models (Khattak et al., 2011) and planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • built environment significantly impacts mode choice (Dong et al., 2016; Hossain et al. 2022; Cattaneo et al., 2018; Whalen et al., 2013) as well as available mode options • barriers to access education indirectly affect students’ success and the quality of the university (Allen & Farber, 2018)
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Source: own work.

Universities need a clear sustainable mobility strategy that would objectify sustainability in relation to students’ commute to/from campus(es). It should offer guidelines on sustainable mobility by building on the existing approaches (Meesit et al., 2023; Ribeiro and Fonseca, 2022; Schubert et al., 2020; Sultana et al., 2018; Urmi et al., 2022; Vahedi et al., 2021), while also acknowledging the faculty location specifics, student body behaviour and attitudes, and built environment limitations. Sustainable mobility strategy requires a comprehensive action plan (short term and long term actions, with assigned responsibility) while shaping students’ mobility not only influences their future patterns (Hasnine et al., 2018) and their health (Kotval-K et al., 2024), but also regional sustainability (Hossain et al. 2022).

Built environment and the available mobility options (i.e. mode choices) are found to be an underlying issue in relation to identified mobility patterns and individual CF differences, while certain alternatives are not included in commuting by being non-existent (scooter-share, bicycle-share, *Ride&Bike* options). In this case, the Faculty location (outside larger urban area) is a key limitation. Aside unavailable modes, the available mobility options also recognize limitations. For example, the commute to the Faculty takes longer by PT (and combinations) than with the car, whose possession and usage is quite high. To change the car-dominated patterns, PT would need to become more attractive (by reducing travel and wait time, and introducing direct lines) and more alternative options would need to be introduced. Simultaneously, car travel would need to be discouraged (limiting parking, introducing parking charges). At the moment, PT is the only available alternative to cars on the standard commute distances between university centre and faculty campus, but its latent demand is larger than the actual (more transit pass ownership than actual usage).

Car-sharing is considered a ‘better’ alternative to owning a car on societal level, but its usage would not lower the GHG nor contribute to modal shift in this case, if used for daily commute. While there is a high level of car ownership and car availability among the students, and the location of the faculty is accessible by PT (and intermodal connections) on longer distances, and by active mobility and micro-mobility modes on shorter distances, introducing car-sharing is not considered a

priority. However, carpooling incentives are, due to their contribution to lower GHG of students that share rides (Table 2).

Riding a bicycle results in 21g/km CO₂, which is approximately one third of walking-related emissions (Cycling UK, n.d.; ECF, 2016). Limited accessibility (lack of facilities) by bicycle and infrastructural unavailability (built environment) deter students from cycling to campus (Rybarczyk & Gallagher, 2014), while it influences safety perceptions. Increasing PT, cycling and walking shares has the potential to reduce car trips to the universities and the total GHG/CO₂ emissions (Pérez-Neira et al., 2020), especially when integrated with housing and parking measures (Mesarec & Trčak, 2024). Lack of cycling infrastructure and any bike-share option in the studied case implies disregarding the potential of bicycles to lower the CF of commuting (at least on shorter distances). Therefore, measures listed in Table 4 are aimed at increasing cycling share, as an alternative to cars on short to medium distances. None of the suggested actions is to be done in isolation while mobility management, i.e. transportation demand management, strategies have larger impact when combined (GTZ, 2003).

Limitations of the built environment and more fundamental interventions like introducing new mobility modes (measures and actions identified in Table 4) require more time, collaboration of different stakeholders and substantial investments. However, in short term, universities could implement easier to achieve incentives, guided by surveying students on the incentives that would influence a change. This research recognizes mobility education and sharing information on mobility management as a transversal issue in addressing the transformation of mobility patterns of students, while affinity to use more sustainable mobility modes relates to being informed (Cattaneo et al., 2018), and the implementation of any sustainable mobility policy requires communication about potential environmental and social benefits (Sobrino & Arce, 2021). Offering courses on sustainable mobility should support such efforts (Hamad et al., 2021) while students' attitudes towards different aspects of mobility are key in achieving more sustainability (Cattaneo et al., 2018). Researching students' attitudes towards aspects of mobility could help promote more sustainable choices (Duque et al., 2014; Fürst, 2014).

This research had shown that participating in any kind of mode-sharing schemes for commute purposes results in a smaller CF in comparison to using a car. The priority in increasing the sustainability of student mobility should therefore be on actions and measures related to non-motorized means, with regard to their (smaller) spatial requirements, low GHG emissions and noise, and positive health impacts. The change should be strategically approached and acknowledge site specifics, student population behavioural and attitudinal aspects, and the existing practice that provides the reference for implementing specific actions.

6. CONCLUSION

Transportation choices directly reflect on local and regional sustainability, and it is also the objective circumstances (e.g. available alternatives, built environment, individual aspects) that shape students' mobility in patterns that are indicative of their

future mobility preferences. Therefore, managing student mobility should be aligned with the (global) need to lower the GHG emissions of mobility and aimed towards reducing the general need for mobility, increasing the modal shares of collective transport, or the share of active mobility modes.

Student mobility was explored through the lens of direct local environmental impact (i.e. the CF of commuting), and a number of factors with the potential to influence students' mode choices were acknowledged. This research fulfilled its exploratory purpose and confirmed the hypothesis that the level of sustainability of student mobility (quantified as the size of CF) is also determined by a set of additional factors that influence mobility, aside determinants of mobility patterns set by previous studies. In the context of EU commitment to more sustainable mobility this research results confirmed that in objectifying the GHG reductions of everyday mobility determinants like academic calendar (in relation to class attendance and commute frequency), the availability of a family/company car, housing options/choices, or student employment, also need to be considered.

By quantifying the CF generated by students' mobility and identifying the explored and neglected factors that influence its size it is possible to steer the mobility of young generations towards more acceptable patterns of mobility. This paper fills a gap in the existing studies on student mobility by widening the research focus to more determinants of student mobility choices, by including a wide(r) range of mobility options than previous studies, and by focusing on the actual academic schedule, and the GHG emissions of functional mobility.

Future research would need to re-examine the findings of this study on other examples (other universities) to enable more generalized recommendations on achieving more sustainable student mobility, based in confirming or disproving the suggested additional determinants that impact students' mobility patterns. Also, scenarios of different measures on reducing the CF of students' mobility from the existing studies would need to be further explored in line with addressing the additional set of variables. Research of student mobility would also benefit from monitoring the trends in student mobility in longer periods of time.

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AN ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTIVENESS PERSPECTIVE ON LOGISTICS PROCESSES WITHIN THE REVERSED WOOD BIOMASS SUPPLY CHAINS

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Abstract

Effective supply chain management is challenging regardless of the sector, commodity, chain design and stakeholders involved. For wood biomass supply chains, the high degree of diversity of the types of biomass handled and the sources of harvesting can be an even more significant issue. It is therefore important to understand what mechanisms influence the efficiency of supply chain management and design. The aim of the research presented is to verify the relevance of performance evaluation parameters from an environmental perspective. Using a Computer Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI) research method, it was possible to verify the potential development directions of reverse supply chains of wood biomass, depending on the most critical process parameters identified within the wood biomass processing centres located in Poland. It was concluded that the emissivity of transport processes for handling wood biomass can be one of the elements for assessing their efficiency, in combination with the type of loading units and means of transport chosen to handle the flows. The research carried out was limited to the specifics of Polish processing companies, further research could be carried out on a wider economic area. Conclusions indicating the relationship between specific risks related to both wood biomass material handling and certain stages of logistics might be efficiency beneficial while implemented in real business environment of reversed transportation supply chains of wood biomass.

Keywords: wood biomass, reversed supply chains, supply chain design, control parameters within supply chain

1. INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of opportunities to minimize the environmental impact of logistics processes as well as to reduce their carbon footprint is the concern of numerous worldwide studies (Baldo et al., 2009; Chen & Chen, 2017; Farm Europe, 2019; ITF, 2018). Implemented regulations support the efforts to decarbonize logistics processes

(European Commission, 2020), but these should also be supported in the scientific field. Increasing knowledge in this area can bring far-reaching benefits and raise awareness among decision-makers and affect the efficiency of reversed supply chains of wood biomass. The proper handling of returning flows of goods and resources including wood biomass can have a significant impact on the attractiveness and value of material (Zaarour et al., 2014). Managing material flows in a sustainable manner can positively influence the perception of the entire wood industry and minimize the anthropological impact on the environment (Cambero & Sowlati, 2014). Decreasing the carbon footprint of logistic processes is an indispensable element of properly managed supply chains. This parameter may also indicate the level of organizational maturity of the supply chain (Sherafati et al., 2020).

This article focuses on the factors that influence environmental effectiveness of logistics processes within the reversed wood biomass supply chains, using CATI quantitative research method among companies involved in the wood industry. It has been examined how wood biomass processing companies handle wood residues.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The increasing global emphasis on sustainable resource use has prompted industries, including the wood biomass sector, to reassess their logistical and operational strategies (Aranguren et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2022). Specificity of wood biomass reversed supply chains may be related to the concept of “two-way” economy that is focused on overall product life cycle assessment. Such a recovery supply chain concept refers to the specific control parameters as well as proper forecasting and in advance planning that supports its efficiency improvement (Kawa & Golinska, 2010). The evolution of contemporary supply chains is directed towards progressively increasing the efficiency of the processes occurring within them. This includes reviewing existing performance indicators (KPI), implementing changes and conducting reassessment (Obora, 2010). An interesting approach is the implementation of flow handling standards aimed at ensuring greater predictability of logistics processes. A case study of car crash repair sector conducted in United Kingdom focuses on changes of supplier capability according to changes in parts and processes codification standards (Aitken & Harrison, 2013). An important element taken into account is the technological maturity of companies. The appropriate level of digitalisation of processes impact management and control conditions. It has been analysed in comparative analysis in cotton production industry between Pakistan and India that the level of technological advancements determine the overall efficiency of supply chains (Shabbir & Yaqoob, 2019). Simultaneously it has been concluded that wood biomass reversed supply chains are most often digitally simplified logistics models, that directly influence its effectiveness (Dubisz & Kawa, 2023). A lack of appropriate technology can determine a decrease in efficiency. It has been admitted that wood biomass supply chains are a specific example of networks that focus on the organization of return flows and due to the origin of raw material a special handling might be required. Sourced material is often gathered from various sources thus unknown contamination may occur. This requires proper risk assessment and handling

(Junginger et al., 2019). The raw material processed is not homogeneous. Its origin is dispersed and the physical form of the material being processed can vary widely and require different actions and involvement of logistical processes depending on the moisture content, degree of contamination, origin (Alakangas et al., 2015). Reversed supply chains of wood biomass can be identified as flow models that undertake transport, processing, storage and distribution processes under closed-loop conditions. It is therefore necessary to implement synchronized processing planning and dynamic rejection of raw material that is not suitable for further processing for quality reasons. Thus, it is feasible to save resources for the performance of selected logistics processes (Golinska et al., 2007). The current economy focuses on the re-use of available resources. Wood biomass is an example of the use of these resources, but it is important to have a thorough understanding of how to identify the raw material, segregation, classification, verification of the possibility of processing and further utilization. A lack of sufficient quantitative research into the parameters affecting both transport, storage and processing processes has been identified. The potential information gained from wood biomass processing specialists could be a valuable source of information which, if processed appropriately, could support management processes in real-world market enterprises.

Modelling the progression of reversed wood biomass supply chains is important in terms of the types of raw materials handled and their purpose. The case of utilization of wood biomass for energy purposes significantly determines the processes involved in storing and transporting the raw material (Nunes et al., 2020). These insights may prove important in assessing the results obtained from the CATI research conducted. Another example of the impact on efficiency is the purpose of the wood biomass processing product. The use of the processed material as a fuel can result in different levels of environmental performance depending on the type of fuel produced. Forest wood-based fuel has a significantly lower environmental impact than oil, however, higher than natural gas (Paolotti et al., 2017). Economic and environmental modelling methods are also present in reversed supply chains of wood biomass. A proposal for a management method based on economic and emission factors indicates that there is potential to adopt such a solution in the wood biomass sector. However, the presented method does not take into account the relevance of the parameters, which can vary significantly depending on the conditions in which the reversed supply chain of wood biomass operates. Hence, it is important to take into account the parameters extracted from the CATI research in order to be able to better tailor recommendations and conclusions to the current needs of the specific area of supply chain operation (Hrechyn et al., 2021).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to verify the logistic processes of wood biomass in an environmental perspective, it was therefore decided to carry out a proper basic research. Following a clear definition of the research purpose of understanding the relationship between logistic processes and their environmental efficiency, two research questions were posed:

RQ1: Are there types of drivers that can influence the emissivity level of logistics processes?

RQ2: What are the importance levels of the different process drivers and logistical processes and how do they affect each other?

The literature review aimed to verify the most recent trends in supply chain management, also taking into account environmental parameters. The literature review focused on reviewing research papers indicating opportunities to improve the efficiency of logistics chains of organisations handling reused materials.

Within the next research step, the focus was put on conducting a Computer Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI) research. The assumptions for the research, the size of the group surveyed and the method of posing the questions and recording the responses were developed in accordance with the elements of the CATI method indicated in Bassili and Fletcher (1991) method describing publication . The research was conducted in the fourth quarter of 2022. The research was conducted among 300 participants with current experience within the supply chains of wood biomass. The research was directed at reviewing the origin of the source material, the destination, the difficulties in handling the flows, the most important risks and the difficulties affecting the efficiency of the processes. During the study, an attempt was made to assign importance indicators to the individual processes and defined risks.

Following the CATI research, it was possible to confront the results obtained with the findings from the literature review, which consequently allowed to create a mutual dependency matrix, answer the research questions and formulate recommendations for stakeholders managing of reversed supply chains of wood biomass. The research logic used is outlined in the following Figure 1.

Figure 1 Research methodology adapted within this research

Source: own elaboration.

4. QUANTITATIVE APPROACH FOR REVERSED SUPPLY CHAINS

The research included individuals involved in the operation of wood biomass supply chains. Those responsible for implementing processes included operators, managers and executives. The aim was to capture the characteristics of the entire design of reversed supply chain operating within related country, not just a selected region. It has been obtained by involving research participants from various companies across whole Poland. The following Figure 2 shows the origin of the research participants by voivodship. In order to determine for which areas of the country the state of the reverse supply chains of wood biomass is identified, information on the origin of the participants of the research was presented. It was

demonstrated that the distribution of respondents is relatively balanced and corresponds to the population density in Poland, thus it can be expected that the result of the research is reliable and can apply to the entire territory of Poland.

Figure 2 CATI research participants by voivodship

Source: own elaboration

The employment structure of the surveyed enterprises was examined as a further step to understand their complexity. The vast majority of enterprises (80%) employ between 1 and 9 persons. The exact employment structure is shown in the Figure 3 below. It can be seen that organisations with a very complex structure are in the vast minority in the wood sector analysed. Enterprises with more than 250 employees represent only 1.3%.

Figure 3 Number of employees in the respondent's company

Source: own elaboration

The classification of the respondents is the result of the classification of the participants of the study. After collecting preliminary information on the specificity of the processing centres where the respondents are employed, it was decided to apply three principal criteria, i.e. agricultural and forestry wood residues, post-production residues and post-consumer wood. In each of the three main enterprise groups, i.e.

agricultural and forestry wood residues, post-production residues and post-consumer wood, the majority of the researched worked in enterprises employing between 1 and 9 persons. This value varies between 79,1% and 87,7%. For enterprises with more employees, the differences are either larger or the group is not represented. Details are presented in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 Number of employees in respondents' enterprises by type of processing

Source: own elaboration

To provide a complete understanding of the specifics of the wood biomass industry analysed, the level of annual turnover for each enterprise group was verified. Gathered data has been presented in the Figure 5.

Figure 5 Annual company turnover

Source: own elaboration

4.1 Potential for reducing the environmental impact of logistics processes

Respondents identified the moisture level of the raw material as one of the main parameters important in the wood biomass processing industry. Simultaneously 70% of the material is stored outdoors which affects this parameters directly. The main logistics processes indicated by respondents were storage and transport. External factors such as physical parameters such as volume and weight are essential for efficiency, so regulating these parameters can contribute to increasing the efficiency of the entire reversed supply chain of wood biomass. Importance of logistics processes regarding the source of gathered biomass material has been also verified and presented in the Figure 6.

Figure 6 Logistical processes regarding wood biomass residues. Owned and outsourced

Source: own elaboration

Simultaneously, it was identified that the intended purpose of the use of wood biomass residues depends on the sources of harvesting, as shown in the Figure 7. The dominant purpose is oriented towards energy production and reuse as a production material, which is consistent with the Circular Economy approach and beneficial for supporting sustainability within the reversed supply chains.

Figure 7 Use of wood biomass residues

Source: own elaboration

Following the identification of the characteristics of the logistics processes, the types of risks involved in handling wood biomass flows were determined. By applying a risk impact scale, it was possible to determine their level of importance. The identification of risks and their significance is presented in the following Figure 8.

Figure 8 Evaluate the importance of the given factors in terms of the organisation and conduct of the logistical processes carried out in relation to the residue.

Source: own elaboration

5. DISCUSSION

The research showed that the most frequently reported processes related to the handling of post-production wood biomass (post-production residues) are storage and transport processes. In the case of agricultural and forestry residues, the most common processes are forest transportation and material transshipment. For post-consumer wood, similar to post-production residues, transport and storage were indicated as the most common processes. The obtained results confirm the observations indicated by Braghiroli and Passarini (2020) on the possibility of using wood biomass of forest origin in the production of biofuels and wood. The obtained result confirms the desire of Polish enterprises to implement the assumptions in the field of circular economy and apply the principles characteristic of sustainable supply chains. In a study by Sosa et al. (2015) it was outlined that the moisture of the raw material is of important factor for planning transport processes. Proper planning of the wood biomass supply chain can regulate the efficiency of processes, which translates into the cost effectiveness of delivering wood biomass to energy plants. However, the results of the CATI study showed that the impact of raw material moisture on transport and storage processes is at medium level. The research revealed that the greater importance of physical moisture impacts the reloading processes, which are directly related to its mass and the technical infrastructure necessary for this purpose in wood biomass processing centres. This correlation between those parameters was more deeply described in (Zhao et al., 2016). The conducted CATI research confirmed that, also in Poland, enterprises processing wood biomass residues are used to the greatest extent for the specialised in the production of energy carriers, pellets, biofuels, etc. Similar utilisation of wood biomass residues has been reported in other studies (Alakangas et al., 2015; Kot & Ślusarczyk, 2013; Nunes et al., 2020). This trend is particularly noticeable in the study for the category of post-production biomass that has been partially examined by (Kosakowski et al., 2020). In relation to the research questions, it has been shown that there are parameters that can have an impact on fundamental

logistics processes such as storage and transportation. Inadequate execution of these processes has a direct impact on their environmental efficiency, which has been demonstrated in previous studies (Allen et al., 1996; Aranguren et al., 2018; Dubisz, 2023; Dubisz et al., 2022; Dubisz & Golinska-Dawson, 2021; Dubisz & Kawa, 2023; Paolotti et al., 2017). It can therefore be concluded based on current CATI research that there is a relationship between the environmental efficiency of transport and storage processes and the physical parameters of wood biomass within reversed supply chains. Table 1 shows the different levels of significance of specific parameters that are important within the reverse supply chains of wood biomass. The analysis carried out highlights the importance of a group of parameters related to the structure of wood biomass, origin, sourcing process and physical parameters such as moisture. The importance of each parameter and its influence on the overall efficiency of different logistics processes has also been identified during the research work. The information provided is based on the primary data sets containing the answers of the respondents collected during the CATI research. It extends the scientific knowledge in this field.

6. CONCLUSIONS

According to the results obtained, a number of risk factors have been identified that can have a significant impact on logistics processes. The smooth flow of the fundamental logistics processes is directly related to the planned and controlled level of emissions. A deviation from the adopted course of processes determines the increase in emissions, so it is essential to identify risks the occurrence of which will have a proportional impact on the increase in emissions. Proper management of the risks identified in Tabl 1 and factors affecting the organisation of logistics processes will help control the level of emissivity and efficiency of those. Among the risks identified were the sourcing of the raw material, the origin of the raw material, the moisture content of the material, temperature of the material, the physical form of the wood biomass load, and the possibility of ignition of the biomass. A significance factor was assigned to each driver based on the responses from the respondents. A value of 1 - indicates a low impact, 2 - a medium impact and 3 - a high impact on the logistical process. The following areas were identified among the logistical processes: identification and labelling of wood biomass, transport from the forest, handling of raw material, transport and storage. Each process was given a relevance factor according to the answers given by the respondents. Among the factors, and in the list of processes, the 'other' categories were left in order to show that the conducted research took into account all the most important areas from the point of view of the respondents.

Table 1 Risk and process factor impact matrix

		logistics processes					
		identification and labelling of type of raw /wood biomass and product	field/forest transport	other	handling and reloading of payload among trucks	transport	storage / warehousing
		Factors influencing the organisation of logistics processes as rated by the expert panel					
Defined risk factors		Impact factor of the risk according to Expert Panel	1	1	1	2	3
Sources and harvesting of wood biomass residues	1	low impact	low impact	low impact			
Origin, structure and composition of wood biomass residues	3					High impact on transport processes	High impact of risk for warehousing processes
Required moisture content of wood biomass residues and/or product	2				Medium impact for handling and reloading of payload among trucks		
Required temperature of wood biomass residues and/or product	2				Medium impact for handling and reloading of payload among trucks		
Physical form of the wood biomass residue	3					High impact on transport processes	High impact of risk for warehousing processes
Degree of ignition risk of the wood biomass residue	3					High impact on transport processes	High impact of risk for warehousing processes
Other	1						

Factor relevance scale
 1 - low impact; 2 - medium impact; 3 - significant impact

Source: own elaboration.

The study identified transport and warehousing among the most vulnerable processes. Based on the research, a matrix (Table 11) indicating the relevance of the factors regulating the logistical processes of wood biomass was developed and given an appropriate relevance index based on the respondents' answers in the CATI survey. The information contained in the matrix can support the decision-making process in shaping the course of reversed wood biomass supply chains. Focusing on the parameters indicated in the matrix that have the most significant impact on the environmental performance of the processes can make a significant contribution to decarbonising them. It is most significantly affected by the origin of the raw material, whose contamination can obstruct transport or storage. Further significant risk is the unexpected physical form of the wood biomass. The unpredictable character of the resulting material can interfere with its transport or storage. Among the risks identified, one that directly affects the safety of operators carrying out the process is the risk of ignition of residual wood biomass.

6.1 Theoretical implications

The research indicates that the course and efficiency of reversed wood biomass supply chains are highly dependent on the source of raw material. Companies using post-consumer wood raw material account for 85.7% of companies employing between 1 and 9 people. In all other classifications of businesses by employment size, it is also the dominant group (10-49, 50-250, more than 250). The result shows the important role of circular strategies, which are indicated as one of the basic principles defining how to handle wood biomass residues within the supply chains reversed. The research's conclusions are consistent with the results presented by Amir et al., (2022).

6.2 Practical implications

The results of the CATI research show the potential for their use in real market conditions. The biomass wood source and the harvesting method determine how transport and storage are handled. It has been revealed within the research that 29.7% of respondents considered this factor to be very important. Since 80% of the

respondents represented small companies with 1-9 employees and an annual turnover not exceeding PLN 500,000, it appears that the appropriate design of logistic processes can have a significant impact on process efficiency and profitability of the operation.

6.3 Research limitations and further research

The research conducted was limited to the Polish area only. As a result, the image of the organisation of wood biomass flows may appear somewhat distorted. Representatives of three groups involved in biomass extraction from agricultural and forestry residues, post-production residues and post-consumer wood participated in the research. The study did not include representatives from biomass waste management companies whose origin is not defined or from all groups combined. The incorporation of representatives from these groups in future research may provide valuable data for analysis.

Further research could be extended to include examples from other countries. Research among participants from Poland only does not reflect the specifics of handling wood biomass flows globally. An analysis of only one country, may not take into account the problem affecting the environmental impact of wood biomass handling processes in other geographic areas. Further research could be conducted using qualitative methods (FGI) to obtain a better view of the research area.

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THE USAGE OF CHOSEN DIGITAL TOOLS IN THE PROCESS OF HUMANITARIAN LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

In the XXI century digital transformation significantly contributes to humanitarian logistics improvement. Most humanitarian organizations consider the area of information and communication technology very important for efficiency in providing help and lifesaving. Through information and communication technology actors can conduct electronic training at a distance, coordinate activities and connect and align on time among each other. The successful implementation of humanitarian logistics operations depends on adequate and efficient use of digital tools. In this paper, using available secondary data and in-depth case study analysis we describe ERP software and web-based DSS applications and their use in humanitarian environments. Our findings show that despite the undoubted importance of information and communication technologies in humanitarian operations, the research of digital systems use in humanitarian logistics is still immature and has so far been mainly oriented towards the isolated effect of individual technologies on humanitarian logistics activities, such as storage, procurement, planning, human resources and finance. Considering this, the existing literature in this area is fragmented and dispersed into different streams of research, which hinders unique comparisons between technologies and makes it difficult to draw important conclusions about their goals in humanitarian logistics, domain adoption, as well as their implementation within the framework of humanitarian logistics. Also, humanitarian organizations lack integrated information technology, and only a small percentage of aid agencies rely on modern tools. These noted shortcomings shall be the starting points for our future research efforts in this area.

Keywords: Digital technologies, digital tools, information, communication, humanitarian logistics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The subject of this paper is a detailed analysis of the impact of ERP (enterprise resource planning) software and web-based DSS (decision support systems) applications on the implementation of the humanitarian logistics process and its key activities. In regular market circumstances, the incentive for timely delivery of goods and services of appropriate quality and price is to make a profit. In humanitarian operations, profit has been replaced by another goal, which is to provide adequate assistance to vulnerable areas and people.

ERP software and web-based DSS applications have a wide use in humanitarian logistics operations. Given technologies should improve coordination among humanitarian organizations, the operational and security environment for staff and timely access to critical information. The information provided relates to the entire range of relevant logistics data, such as: supplier efficiency, timeliness of response, information management and quality of donated goods. The mentioned aspects can be crucial for the preparation of future operations and plans.

The aim of this paper is to point out the importance of the role of ERP software and web-based DSS applications in humanitarian logistics operations for the sake of timely response to emergency situations and their effective management. As natural disasters cannot be predicted with precision, infrastructural and organizational unpreparedness represent an additional danger when reacting adequately and suppressing the negative effects of emergency situations. Bearing in mind these facts and specifics, it is of great importance that humanitarian logistics supported by technologies effectively respond to natural disasters, reduce the consequences and provide a good basis for future plans and actions.

Within this paper we conduct a systematic search in academic databases using relevant keywords to identify papers focusing on digital tools in humanitarian logistics. Selection criteria include relevance to the topic and direct discussion of digital tools' application, impact, challenges, or future trends. Selected papers undergo screening, evaluation, and data extraction, followed by synthesis and comparative analysis to identify common themes and trends. Quality assessment ensures rigor and validity. Findings are summarized, highlighting insights and recommendations for future research as well as open questions. The iterative process allows for refinement based on emerging findings and feedback. This methodology provides a systematic approach to review literature on digital tools in humanitarian logistics management.

The basic research questions used when writing this paper are as follows:

Research question 1: The possibilities of humanitarian logistics to effectively respond to natural disasters are conditioned by an ERP systems and web-based DSS applications and the degree of training of the participants to work with concrete technological solutions.

Research question 2: In actions to help affected areas, there is a negative correlation between drastic consequences and the use of ERP systems and Web-based DSS applications.

In addition to the introduction and conclusion, this paper is divided into three parts. The first part of the paper is devoted to defining the concept of Web-based DSS applications and their use in humanitarian logistics. The second part of the paper

explains the concept of ERP systems and their characteristics that can be of crucial importance in humanitarian logistics operations.

The last, third part of the paper is devoted to the analysis of the application of Web-based DSS applications and ERP systems within practical example of floods as a motive for the development and application of specialized electronic applications in humanitarian logistics activities in France.

2. WEB-BASED DSS APPLICATIONS IN HUMANITARIAN LOGISTICS

Humanitarian logistics is a branch of logistics that deals with the preparedness and response phases of a disaster management system. The critical factor for humanitarian logistics is time and effective response. Web-based DSS applications support aid agencies and organizations in disaster preparedness, response coordination, and risk mitigation. They facilitate situational awareness, resource allocation, and decision-making during emergencies and natural disasters to save lives and protect property.

2.1 Definition of the web-based DSS applications

A Web-based Decision Support System (DSS) is an application or system that insures decision support capabilities through web-based interfaces. It uses web technologies to provide information, analysis tools, and decision-making support. Data-driven systems, such as Decision Support System (DSS) and model-driven DSS, have become very powerful and sophisticated because they provide detailed information for decisions that allow a company to coordinate and integrate internal and external business processes much more precisely (Lawrence & Tavakol, 2007). DSS systems help companies to improve supply chain management (SCM) or to create a plan scenario for changing business conditions. These systems can be used to align customer relationships. To provide decision support tools for both employees and end users DSS today can use the interactive capabilities of the web (Campbell, 2005; Van Wassenhove, 2019).

The most important web-based DSS points are: web interface, data access and integration, platform independency, advanced analytics, data management centralization, cross functional alignment and collaboration, visualization, accessibility, data protection, scalability, real-time data integration, adaptability, customization and extensibility. A Web-based DSS can be accessed using well known browsers such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox or Microsoft Edge. Overall, Web-based Decision Support Systems provide their users a strong network for data-driven inputs, encouraging collaboration and ensuring decisions in a fast-changing and interconnected world. Their accessibility, scalability, and flexibility make them indispensable tools for modern decision-makers across various industries and domains (Cordella, 2012).

While Web-based Decision Support Systems (DSS) offer numerous benefits, they also come with some potential limitations: they are dependent on internet connectivity, Security Concerns, performance and compatibility issues, data privacy

concerns, cost of establishment and maintenance, user education, control and the ownership of the data as data breaches, unauthorized access, and cyber-attacks. Despite these potential cons, many organizations believe that the good sides of Web-based DSS notable out-weight the potential limitations, even more when implemented thoughtfully and with careful awareness of data privacy, performance, costs and usability factors. By considering and allocating these negative factors on time, organizations can minimize risks and maximize the value of their decision support systems.

2.2 Advantages and disadvantages of the web-based DSS applications

All humanitarian operations depend on logistics, and logistics should be treated as a key priority in all humanitarian projects. The efficiency and effectiveness of humanitarian logistics can be greatly enhanced through the utilization of Web-based Decision Support Systems (DSS), which amalgamate data, use analytical tools, and implement human expertise to facilitate informed decision-making processes.

A web-based DSS is used to assist volunteers and humanitarian organizations in selecting the right route, to find the right medicines and help and to provide them in sufficient quantity. It can provide information from multiple sources. Other DSS combine transactional data from the website with data from the different organizations. With this system, users and organizations can take advantage of Internet information resources and web opportunities for providing a quick response to nature disaster. With a web-based and Internet-based DSS, decisions can be made by providing access to various databases and information repositories, along with data analysis software. The decision-making process can be conducted through CDSS. Today, organization's decision on which product and services will provide the best help is based on a greater amount of information than before (Maric et al., 2022; Tang, 2017).

One of the most significant advantages of Web-based DSS in humanitarian logistics is the ability to make real-time decisions. During emergencies, circumstances can change rapidly, needing swift and well-informed actions. Web-based DSS can gather and analyze data from various sources, such as weather forecasts, transportation networks, and supply chain inventories, enabling aid organizations to adapt their strategies dynamically in response to evolving situations.

Humanitarian operations often mean the allocation of scarce resources, including personnel, vehicles, and supplies, across multiple locations with diverse needs. Web-based DSS equipped with optimization algorithms can assist in determining the most efficient distribution of these resources, taking into account factors such as geographical constraints, demand fluctuations, and cost considerations (Kham et al., 2019). By optimizing resource allocation, aid agencies can maximize the impact of their interventions and reach more beneficiaries with limited resources. Humanitarian crises are requesting involvement of multiple actors and organizations, coordination and alignment among various entities are of tremendous importance for providing an adequate response. Web-based DSS provide a platform for sharing relevant information, coordinating activities, and collaborating with partners in real-time. By centralizing data and communication channels, these systems foster more effective

collaboration among humanitarian actors, empowering coordination, reduced duplication of efforts, and enhanced overall effectiveness of the response. Humanitarian operations are often fraught with uncertainties and risks, ranging from natural hazards to security threats. Web-based DSS equipped with risk assessment tools enable aid agencies to identify, evaluate, and mitigate potential risks proactively.

By building scenario analyses and contingency planning within these systems, humanitarian actors can develop adaptable strategies to cope with unexpected challenges, thereby enhancing the resilience and adaptability of their operations in volatile environments (Khan et al., 2022). Evaluation of humanitarian interventions is crucial for assessing their impact, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring accountability to donors and beneficiaries. Web-based DSS can facilitate monitoring and evaluation by aggregating and analyzing data on key performance indicators (KPIs), such as delivery timelines, beneficiary satisfaction, and resource utilization. By providing stakeholders with timely and accurate insights into the outcomes of their actions, these systems support evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement in humanitarian operations.

In conclusion, the integration of Web-based Decision Support Systems into humanitarian logistics represents a significant advancement in the field of humanitarian aid. By harnessing the power of data analytics, optimization algorithms, and collaborative technologies, these systems enable aid organizations to enhance their operational efficiency, responsiveness, and impact, ultimately leading to more effective and timely assistance for populations affected by crises and disasters. As technology continues to evolve, the potential for Web-based DSS to revolutionize humanitarian logistics and save lives remains boundless.

3. ERP SYSTEMS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTION TO DISASTER RECOVERY

Solving the problem of controlling all major business processes with one information system in real time is made possible by improving the client/server data processing and Internet applications. Implementing an ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning - ERP) system is best achieved by integrating business processes and information resources. By using the ERP system, the organization improves product quality, increases efficiency, productivity and profitability. In the humanitarian logistics, organizations have different goal, saving people lives replaces profitability as the main purpose. In order to improve humanitarian response, humanitarian organizations must respond quickly to short-term changes such as beneficiary demands (such as agility), adapt to humanitarian environments that are dynamic and complex (such as adaptability), and integrate and coordinate processes with all partners participating (such as alignment) (L'Hermitte et al., 2016, Tatham & Kovács, 2018).

3.1 Definition, history, advantages and disadvantages of the ERP systems

ERP systems are software platforms that help organizations manage and integrate core business processes. These processes may include finance, human resources, supply chain, manufacturing, procurement, and more. ERP systems typically feature a centralized database and a unified interface to streamline operations and improve efficiency across an organization. Some of the most recognized ERP systems are: SAP ERP, Oracle ERP Cloud, Microsoft Dynamic 365, Net Suite, Info ERP, Workday etc.

The concept of ERP systems first showed up in the 1960s and 1970s with the growth of Material Requirements Planning (MRP) systems, which first focused on manufacturing processes and inventory management. The term "ERP" itself came into use in the early 1990s to describe software platforms that expanded beyond MRP to integrate various business functions across an organization. The most common advantages of ERP systems are: integration, manual work reduction, data management, streamlined operations, improved visibility, enhanced customer service, compliance and reporting, cost savings, standardized processes, improved collaboration and faster decision making. Overall, ERP systems offer numerous advantages for organizations seeking to improve operational efficiency, agility, and competitiveness in today's dynamic business environment (Arudin & Saidi-Kabeche, 2022; Scholz & Seuring, 2016).

Despite the all advantages mentioned above, there are also a notable disadvantages of the ERP systems mostly focused on the significant initial investment. Implementing an ERP system involves a significant upfront investment in terms of software licenses, hardware infrastructure, implementation services, and training. Beside the disadvantages caused by high costs, there are a few more negative sides of ERP systems highlighted: complexity, integration challenges, organizational changes, vendor dependency, performance issues and data privacy. However, having in mind all flaws as well as benefits of ERP Systems, organization see the good side more important for their operations particularly when ERP initiatives are well-planned, properly executed, and aligned with business objectives.

3.2 ERP Systems in Humanitarian response

Humanitarian groups function within unique and intricate settings, facing challenges like unpredictable demand, resource constraints, inadequate infrastructure, and heavy reliance on donor support (Gatignon et al., 2010). Agility, adaptability, and alignment are crucial supply chain aspects directly impacting performance, enabling organizations to detect and respond to environmental shifts, particularly in dynamic markets. The integration of all company departments and functions is a key aim of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. ERP systems play a vital role in fostering Triple-A supply chain capabilities and are pivotal for effective humanitarian aid operations (Schniederjans et al., 2016). Despite the digital era, many humanitarian workers still utilize manual methods like paper lists and Excel files, lacking enterprise-level software features such as application integration and data compatibility. This reliance on outdated systems often leads to reactive management

rather than proactive supply chain strategies. Moreover, limited access to ERP software prevails among aid agencies (Gavidia, 2017).

To address operational hurdles and enhance response efforts, humanitarian organizations increasingly adopt or enhance their information systems, including ERP systems. Implementing ERP systems in unconventional contexts like humanitarian aid poses significant challenges and typically demands longer timelines compared to commercial settings (Gavidia, 2017). ERP systems in healthcare for humanitarian aid must adapt to unique circumstances characterized by infrastructure limitations, distribution speed priorities over precise inventory tracking, scalability for project adjustments, and specific ancillary item requirements. The development of information and communication technology, particularly ERP systems, for humanitarian groups is still in its early stages (Comes & Van De Walle, 2016). Nevertheless, the necessity for ERP systems incorporating a Triple-A perspective in humanitarian organizations is increasingly recognized. Designing ERP systems involves problem-solving and innovation to address organizational needs. Principles of information and communication technology design offer systematic approaches for developing ERP systems tailored to organizational requirements. Utilizing the content of humanitarian organizations' websites effectively fosters donor relationships. Establishing a compelling reason for donors to revisit the organization's website is crucial. Websites should offer comprehensive information and services beyond mere product details, ensuring visitors access essential information and services freely (Stoel & Muhanna, 2009; Wang & Wang, 2016; Sturgeon, 2015).

4. FOOD AID AS A MOTIVE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND USE OF SPECIALIZED ELECTRONIC APPLICATIONS IN HUMANITARIAN LOGISTICS ACTIVITIES IN FRANCE

In 2014, approximately 607 million individuals faced undernourishment, a figure that escalated to 811 million by 2020 due to the global pandemic (United Nations, 2021). Nevertheless, the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) of the United Nations asserts the right to food as a fundamental human right, essential for the fulfillment of other rights such as health, life, access to water, adequate housing, and education (UNCHR). The United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development identifies food security as the second goal following poverty eradication. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) defines food security as the continuous access to safe and nutritious food fulfilling dietary needs for active and healthy living (FAO; IFAD; UNICEF; WFP; WHO, 2020). Food insecurity is not confined to developing nations.

In France, addressing food insecurity involves public policy initiatives like the "fight against food shortage," which supports the food aid sector financially. This sector, predominantly relying on charitable efforts, operates through food aid offices. The intricate organization of food aid in France entails various actors—public, private, and associative—funding sources, food supply methods, logistics, and distribution channels. The COVID-19 outbreak underscored the significance of these offices while accentuating existing limitations (Cavaillet et al., 2021).

Almost all food aid in France integrates into a comprehensive structure involving public entities, private donations, and the operations of food aid offices, serving as its foundation. The primary food sources for these offices include budgets from the European FEAD and CNES, supplemented by donations from economic entities such as supermarkets and industries.

Within these organizations, information management is crucial, facilitated through various means including spoken, written, and electronic communication systems. Non-profit organizations managing food aid in France exhibit diverse structures and sizes, all striving to maximize their social impact through efficient resource management (Rousseau, 2007). Three prominent food aid initiatives in France include Association ReVivre, French Association of Food Banks, and the emerging Geographical Information System and HopHopFood smartphone App. This paper focuses on describing the latter initiative (République Française, 2016).

HopHopFood, founded in 2018, aims to bridge individuals in need with surplus food suppliers through digital platforms, combating food waste for the benefit of vulnerable populations. The Association's smartphone application facilitates access to unsold goods from local stores under favorable conditions for people with modest incomes, particularly those underserved by traditional food aid systems. Unlike commercial platforms, HopHopFood operates as a non-profit organization, emphasizing inclusivity and minimizing stigma associated with food assistance. Users obtain access codes from social workers to access the application and select desired products for pickup from participating stores. Retailers are compensated through fiscal incentives as per relevant laws. Despite its advantages, logistical challenges and limitations in product variety persist, albeit mitigated by HopHopFood's digital approach. This digital solution offers advantages over traditional methods, including inclusivity of all food types and streamlined logistics, facilitated by detailed performance metrics and evolving services provided through the smartphone app.

5. CONCLUSION

In the natural disaster management system, humanitarian logistics is a branch of logistics that deals with the preparedness and response phases. Humanitarian logistics is the process of planning, implementing and controlling the economical flow and storage of goods and materials. It is also the process of linking information from the point of origin to the point of consumption for the purpose of alleviating the suffering of vulnerable people. Humanitarian logistics includes a range of activities, such as preparedness, planning, procurement, transport, storage, tracking and customs clearance. Participants in humanitarian logistics are governments, the military, aid agencies, donors, non-governmental organizations and private sector companies. Business and humanitarian logistics have an economic function. However, the nature of demand in humanitarian logistics is highly uncertain because the disaster's timing, location and intensity are not known until the disaster occurs.

Humanitarian operations aim to provide adequate assistance to vulnerable areas and people. Management support systems in humanitarian logistics operations are DSS applications in a web environment and ERP systems. Through these solutions,

images, maps, videos and information can be sent and all ongoing humanitarian operations can be followed. Through one platform in humanitarian logistics, organizations can connect with all regional and local actors. The effectiveness of Web-based DSS applications and ERP systems in humanitarian logistics is demonstrated through responsibility, security, trust, transparency and speed. Digital solutions play a significant role in improving fast, fair and secure humanitarian logistics.

Humanitarian logistics of food aid has been developed in France. This humanitarian logistics relies not only on food aid to people in need, but also pays attention to their dignity. The food aid system provides an adequate response to specific forms of vulnerability that lead individuals (or groups of individuals) to a situation of food insecurity. Associations have developed application HopHop Food that connect retail chains that have food surpluses with people in need of food.

Based on the analysis within the paper both research questions have been accepted.

Further research on the impact of digital tools in humanitarian logistics is needed, focusing on empirical assessments of their effectiveness. Integration challenges, such as interoperability and data security, must be addressed, alongside exploring strategies for overcoming adoption barriers. Investigating how digital technologies like blockchain and AI can enhance supply chain resilience is crucial. Additionally, research should explore how digital tools can facilitate collaborative decision-making among diverse stakeholders. Ethical considerations regarding data privacy and equitable access must be examined, and efforts to build capacity and transfer knowledge on digital tools are essential for their effective utilization in humanitarian settings. Advancing research in these areas will contribute to improving the efficiency and effectiveness of humanitarian logistics operations worldwide. All these open questions and future research directions remain to be tackled.

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CHALLENGES OF INVENTORY MANAGEMENT IN CRISIS SITUATIONS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF FOOD RETAILERS

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Abstract

Our study focuses on food retailing and its inventory practices, which have been severely affected by the panic buying wave following the recent crisis situations which have occurred in Europe (e.g., military conflict near the borders of the EU, energy crisis, or the epidemic). The aim of this paper is to present the management options for the inventory mechanisms of food products in a crisis situation - for retailers on the downstream side of the supply chain, who were the first to face the demand fluctuations caused by the crises of recent years - and to describe, through case studies, how to identify and manage inventory difficulties that arise. The objective of the study is to explore, through the examples of three food retailers under study, which of the management solutions available in the literature can be applied in practice. Our results show among other things that, although the literature suggests that the safety stock is one of the methods to reduce uncertainty, it has not been found to be an effective method in the current circumstances. Other findings reveal that the companies in the sample have a short-term approach to crisis management and they apply them to create specific scripts for the possible crisis. A key finding of the research is that it provides practitioners a summary of good practices to contribute to their crisis management interventions at a planning level.

Keywords: food retail, crisis management, challenges, inventory practices

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent years worldwide have been affected by several crises situations (Covid-19 epidemic, energy crisis, inflation crisis, Russian-Ukrainian war conflict) which have forced dozens of industries across Europe to change their operations (Aday & Aday, 2020; Lai & Wong, 2020; Ertugrul & Kozma, 2021; Sid et al, 2021; Jám bor & Nagy, 2022a; Nagy, 2023; Rudyk et al., 2023). Regardless of the industry, the trade sector is the first member of supply chains which encounters the consumer, so for both

positive and negative impacts, trade is at the forefront of facing difficulties both downstream (e.g., volatility of solvency) and upstream (e.g., difficulties in sourcing raw materials/goods, logistical difficulties...etc.) of the given supply chain. Our study focuses on food retailing, as recent crises have highlighted the vulnerability of food supply chains to global interlinkages, with minor disruptions leading to a shift towards self-reliance (Nagy & Jámber, 2021; Jámber & Nagy, 2022b). However, this does not seem a feasible option in a highly dependent system. The focus on food retailing is further supported by the fact that, among the Critical Infrastructures formulated by the European Union and also applied in Hungary, Food is ranked 5th among the ten priority sectors for the maintenance of social infrastructure (COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2008/114/EC, 2008; Freund et al., 2023). The objective of our study is to conduct a downstream sideways analysis to gain insight into the steps following the identification of a crisis situation. Our research question focuses on what crisis management methods are used by food retailers in one of their most prominent areas of operation, inventory management. Building on key findings from the literature, our research is exploratory in nature and the primary data collection is based on semi-structured interviews with 3 dominant players in the food retail industry. In presenting the results of our research, it is detailed among other things, that although the literature suggests that safety stock is one of the tools to reduce uncertainty, it has not proven to be an effective method in the present situation. Other findings include the finding that the companies in our study tend to have a short-term approach to crisis management. After analysing the qualitative interviews, good practices are identified that can benefit practitioners, whether they are micro, small, medium, or large trading companies.

2. LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Over the past decade, there have been several global, regional, and national crises that have forced companies, including retailers, to make sudden decisions. In our literature analysis, the importance and characteristics of inventory management in retailing are reviewed. Then the paper presents crisis management solutions formulated in the literature that can help decision-makers in the FMCG industry. Finally, a brief outline of the inventory challenges that have hit the retail sector as a result of the most widespread crises of the last decade (pandemic COVID-19 and the Russian-Ukrainian war) is introduced.

2.1. Challenges of value creation - focusing on inventory in retail

A general definition of the value creation process is the procurement, management and use of resources to create value for customers (Sharma et al., 2007). In retailing, the characteristics of these processes differ somewhat from this understanding, as value creation in the industry is derived from the fact that customers pay for the products produced, even though it was not produced by the retailer, as they recognise the value of the product added by the commercial labour (Levy & Weitz, 2012). Retailers deliver goods to consumers more efficiently and economically

through their value creation process than producers (Dudás, 2012). That's why in our case the process is equivalent to the steps of inventory management (steps are illustrated in Figure 1).

Figure 1 Steps in the value creation process in retail

Source: own editing based on Dudás, 2012, Nemtajela and Mbohwa, 2017, Czakó and Reszegi, 2010; Hausmann, 2020, Olcott et al., 2022, Allam et al., 2022 and Schmidt, 2021.

In each case, the evolution of the product-level inventory level is influenced by two main factors: the pattern of demand for the item and the pattern of supply of the item (Gelei, 2016). The different inventory management mechanisms allow these factors to be understood and adapted to. There are traditional inventory mechanisms which influence the essential inventory processes of retailers as well. These mechanisms can be applied to different business circumstances because of their diversity. The situation in which each model can be applied effectively depends strongly on its advantages and disadvantages. Although the (t,q) model is nowadays considered to be an obsolete method, it does provide suppliers with predictable supply. This aspect plays a very important role in the procurement of FMCG products. The main advantage of the (t,S) model is the ease of scheduling of purchases, due to the predictability of ordering times under this mechanism, but unfortunately the company may lose its price advantage due to different order quantities. The (s,q) model, like the (s,S) model, requires continuous inventory monitoring, which can be both advantageous and disadvantageous (Hadley & Whitin, 1961; Goh, 1992; Paterson et al., 2011; Benkő, 2018; Péter, 2021).

The whole process, as well as the individual sub-processes, has been seriously challenged by recent global events. Inventory management is increasingly emphasized nowadays, as inadequate management of inventories can lead to a decrease in sales or even the closure of the business (Nemtajela & Mbohwa, 2017). One of the most important tasks of the activity system is to minimize the costs associated with inventory management (Dudás, 2012). The JIT system applied to FMCG products can be used to minimise inventory holding costs, but the two global

events have made it challenging to achieve this goal (Czakó & Reszegi, 2010; Hausmann, 2020). While the Covid-19 virus and the military conflict had a significant impact on the price of certain procurement and inventory services (e.g.: transport costs, warehouse heating costs), panic buying of certain products (e.g.: toilet paper (Banker, 2021), yeast (Deutscher Verband der Hefeindustrie e.V., 2022) forced companies to purchase more than planned, as empty store shelves suggest that emergency stock held to avoid inventory shortages was also used up, which can be partly explained by the low stockholding principle of JIT procurement (Hausmann, 2020). In general, increased energy prices have mostly affected the administrative costs of warehousing within the fixed costs of inventory, while in the case of purchasing, the transport costs have been affected (Dudás, 2012). As a consequence of the 'lock-in' that occurred during the coronavirus epidemic, some factories ceased production, leading to disruption of supply chains (Olcott et al., 2022). This resulted in higher costs of finished goods, longer delivery times, limited access to raw materials, and increased inequality in supply chains (Allam et al., 2022 Schmidt, 2021). One of the major drawbacks of the JIT system is that it increases the risks of business continuity (Czakó & Reszegi, 2010; Hausmann, 2020), which has been brought to light by the current crisis. Indeed, Hausmann has shown "a correlation between the exposure of industries to the economic crisis caused by the Covid-19 virus epidemic and the stockholding volumes and accumulation policies of individual industries. [...] Smaller inventories, which were mostly built up in the past in the spirit of just-in-time, lean management and optimisation, [...] are not sufficient to maintain production levels in a temporary period of liquidity and demand shortages, and therefore the factories in these industries are forced to shut down sooner" (Hausmann, 2020, p. 139). Figure 1 visualises the main challenges of inventory management.

2.3 Crisis management methods according to maturity

Firms tend to face various crises in their operational phase (Székely, 2009), which have increased in recent years due to turbulent crises (Aday & Aday, 2020; Sid et al., 2021; Jámber & Nagy, 2022a; Nagy, 2023; Rudyk, et al., 2023), regardless of the maturity level of firms (Kocziszky, 1994; Szerb, 2000; Javaid & Raza, 2023) and their sectoral affiliation. The maturity curve of a firm is composed of stages of entry, growth, maturity and decline (Kocziszky, 1994; Phelps et al., 2007), and the remeasures of a firm experiencing a crisis may differ in relation to where it is positioned on the maturity curve. Székely (2009) points out in his research that, although firms are more likely to face crisis situations (not specifically as a consequence of external disturbances) in the decline stage, they can face crisis situations at any stage of maturity. The current crises affecting Europe (such as the Covid-19 epidemic, the energy crisis and the Ukrainian-Russian war) have also put the retail companies in focus on in a difficult situation.

The crisis management methods available to companies were first published in the military literature (Resperger, 2018), which at first sight seems difficult to adapt to the retail sector. Resperger's (2018) approach also identifies dominant phases for crises, which are usually the initial phase, followed by an unfolding phase, followed by the peak of the crisis and finally the period of termination. This analogy can also

be applied to recent crises. It can also be concluded from Resperger's (2018) study that the characteristics of crises are that they are periodic, with well-defined boundaries, which are not yet known at the initial stage. The so-called DIADAL (DDADAC in English) method (Komócsin, 2009), which builds its process elements through the analogy of the common method of process improvement (PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) analysis) (ISO, 2015), as included in the ISO 9001:2015 standard, can be considered as a general (non-military) crisis management method. In his study, Giorgetto (2021) confirms the application of this logic in crisis management (Giorgetto, 2021). The mosaic consists of the following successive steps: diagnosis - direction - alternatives - decision - application - closure (Komócsin, 2009; Resperger, 2018). The cycle can serve as a structured method for companies. It can be seen that it is necessary to focus primarily on identifying the situation, and then, after defining the character, formulating the strategic objectives, thus drawing the guiding principles of crisis management (). The listing of alternatives is already the result of targeted research and appears on the palette on the basis of which a decision can be made. This is followed by the application of the chosen procedure based on the decision, which, if successful, is followed by the final step, the feedback (Resperger, 2018). However, this approach may be supported by the PDCA cycle approach for longer-lasting crises, which may be linked to a restart of the process, so that a return to the Alternatives position is possible in case of unsatisfactory results.

Flexibility and reliability are essential features of the process. Reliability plays a key role in establishing the credibility and comprehensibility of the information provided to key stakeholders. It can be shown that in crisis management methods it is important to pay attention to the people to be involved. The development and selection of the method is a matter for senior management, but it is worth involving experts from the relevant areas in the steps of the process (Khodarahmi, 2009). In the following, the challenges related to the inventory issues that are the focus of our research are described.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

After an analysis of our exploratory, semi-structured interviews, our findings are formulated. The interviewees were selected randomly and on the basis of opportunity, given that inventory strategies are a central activity and therefore a sensitive area in the life of retailers. Table 1 introduces the food retailers interviewed. They are all located in Hungary but have different coverage and ownership backgrounds.

Table 1 Introduction of companies that participated in the research

	Food retail chain (FRC)	National retail chain (NRC)	Online supermarket
Main activity	food retail	food retailing	online retailing
Company background	Hungarian subsidiary	only domestically owned	Hungarian subsidiary
Operating time in Hungary	20+ years	20+ years	5+ years
Way of operation	offline traditionally and online	offline traditionally	online traditionally and offline newly

Source: own editing based on Nemzeti Cégtár (2023), 2024

The research steps included a systematic literature review focusing on challenges for inventory management and their relations to the traditional inventory mechanisms and a qualitative analysis as an exploratory research which aims to extend the statements of the current literature. Prior to the empirical research, in addition to the literature analysis, secondary research was carried out in the form of analysis of websites, industry data, etc. Based on the information collected, a cross-case case study was conducted to understand the operation of the companies and provide multi-perspective support, which is presented in the next chapter (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Our aim is to gain a deeper understanding by applying this methodology, and therefore the analysis of the interviews seems to be suitable to answer the research question. The interview questions were derived from the highlights and gaps of the literature review and turned to be suitable for the observed retailers. The interviews were carried out online and took 50-60 minutes. The interviewees agreed to record the interviews so the interviews could be transcribed. The transcripts were analysed and coded. The four subchapters of the empirical analysis are built onto the codes which appeared during the analysis of the interviews. The results obtained cannot be used as a basis for generalization and thus cannot be called representative (Yin, 2012), but the diversity of interviewees (national, international, online/offline) contributes to a broad understanding of the functioning of the food retail sector in a crisis.

4. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

To apply the chosen qualitative methodology, four aspects emerging from the literature were chosen as the framework for analysis. These range from the general characteristics of the actions, through an analysis of the time span of their implementation, to an examination of the role of communication. Finally, an examination of the situation within the corporate function under study is shown.

4.1. Actions in crisis situations

As a first step in the analysis of our research results, the actions taken by the companies that participated in the research, which were specifically put in place to deal with the crisis situations of the last decade (pandemic COVID-19 and the Russian-Ukrainian war) are examined in detail. These actions are presented along the following lines: solutions concerning purchasing, solutions concerning inventory management and solutions concerning online activities.

In the case of procurement steps, all three companies are highly dependent on imports, as they are forced to import goods due to the characteristics and specificities of the Hungarian market and agriculture (OECD, 2017). It is therefore not surprising that the procurement difficulties were caused primarily by the fact that shipments were blocked by border barriers during the epidemic. In addition, the rise in fuel prices due to import dependency during the Russian-Ukrainian conflict also posed a huge challenge for the companies surveyed. However, the extent to which they were exposed to these challenges and the type of actions they decided to adopt in response to them depends to a large extent on their specific characteristics. In the case of FRC, as it is a Hungarian subsidiary, risk management at the parent company level is reflected. The standards are set by the parent company and the adaptation to the country is the responsibility of the subsidiary. For our research, this meant that the FRC had several scenarios, one of which had to be adapted to the specific situation. Another action that could be mentioned for the company was the search for new suppliers. Given the size of the chain, this was possible at short notice, as they have a high bargaining power with suppliers. In the case of online supermarket, it is worth highlighting the fact that they operate as supermarkets and not discounters, which means that they have a much larger range of products. This characteristic has been the main challenge for online retailers during the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus and has led to a significant simplification of their offer. Today, they have returned to a more complex offering, so this intervention can be considered a crisis management solution. One of the features of the NRC's activities is the large number of domestic products distributed, which has led to better relations with domestic suppliers and producers and has made it less costly for it to switch to more domestic suppliers as imports ceased. However, this company is also import-dependent, with increased transport costs being the main challenge. It is important to underline that crisis management initiatives are also heavily influenced by the impact of the crisis. In the two crisis situations under review, Hungary did not experience product shortages, with the epidemic causing a problem of blocked shipments, while the armed conflict affected the production of only one product, *Balaton szelet* (which is an originally Hungarian chocolate bar), in Ukraine, which was in short supply.

An unforeseen consequence of the Covid-19 virus outbreak was the start of a panic stockpiling among consumers, which also posed difficulties for stockpiling. In general, our sample was not characterized by the accumulation of extra inventories. One of the reasons for this was goods in transit, e.g., inventory whose transport had to be stopped due to border closures. Products in inventory were already there but had not reached the companies. Another reason for not opting for restocking was that companies were more concerned about not being able to sell their inventory before

the expiry date than of having a few days of empty shelves for a given product. This mentality is typical of JIT operations. As it has been already established in the case of procurement solutions, one of FRC's major competitive advantages was its size, which meant that it was able to implement work organisation solutions at short notice, as night restocking was introduced during the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus, with large numbers of workers being taken on from other sectors (typically hospitality). For the online supermarket, the main challenge was inventory management due to the characteristics of the company (online sales and relatively young), which by its nature does not have an offline shop and therefore all products are stored in a warehouse. Due to the sudden increase in demand, they were finding it difficult to manage their inventory processes and decided to rethink these processes. One of the most important characteristics of the national retail chain for our research is that it has both company-owned and not company-owned stores. One of the most significant solutions, which also affected inventory management, was therefore the allocation of goods on a store-by-store basis. The proportion of goods delivered between stores was maintained, but the volume delivered was reduced.

Last but not least, the actions affecting online activities will be analysed in more detail, as the pandemic has shown that any form of digitalisation can provide a significant competitive advantage for companies (García-Salirrosas et al., 2022) FRC was also characterised by the operation of an online shop before the epidemic, but the crisis has led to a greater emphasis on this, although offline trade remains its main profile. This is also the result of a conscious decision, as the company is aware that the coverage of its stores in Hungary gives it a significant competitive advantage (differentiated competitive strategy). In the case of the online supermarket, it is not relevant to compare the extent of offline and online activity. Our research on the company found that its nature was characterised by the adoption of courier logistics solutions to deal with increased demand. Finally, the national retail chain does not operate an online shop before, during or after the epidemic, but its physical coverage is significant not only in larger cities but also in rural areas, small towns and poorer regions of the country, so it does not consider it justified to build a web shop. It can therefore be concluded that, although companies are typically affected by the same impacts, the extent of the impacts and the actions taken to deal with them are significantly influenced by the specific characteristics of the company.

4.2 Time span

In examining the time horizon, the aim was to explore whether the actions described above will have short-, medium- and long-term actors. There was unanimous agreement among our interviewees that their initiatives would be determined by the crisis situation, and that they did not consider long-term actions. In the case of the FRC, the short term (maximum of a quarter of a year) until the next revision was typical. Those introduced under the Covid-19 pandemic, e.g., the operational group, were disbanded after its dissolution. FRC has a well-established base to fall back on. They prepare themselves mostly for turbulent changes, so they do not plan for the long term, but build foundations to accelerate the response. NRC has also seen the effects of the actions introduced in the short term. However, the Online supermarket

has incorporated some of the changes in the long term in view of the growth phase. Their delivery service was improved under Covid-19, a service level (Christopher, 2016) that has been maintained ever since, and their response to the inventory management challenge has been incorporated into their long-term operations, simplifying their palette, and narrowing their offer.

4.3 The role of communication

Communication plays a crucial role in all management transactions, especially in crisis situations. For the retailers studied, it can be said that the international group enjoyed an advantage due to its network of contacts. In the case of the retailers, internal communication in support of security of supply is digital, partly supported by software (originating from the parent company). Crisis management was supported by the parent company's network. There was intensive communication with other actors in the country. A recurrent method has been to communicate with the areas affected by the Covid-19 virus, as the applicable protocols have been established earlier, thus facilitating the preparedness in Hungary. Focusing mainly on internal supply (warehouse and store network), FRC started an IT development process which supported the reduction of the order backlog and the development of security of supply. For this one actor under review, there is a guide for internal operations, which was touched upon during the Covid-19 pandemic. It provided a good basis for how to communicate with customers and staff on security of supply. They are also consciously preparing to manage risks. They have a business continuity plan and a risk management description using different methods to describe how different contingencies could occur. There is less intensive communication with the outside (suppliers and customers), and it is difficult to talk about conscious supply chain management thinking on the part of the trader towards external actors. Basic communication has been established with consumers, but no closer communication with the supplier side has been established in the context of crisis management. In the logistics planning of FRC, the large number of items in the inventory is noticeable, the active planning relationship can only be established with the larger suppliers. A common feature with NRC is the intensification of communication with the authority (operational trunk) during the pandemic. This was typically a one-way relationship in the form of external intervention (quantity limitation) to avoid shortages. Nonetheless, both interviewees (FRC and NRC) also consider continuous communication with the decision-making bodies during crisis situations to be essential. FRC communicated with the relevant government bodies in cooperation with its partners in the trade association. NRC also highlighted that the increased communication with the government may have been triggered by the strategic importance of food inventory for all countries in an emergency (Freund et al., 2023), so that in their case, on the recommendation of the operational staff, a military agent arrived at the warehouse centre to seize the inventory if necessary. The representative of NRC believes that the flow of communication between top management and employees is much more flexible than in a multinational company. This is meant to indicate that communication in both directions was based on personal experience, in the absence of an international background. General information was provided to small shops,

details could be obtained from top management, which was routinely embedded in the corporate culture. External communication to customers was typically one-sided and indirect, e.g., queuing stickers, Plexiglas at checkouts during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Online supermarket under study does not have such a communication platform, but it does have an online platform with excellent data collection capabilities. This retail unit also did not communicate directly with its customers, but monitored consumption patterns of e.g., price-stopping products in order to be able to plan. It observed an upsurge of these products, despite the fact that the basket they were monitoring also included a range of traditional premium products that customers were used to. This showed that consumers were shifting towards products with a price stop. Despite this, no action was taken towards suppliers, no overstocking was targeted and based on well-documented consumption data, they weathered the Covid-19 period without more specific supplier crisis management coordination with their forecasts. In contrast, communication with couriers (as a service supplier) (for recruitment reasons) became a central issue for them. To balance the trade-offs (Hugos, 2024) towards the buyer, they resorted to raising the minimum order value and the free delivery threshold in relation to energy costs, which can be perceived as an example of one-sided communication. The Online supermarket under study is part of a group from a European country but was less able to take advantage of the common know-how held by the SCC in terms of shared experience. This may be due to the fact that they had developed together in the pre-Covid period (2015-2019) (Christopher, 2016), so there was no justification for turning to the parent company, they are characterized by similar maturity.

4.4. Inventory mechanisms

The final point of our analysis was to examine which of the inventory mechanisms described in the literature review is the most typical for which company, and whether crisis situations have changed their use.

In our opinion, it is difficult to determine which inventory mechanism dominates in the FMCG industry itself. According to the findings of the research, the (t,q) model is the primary mechanism within basic foods, perishables such as milk, bakery products and fruits. Although described in the literature as an obsolete method, the fast rotation speed and low seasonality of these products generate a steady demand, which is well predictable from the procurement side. In contrast, durables (flour, sugar, toilet paper) are purchased along the (s,q) mechanism. It is difficult to give a precise answer to the question of how this has been changed by the pandemic. While it is true that the companies did not accumulate excessively large inventories, the increased demand forced them to purchase more than they normally would have done. As a consequence, in the short run the (t,S) model took the lead, as purchasing was characterised by variable ordering times and quantities. This suggests that firms acted in a reactive way, trying to catch up with the market. At this point in our paper, it is considered important to highlight that the literature suggests that the (s,q) model is best suited to deal with uncertainty (Demeter et al., 2022) If companies and the inventory management mechanisms they use are compared, it can be seen that in the case of the online supermarket, two models are used due to the complexity of the offer.

For typical FMCG products (higher rotation rate), the (s,q) model prevails, as it is characterised by automatic inventory monitoring, since the online shop only offers the products that are visible in their inventory management system. In contrast, for luxury, seasonal or limited products, maximum inventory replenishment is sought, so the (s,S) model can be considered relevant. At the same time, it is important to underline an important tool of online trading, which is the following: there is a restrictive intervention by the company during the ordering process, since the order can only be modified up to a given deadline. This does not make sense for an offline shop. FRC is not a supermarket, but a grocery retailer, so it does not have a very complex offer. Our study shows that the (s,q) inventory control mechanism was dominant during the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus, as the consumption of products was constantly monitored through the cash registers and used as a basis for deciding on interventions to limit the quantity of purchases. The NRC found a difference in demand between small and large shops. While small stores are characterised by lower demand, which is less predictable, the (t,S) model seems to be a dominant one. In contrast, larger stores are characterized by higher, more predictable demand, which supports the (s,q) model. Whether there is a difference in the frequency of deliveries between stores of different sizes was not answered in our research.

In conclusion, since there was no further large-scale stockpiling in the medium to long term for any of the companies, the stockpiling mechanism used did not change, except in the short term, on a temporary basis. It should be emphasized, however, that the action concerning the supply of the online supermarket remained in place in the medium term but has now reverted to a complex supply.

5. CONCLUSION

From the case studies, it became clear to us that when asked about crisis situations, the primary example cited by our respondents was the actions taken reacting to the Covid-19 virus caused pandemic. The Russian-Ukrainian war situation was less frequently raised to the level of the main cause of the challenges. What they all reported in terms of their supply portfolio was a temporary shortage of Balaton slices (chocolate bar), as this product is produced in Ukraine and the manufacturer has cut back capacity to protect its workers in the context of the war (Péncentrum, 2022). The solution to this was beyond the scope of the retailers. However, the online supermarket highlighted the energy crisis, which affects everyone but is less a temporary crisis, causing a fundamental reorganization of their operations. The analysis has resulted in the good practices shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 is based on a framework of criteria developed on the basis of an analysis of the literature to answer our research question. These can all be considered as areas of use in crisis management within the company.

Figure 2 Summary of good practices for communication

Source: own editing.

The collections in Figure 2 illustrate that firm characteristics, such as the degree of maturity and the firm's background, are seen as influencing factors from which commercial units from other backgrounds can also benefit, and therefore no attempt is made to break down the data into categories. Among the good practices, the role of communication towards both internal and external stakeholders stand out. This means to strengthen internal communication can be to develop appropriate methodologies (formally: e.g., developing crisis/risk management procedures that can be adapted to different potential crises; informally: implementing open, two-way, rapid communication between employees and management) and to develop channels for intensive information exchange within the group, so that sharing good practices can become a routine activity. Of course, this requires appropriate coordination, which also involves resources, but it can play a useful role in the long-term vision. Communication to external parties, such as customers, has tended to remain one-sided, with clarity being the example to follow. Increasing cooperation with decision-makers and professional organisations, and at the same time participation in the dialogue, can help to understand the crisis situation and provide a basis for preparing appropriate action. There was no major intensity of communication towards suppliers, which raises the issue of the existence of a supply chain management approach. However, this is in response to the wide range of goods on offer, which does not allow for closer communication with individual suppliers.

On the other hand, it could be seen that supplier relationships have become more valued, which is now a matter of supply function management. Figure 3 represents the interpretation of management actions found during the analysis.

Figure 3 Summary of good practices for management

Source: own editing.

That was clear from our interviews that in a crisis situation, the main focus was on high bargaining power with suppliers and building good relationships with domestic suppliers. These aspects can help to overcome difficulties such as border barriers. In order to secure supply, our respondents have also modified their sales methodology, namely by rationalising their complex offer. This practice has made it possible to support purchasing on the basis of consumer trends, which has also ultimately minimised the emergence of inventory shortages. Regarding inventory management, our interviewees pointed out that the sudden surge in demand did not affect the premises evenly, as they found differences in the intensity of demand depending on the size of the shop. This implies that larger stores will be hit by demand effects sooner, so that adjusting stockholding mechanisms to store size can lead to results. In general management tools, there has been an emergence of short-term thinking with a longer-term perspective. It is worth building into operational practice the periodic review of the established actions and the evaluation of their long-term serviceability, which resonates with the process approach in Giorgetto (2021) and Resperger (2018) (Giorgetto, 2021; Resperger, 2018). The time horizon of actions was limited to the short term for the interviewees more mature in terms of life cycle, mostly formulating formal/informal operational recommendations and good practices based on past experience. In contrast, the interviewee in the growth phase sought to exploit opportunities. They were aiming for long-term integration of procedures and methods imposed by the crisis. Building on these points, it is worthwhile to build a conscious attitude into the corporate culture, so that panic reactions can be avoided and a quick and effective response to crises can be developed.

6. SUMMARY

To conclude our article, the main findings of our study are briefly summarised. Our research question focused on the crisis management methods and actions used by food retailers in one of their most prominent areas of operation, inventory management. In order to answer our research question as accurately as possible, our literature review outlined the importance and role of inventory management in retailing. After that, the crisis management methods affecting this area of operation, aimed primarily at dealing with the effects of the Covid-19 epidemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war, were presented, as well as the challenges that caused them and related to inventory management. The results of our research were then presented in detail. Among our main findings, it is found that, although the literature suggests that safety stock is a tool to manage uncertainty and achieve greater resilience, it is not necessarily appropriate to deal with all situations in a comprehensive manner. In addition, the companies in our study were characterised by short-term thinking, as their crisis management actions were typically temporary, regardless of the operational area targeted. However, the conscious management of risks in crisis situations plays an increasingly important role today (Abdel-Basset & Mohamed, 2020). However, beyond conscious risk management, the maturity level of companies and their capabilities (e.g., international integration) also have a strong influence on their reasures. Consequently, the development of crisis management methods (Resperger, 2018; Giorgetto, 2021) can make a major contribution to the management of turbulent crisis situations. As a result of this research, good practices for practitioners will cover both general management approaches and set-specific recommendations. In addition to this, the exploratory research has highlighted the issue of managing communication in a considered way, both internally and externally. The limitations of our research are, first of all, the small sample (hence the lack of representativeness), the exploratory nature of the analysis, which stems from the qualitative methodology, and therefore the lack of generalisability of our results. On the other hand, however, the methodology chosen for this research allows us to gain a deep understanding of the actions adopted by the companies involved in our research and the thought processes behind them. Further research is needed to overcome these limitations and to involve a wider range of FMCG retailers. It is therefore necessary to extend the subjects of our research, not only at national but also at global level. Moreover, a more detailed understanding and better comparability would be facilitated by analysing food retailers by category (e.g., discount, supermarket).

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III. OPTIMIZATION IN SUPPLY CHAINS

ORGANISATION AND OPERATING PROCEDURES IN DATA-DRIVEN URBAN MOBILITY

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Abstract

This paper aims to present the possibilities of applying innovative organisation approaches and methods in the decision-making process and traffic management system in the city of Rijeka using simulation tools. In this research, a simulation tool was used for testing standard operating procedures, i.e. traffic events and conditions that occur regularly or are extraordinary in the city of Rijeka. The paper presents the process of creating an organisation and traffic model that serves as a basis for simulating a total of six dynamic scenarios. It aims to demonstrate that the application of the simulations to the example of the city of Rijeka contributes to the development of modern organisational approaches and traffic sector improvements. In addition, modern organisational development of the traffic sector in Rijeka requires access to quality and realistic (real-time) data on the state of traffic. For this reason, an advanced information and communication program is necessary as a support for the decision-making process and tools as well as the organisational management of urban mobility.

Key words: organisation, simulation model, standard operating procedures, traffic management, urban mobility

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban areas around the world are facing major challenges due to increasing traffic density. The number of vehicles on the roads continues to increase, putting immense pressure on existing infrastructure and creating a number of problems such as congestion, road safety and pollution. Traffic congestion mainly causes delays,

hinders the transportation of emergency services and contributes to air and noise pollution (Masek et al., 2016).

Congestion has become a critical issue in Rijeka, a city suffering under the burden of growing car traffic. The city's infrastructure is struggling to accommodate the growing number of vehicles, leading to frequent bottlenecks, delays and safety risks, especially during rush hours. Studies have highlighted the imbalance between traffic demand and infrastructure capacity, which has led to inefficient traffic flow and long travel times (Qiao et al., 2021). This not only affects daily commuters, but also has a direct impact on the performance of emergency services and exacerbates traffic management problems in the city.

To address these challenges, the CEKOM Connected Traffic project was launched with the aim of improving traffic management through innovative organizational approaches and decision-making tools. The project defines Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that enable a structured response to both regular and exceptional traffic events such as accidents, road closures and severe weather. The SOPs serve as predefined management tools that enable real-time decision making, optimize traffic flow and ensure a more responsive traffic management system.

An important part of the CEKOM project is the development of simulation-based traffic management solutions. By simulating various traffic scenarios, such as accidents or road works on major roads, the project will investigate how Rijeka can improve its traffic system and decision-making processes. The use of simulation tools makes it possible to test different strategies in a controlled environment before applying them in the real world of traffic management. This approach is widely recognized for its potential to alleviate traffic congestion and improve the efficiency of transport systems (Chung et al., 2020; Dunkel et al., 2011).

In this context, intelligent transportation systems (ITS) play a crucial role in modern urban traffic management. ITS solutions, such as advanced sensor technologies, distributed control systems and real-time communication networks, are designed to monitor and influence traffic conditions in real time. By using advanced data collection and processing technologies, ITS can reduce congestion, improve safety and minimize the environmental impact of traffic (Makino et al., 2018; Perallos et al., 2015). These technologies and processes are usually embedded in smart city concepts, where they support holistic city management.

The aim of this article is to present the opportunities and challenges related to the use of ITS solutions in Rijeka's urban traffic management system. Building on the results of the CEKOM project, it will show how simulations and SOPs can improve decision making and traffic flow, reduce congestion and improve overall mobility in the city. Furthermore, the work aims to show that the application of these solutions, supported by modern data-driven tools, can lead to the development of more responsive and effective traffic management practices.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review was conducted according to the methodology described by Vukelić et al. (2023) and Debelić (2024), which is suitable for similar research

projects. The process involved several important steps: obtaining materials, conducting a descriptive analysis, selecting categories and evaluating sources. The materials sourcing phase took place between February and June 2024, using a variety of approaches to ensure a comprehensive collection of relevant literature. The timeframe for this literature search included all references available in selected databases that were published by the end of 2023. Only peer-reviewed articles from reputable journals were considered, with the Web of Science Core Collection serving as the primary database. Keywords such as “urban mobility”, “organisation” “standard operating procedures (SOPs)” and “intelligent transportation systems (ITS)” were used to refine the search results. Boolean operators and truncation symbols were used to narrow the search, focusing on titles, keywords and summaries. The final selection of references was analysed using the VOSviewer software and the graphical representations of the Web of Science (WoS) services. The descriptive analysis of the selected material was conducted across different time periods and focused on publications between 1994 and 2023 that dealt with key concepts such as urban mobility and organizational aspects. A total of 180 journal articles were identified in the target area, with the number of articles and citations increasing significantly since 2008. This growth coincides with the increasing attention being paid to the challenges of urban mobility in rapidly growing areas. Several studies stand out in this literature. For example, Chung et al. (2020) investigated the development of decision support systems for integrated active transportation management, focusing on travel time reliability. The results of the study highlight the need for more efficient traffic management strategies in urban areas. Similarly, Dunkel et al. (2011) emphasized the importance of event-driven architecture to support decision-making processes in traffic management systems. These studies are closely related to the objectives of the CEKOM Connected Traffic project, which aims to improve traffic management in Rijeka through the development and implementation of SOPs. Research on intelligent transportation systems (ITS) can also be found in the literature, such as Makino et al. (2018), who investigated the application of ITS technologies to solve urban traffic problems. They concluded that advanced sensor technology, distributed control systems and real-time communication play a central role in improving traffic flow and reducing congestion. These findings support the direction of this study, particularly with regard to the use of ITS to improve urban mobility in Rijeka. Similarly, Shelke et al. (2019) and Zambrano-Martinez et al. (2018) investigated how predictive systems and wireless sensor networks can help to detect and reduce traffic congestion. Qiao et al. (2021) investigated the problem of traffic congestion and identified an imbalance between traffic demand and infrastructure supply as the main cause. This finding is particularly relevant for Rijeka, where traffic congestion has become a growing problem. Guo et al. (2020) also emphasized the role of smart city initiatives in alleviating traffic congestion, although this study avoids overgeneralizing the concept of “smart cities” and focuses specifically on traffic management technologies. By summarizing these different studies, the study lays the foundation for understanding how the SOPs and simulation tools of the CEKOM project can be used to address the specific challenges of traffic management in Rijeka. This study builds on existing research but focuses on the practical application of these technologies in a real urban environment, with the aim of improving traffic flow,

reducing congestion and improving decision-making processes within urban transportation systems.

Figure 1 Publication and citation time distribution for articles acquired through Web of Science for the field of organisation in urban mobility

Source: Authors using WoS web service

The majority of publications were in urban studies (34), followed by transportation (33) and environmental studies (24). Detection of relevant subject areas is important as it helps the research being comprehensively focused on the papers that support the same research area while indicating the profiles of scientists.

Figure 2 Subject areas distribution for articles acquired through Web of Science for the field of organisation in urban mobility

Source: Authors using WoS web service

Figure 3 Weight of items based on the analysis of titles, abstracts and keywords for articles acquired through Web of Science for the field of organisation in urban mobility

Source: Authors

The selected papers were quickly skimmed through to look for any potential inconsistencies in their summaries and conclusions throughout the materials evaluation process. This was done to ensure that the credibility of the literature review and the author's emphasis were maintained.

3. SIMULATIONS AND STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES IN TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT

3.1 SOP in urban mobility

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are documents that contain a set of clear instructions provided to members of a team and members of an organization to properly perform certain activities and complete certain processes. In addition, documentation SOPs are not just a document with procedures, but documentation SOPs consist of clearly stated procedures that must be applied to complete certain processes as planned. Also, the use of SOPs serves to reduce errors, increase efficiency, profitability and provide guidelines for resolving problems and overcoming obstacles.

SOPs are effective because they provide clear step-by-step instructions necessary to perform specific processes and they inform process participants of potential risks associated with the process. It is also necessary to first assess the risks

associated with all steps of the process to identify obstacles that may occur in the process and describe the processes that form the basis for developing SOPs.

3.2 Modelling and simulation

A range of simulation software has been developed to facilitate the use of modelling and simulation for the purposes of traffic planning and engineering (Fujimoto & Leonard, 2002). The use of modelling and simulation in traffic systems has an important role in the development of the system and the evaluation of traffic conditions. Testing traffic management in practice is costly and time-consuming. For this reason, the use of simulation tools in a laboratory environment is necessary (Esser & Schreckenberg, 1997).

By creating a traffic model for a specific city, simulation results should be obtained for the purpose of traffic optimization. The development of a traffic model requires traffic information in the form of the origin-destination matrix (OD matrix), i.e. trips in the traffic network based on the rules for route selection (Zhang et al., 2020). Therefore, it is necessary to know the distribution of traffic within the defined zones as well as between them, which requires analysis and qualification of traffic (Zambrano-Martinez et al., 2018).

Depending on the precision of the description, the traffic simulation model is divided into three categories: macroscopic, mesoscopic, and microscopic models. The microscopic simulation model is the most accurate, implementing vehicles as model units, while macroscopic simulation model can describe traffic flow using flow density functions (Qiao et al., 2021).

4. DEVELOPMENT OF SOPS IN THE CITY OF RIJEKA

In the example of the SOPs developed as part of the CEKOM Connected Traffic project, the goal is to define in advance clear procedures to be applied to specific traffic scenarios, which include incidents, i.e. regular and emergency situations. After defining the goal, the format is created, which can be a flowchart, simple steps or hierarchical steps.

4.1 Analysis of existing SOPs in the city of Rijeka

The analysis of existing scenarios and standard operating procedures for decision support in urban transport, urban mobility and multimodal transport defines possibilities of traffic management in specific situations in urban traffic. The existing system can manage urban traffic with multiple scenarios, but the system uses only one scenario that covers regular situations. By monitoring the parameters of traffic flow, traffic density, speed of vehicles at intersections, categorization of vehicles, and monitoring traffic flow by zones and lanes, new or improved existing management scenarios are proposed for standard and non-standard traffic situations.

Table 1 Existing SOPs

TECHNICAL VERIFICATION PROCEDURES FOR THE OPERATION OF THE SYSTEM		TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES – REGULAR AND EXTRAORDINARY EVENT	
GROUP 1 – ATM ³ System	GROUP 2 – Video surveillance	GROUP 3 – Regular event	GROUP 4 – Extraordinary event
Technical verification procedure	Technical verification procedure	Procedures in regular situations are developed internally	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Traffic light malfunction – traffic lights off or out of action 2. Blockade of the main traffic route of the 1st corridor through the city – a detour required 3. Blockade of the main traffic route of the 2nd corridor through the city – a tour required 4. Rapid Intervention Vehicles (RIV) 5. Traffic collision on the main traffic route 6. Improper stop/parking on the main transport corridor 7. Roadworks, manifestations, etc. 8. Severe weather or natural disaster 9. Passage of protected/VIP vehicles through the city centre

Source: CEKOM, 2022.

In Table 1. the structure of existing standard operating procedures is presented. Procedures for technical verification of the system operation can be carried out using video surveillance or through the ATM System. Traffic management procedures differ in regular and emergency events. It should be emphasized that procedures in regular events as well as the technical verification through the ATM System and the video surveillance are developed internally. The extraordinary events are grouped into 9 specific situations. For each of these events the standard method of reporting and the recommended method of reporting to the city traffic centre are defined. Furthermore, for each scenario, a corrective measure that should be taken has been determined and analysed.

4.2 Development of new SOPs in the city of Rijeka

Based on the existing SOPs and the newly developed functionalities of the innovative system, new SOPs were defined. Characteristics of the new SOPs are manifested in the activation, which is manual or automatic depending on the range of values collected by the data aggregation platform, and automatic by direct notification (Fig. 4).

³ ATM – Automatic Traffic Management System in the city of Rijeka, with its technological capabilities, aims at optimal management of traffic under given conditions. Modern traffic management technology enables the management of light traffic signals depending on the current traffic loads on the traffic network.

Figure 4 Activation process SOPs and data process and flow

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

During the occurrence of a traffic situation, the sensors installed in the field detect the traffic situation and send information about it to the data aggregation platform. From the platform, the information is forwarded to the application layer, which initiates the optimal procedure depending on the type of information, categorization, or value. Therefore, situations observed in the field lead to measurement values. For example, the number of vehicles on the section, the speed on the section, meteorological values, environmental parameters, etc. If the measured value or a combination of these values exceeds the predefined frames, the corresponding SOPs are activated. In addition, there is the possibility of direct alerting, i.e. if the sensor detects certain traffic situations, such as running a red light, a SOP is automatically activated and does not need to be locked by the platform or application solution.

The CEKOM Connected Traffic project identified newly developed SOPs and configured the software in a newly developed application solution for traffic monitoring and management. The newly developed SOPs (CEKOM, 2022) are:

1. Closure of the main corridor route through the city – required inspection,
2. Traffic collision,
3. Improper stopping/parking,
4. Severe weather or natural disasters,
5. Running a red light at a signal intersection,
6. Improper turning,
7. Detection of fires in the infrastructure,
8. Roadworks, manifestation,
9. Rapid Intervention Vehicles (RIV).

5. MODELING AND SIMULATIONS ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF RIJEKA

By defining scenarios and creating prototypes for simulations, the structure of traffic management should be clarified and acted on the example of sustainable transport and solving emergencies. The development of prototype simulations was preceded by the definition of innovative scenarios. To define a scenario, certain characteristics had to be known, i.e. the scope (zones, corridors within the city, etc.), the call of the selected scenarios, the conditions for activating the scenario, the activities of each actor in the scenario, and the conditions for termination system.

The simulation tool applies various strategies and measures in the field of traffic management. The use of simulation through the direct implementation of traffic events and conditions in the simulation model allows for easy use by traffic management bodies at strategic, tactical and/or operational levels. Such scenarios, strategies and measures are created based on SOPs describing different events and conditions that are simulated within the simulation prototype.

5.1 Methodology

The urban area and the wider administrative area of the city of Rijeka were considered regarding the functionality of the simulation model. The development of a simulation model represents the basis for a prototype simulation solution. The process of creating a simulation model required the use of multi-layer traffic models, the creation of a traffic network, i.e., the creation of a basic road network as well as the categorization of traffic and the regulation of intersections. The travel needs of different social groups by population and trip purpose were analyzed to define the demand zones. In addition, definitions of travel demand for a given time interval representing the OD matrices were created.

The process of creating traffic models requires different phases, the application of which depends on the objectives and purpose to be achieved by the simulations. The definition of travel demand depended on the travel needs of different social groups depending on the population size, according to the purpose for which the trip was made. Therefore, it was necessary to identify the generating zones and attractions, i.e. to divide the urban area into zones.

In the CEKOM Connected Traffic project, simulation is used to demonstrate the possibility of using the simulation tool in the decision-making and traffic management process as an innovative method within intelligent traffic management solutions in cities. Furthermore, the use of simulations served the purpose of prototyping, testing innovative scenarios and standard operating procedures to support decision-making within the project activity.

The tool used for modelling and simulation process is Aimsun Next Advance software that integrates microscopic, mesoscopic, macroscopic and hybrid simulation.

5.2 Modelling process and creating a transport network

Development of the traffic model in the city of Rijeka covers an area of about 44 km², with the main supply line in the west-east direction reaching a length of 19 km. The area also includes 34 local committees representing urban zones. Since the SOPs include procedures that affect traffic flow along entire corridors and beyond (e.g. corridor closures), it is necessary to model traffic throughout the affected area. For traffic modelling, a multi-layered modelling methodology was used that includes macro, meso, and micro levels of traffic simulations. Specifically, a traffic network is created to which all three layers are connected depending on the level being simulated. A characteristic of each level is the level of analytics, i.e. the resolution of the individual elements of the traffic network. Furthermore, the change in the network has an impact on all three levels.

Since the transport network covers the entire administrative territory of the city of Rijeka, its development was preceded by the creation of the basic road network, the categorization of roads and the regulation of intersections.

Based on the importance and permeability of each section, the categorization of roads was made. The most important elements of certain categories are throughput, traffic speed, number and width of lanes, and the purpose of each lane or road in relation to modes, i.e. transportation types.

Figure 5 Road network and category of roads according to the developed model

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

In addition to the basic road network and categorization of roads, it was necessary to arrange the intersections (Fig. 5). The arrangement of the intersections included geometry and rules for movement through the intersections, the processing of individual trajectories, the start and finish lanes, the stop lines and the rules for overtaking priority. Furthermore, it was necessary to create signal plans for signal transitions, define signal groups, and determine signal cycles and phases.

5.3 Defining traffic demand zones and creating OD matrices

For the purposes of the project, zoning based on mobility data collected through GSM base stations was used. The zoning is less different from the administrative zoning of the city of Rijeka, and more accurately determines the areas covered by GSM network data (Fig. 6).

Within the central zone, there is a special object that defines the centre of the generated and attracted currents in each zone: the centroid. Centroids connect the connectors to the objects of the transport network to which the demand is directed, i.e. from which the demand is collected in the zone. Centroids are nodes (intersections), sections, or endpoints (e.g. parking lot entrances and exits). Each centroid has several pairs of connections.

Figure 6 Zoning with focal connections

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

The creation of an OD matrix starts with the definition of the traffic demand for a given time interval. In this case, an interval of 3 hours in the morning between 6 a.m. and 9 a.m. was chosen for the standard day. Then OD pairs are created based on the movement in the share of car traffic. Public transport and other modes of transportation (e.g. walking) were not considered.

The basic data on movements based on GSM measurements are aggregated for a 3-hour interval. Therefore, in this case, trips are evenly distributed, which is not a realistic situation. Furthermore, it was necessary to break them down into shorter time intervals and distribute the shares of demand for these intervals. The validation was based on data on the number of vehicles per individual access for seven major intersections in the city. In addition, the proportions and changes in proportions of total demand were observed for the 3-hour interval. Therefore, 15-minute intervals were defined, i.e. 12 intervals for the observed period, which is sufficient for the result of the actual distribution of traffic demand.

Figure 7 Traffic demand profile for the period from 6 a.m. to 9 a.m.

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

The result is a histogram of the traffic demand profile, i.e. a representation of the distribution of traffic load for the target period. It was found that the obtained distribution has more pronounced peak loads in the periods between 7:30 a.m. and 8:30 a.m., which corresponds to the actual distribution of peak loads in the city of Rijeka (Fig. 7).

6. DEFINITION OF SIMULATED SCENARIOS AND RESULTS

The prototype simulation solution defines and initiates different scenarios describing traffic phenomena, initiates certain action strategies, tests the main traffic parameters, and finally uses them for traffic management decision-making.

Figure 8 Content of the simulated scenarios within the developed prototype

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

Traffic scenarios include regular and extraordinary events and traffic conditions (Fig. 8) consistent with the categories and action forms described in the traffic management Standard Operating Procedures. Events and traffic conditions require the initiation of certain actions that may be within the purview of traffic management or may be outside the purview of agencies that manage traffic or initiate the execution of certain automated procedures.

6.1 Scenarios and results

Within the framework of the developed traffic simulations, it is possible to create various performance policies and analyse them in terms of selected traffic variables and traffic parameters to improve traffic efficiency and increase the level of service. Six dynamic scenarios, combinations of traffic events and conditions were correlated with the previously defined SOPs within the CEKOM Connected Traffic project activity (Fig. 8).

The simulated scenarios that include regular traffic situations are illegally parked vehicles, traffic collisions and emergency interventions for the passage of VIP vehicles. The scenarios that analyse situations of high traffic density leading to traffic congestion represent specific traffic conditions. The simulated scenarios within extraordinary traffic situations are the closure of a determined road due holding of an event and overregulation of traffic due to roadworks.

Table 2 shows one of the examples of a regular event – traffic accident scenario.

Table 2 Scenario example: Regular event – Traffic accident

Event description	Event activation	Event settings
Traffic accident on the extreme right lane of the road Žrtava fašizma (northern traffic corridor). In this case, the right lane is blocked, vehicles have to be rearranged and move to the left lane in the accident area. In this example, due to the nature of the road, there is no impact on traffic from the opposite direction.	It is an occasional event that is activated at a selected time interval, based on the desired distribution (random).	The length of the lane was set at 25 m, the speed was adjusted, due to the traffic accident, the speed was reduced to 15 kmph before arriving at the event zone and in the event zone.

Source: CEKOM, 2022.

Figure 9 a) Scenario – traffic accident area b) Comparison of travel time due to a traffic accident in relation to the condition without

Source: Adapted from CEKOM, 2022.

The analysis of the results demonstrates the possibility of measuring the consequences of the event on the traffic flow through the impact on the travel time on the route where the event occurred. The Figure (Fig. 9) shows the results that prove an increase in travel time (in seconds) and a decrease in travel speed because of a traffic accident.

6.2 Research limitations and prospectives

The relevant limitations of this research are that efforts to research possible applications of innovative organisation approaches and methods in the decision-making process and traffic management system of a city are limited by two simultaneous perspectives – one that innovative organisation approaches are a continuously overgoing process, and other that decision-making process as well as traffic management system of a city are micro specific. On the other hand, a simulation tool used in this research enables to partially overcome those limitations through generalisation of the model, but at the same time there is a new emerging limitation of such an approach in the sense of possibilities of potential oversimplification of the model as well as its practical implications when using simulation models, particularly when the model aims to demonstrate that the application of the simulations to a specific city contributes to the development of modern organisational approaches and traffic sector improvements.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the use of simulation tool on the example of the traffic model of the city of Rijeka. Different scenarios are defined, i.e., regular, or extraordinary traffic events or conditions that activate standard operating procedures. Within the CEKOM Connected Traffic project, six dynamic scenarios were created, representing a combination of traffic situations with defined standard operating procedures. With the help of simulations using the city of Rijeka as an example, information was collected on the state of traffic at a given time and influence. Furthermore, the collected information is used to improve the traffic system and support decision-making in urban traffic.

By applying the elaborated elements of the decision support system in transport, the efficiency of the Automatic Traffic Management System in the city of Rijeka is improved. The platform derived by the simulations is tested in the function of the Centre for Monitoring and Management of Integrated Traffic. More efficient and faster automatic distribution of data with easy availability to all interested users will improve the traffic flow in the city centre thus reducing the congestion.

Nowadays, the excessive use of cars and vehicles in cities is facing increasingly unfavourable traffic situations especially in urban centres. Finding an effective solution for most cities is still a great challenge. Research and development solutions within CEKOM Connected Traffic project develop innovative systems for urban traffic control and management to reduce traffic congestion as well as improved systems for collecting and sharing traffic data among all users. These prototype solutions and innovative systems could be used within traffic management systems in small and medium cities to reduce congestion and improve decision-making processes within urban transportation systems.

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E-COMMERCE WAREHOUSE SUPPLYING PROCESS USING ERP MODERN SYSTEM

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Abstract

E-commerce logistics is a key element of success of e-commerce, encompassing the management of the supply chain from the moment a customer places an order through to the delivery of the product. Successful e-commerce logistics requires the optimization of warehousing, packaging and shipping processes to ensure fast and efficient customer service. Technologies such as warehouse automation and shipment tracking are essential to a smoothly functioning e-commerce logistics system. The continuous development and improvement of logistics strategies is an integral part of the competitive e-commerce environment to meet increasing customer expectations and dynamic market changes. Modern solutions which supports described processes are ERP systems. Despite their numerous advantages, ERP systems require constant supervision and regular analysis of performance indicators in order to realise their full potential. The research hypothesis assumes that modern ERP systems are very helpful in the supplying process, but that their constant supervision and analysis of indicators concerning the efficiency of the procurement process are necessary. The aim of this article is to present selected indicators used to measure the level of efficiency of the procurement process and to identify the reasons for their unsatisfactory values. The analysis of these indicators will allow for a better understanding of which elements of the process need to be optimised, as well as identifying specific corrective actions. The article includes an introduction, a review of the literature, a discussion of the formulas used and their description, and an analysis of the values of the indicators obtained. The text concludes with an indication of the reasons for the unsatisfactory values of the indicators and a proposal of improvements that can be made in the company to increase the efficiency of the procurement process.

Keywords: supply chain, procurement, optimization, ERP systems

1. INTRODUCTION

The main task of supply logistics is to ensure all necessary materials that enable uninterrupted and continuous operations (Semenov & Jacyna, 2022, Borucka et al. 2023). Several elements are key in this area. The correct structure of the warehouse and avoiding unnecessary costs require maintaining a minimum level of inventory that will adequately cover the enterprise's needs, taking into account complex orders and forecasted sales (Zhang & Zhao, 2023). Factors such as potential product shortages from the supplier's side and delivery delays should also be considered (Zabielska et al., 2023). Predicting situations, especially those where obtaining necessary goods is difficult, allows companies to minimize the costs of shortages and reduce the risk of lost sales. To guarantee timely, complete, and quality-compliant deliveries, it is necessary to build a base of reliable suppliers (Saputro et al., 2022). They should offer products of the highest quality at competitive prices. Maintaining good business relationships with partners in the supply chain and transparent communication are crucial. Providing information about potential availability problems, as well as proposed discounts, forms the basis of cooperation based on mutual respect. All jointly taken actions should ultimately lead to ensuring the best possible product availability for the end customer (Yadav et al., 2022).

The authors of presented research used a set of indicators to assess the effectiveness of procurement logistics. First, an introduction to the study carried out is provided by reviewing the current literature. The indicators used and the characteristics of the company under study are presented. Subsequently, the values of each of the calculated indicators were analysed and described. The article concludes with a discussion of the results and a summary with recommendations.

2. INTRODUCTION TO THE RESEARCH PRESENTED

Currently, supporting the functioning of logistics in a company are ERP-class information systems (ERP - Enterprise Resource Planning). Software of this type is characterized by encompassing and integrating all significant areas of a company's operations and ensuring efficient flow of information. An ERP system allows for controlling logistics activities both quantitatively and in terms of value, and above all, enables a company to react quickly to dynamic changes in demand (Alsudani et al., 2023).

ERP system providers are now able to create tailored solutions according to the needs of the company. Software suppliers ensure that by utilizing their modern product, the company will be able to reduce costs by optimizing warehouse stocks (Guzanek et al., 2023, Rosiński et al., 2024). A modern ERP system reacts not only to sales dynamics but also to recurring delays that deviate from the planned delivery time entered into the system beforehand. It recognizes trends and seasonality of data groups of products based on their historical sales, as well as additional data input by users (Rodrigues et al., 2022). The most advanced systems can adjust forecasts to the expected weather in the coming weeks. High-class ERP systems seamlessly cooperate

with other systems used in companies, leveraging their databases (Grobler-Dębska et al., 2022).

Utilizing ERP systems brings both benefits and challenges (Baranowski, 2022). First and foremost, they allow for gathering information in one database, accessible to all relevant departments (Danilczuk & Gola, 2020), and the high complexity level of the software enables increased accessibility for all users, both within and outside the organization (Krithika et al., 2020). Implementing a modern ERP system also brings benefits in the form of standardizing work processes across different branches of the same company (Nawaiseh, 2022). Additionally, utilizing automated software improves relationships between the company and its suppliers (Svensson & Thoss, 2021). By utilizing specific metrics and generated reports, the company can share current strategic data with suppliers.

A significant obstacle in ERP system implementation undoubtedly lies in the high costs of purchasing the license itself, as well as maintaining the software (Amado & Belfo, 2021). A major challenge in ensuring a stable ERP system management process is the difficulty of continuous updating. In the case where the system is tailored to the needs of a particular company, it will have a longer and more complex scope of required modifications (Hustad & Stensholt, 2023). It is also crucial to adjust expectations for the system to its actual capabilities (Basl & Novakova, 2019). ERP software is a tool used to handle many transactions occurring within and outside the company. Its functioning is based on algorithms grounded in statistical methods or, in advanced systems, machine learning methods. Without the intervention of an employee monitoring the system's behavior, such as in determining forecasts for actual sales dynamics, the results of using the software may yield unsatisfactory outcomes. The authors point out various reasons for such situations. These can include issues related to system performance and data transmission limitations resulting from limited network speed and reliability (Kim et al., 2009; Duan et al., 2013). Problems also arise from interoperability with other applications and integration with the company's IT infrastructure, leading to erroneous indications (Karabek et al., 2011, Puchalski & Komorska, 2023).

Competence of employees is also a significant challenge. Due to the complexity of ERP systems, employees must undergo special training before working with the software. Knowledge transfer is not always effective and can lead to mistakes, especially for individuals lacking IT knowledge (Dorobat & Natase, 2021; Hart et al., 2019).

Effective communication is also crucial for ERP-class systems. These multifunctional systems require coordination among users from different departments and the transmission of appropriate information (Kiran & Reddy, 2019; Tavana & Hajipour, 2020).

Another problem is the high trust in such systems and the uncritical implementation of solutions designed by them, without control and verification (Davis, 2020).

As indicated by the literature review, the benefits of using ERP-class systems are not always straightforward. Additionally, the requirements for the e-commerce industry will be different. Despite advanced algorithms and extensive capabilities, it is necessary to control the received results and not accept them uncritically. In the

article, the authors present their own experiences in this area. Using a selected e-commerce company as an example, they illustrate the functioning of an ERP system and the associated problems. Additionally, they present indicators enabling a comprehensive assessment of the supply logistics processes. Therefore, the scientific objective is to analyze and evaluate the effectiveness of supply logistics in an e-commerce company equipped with a modern ERP-class system. The scientific contribution of this study is as follows:

- presentation of indicators for assessing the efficiency of supply logistics;
- analysis and evaluation of the functioning of a modern IT system in the procurement process;
- identification of problems associated with using ERP-class systems;
- presentation of recommendations to improve the functioning of the company;
- presentation of the specifics of an e-commerce company.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Selected indicators for assessing the procurement process

Due to the significant role of supply logistics in the entire supply chain, it is necessary to monitor and systematically evaluate its functioning. Controlling the procurement process allows for quick reactions and implementation of corrective actions, ensuring that the product reaches the end customer precisely at the time of demand.

There are many indicators for assessing the effectiveness of the procurement process (Twaróg, 2003). The article presents selected ones. The simplest indicator is the ratio of the number of fulfilled deliveries to the number of placed orders (formula 1):

$$\text{Ratio of delivered orders to placed orders} = \frac{\text{Number of delivered orders}}{\text{Number of placed orders}} [\%] \quad (1)$$

It is also important to compare the number of products delivered to those ordered (formula 2):

$$\text{Ratio of delivered products to ordered products} = \frac{\text{Number of delivered products}}{\text{Number of ordered products}} [\%] \quad (2)$$

The calculation of the ratio of delayed deliveries to all deliveries (formula 3) also provides important information:

$$\text{Share of delayed deliveries} = \frac{\text{Number of delayed deliveries}}{\text{Number of succesful deliveries}} \quad (3)$$

Differences between demand forecast using the ERP system and actual sales were also evaluated (formula 4):

$$\text{Ratio of the number of units sold to the forecasted demand} = \frac{\text{Number of sold pieces of products}}{\text{Forecasted demand for products}} \quad (4)$$

A basic assessment of delivery performance can also be made using four metrics: time, reliability, quality, and flexibility. Delivery time refers to the period required to complete the delivery process. This process includes order transmission, fulfillment, and transportation of goods to the destination. The delivery time must be defined at the contract signing stage between the ordering company and the supplier. Unfortunately, contractual assumptions are often not adhered to. Due to significant difficulties regarding delivery timeliness, this article examines the average delay in order delivery time. Delivery reliability is defined as the certainty of its delivery, or alternatively, the probability of delivering an order within a specified timeframe and delivering the ordered goods in the desired quantities and quality. This aspect is closely related to the mentioned delivery quality. This metric focuses on determining the degree of order fulfillment in terms of delivering the correct type of goods in the required condition. Desired delivery quality also relates to how the order is fulfilled in accordance with contractual agreements. Delivery flexibility, on the other hand, is associated with the ability to meet “special requests” related to the order being fulfilled. Examples of such requests include: changing delivery time, changing delivery size, and ad hoc delivery.

It is worth emphasizing that e-commerce stores, which customers uses for on-line purchases, have a completely different nature than those where sales occur in a traditional manner. Hence, there is a growing interest in improving the methods of stocking warehouses where goods sold in online shops are collected. Additionally, links in global supply chains still face problems with raw material availability and difficulties in securing carriers. Potential delays and incomplete deliveries have a negative impact on the efficiency of the company's supply logistics system. This, in turn, translates into the company's final sales results and lower customer satisfaction. Ensuring product availability in an e-commerce warehouse is therefore a challenge for modern companies, including those equipped with advanced IT tools.

3.2 Characteristics of the research subject

The subject of the study is a retail international company specializing in the sale of cosmetic and hygiene products with wide range of prices, dedicated for people all ages. The company currently operates in 15 European countries. In some countries, only the company's online store is available. In Poland, the company offers products to customers both in physical stores located in major cities and through online

channels. The company's portfolio includes 30,000 products across 6 categories. The procurement process is facilitated by a modern ERP system implemented in the company in 2022. Additionally, procurement is supported by dedicated tools for reporting and data collection.

The company purchases goods from 300 suppliers, distributing a total of 1000 brands. Orders to suppliers are placed cyclically: weekly, every two weeks, or once a month, on designated days of the week. There is the possibility of placing additional orders outside the schedule, for example, to ensure an adequate number of products for a promotional period.

Orders are delivered by suppliers to the described company's central warehouse. The company uses the services of a logistics operator to manage the warehouse. Goods are received at 10 designated stations. After finalizing the receiving process and verifying the documentation, the goods are shelved and entered into the inventory. This automatically changes their status on the website and signals their availability for purchase. Upon receiving a purchase done by a customer at on-line page, warehouse staff receive the appropriate information and immediately begin picking and packing. From the moment the customer places an order to its shipment, no more than one business day passes. The delivery of goods to the selected point or directly to the buyer is facilitated through courier companies.

The main challenges affecting the entire supply logistics system that the company faces primarily occur in the delivery process. Orders from suppliers are either not delivered at all or are incomplete, and often exceed the contractually agreed-upon delivery time. The limited number of receiving stations and deliveries arriving at the warehouse not according to the schedule exacerbate the problem of product unavailability on the website. Therefore, it was decided to examine the efficiency indicators of the supply logistics in the surveyed company to identify problematic areas. After conducting the calculations, corrective and improvement actions were proposed to enhance the supply logistics system.

4. ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF SUPPLY LOGISTICS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS – CASE STUDY

4.1 Number of orders placed and delivered by suppliers

The supply process was subjected to analysis. Research presents an analysis and evaluation of the level of deliveries fulfillment. It was also examined whether they were delivered on time. Additionally, actual sales results expressed in units were compared with the forecast generated by the ERP system.

For presented research, described steps were taken: The necessary data from whole 2022 on deliveries received and estimated demand have been collected for analysis. Provided values came from the supplying system, used in the company. The enterprise had already implemented an advanced ERP system during the selected period.

The formulas presented above were then applied and the indicator values obtained were described in turn. Authors highlighted the most important factors which had an impact on the received values.

The first step of the analysis was to determine the number of orders placed and delivered in each month of 2022. The total number for the e-commerce store during the year was 15,323 items, with an average value per month of 1,407. The highest number of orders was recorded in November – 1,596, while the lowest was in January – 1,209. The high result in November is associated with the company preparing for increased sales during the Black Friday and Christmas period. The low value, on the other hand, is due to limited needs following the stock remaining from the 2021 holiday season.

Despite the reported needs, suppliers only fulfilled 9,231 items in 2022, which is only 60.24% of the desired orders. The highest effectiveness was observed in January, reaching 71.63%, while the lowest was in November at 44.11%. This is associated with a higher than average number of orders placed by the company, as well as with the issue of product availability on the suppliers' side in the last quarter of 2022. The average monthly number of deliveries fulfilled to the warehouse was 843. The results of the analysis described above are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Ratio of delivered orders to placed orders in individual months of 2022

Source: own elaboration

4.2 Number of products ordered and delivered

Next, a comparison was made between the number of ordered and delivered products. In 2022, the company requested 3,617,365 units of products from suppliers. The highest demand for goods was identified in September, reaching 783,530 units,

while the lowest was in June at 188,190 units. September is the last month of the company's fiscal year, and the final purchases of products needed for the last quarter of the calendar year are made then. Often, the delivery time is extended during this period.

However, the analysis of the number of delivered products showed that throughout 2022, only 1,505,409 units were delivered to the e-commerce warehouse, representing only 41.62% of the reported needs. The highest value was achieved in January at 52.59%, while the lowest was in May at 25.46%. The average monthly level of delivery fulfillment expressed in units of product was 40.86%. This is a very concerning result. The expected order fulfillment rate in the company is 96.00%. The described level of order fulfillment is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Ratio of delivered products to ordered products in individual months of 2022

Source: own elaboration

4.3 Delays in deliveries

The next step of the analysis was to focus on the issue of delays. Their number was calculated for each month and related to all deliveries made. Throughout the year, 7,287 orders did not arrive on time, accounting for 73.32% of the total. The greatest delay occurred in September – 85.67%, while the smallest was in December – 58.51%. The average monthly value of orders fulfilled after the specified deadline was 607. The data described above are presented in the form of the following chart.

Figure 3 Number of delayed deliveries and their share in all delivered orders

Source: own elaboration

Delays are a significant aspect affecting the efficiency of supply chain logistics in the company. Nearly $\frac{3}{4}$ of the deliveries made were delivered after the specified deadline. Therefore, it was necessary to examine the extent of these deviations.

The largest differences between the contractual and actual delivery times were noted in September. The average delay in that month was 11 days. This issue was least noticeable in October, with orders arriving at the warehouse on average 5 days after the defined deadline.

Throughout the year 2022, orders were delivered on average 7 days late. This value, compared to the contractual delivery time of 3 or 4 working days, indicates a significant problem with timeliness on the part of the suppliers.

The analysis also considered the time required for warehouse staff to process an order, which is 2 working days. Therefore, the indicated average delays only concern negligence on the part of the supplier and those related to transportation. They are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Average delivery delay in months of the year 2022

Source: own elaboration

4.4 Forecasted Sales vs. Actual Sales

The final stage of the analysis was to verify the demand forecasts generated by the ERP system and compare them with actual sales. In 2022, the program generated sales forecasts for a level of 2,204,947 units of goods, while the actual sales over the year amounted to as much as 4,391,919 units. The ratio of the number of products sold to the forecast was therefore 199.18%. The highest sales were planned for December (417,459 units), and indeed, they were the highest, reaching 818,219 units, which accounted for 249.22% of the forecast. The month with the lowest forecasted sales volume (158,262 units) was April, during which 352,376 products were actually sold, indicating an underestimation of 123%. Meanwhile, August was the month with the lowest number of units sold, with a forecasted sales of 193,645 units, while 299,821 units were actually sold, representing the smallest difference between forecasts and actual sales (154.83%). The comparison of the demand forecast generated by the ERP system with actual sales is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Comparison of forecasted demand generated by the system with actual sales

Source: own elaboration

The values obtained from the conducted analyses are unsatisfactory from the perspective of the company and the procurement process realization. The ratio of delivered orders to placed ones significantly deviates from the desired level. Similarly, the ratio of delivered products to ordered ones – satisfactory value over the course of 2022 has not been achieved. The share of delayed deliveries is too high and should not occur. The ratio of sold pieces to sales forecasts is also not close to the desired value. The above considerations are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Values of indicators and metrics related to the procurement process

Indicator or Metric Name	Total/Overall Ratio	Maximum	Minimum	Average	Desired value
Number of orders placed [pcs]	15,323	1,596	1,209	1,407	-
Number of orders delivered per month [pcs]	9,231	1,023	704	843	-
Ratio of orders delivered to orders placed [%]	60.24%	71.63%	44.11%	60.24%	98.00%
Number of products ordered [pcs]	3,617,365	783,530	188,190	336,141	-
Number of products delivered [pcs]	1,505,409	216,690	77,645	125,451	-
Ratio of products delivered to products ordered [%]	41.62%	52.59%	25.46%	40.86%	96.00%

Number of delayed deliveries	7,287	807	511	607	-
Share of delayed deliveries in those completed [%]	73.32%	85.67%	58.51%	72.14%	12.00%
Average delay [days]	7	11	5	7	-
Anticipated demand [pcs.]	2,204,947	417,459	158,262	218,534	-
Actual sales [pcs.]	4,391,919	818,219	299,821	434,178	-
Difference sales – forecasted demand [pcs.]	2,186,972	400,760	106,176	215,644	-
Ratio of sold units to forecasted demand [%]	199.18%	249.22%	154.83%	198.99%	90.00% - 110.00%

Source: own elaboration

The company does not have direct control over the level of delivery realization by external contractors or the delays they generate, however, it can ensure greater accuracy of sales forecasts, as proposed below (Kozłowski et al., 2023).

5. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

The conducted study revealed that the actual values of procurement logistics efficiency indicators are not close to the desired values assumed by the company. There are several reasons that may affect the improper ratio of delivered orders to placed ones:

- lack of raw materials at the beginning of the supply chain;
- absence of goods for distribution at the supplier level;
- incorrect information about the supplier in the system;
- outdated statuses of products;
- outdated information about the validity of agreements with the supplier.

Improving this indicator's value can be achieved by providing forecasted purchases to the supplier in advance, to verify the availability of products on their end or to obtain information about anticipated shortages as early as possible.

The unsatisfactory value of the supplier's order fulfillment indicator for individual products may mainly result from:

- lack of raw materials at the beginning of the supply chain;
- absence of goods for distribution at the supplier level;
- outdated statuses of products.

To reduce the scale of the problem, actions related to confirming the forecasted purchase quantities and the number of available products that the supplier can reserve for the company should be taken. It is also necessary to regularly update data regarding the assortment entered into the system. Deactivating references or temporarily blocking them during unavailability will positively impact the indicator value.

The company is struggling with delayed deliveries. Suppliers do not adhere to contractual order fulfillment times. It is necessary to verify the actual time it takes for

an order to reach the company's warehouse and compare it with the terms agreed upon in the agreement. In case of non-compliance with contractual provisions by partners, it is recommended to introduce financial penalties for delays in delivering goods.

The ratio of sold products to forecasted sales also does not reach the desired level. The majority of goods offered in e-commerce stores are characterized by highly variable demand. The power of social media can cause a selected product to disappear from warehouse shelves in just a few hours after months of no sales. Therefore, appropriate actions should be taken to improve the quality of forecasts in this area, such as:

- manual adjustment of forecasts for selected brands or suppliers;
- artificially extending the delivery time.

It is recommended to introduce a mandatory safety stock value. Additionally, it should be noted that for products with variable demand, it will be inevitable to place additional orders necessary to meet consumer needs. Considering the ordering method for fast-moving goods with a longer coverage period is advisable.

6. CONCLUSION

By conducting an analysis of the efficiency of the supply chain logistics system in the context of support provided by an advanced ERP system in an e-commerce company, the article's objective was achieved. The proposed efficiency indicators enabled an assessment of both the supply chain logistics and the functionality of the IT system. The conducted study allowed for diagnosing the company by comparing actual values with desired levels. Based on this, recommendations were proposed to streamline the procurement process.

An important conclusion drawn from the analysis is that even the most advanced technologies, including modern ERP systems, require constant and strict monitoring. The main intention of the authors was to indicate that ERP systems can be extremely helpful in optimizing processes but can also be prone to errors, leading to incorrect decisions. Therefore, control and supervision over them are crucial aspects of maintaining their effectiveness and proper functioning.

It is worth noting that awareness of the need to monitor and improve both IT systems and logistics processes should become a fundamental element in maintaining the competitiveness and effectiveness of the company. Monitoring the performance of ERP systems in the context of supply chain logistics is crucial for process optimization, identifying potential issues, and quickly reacting to market changes, ultimately leading to increased efficiency.

It is also essential to acknowledge that many companies do not have the capital to invest in such advanced yet costly software. In the procurement process, many companies rely on calculations performed using popular tools such as spreadsheets (e.g., Microsoft Excel or Google Sheets). Methods based on manual calculations are unfortunately flawed. The lack of use of sophisticated algorithms can increase the risk of error, for example by including in the predicted demand calculation an abnormally inflated historical sale caused by a pricing error. While an advanced machine learning algorithm will exclude an above-normal value by classifying it as an outlier.

It is worth to highlight that, there are limitations which are caused by factors beyond the control of the company being described in presented research. If a manufacturer has a shortage of raw materials, the distributor who cooperates with the described company, will not be able to ensure an adequate level of completeness of supply. This is independent of the retailer and its technology.

It is also worth noting the occurrence of errors in the masterdate of products, so suppliers are unable to fulfil individual orders and unfulfilled items negatively affect the delivery rates. The number of suppliers serving the described company is makes that such errors cannot be completely excluded.

Despite the use of modern solutions, there are still areas where improvements can be made. This study may serve as a basis for further analysis, which can be conducted by expanding the set of efficiency indicators and considering other inventory forecasting models, which will be the subject of further research by the authors.

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UNDERSTANDING CUSTOMER DEMAND VARIABILITY: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH

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Abstract

Customer demand variability refers to fluctuations in consumer purchasing behaviour over time. This research delves into the causes, implications, and strategies to manage demand variability. As methods used to perform this paper, was based on a study case approach. Delving into a set of hystorical data regarding customer order development, the analysis will look into the effects of fluctions on inventory for the raw materials and order behaviour. Customer demand variability is a critical challenge in supply chain management, impacting inventory levels, production planning, and overall business performance. Variability can arise from numerous factors, including seasonality, market trends, economic conditions, and promotional activities. The purpose of this paper is to give an insight of how the raw materials fluctuations are driven by a customer function, and to see the impacts on the inventory level, as the manufacturing company is more inclined to risks. This paper is using as a base a study case, and through data analyzing is proposing as a short term-solution the frozen period is showing that the fluctuations can be reduced, but they are unpredictable outside this time frame. Understanding these drivers is essential for developing effective demand forecasting and inventory management strategies.

Keywords: customer demand variability, fluctuation, inventory management

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer demand variability refers to the ups and downs in how much and how often consumers buy products over time. These fluctuations, influenced by factors like seasonal changes, market trends, economic conditions, and promotional efforts, can greatly affect how businesses run. Managing these changes is essential for keeping the right amount of inventory, efficient production schedules, and high-quality customer service.

In today's complex business environment, where global supply chains are interconnected and markets are constantly shifting, demand variability is a major challenge. Businesses need to carefully balance their inventory to avoid having too

much (which increases storage costs and risks products becoming obsolete) or too little (which leads to missed sales and unhappy customers).

This research will look into what causes customer demand variability, how it affects supply chain operations, and effective strategies to manage it. Based on a study case this paper is using both numbers and detailed analysis, we aim to provide a clear understanding of demand variability and practical solutions to help businesses stay resilient and efficient despite changing consumer demand.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer demand variability, which refers to the fluctuations in consumer purchasing patterns, significantly impacts supply chain management, inventory control, and overall business performance. This literature review explores the primary causes of demand variability, its effects on supply chains, and strategies to manage this variability, supported by relevant references.

The numbers of the research papers regarding the behavioral factor on bullwhip effect had fluctuated over the years (Yang et al., 2021), there were increases starting 2002 and starting to decline from 2015. Post pandemic it is visible a slight increase once again. In the same paper the authors refer to the most common used methods when referring to studies implying the bullwhip effect as being controlled experiment (56.6%), modeling (26.4%), simulation experiment (17%), surveys (17%) and case studies (3.8%), most of the experiments were based on the so-called “beer game”.

The game is around 70 years all, if we take into consideration the first appearance into the literature, and according to Martinez-Moyano I. J. The structure of the Beer Game and the process for running it have evolved over the years into what is now considered a de facto standard approach. In all the simulation exercises presented in his research, the dynamics are triggered by a change in customer demand, which can occur either suddenly (step) or gradually (ramp).

Seasonal variations are a well-documented source of demand variability. For example, the retail sector often sees peaks during holidays and dips in off-seasons. Fisher et al. (2001) highlight that seasonal demand changes can cause significant variability in industries like apparel and consumer electronics.

Shifts in consumer preferences and emerging trends also drive demand variability. McCarthy et al. (2006) note that fashion trends, technological advancements, and health consciousness can lead to sudden changes in demand for specific products.

Economic indicators such as unemployment rates, consumer confidence, and disposable income levels greatly affect demand. During economic downturns, demand for non-essential goods tends to decline, while demand for essential goods may stay stable or increase. Gaur and Kesavan (2015) found that macroeconomic conditions significantly impact demand variability, especially in the retail sector.

Sales promotions, discounts, and marketing campaigns can create temporary spikes in demand. Blattberg and Neslin (1990) discuss how promotional activities can lead to demand variability by prompting consumers to buy more during promotional periods, sometimes causing stockouts and subsequent low sales periods.

High demand variability necessitates maintaining larger safety stocks to buffer against uncertainty, increasing holding costs. Chopra and Meindl (2013) explain that companies with high demand variability often struggle with balancing inventory levels to avoid excess stock and stockouts.

Fluctuating demand complicates production scheduling, potentially resulting in overproduction during low-demand periods and underproduction during peak demand periods. Stevenson (2009) notes that production systems need to be flexible enough to adjust quickly to changing demand levels to maintain efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

Variable demand affects logistics and distribution planning, often leading to inefficiencies and increased costs. Christopher (2016) points out that logistics networks must be responsive to demand changes to ensure timely delivery and optimal inventory positioning.

Inconsistent demand can negatively impact service levels, leading to customer dissatisfaction and reduced loyalty. According to Hopp and Spearman (2008), maintaining high service levels despite demand variability requires robust forecasting and flexible supply chain practices.

Advanced forecasting techniques, including machine learning and data analytics, have improved the accuracy of demand predictions. Hyndman and Athanasopoulos (2018) highlight that these methods outperform traditional forecasting models by better capturing complex patterns in demand data.

Implementing just-in-time (JIT) inventory systems and dynamic safety stock levels can help balance supply and demand. Silver et al. (1998) emphasize that effective inventory management strategies are crucial for mitigating the impacts of demand variability.

Enhancing the flexibility of supply chain operations allows businesses to quickly adapt to changes in demand. Swafford, Ghosh, and Murthy (2008) suggest that agile manufacturing and responsive logistics networks can significantly improve supply chain resilience. In their research regarding the bullwhip effect in a hybrid manufacturing/remanufacturing supply chain that includes a retailer, manufacturer, supplier, and third-party collector, Giri and Glock (2022) emphasize the importance of accurately modeling demand to manage the bullwhip effect, especially in systems involving remanufacturing. It also highlights the role of price dynamics and remanufacturing in potentially mitigating the negative impacts of the bullwhip effect.

In their study case Buchmeister et al. (2014) utilize real market demand data to simulate a single-product, multi-level supply chain. The simulation covers 48 weeks of data, considering factors like seasonality and deseasonalization. The model includes a three-stage supply chain with a retailer, manufacturer, and supplier, employing min-max inventory policies and considering overall equipment effectiveness in lead time calculations. In their conclusion the lower overall equipment effectiveness levels result in higher order variability and stronger bullwhip effects due to production deviations. The bullwhip effect in supply chains is influenced by various factors, including poor communication, free return policies, order batching, and demand forecasting. Accordingly, Elham Rafati with human behavior is often cited as a primary cause, with the magnitude of the bullwhip effect varying by business environment. Factors like demand forecast updating, order

batching, material delays, and information delays are critical contributors. Advanced forecasting techniques, such as artificial neural networks and big data analytics, have been developed to mitigate these effects.

Collaborative planning, forecasting, and replenishment (CPFR) with suppliers and customers align expectations and actions, reducing the bullwhip effect and smoothing demand variability. According to Aviv (2001), CPFR initiatives can lead to more accurate demand forecasts and better-coordinated supply chain activities.

The COVID-19 pandemic provided a unique context for studying the bullwhip effect, as the event has shown how easily the supply chain can be impacted, created a unique bullwhip effect (BWE) and ripple effect on the global business environment. (Scarpin et al., 2022). The supply chain is constantly changing and such unexpected events, adding in this category natural disasters cannot be predicted, but are likely to occur. On the same account, Patel and Brown (2023) expanded on this by examining post-pandemic recovery efforts and their impact on the bullwhip effect. Their findings suggest that supply chains that had invested in resilience-building measures, such as diversification of suppliers and adoption of digital technologies, were better able to dampen the bullwhip effect during the recovery phase.

The literature underscores that understanding and managing customer demand variability is vital for maintaining efficient and responsive supply chains. By leveraging advanced forecasting techniques, optimizing inventory, enhancing supply chain flexibility, and fostering collaborative planning, businesses can better navigate the challenges posed by demand variability and improve overall performance.

3. METHODS AND RESULTS

3.1 Study case data

This research was based on a study case. The study case will have the focus on a single finished good due to its tendency of variability. The finished good is a part for the after-sale market in the automotive industry. The manufacturing company is middle size and as working schedule they operate 80 hours per week. The finished good can be produced on a single machine, and this is leading to capacity constraints. The maximum capacity is of 1,800 pieces per hour, 144,000 per week and approximately 576,000 per month. The manufacturing company also consider the time required for starting the production and stated that the conservative quantity achievable monthly is around 550,000 pieces.

The finished product has in his components 3 raw materials, and each one of them has a different usage factor.

For the production process the one of the raw materials is used in the plastic injection molding process and is a thermoplastic material accountable in kg. The other two materials are used after, in an assembly process which is realised at the machine station.

The study case was realised because of the demands variability. In the forecast received from the customer the requested quantity was higher than the monthly capacity, the yearly volume could be meet, nevertheless the monthly was

unachievable, so the company needed to assert the situation and search for solutions to meet the customer requirements.

3.2 Analysis and results

We will start by looking into the details of one finished good and the order behaviour for this component-named in this paper as product A, and afterwards we will look into the details of how the 3 raw materials that enter into this finished good were impacted by the variability present into the orders transmission.

For this analysis were taken into consideration the order transmission from 2023, for 2024. For this specific product the order transmission is weekly, but for this research it was selected the first transmission for every month in 2023. The data are presented in table 1.

Table 1 Customer order transmissions for 2024

Product A	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24
Jan-23	446,227	162,470	490,034	240,626	674,825	526,262	122,795	587,104	530,434	296,519	562,574	675,910
Feb-23	262,049	192,158	203,420	214,703	473,538	345,599	533,446	134,299	492,132	353,094	571,869	390,224
Mar-23	473,077	516,064	598,041	422,431	585,736	228,177	519,456	616,774	239,359	383,787	498,667	439,929
Apr-23	424,004	330,266	136,075	293,489	549,843	405,168	606,206	195,762	239,662	199,190	626,656	238,226
May-23	293,152	180,816	581,783	259,613	182,216	421,497	110,975	600,730	192,859	267,225	416,251	336,691
Jun-23	532,716	182,732	319,645	348,982	603,906	549,939	289,766	516,218	257,498	354,603	662,894	632,528
Jul-23	531,056	397,169	245,571	111,924	202,157	197,240	158,839	461,978	450,861	497,165	395,270	274,079
Aug-23	623,347	332,284	383,604	447,136	676,046	194,094	345,902	505,360	164,156	102,318	256,088	313,219
Sep-23	636,020	632,716	452,353	633,764	634,092	404,334	671,286	475,541	162,004	371,648	599,817	472,968
Oct-23	560,983	543,190	348,080	524,596	601,031	483,292	106,164	148,005	276,989	258,324	671,001	542,441
Nov-23	513,490	670,531	196,982	174,073	235,229	222,510	466,331	362,916	477,505	342,272	309,255	561,039
Dec-23	309,456	415,047	547,180	115,889	357,800	270,627	652,661	308,100	361,170	549,703	390,670	534,114

Source: Authors research

As visible in figure 1, if we are looking and the grand total for volumes for 2024, in the first transmission we had orders for 5,315,780 and in the last transmission from December we had an overall volume of 4,812,417, marking a decrease in volumes of 9%. The highest value for the order volumes was in the transmission from September, of 6,146,543, where we had an increase of 14% comparing with the initial volumes, and if we are comparing with the last transmission, an increase of 22%.As visible in figure 2, we are having fluctuation from transmission to transmission, and we do not have linearity into the orders, as they were still not placed in the frozen period.

Figure 1 Total volumes

Source: Authors research

If we are comparing the first transmission in 2023, for 2024 with the last transmission in 2023 for 2024, the image of variability is clearer stated. The biggest fluctuation on the positive axis is in July, with a difference of approximately half a million, on the negative axis the biggest difference was in May, with a difference of approximately 300,000 pieces.

Figure 2 Comparison between first transmission and last transmission for 2024

Source: Authors research

For this specific finished good, the manufactory company use 3 raw materials that are bought from sub-suppliers. These 3 raw materials will be noted in this paper as R1-raw material 1, R2-raw material 2 and R3-raw material 3. In the nomenclature of the finished good is specified that each material has a different usage factor. Taking into consideration we will have as it follows, for R1 are used 2 pieces for finished

goods, for R2 are used 3 pieces per finished good, and for R3 there are used 6 pieces per finished good.

The orders trend to these sub suppliers is the equivalent with that of the orders of the customer. Looking into more details, as visible in figure 3, the volumes for R1 have the same trend, with the peak volume in September, a slightly exceeding 12 million.

Figure 3 Volumes for R1

Source: Authors' research

In figure 4 we can see, that regarding the fluctuations in our orders towards the sub supplier, the outlook of the fluctuations is identical with the ones in the customer orders, nevertheless what is different is the volumes, the peak volume on the positive axis is over one million, and the peak volume on the negative axis is close to 700,000. These gaps are increasing based on the bullwhip effect, as the manufacturer require more quantity for the production, and also needs to have a buffer of safety stock.

Figure 4 Comparison R1 first transmission-last transmission

Source: Authors' research

We are having the same situation for R2 material. Here as the usage factor is 3, the gap is only increasing. As visible in figure 5, the peak on the positive axis is 1.7 million, and on the negative axis is a little bit over 1 million.

Figure 5 Comparison R1 first transmission-last transmission

Source: Authors' research

We are having the same situation for R3 material. Here as the usage factor is 6, the gap is only increasing. As visible in figure 6, the peak on the positive axis is 3.5 millions, and on the negative axis is a little bit over 2 million.

Figure 6 Comparison R3 first transmission-last transmission

Source: Authors' research

Looking at all the data together we can see the bullwhip effect clearly, and how the fluctuations have the same trend, only the suppliers will face fluctuations with bigger volumes, as visible in figure 7.

Figure 7 Comparison finished good-raw material fluctuations

Source: Authors' research

Taking into consideration the fluctuations for the raw materials generated by this finished product, one contra measure set in place was to have a frozen period, of 3 months, where the customer will keep the orders fixed, and any further modifications will be done outside of the frozen time frame. Looking into the frozen time frame, as visible in figure 8, we can deduce that for that period, there were no fluctuations.

Figure 8 Frozen period

Source: Authors' research

When comparing the orders in a shorter term, with the frozen period, we can also see, that in short term, the overall fluctuation is lower than when we are looking at the data set, from one year apart, as visible in figure 9.

Figure 9 Fluctuation in the frozen period

Source: Authors' research

Even if the set-up for the frozen period is different from customer to customer, is uncommon to have an extended time frame for this solution. It is mainly used as a method to combat short-term increases or decreases. Nevertheless, as to answers why this customer agreed as the three months frame, several aspects were taken into consideration in the negotiations: the manufacturing company capacity, costs for capacity increase, the transit time (here the finished products were transported to two different distributions hub-in total 6 weeks for normal transportation 1 week on premium freight), risk of stoppage and incapability to recover backlog. Taking all the above mentions into consideration the customer was more leaning to the agreement of the frozen period to gain more stability.

Taking into consideration today market and production processes for certain raw materials where the lead time can be equal with one year, it is doubly understood that we are required to investigate long term solutions. With the expansions of the emerging technologies, we can look forward to automatizing strategies, for example demand forecasting with the utilization of AI and machine learning, algorithms that can predict volumes based on history, seasonality, trends. In the market some global companies have already implemented such strategies. Another strategy applied by multinational companies, is the demand-driven supply chain, here we are having as an example Coca-Cola company, that focuses on the bottling operations based on real demands.

The questions that are still remains is are the data available with those methods reliable, are there any risks to jeopardize the production or do they lead to overstock. Another concerning taboo subject here is regarding the human behaviour mainly the readiness of humans to fully rely on AI which is a complex and multifaceted issue that involves technological, ethical, social, and psychological considerations. For further research

4. CONCLUSIONS

The bullwhip effect is visible from the slightest change into the customer orders, so the fluctuation that the manufacturer is having to the sub suppliers is directly correlated with these changes in the customer orders behaviour.

Nevertheless, as stated into this paper, as a short-term solution, we can work around with the frozen period for a decrease in these fluctuations. In the first scenario, without the frozen period, the highest increase was of 432%, for July, from the first transmission to the last transmission of 2023. On the other hand, the highest decrease was of 47%, in May. For the time frame analysed with the frozen time frame, the highest increase was in October, of 61%, and the highest decrease was of 24%.

The frozen time frame for orders is a solution that is working on short term, but nevertheless, unfortunately is not very successful and cannot be implemented on a longer-term basis. And in the current market, where the lead time for the raw materials is increasing, the customer frozen period, is not helping deviate these types of fluctuations for the manufacturing companies and their suppliers.

As a next step into the research is how to implement emerging technologies into predetermining the fluctuation and combat them, to analyse the human expectation based on survey method from automatized strategies, and on the other hand another point that can be analysed here is what methods can be used in order to at least correct the fluctuations for the expensive or large in volumes materials, to balance the raw materials with high usage factors at the peace of the ones with lower usage factor.

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AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODS: A CASE STUDY APPROACH

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Abstract

This paper provides a comprehensive overview of agile methods, exploring how they contribute to improving efficiency and effectiveness in project management. It describes in detail how agile methods enable organizations to respond more quickly to changes, improve communication within teams, and increase the efficiency of project execution. The analysis includes the advantages of agile methods compared to traditional project management approaches, emphasizing their adaptability and focus on continuous improvement. The research method utilized in this paper is a case study. It highlights the importance of integrating agile principles and how this integration contributes to greater flexibility and better results in the dynamic environment of modern business. Through theoretical analysis and practical demonstration, the study provides valuable insights into how organizations can successfully implement agile methods and how managers can effectively lead teams and projects in such an environment. This paper contributes to the literature in management studies and offers valuable practical applications for other companies.

Keywords: agile methods, product manager, agile management

1. INTRODUCTION

Agile project management methods, as analyzed in this paper, illustrate key principles that enable organizations to effectively navigate the dynamic challenges of today's business environment. Compared to traditional project management methods, which often follow a linear and sequential approach such as the waterfall model, agile methods offer flexibility and a faster response to changes throughout the entire project cycle (Mokhtar & Khayyat, 2022). The fundamental principles of agile methods include several key elements.

Firstly, development is both iterative and incremental. Projects are broken down into smaller, more adaptive elements called iterations or sprints, each resulting in the delivery of a partially functional product or feature. This approach allows for continuous monitoring of progress and alignment with the actual needs of users, thereby reducing the risk of significant errors and failure to meet user expectations. Another key element is collaboration and communication. Agile methods emphasize the importance of cooperation among team members and between the team and stakeholders. Frequent meetings, such as daily stand-up meetings, retrospectives, and sprint planning sessions, foster transparency and enable quick identification of problems. This intensive communication helps the team remain aligned and coordinated while allowing for faster resolution of issues that arise during development. Regarding communication, some authors develop specific agile teamwork models in software development industry focusing on collaboration (Strode et al., 2022).

Furthermore, Agile methods allow the project plan to be adjusted based on feedback and evolving requirements. The goal is to react swiftly to changes instead of strictly adhering to a pre-defined plan. This adaptability makes agile methods particularly effective in dynamic environments where requirements frequently change. Quality and sustainability are also integral principles of agile methods. Quality is continuously checked through testing and feedback, reducing the risk of significant issues later in the project. Agile methods also promote a sustainable work pace, avoiding excessive workloads and ensuring long-term productivity.

The primary goal of this paper is to compare agile methods with traditional approaches to project management, with a particular emphasis on the advantages and disadvantages of the agile approach. Traditional models, such as the waterfall model, often face challenges in adapting to new requirements and changes during project development. In contrast, agile methods follow an iterative approach, wherein projects are developed through a series of short cycles or sprints, allowing for continuous adjustments based on feedback from users and stakeholders. The specific objective of this paper is to provide insights into the application of agile methods in a selected company using a case study approach.

The research process of this paper is designed to examine the effectiveness of Agile project management methods through a combination of theoretical analysis and practical application via a case study of Arges Ltd. The research follows a structured approach, beginning with a comprehensive literature review to establish a theoretical foundation on Agile methods. Following this, the case study method is utilized to explore the practical implications of Agile methods in a real business environment. The research process involves several key steps:

Literature review: The initial step involves a detailed analysis of existing literature on Agile management methods. This includes reviewing foundational works such as the Agile Manifesto and specific methodologies like Scrum, Kanban, and Extreme Programming. The literature review also identifies the challenges and benefits associated with Agile implementations across various industries.

Research methodology and data collection: A single-case study approach with embedded units (Yin, 2003) was selected to explore the implementation of Agile methods in practice, specifically within the context of Arges Ltd. This methodology

is appropriate as it allows for an in-depth examination of a single organization, offering insights into the specific processes, challenges, and outcomes associated with Agile transformations. Data were gathered using both qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews, observations, and document analysis within Arges Ltd. Initially, interviews were conducted with managers at Arges Ltd., followed by interviews with employees. Subsequently, the authors observed the transformation process and noted changes in business operations and specific projects following the Agile transformation. The entire process lasted for six months. These methods provided a comprehensive understanding of the company's Agile practices, project management processes, employee experiences, and client outcomes.

Analysis and findings: The collected data is analyzed to identify key success factors, challenges, and the overall impact of Agile methods on project outcomes at Arges Ltd. The analysis focuses on how Agile principles such as iterative development, collaboration, and adaptability are applied and how they influence the efficiency and effectiveness of project management.

Conclusions and recommendations: The research concludes by summarizing the findings and offering recommendations for future research and for other organizations considering a shift to Agile methods. The paper also discusses the limitations of the study, such as the focus on a single company, and suggests areas for further exploration, including cross-industry comparisons.

This structured research process ensures a comprehensive examination of both the theoretical and practical aspects of Agile project management methods, providing valuable insights for both academic and industry audiences.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW ON AGILE MANAGEMENT METHODS

Agile methods in project management have been developed in response to the challenges and limitations of traditional methods, especially in the context of complex and dynamic projects in the software industry (Seymour & Hussein, 2014).

Traditional software development methodologies, often referred to as plan-driven or process-oriented approaches, are characterized by a formalized structure that typically requires extensive documentation. However, by the mid-1990s, some practitioners began to view such practices, particularly the emphasis on complete documentation, as cumbersome and time-consuming (Highsmith, 2002). According to McCauley (2001), the foundational philosophy of these traditional methods involves freezing all functional requirements at the outset of the project before proceeding to subsequent phases like design and development. This rigid approach is often impractical for many software projects. Consequently, there is a growing need for flexible and agile development methodologies that allow developers to modify or adjust specifications during the development process (Islam & Ferworn, 2020).

The history and development of agile methods can be divided into several key phases and events.

Royce (1970) introduced the concept of the "waterfall model" and although the model became very popular, Royce himself pointed out the disadvantages of a strictly sequential approach and the need for feedback and iterations.

Boehm (1988) introduced the Spiral Model of Software Development, which combines elements of iterative development and risk analysis, representing a significant step towards modern agile approaches. From the 1990s to the 2000s, specific agile methods began to emerge. During this period, the development of specific agile methods such as Scrum, Extreme Programming (XP), and DSDM (Dynamic Systems Development Method) commenced.

Sutherland and Schwaber (1994) formalized the Scrum framework, which began to be applied in various software projects. A key moment in the history of agile methods occurred in 2001 when 17 software development experts met in Snowbird, Utah. The result of this meeting was the "Manifesto for Agile Software Development," which formalized the principles of agile development and provided guidelines for its application. The Agile Manifesto emphasizes four fundamental values: individuals and interactions over processes and tools, working software over comprehensive documentation, customer collaboration over contract negotiation, and responding to change over following a plan (Beck et al., 2001; Cockburn & Highsmith, 2001; Dingsøy et al., 2012). The manifesto also defines twelve principles of agile development, including continuous delivery of functional software, close collaboration with users, autonomous teams, and regular reflection on processes to improve efficiency.

The development of agile methods was motivated by the need for a more flexible, efficient, and adaptable approach to project management. From early iterative models to modern frameworks like Scrum and SAFe, agile methods have transformed the way organizations develop products and deliver services. Key events, such as the publication of the Agile Manifesto, significantly contributed to the popularization and formalization of agile approaches, which are now the standard in many industries. Agile project management is based on several key principles that enable flexibility, efficiency, and continuous improvement in project management. These principles include iterative development, adaptability, and collaboration, each with specific characteristics and advantages that contribute to successful project management (Ashmore & Runyan, 2014). Although many companies pursue agile projects, there is still lack of research on Agile project management determinants (Radharishnan et al., 2022).

Iterative development is one of the most important principles of agile management. Instead of developing a project in one continuous process, iterative development allows for breaking the project into smaller, manageable segments or iterations (Kumar & Bhatia, 2012). This approach reduces the risk of major errors as it allows for early identification and correction of problems. Iterative development also allows for more flexible change management, as requirements and specifications can be revised and adjusted based on feedback received after each iteration (Salo & Abrahamsson, 2007).

Adaptability is another key principle of agile project management and yet an interest topic to investigate. It is important to discover the empowerment methods for teams and managers for improving company adaptability (Grass et al., 2020). In the modern business environment, where changes are rapid and often unpredictable, the ability to quickly adapt becomes essential for the success of projects (Woogon & Lee, 2019). Agile methods enable teams to efficiently adapt to new requirements, changes

in market conditions, or technological innovations. Project managers are particularly sensitive to adaptability due to complex and dynamic work conditions (McLoughlin & Priyadashini, 2021). This adaptability is achieved through continuous monitoring of progress, regular revisions of the plan, and open communication with stakeholders. Agile teams are trained to make quick decisions and change direction when necessary, allowing them to stay aligned with project goals and user expectations.

Collaboration is the third fundamental principle that supports agile project management. Agile approaches emphasize the importance of team collaboration, transparency, and communication among team members, as well as between the team and stakeholders. Process transparency and open communication foster trust and cooperation among team members, improving team spirit and effectiveness. Agile teams often include diverse experts who work together to develop solutions, which allows for better utilization of different skills and perspectives within the team.

2.1. Main agile frames (Scrum, Kanban, Lean, XP)

Among the most widely adopted agile frameworks are Scrum, Kanban, Lean, and Extreme Programming (XP), each offering unique characteristics, applications, and benefits.

Scrum is one of the most prevalent agile frameworks, particularly in software development. The Scrum framework is structured around recurring time intervals known as sprints, typically lasting between two and four weeks. During each sprint, the team focuses on delivering a partially functional product increment. Scrum encompasses specific roles such as the Product Owner, Scrum Master, and Development Team. The Product Owner is tasked with defining and prioritizing the work, while the Scrum Master ensures adherence to Scrum principles and removes any impediments that might hinder the team's progress. To effectively monitor progress and maintain process transparency, Scrum teams utilize artifacts like the product backlog, sprint backlog, and increment (FasterCapital, 2024). The key advantages of Scrum include enhanced team collaboration, flexibility in managing changes, and accelerated delivery of functional products.

Unlike Scrum, the Kanban framework does not enforce fixed time intervals, promoting instead a continuous workflow where new tasks are added as existing ones are completed. A critical feature of Kanban is the limitation on the number of tasks being worked on concurrently (Work in Progress, WIP), which helps to minimize downtime and increase efficiency (Digité, 2024). The key benefits of Kanban include simplicity in implementation, visual clarity, and continuous process enhancement.

The Lean framework originates from the production methodologies developed by the Toyota Production System and has since been applied across various industries, including project management. Lean focuses on eliminating waste while maximizing value for customers. Core principles of Lean methodology involve defining value from the user's perspective, identifying and eliminating waste, creating a continuous value flow, implementing a "pull" system where production is initiated based on actual demand, and practicing continuous improvement through kaizen (Blake, 2021). Lean methodologies encourage teams to continually evaluate their processes, seeking opportunities to reduce waste and improve efficiency. The benefits of Lean include

cost reduction, improved quality, and expedited product delivery (Kišš & Rossi, 2018).

Extreme Programming (XP) is a framework explicitly designed to enhance software quality and promote agility within development teams. XP emphasizes technical excellence and includes practices such as pair programming, test-driven development (TDD), continuous integration, and code refactoring (Wells, 2013). Pair programming involves two developers working on the same task, fostering ongoing code review and knowledge exchange. TDD mandates that tests be written before coding, ensuring alignment with requirements and facilitating error detection. Continuous integration enables regular integration and testing of code changes in a shared repository, reducing integration issues. Code refactoring supports the ongoing enhancement of code quality without altering its functionality. The primary advantages of XP include improved software quality, faster error detection and correction, and enhanced collaboration and knowledge sharing within teams (Bryant, et al., 2018). Each of these agile frameworks presents distinct characteristics that make them suitable for varying types of projects and organizational needs.

2.2. Challenges and limitations of using agile management methods

The implementation of agile methods in organizations often encounters significant cultural and organizational challenges. One of the most common problems is the tendency of stakeholders to resist change. Organizations that have long operated under traditional project management methods, such as the waterfall model or other linear approaches, often have entrenched processes, procedures, and hierarchical structures (Tomasini & Kearns, 2012). Changing these deep-rooted systems and cultures can be extremely challenging (Nerur et al., 2005). Employees are accustomed to clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and expectations, and the shift towards an agile approach can represent significant stress and uncertainty for them (Cockburn & Highsmith, 2001).

In such environments, the key challenge is to manage change in a way that minimizes resistance and facilitates the transition to agile methods. Resistance to change can occur at all levels of an organization, from executives to operational teams (Seymour & Hussein, 2014). Managers accustomed to the control and predictability of traditional methods may be reserved about the idea of self-managing teams and iterative processes that characterize agile methods. Conversely, operational teams may feel overwhelmed by new demands for collaboration, transparency, and constant adaptation. The implementation of agile methods in organizations faces not only cultural and organizational challenges but also technical and operational obstacles (Ashmore & Runyan, 2014). These challenges can significantly impact the success of an agile transformation and require careful planning and management.

One of the main technical challenges is the integration of agile methods with existing systems and technologies (Hoda et al., 2013). Organizations often already have systems in place for project management, performance monitoring, and communication, which are designed for traditional management methods (Rasnacis & Berzisa, 2017). Transitioning to agile methods may require the adaptation or replacement of these systems, which can be technically complex and expensive. For

example, resource and financial management systems are often integrated with projects in a way that does not support iterative development and the flexibility of agile methods (Al-Bayati, 2017). Implementing new tools and software solutions that support agile practices, such as Jira or Asana, can help solve these problems, but it also requires user education and adaptation (Blake, 2021).

Scalability is another significant technical and operational challenge (Komus & Kuberg, 2017). While agile methods can work well in smaller teams and projects, scaling these practices to an organization-wide level can be complex (McHugh et al., 2011). Large organizations with multiple teams working on different parts of the same project can face difficulties in coordinating and harmonizing work (Dingsøyr et al., 2012; Strode et al., 2022). Existing agile frameworks, such as the Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) or Large-Scale Scrum (LeSS), offer guidelines for scaling agile methods, but their implementation requires significant changes in the organization's structure and processes (Yin, 2018). Managing interdependencies between teams, ensuring consistency in practice, and maintaining product quality become more complex as an organization grows (Eisenhardt, 1989).

Additionally, agile methods require a high level of technical expertise within the team (Wells, 2013). Practices such as pair programming, test-driven development (TDD), and automation require specific skills and knowledge (Budwig, 2009). Education and continuous training of team members are key to the successful implementation of these practices. Organizations that lack sufficient resources or expertise may face difficulties in maintaining high standards of quality and efficiency (Mokhtar & Khayyat, 2022).

Operational challenges include managing changes during the course of the project (Sutherland & Sutherland, 2014). Agile methods encourage frequent changes and adaptations, which can cause operational problems if the organization does not have processes in place to manage these changes (Seymour & Hussein, 2014). Maintaining clear documentation, managing software versions, and ensuring regulatory compliance become more complex in an agile environment (Royce, 1970). Organizations must develop flexible operational processes that support agile principles without compromising the stability and reliability of projects (Boehm, 1988).

3. AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN COMPANY ARGES Ltd – A CASE STUDY

The following chapter provides an example of the transformation undertaken by Arges Ltd. as it transitioned from a traditional project management model to agile project management. The case study in this paper was based on works of Eisenhardt (1989), Stake (1995), Yin (2018). Other authors also use case study approach to analyse implementation of agile methods (Budwig, 2009; McHugh, 2011; Rasnacic & Berzisa, 2017; Carneiro, 2018; Mokhtar & Khayyat, 2022).

Successful implementations of agile methodologies have been documented across various industries, highlighting their effectiveness in improving project outcomes and organizational efficiency. For instance, Gonçalves and Linders (2012)

describe numerous retrospective exercises that teams can use to continuously improve their processes and outcomes, demonstrating how agile practices can lead to sustained improvements over time. Another study by Komus and Kuberg (2017) investigates the use of agile methods in German-speaking countries and finds that many organizations report increased productivity and faster time-to-market as a result of their agile transformations.

One particularly notable example of a successful agile implementation is described by Sutherland and Sutherland (2014), who detail how a large telecommunications company was able to reduce its time to market by 40% and increase overall productivity by 25% through the adoption of Scrum. This case study illustrates the significant benefits that can be achieved by embracing agile principles, such as iterative development, continuous feedback, and team empowerment.

3.1. Basic information about the company Arges Ltd.

The company Arges Ltd. was founded in 2010 with the vision of providing top-quality services for the development of customized software solutions for business users. Initially, the company specialized in the creation of websites and web shops tailored to the specific needs of clients. With the development of technology, the company expanded its activities to include the development of mobile applications, which today are a key part of their portfolio. The mobile applications they develop enable clients to access their services and products in new and innovative ways, thereby further increasing their competitiveness in the market.

3.2. Reasons to shift to agile methods

Traditional project management at Arges Ltd. relied heavily on the waterfall model. However, as project complexity grew and client demands became more dynamic, the limitations of this approach became evident. A major issue was project delays. Fixed timelines for each development phase often failed to accommodate unforeseen challenges, leading to delays and client dissatisfaction. Budget overruns were also common. Initial budgets were set at the project's outset, but later changes in client requirements or technical specifications were not properly reflected, making financial adjustments difficult. The rigidity of the waterfall model exacerbated this problem, as it did not allow for easy budget modifications during the project, resulting in additional costs or renegotiations with clients.

Another critical challenge was the model's lack of flexibility in adapting to evolving client needs. The waterfall approach assumes all requirements are defined at the beginning, which is often unrealistic in a dynamic business environment where client needs can shift. Consequently, products frequently fell short of client expectations, as changes were costly and time-consuming to implement after the initial planning phase.

Communication gaps between teams were another drawback. The strict phase structure led to siloed operations, with teams working in isolation, causing inefficient information exchange and misunderstandings. This fragmentation reduced the quality

of the final products, as issues identified later in the process were difficult to resolve due to poor inter-team communication and coordination.

Moreover, defining project completion was often ambiguous in the waterfall model. As client requirements evolved during the project, scope creep became a recurring issue, leading to constant additional demands and expanding workloads. This ambiguity made it difficult to close projects and transition to new tasks, resulting in further delays and cost escalations. Teams struggled to balance client satisfaction with maintaining realistic timelines and budgets.

Finally, the limited integration of feedback during development exacerbated these issues. Feedback was often either ignored or incorporated too late, making adaptations costly and complex. As a result, products frequently failed to meet client expectations, requiring additional iterations post-development, further extending timelines and inflating costs.

3.3. Planning and implementation of agile transformation

The initial step in the agile transformation at Arges Ltd. involved analyzing the company's existing needs and challenges. Workshops and meetings identified key issues in the current project management processes, highlighting areas for improvement through agile transformation.

A primary finding was the need to reduce project delivery times to stay competitive. Clients demanded faster deliveries to adapt to market changes, prompting the company to implement agile methods for quicker, iterative development. Short iterations were introduced to expedite delivery, enabling clients to realize value sooner.

Improving product quality was another objective. The traditional approach often resulted in products with bugs or unmet needs due to insufficient iterative testing and feedback. Agile methods, emphasizing continuous testing and feedback, aimed to enhance quality, ensuring each product segment met high standards and client expectations.

Enhancing communication within teams was also crucial. Agile methods prioritize collaboration and transparency, so regular meetings and transparent project monitoring tools were implemented to improve teamwork, efficiency, and coordination across the organization.

Following this evaluation, management chose a hybrid approach, combining waterfall and agile methodologies, termed the water/Kanban/fall method. This integrates the structured planning of the waterfall model with the flexibility of agile methods, particularly Kanban, leveraging the strengths of both. The waterfall method establishes a clear project plan with defined phases, while agile methods, like Kanban, provide flexibility and responsiveness during design and programming stages, improving efficiency and enabling rapid adaptation based on feedback.

This hybrid approach allows teams to start with a structured plan and switch to agile practices when needed, reducing delays, controlling costs, and better meeting client needs. It also facilitates a smoother transition for teams accustomed to traditional methods, minimizing resistance to change. Management recognized this approach as

optimal for balancing structure and flexibility, essential for a successful agile transformation.

To support agile project management, Arges Ltd. implemented Asana, a project management tool that enhances transparency, task management, and collaboration. Asana facilitated efficient project tracking using the water/Kanban/fall method, providing transparency to all participants and ensuring clarity in responsibilities and deadlines. Its Kanban boards and timelines improved progress tracking and bottleneck identification.

Asana significantly improved efficiency and communication, supporting agile project management while aligning project planning, tracking, and delivery with client expectations. The tool's transparency also enhanced client satisfaction by providing real-time visibility into project progress and enabling prompt responses to changes or challenges.

3.4. Example of a successful project executed by using agile method

One of the significant projects implemented using agile methods was the development of a software solution for managing a football team. The team used a combination of waterfall and Kanban methods to plan and execute tasks. This combination enabled structured planning of the entire project while simultaneously allowing flexibility and rapid adaptation during key development phases. The project was completed within the planned deadlines and budget, and the final product exceeded the client's expectations in terms of functionality and quality.

The project began with a thorough analysis of the client's needs, who wanted to modernize and digitize the management of their football team. The client highlighted the need to centralize information, improve communication within the team, and increase fan engagement. The team used the waterfall method for initial planning, defining clear goals and phases of the project. The Product Manager's role included gathering client requirements and ensuring that all key needs were documented. During this phase, a solid foundation was laid for further iterative processes, ensuring that all key aspects of the project were well documented and understood by all participants.

After the initial analysis, there was a phase of intensive cooperation with the client through a series of interactive sessions and workshops. These activities allowed the team to thoroughly understand the client's needs, identify challenges, and define the key functionalities of the application. The Product Manager coordinated these workshops and ensured that all requirements were clearly communicated to the design team. The design team developed a visual identity for the app that reflected the client's passion for football. The interface design focused on the user experience, ensuring intuitive navigation and an aesthetically appealing appearance.

Implementation and Programming

During the implementation phase, the team used the Kanban method for task management and iterative development. The developers implemented the application's functionality using the latest technologies to ensure high performance and security. The Product Manager oversaw the prioritization of tasks and ensured that client feedback was continuously integrated into the development process. Every

functionality, including integrated chat for club management, connection to the COMET system, and management without a classic CMS, was carefully programmed and tested. This iterative approach allowed the team to quickly respond to client feedback and adapt to new requirements.

Key Functionalities

One of the key functionalities of the application was the integrated chat for club management, which enabled members of the management to exchange information quickly and securely. Management without a classic CMS allowed for the administration of all aspects of the application directly within the app, thus increasing the security and simplicity of content management. The Product Manager ensured that all key functionalities were aligned with the client's needs and delivered according to the agreed specifications. The fan page allowed for the purchase of annual tickets and kept fans updated with club news, while integration with the COMET system provided the club and users with access to all relevant information about match results and statistics. Tracking player statistics enabled coaches and managers to make informed decisions.

Testing and Optimization

After implementation, the application was subjected to thorough testing to ensure stability and reliability. The team used tools such as Crashlytics to identify and fix app crashes and Analytics to track app usage and identify areas to improve the user experience. The Product Manager coordinated the testing process and ensured that client feedback was promptly implemented, as client feedback was crucial during this phase. This allowed the team to quickly make necessary adjustments and optimizations.

Launch and Handover

The launch of the mobile application marked the successful completion of the project. The client was extremely satisfied with the final product, which exceeded all their expectations. The application enabled efficient management of the club, improved communication within the team, and increased fan engagement. The handover of the project included detailed training for the client's staff on how to use the application and the provision of continuous technical support. The Product Manager was responsible for all these activities.

This successful project demonstrated the power of combining waterfall and agile methods, enabling the team to deliver a high-quality solution within given deadlines and budget. Users and stakeholders were very satisfied with the results of the software solution development project for football team management. After the implementation and launch of the application, feedback was collected to evaluate the impact and effectiveness of the developed solution. The client pointed out that the application significantly improved operational processes within the club, especially in the areas of team management, communication, and fan engagement.

The client was also very satisfied with the integration with the national system COMET, which provided access to relevant information about match results and statistics. This functionality gave the club a complete overview of sporting events, enabling coaches and managers to make informed decisions based on current data. User feedback indicated that this integration has significantly contributed to the improvement of the team's strategies and performance.

Based on this positive feedback, the client expressed extreme satisfaction with the final product. They particularly praised the team's cooperation and their ability to quickly respond to requests and adapt to changes. The result is a product that not only meets but also exceeds their initial requirements and expectations. The client's satisfaction and the success of the application opened the possibility for the multiplication of the project within the football league in which the team for whom the application was developed plays.

3.5. Key success factors

Key success factors of the agile transformation at Arges Ltd. included several fundamental elements that ensured an effective transition to agile methods and the achievement of desired results. The foremost factor was clear communication at all levels, from top management to individual team members. Regular meetings, well-defined goals, and transparent information exchange ensured alignment and awareness of tasks and responsibilities, enabling quicker problem-solving and informed decision-making.

Management support was also vital for success. The leadership at Arges Ltd. recognized the value of agile methods and actively engaged in the transition process by providing necessary resources such as funding, time, and training. They promoted a culture of innovation, collaboration, and continuous improvement, which enhanced employee motivation and facilitated the adoption of new methods. According to Radhakrishnan et al. (2022), adaptive performance by project team members mediates the relationship between project agility and success.

Adequate employee training was another critical factor. The shift to agile methods required a new mindset and approach, which was achieved through comprehensive training sessions and workshops. These covered both the technical aspects of agile methodologies and soft skills like communication, collaboration, and time management. Continuous education ensured employees were proficient in agile practices, resulting in higher efficiency and work quality.

Flexibility in adapting agile methods to specific project needs was equally important. While the core principles of agile are universal, each organization and project has unique requirements. This flexibility allowed Arges Ltd. to maintain structured planning and control while benefiting from agility and rapid adaptation to change.

The use of tools like Asana also contributed to efficient project management. Asana provided a platform for transparent progress tracking, task management, and team collaboration, allowing the team to visualize project progress, identify issues, and respond quickly. It also enabled clients to monitor project status in real-time, enhancing transparency and satisfaction.

Collectively, these factors ensured a successful agile transformation at Arges Ltd., allowing the company to deliver high-quality solutions within deadlines and budget constraints.

3.6. Challenges during the implementation of agile methods

The transformation of Arges Ltd. to agile project management methods faced several significant challenges. The biggest challenge was resistance to change among employees. Many team members were accustomed to established processes and work methods and felt a certain level of uncertainty towards new ways of working. Changes in work methods often cause fear of the unknown, loss of control, or additional burdens. Management recognized this challenge and approached it with great care, ensuring ongoing support and clearly communicating the benefits of the new methods.

To overcome resistance to change, the company introduced constant and comprehensive employee training. Training sessions and workshops were designed for employees to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to work in an agile environment. The training covered not only the technical aspects of agile methods but also a shift in mindset, encouraging team cooperation and developing new work habits. Through practical examples and simulations, employees could see the concrete advantages of agile methods, which gradually reduced their resistance and increased their willingness to accept changes.

The gradual introduction of changes proved to be a very effective strategy for reducing resistance and facilitating adaptation to new work methods. Instead of a sudden transition, the company implemented agile methods in stages, allowing employees to gradually adapt and adopt new ways of working. This approach enabled teams to experiment with agile practices, learn from their experiences, and continuously improve processes. Gradual change also allowed the company to identify and quickly resolve potential issues, ensuring a smooth transition.

Through constant training, management support, and the gradual introduction of changes, Arges Ltd. managed to overcome the biggest challenges during the transformation to agile methods. Employees gradually adapted to new ways of working, recognized the advantages of agile methods, and adopted them as a standard in project management. This approach allowed the company to significantly improve the efficiency, flexibility, and quality of its projects, resulting in increased client satisfaction and better business outcomes. Obtained challenges correlate with the findings of Nerur (2005).

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH AND RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

Based on the case study in this paper, it can be concluded that agile methods can significantly improve project management. The transformation to agile methods enabled the company to increase efficiency, reduce delays and budget overruns, and enhance client satisfaction. By introducing agile practices, Arges Ltd. improved internal communication, team cooperation, and ensured quick adaptation to changes and new requirements. These results confirm the value of agile methods as a powerful tool for project management in a dynamic business environment. It is recommended that other companies consider similar transformations. The key to successful implementation of agile methods lies in careful planning and the gradual introduction

of changes. It is necessary to thoroughly analyze existing processes and identify key areas that require improvement. Then, it is recommended to start with pilot projects to test agile practices and adapt them to the specific needs of the company. This approach enables the gradual adoption of new methods, reducing the risk of resistance to change and ensuring that employees have enough time to adapt.

Finally, it is recommended to use project management tools that support agile methods, such as Asana. Such tools enable transparent monitoring of progress, efficient task management, and improved communication between team members. The integration of these tools can further increase the efficiency and success of projects, enabling teams to quickly react to changes and continuously improve their processes.

Regarding research limitations, a significant shortcoming identified in this study is the selection of a single company as a case study. For a case study to be more representative, it is crucial to analyze and compare multiple companies. It is important to note that this paper focuses solely on one case study, making it impossible to draw general conclusions; instead, the results are indicative of the specific chosen company. This limitation also provides a direction for future research, suggesting that further studies should consider a broader sample of companies for more comprehensive insights.

5. CONCLUSION

The agile project management methods analyzed in this paper highlight key principles that help organizations navigate today's dynamic business challenges. The study examines the benefits of iterative development, the role of communication in agile teams, and the importance of continuous value delivery. Iterative development breaks projects into manageable components, facilitating progress monitoring and adjustments, thereby reducing errors and unmet user expectations common in traditional management. Emphasizing collaboration and communication within agile teams promotes transparency and effective problem-solving, while adaptability allows for rapid responses to changes, ensuring alignment with market demands. By prioritizing quality and continuous improvement, agile methods create a framework for consistently meeting or exceeding customer expectations.

The case study at Arges Ltd. supports these theoretical insights, showing that adopting agile methods significantly reduced delays and budget overruns, while improving communication, collaboration, and overall efficiency. The use of tools like Asana enhanced progress tracking and task management, leading to higher client satisfaction and solution quality. This success underscores the value of iterative approaches and continuous collaboration, reaffirming the effectiveness of agile methods in modern business contexts.

The research in this paper paves the way for further exploration of the challenges organizations face when transitioning to agile methods, the impact of continuous improvement and a focus on quality on project success, and the best practices for scaling agile methodologies in complex organizations. Additionally, examining how project management tools like Asana contribute to agile transformations and

identifying potential enhancements could provide valuable insights for optimizing agile adoption across diverse organizational settings.

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CHALLENGES, SOLUTIONS, AND OPPORTUNITIES IN WOOD BIOMASS SUPPLY CHAIN

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Abstract

The paper investigates the challenges, potential solutions, and opportunities within supply chain of wood biomass, with a specific focus on logistics and management strategies crucial for optimizing biomass utilization. The study employs a comprehensive literature review, analysing current global practices and policies.

The scope of the paper includes identifying key logistical and operational barriers such as the low energy density of biomass, high transportation costs, and the seasonal availability of resources, which complicate the efficient use of wood biomass. Additionally, the research examines the impact of immature pre-treatment technologies, which contribute to increased operational costs and hinder the supply chain's sustainability.

The findings highlight the importance of strategic planning and innovative logistics management to improve both the economic viability and environmental sustainability of the biomass supply chain. The paper underscores the need for continuous research and development in logistics technologies and strategic supply chain management to overcome existing barriers and leverage the opportunities presented by wood biomass.

Keywords: biomass, wood, residual wood, supply chain

1. INTRODUCTION

Biomass refers to organic materials derived from plants and animals. For plants, biomass is produced through photosynthesis, where green plants capture solar energy and convert it into organic matter. This category encompasses a wide range of vegetation and organic waste (McKendry, 2002). Although biomass can eventually transform into fossil fuels over millions of years, the combustion of these fuels disrupts the carbon dioxide balance in the atmosphere. As a result, fossil fuels are not considered a renewable resource within the timeframe relevant to human life (Letcher, 2020).

Biomass is now one of the key renewable energy sources, gaining increasing importance in the energy sector (Rentizelas et al., 2009; Dashtpeyma & Ghodsi,

2021). Interest in alternative energy sources grew significantly following the energy crisis of the 1970s. Since then, biomass has begun to be seen as an important element in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and in reducing countries' dependence on imported energy. The use of biomass, especially wood residues, has been promoted as a means to mitigate the effects of climate change. An example is the United States, where wood biomass is additionally used as a way to reduce costs associated with hazardous fuel disposal and in forest restoration projects. Nevertheless, challenges related to quality, availability, and logistical costs limit the full exploitation of biomass potential, which poses a problem for the sustainability of companies in this industry (Sundstrom et al., 2012; Dashtpeyma & Ghodsi, 2021; Rentizelas et al., 2009; Raychaudhuri & Ghosh, 2016).

For this reason, the scientific community has significantly increased its interest in biomass logistics management and intensified research in this area (Burnard et al., 2015). Previous research has focused on finding cost savings, improving process quality, and conducting extensive techno-economic modelling for the upstream wood biomass supply chain in bio-oil production (Mirkouei et al., 2017). A key challenge remains the design and optimization of the biomass supply chain, which is essential for the efficient conversion of biomass to bioenergy. Biomass supply chain optimization approaches that simultaneously consider different decision levels (strategic, tactical, operational) and integrate conversion processes into the wood biomass supply chain are rare in the literature (Mirkouei et al., 2017).

In recent years, research has increasingly focused on environmental aspects, with a particular emphasis on reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Mirkouei et al., 2017). Increased consumer awareness and the introduction of environmental regulations have created the need to safely re-market products and implement more sustainable solutions. As a result, logistics must now take into account not only the traditional flow of products from producer to consumer, but also the reverse flow. This process, known as reverse logistics, involves the collection and transportation of materials, components and products from consumers back to producers, recyclers or service centers (Lautala et al., 2015). While reverse logistics poses many challenges, it also offers numerous opportunities.

As a consequence of the above, the aim of the article is to identify the challenges, potential solutions, and opportunities within wood biomass supply chain, particularly focusing on the logistics and management aspects essential for optimizing the use of wood biomass. The methodology includes a comprehensive literature review, an analysis of current practices and strategies used globally, and the author's empirical research (Kawa, 2023).

2. PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES

Attempts to identify the problems and threats of wood biomass supply chain and their divisions are presented in the literature, but are quite diverse. For example, Hasibuan et al. (2022) have been divided the barriers into various dimensions, namely economic, social, technical, and institutional, and policy (Dashtpeyma & Ghodsi (2021), on the other hand, proposed a division into dimensions: environmental,

economic, social, technical, and strategic. Sundstrom et al. (2012), in turn, distinguished the following dimensions: economic, market development, forest service capacity, public trust, access and transportation, workforce, local benefit, NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard). In local and regional settings, these barriers may differ, affecting the effectiveness of biomass activities.

The following section presents a division of challenges based on the literature and the author's empirical research, which is described in Kawa (2023).

2.1 Logistics

Collecting wood biomass from different sources, such as forests, sawmills, construction sites or waste from the wood industry, is a logistics challenge. Each of these sites can be located at a considerable distance from each other, which increases transport time. In addition, the diversity of these sources often requires the use of different equipment and technology to collect the biomass, further increasing operational costs. This is compounded by seasonality (Hasibuan et al., 2022).

Logistics is "just another issue that every commodity faces" and in this sense is not particularly related to biomass products. However, solid biomass products are often characterized by low energy density and relatively low value, which requires more attention (Junginger et al., 2011). There is a lack of advanced pre-treatment technologies that would allow efficient densification of biomass at low cost, making it easier to transport and store. Although densification technology, especially in the context of wood pellets, has developed significantly in recent years, it remains effective only for selected types of biomass. Even after the application of these technologies, the final energy density of biomass is still significantly lower compared to other energy feedstocks such as oil, which is a major logistics barrier. Solid biomass, especially in the form of pellets, still has a lower density per cubic meter, which increases transport costs and limits energy efficiency. On the other hand, in the case of liquid biomass, such as bioethanol or biodiesel, this problem is less pronounced, as their energy density is relatively high, which facilitates transport and storage (Junginger et al., 2011).

2.2 Storage

An important subject related to biomass is its storage (Hasibuan et al., 2022). The literature on the use of biomass energy relatively rarely analyses this issue. Researchers tend to arbitrarily choose the cheapest storage method available, ignoring the impact of this choice on the overall efficiency of the logistics system. The main findings of Rentizelas et al. (2009) are that the cheapest storage method is indeed the most efficient solution for the overall system, but that a multi-biomass approach is more beneficial when combined with relatively expensive storage methods. However, low-cost biomass storage methods carry increased health, safety and technology risks that must always be considered (Rentizelas et al., 2009).

Logistics planning requires careful consideration, especially when biomass is available seasonally and storage may incur additional costs (Hasibuan et al., 2022). However, storing biomass can also provide benefits, such as reducing moisture

content, facilitating transport and ensuring a steady supply to maximize processing capacity (Lautala et al., 2015; Rentizelas et al. 2009; Hasibuan et al., 2022).

2.3 Processing

Wood biomass often needs to be properly prepared before processing, which includes drying, shredding, grinding or other forms of mechanical treatment. These processes are time- and energy-intensive, increasing costs and requiring advanced technology. For example, drying biomass is necessary to reduce its moisture content, which in turn improves its efficiency as a fuel, but requires large amounts of energy and specialized equipment.

Processing wood biomass requires specialized equipment such as wood shredders, dryers, pyrolysis kilns and gasification reactors (Hasibuan et al., 2022). For smaller companies, the cost of purchasing, installing and maintaining this equipment can be a significant barrier to entry. In addition, these technologies need to be developed regularly to keep up with advances in energy efficiency and environmental protection.

2.4 Costs

The cost of harvesting and transporting wood biomass poses a significant challenge, and additional difficulties, such as the low value of the biomass and the lack of an existing industry to use it, can further hinder its utilization (Sundstrom et al., 2012). A key challenge is to optimize the transport of the raw material, which has a low density and high geographical dispersion. In order for the raw material to be efficiently delivered to one or more processing plants, an integrated logistics approach is required. Savings can be achieved by using different modes of transport, such as trucks, rail or water transport. However, the choice of the appropriate mode of transport depends on the specific characteristics of the raw material, the location of the processing plants and local conditions such as the availability of roads, railways or ports (Lautala et al., 2015). Successful biomass logistics therefore requires flexibility and adaptation of the transport strategy to the specific needs and capabilities of the region.

Biomass logistics costs, including harvesting, transport and storage, can account for between 10% and 30% of the total cost of wood supply (Stanula et al., 2023). These high costs often reduce the competitiveness of biomass in the market, especially when compared to more common and more readily available energy sources. In addition, the difficulties associated with efficient collection and transport of wood biomass make its use on a larger scale challenging from both a technological and economic perspective.

It also happens that logistics costs are higher than the production costs of biomass delivered to a farm or factory, thus becoming a limiting factor for international trade (Junginger et al., 2011).

2.5 Prices

Studies indicate that market prices for wood products and harvesting costs are key factors influencing the profitability of wood biomass (Mirkouei et al., 2017; Hasibuan et al., 2022). Market prices of competing products, such as wood pulp, can affect the availability of wood biomass (Mirkouei et al., 2017).

In recent years, the development of new fossil energy sources, such as oil sands and shale, has led to significant volatility in energy prices. This phenomenon is the result of increasing demand for limited fossil resources. Despite the environmental benefits, forest biomass often proves too expensive to compete with fossil fuels in many countries. Lower fossil fuel prices further exacerbate this problem (Mirkouei et al., 2017).

Demand for wood biomass and wood biomass products can be volatile, depending on factors such as fossil fuel prices, energy policy, CO₂ regulations and renewable market developments. For example, a rise in oil prices may increase demand for bioenergy, while a fall in prices may reduce it. These market volatilities can affect the profitability of reverse biomass supply chain investments. Companies must therefore monitor markets closely and be prepared to manage production flexibly.

2.6 Quality and contamination

Wood biomass can vary in quality depending on a number of factors, such as origin, storage conditions and how it is harvested. For example, biomass coming from sawmills may have less contamination, but biomass collected from forests or construction sites may contain different types of contamination.

Wood biomass can be contaminated with a variety of substances such as soil, stones, metal parts, paint or preservatives. They can be a serious problem during biomass processing, affecting the quality of the final products, as well as causing wear and tear on machinery and increasing maintenance costs. In some cases, contaminated biomass may be completely unsuitable for use, leading to losses.

2.7 Technologies and innovation

The implementation of new technologies and innovations in wood biomass processing is often hampered by high initial costs, lack of skilled personnel, and uncertainty about long-term benefits. Companies must invest in research and development to keep up with the latest technological advances. In addition, companies must be ready to adopt new production methods that can increase efficiency, reduce operating costs, and reduce environmental impact.

2.8 Regulatory and environmental issues

Companies processing wood biomass must meet stringent environmental regulations, such as emission limits, sustainability standards, and certification requirements. Meeting these standards often requires significant investments in

technology and processes that minimize negative environmental impacts (Rauch, 2017). Failure to comply can lead to financial penalties, which further increases operational risk.

Implementing sustainable practices in the reverse biomass supply chain is key to minimizing negative environmental impacts. Companies must manage greenhouse gas emissions, energy efficiency, and water use in a way that ensures the benefits of using biomass outweigh its environmental costs

2.9 Infrastructure

Inadequate road quality and underdeveloped infrastructure may be the main reasons why biofuel exports are currently not profitable. In the case of wood pellets, respondents indicated that many ports are designed to handle high-value and bulk goods such as coal. Wood pellets, which have lower value, are difficult to handle and require appropriate infrastructure to be managed effectively (Junginger et al., 2011).

3. SOLUTIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The problems and challenges indicated in the previous section are gradually being solved to a greater or lesser extent in practice and theory. This section presents some of the solutions found in the literature. They do not address all of the problems outlined above, but they do address other problems that are not mentioned. Opportunities for further development for the reverse supply chain of wood biomass are also presented.

3.1 Conversion and pre-processing technologies

The solution to the problems of wood biomass efficiency lies in the development of conversion and pre-processing technologies. Conversion affects production costs, greenhouse gas emissions and the overall efficiency of energy systems, while biomass pre-processing reduces the size of the raw material and dries it. They can significantly alleviate the problems associated with supply chain management (Mirkouei et al., 2017).

One of the most promising conversion processes that is gaining popularity is pyrolysis (Mirkouei et al., 2017). It is a technology that allows for the rapid and efficient conversion of lignocellulosic biomass into bio-oil, which is particularly attractive from an economic perspective, especially in the context of local, small-scale production. This technology allows biomass to be processed in a way that minimizes transport and storage costs while maximizing the energy efficiency of the final product. For this reason, pyrolysis is increasingly seen as a potential solution to the problems associated with local processing of biomass into bio-oil, especially in regions where the availability of lignocellulosic biomass is high.

In the future, further development of both conversion and pre-processing technologies could contribute to even greater energy and economic efficiency in bio-oil production.

3.2 Supply chain collaboration

Effective management of the reverse biomass supply chain is a complex process that requires close and harmonious cooperation between various stakeholders. Key players include producers and suppliers of wood residues, who provide the raw material, and logistics companies, who manage the flow of raw materials and finished products. Equally important are processors, who are responsible for transforming the raw material into value-added products, and end users, who use the finished products, such as fuel or energy (Fan et al., 2019). Coordination between these different entities is essential to ensure a smooth and uninterrupted supply of biomass. A lack of such coordination can lead to downtime, delays, and even financial losses, negatively impacting the industry as a whole. Proper management of information flows and close communication between producers, logistics companies, processors and end users are essential to minimize the risk of downtime and optimize the entire supply chain.

3.3 Sustainable development

Designing biomass supply chains that take into account both economic and environmental indicators not only allows for cost savings, but also opens up new opportunities to protect and enhance the natural environment. For a wide range of stakeholders, such as farmers, processing industries, local communities and policymakers, a sustainable approach to biomass supply chain management is crucial to achieving long-term economic, social and environmental benefits (Lautala et al., 2015). Decisions made at different stages of the supply chain – from selecting the right harvesting equipment, to organizing transport, to storing and processing biomass – have a direct impact on key indicators of environmental sustainability. For example, the right equipment configuration can significantly reduce soil erosion by improving soil structure and water retention. This in turn helps to improve soil quality and minimize negative impacts on local ecosystems.

Greenhouse gas emissions are another key indicator influenced by decisions made in the biomass supply chain. Choosing lower CO₂ transport technologies and optimizing transport routes can significantly reduce the carbon footprint associated with biomass production and delivery. A sustainable approach to supply chain planning can therefore not only reduce operating costs, but also contribute to global efforts to reduce climate change.

For organizations involved in the biomass supply chain, sustainable practices are becoming an increasingly important part of business strategy, which can impact on reputation, stakeholder relationships and the ability to attract funding and government support. In the long term, this approach allows for the creation of more resilient and flexible systems that can meet growing market demands and changing environmental conditions.

3.4 Logistics network

An important aspect is the provision of appropriate infrastructure to enable the efficient use of biomass on an industrial scale (Sokhansanj & Hess, 2009). It is crucial

to build and develop infrastructure that is not limited to traditional transport networks such as roads, railways and ports, but also includes the development of specialized storage facilities and biomass processing centers. These infrastructure elements play a key role in the entire biomass supply chain, from acquisition through transport to processing and final use.

Transport networks need to be designed with the specificity of biomass as a raw material in mind. Biomass transport requires not only appropriate vehicles that ensure safety and minimize material losses, but also route optimization to ensure the shortest possible transport time, which is crucial due to the limited durability of some forms of biomass.

Specialized storage facilities are an equally important element of the infrastructure. These storage facilities must be designed taking into account the specific characteristics of biomass, such as moisture content, energy density and susceptibility to biological decomposition. Proper storage is essential to maintain the quality of the raw material and to ensure continuity of supply, especially during periods of low supply.

Biomass processing centers, which may include plants that produce pellets, briquettes or other forms of biofuels, should be located where there is easy access to raw materials and close to major consumers, such as power plants. This allows logistics costs and energy losses to be minimized, which has a direct impact on the economics of the whole system.

3.5 Supporting tools

Stability and optimization of the bioenergy system are crucial to ensure continuity of supply and sustainable development, especially in the face of the challenges of climate change and limited natural resources. Quantitative methods such as cost analysis, geographic information systems (GIS), simulation and optimization are increasingly used in biomass supply chain research. Cost analysis accurately determines the profitability of each stage of the supply chain, which is crucial for investment decisions. GIS provides data on biomass availability and the location of production facilities, supporting the creation of spatial and temporal models. Although GIS does not directly optimize the objective function, simulation methods, thanks to their flexibility in modelling, allow for a more accurate representation of reality and the analysis of different operational scenarios (Mirkouei et al., 2017).

Mathematical modeling and operations research methods play a key role in decision making at different levels of management (Rentizelas et al., 2013). They are particularly useful at strategic and tactical levels, where many factors need to be taken into account, such as costs, profits, greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption. Thanks to these tools, it is possible to find optimal solutions that maximize benefits while minimizing negative environmental impacts (Stanula et al., 20-23). The integration of these methods into the biomass supply chain management process is crucial for the further development of the bioenergy sector to meet the challenges of the future.

3.6 New information technologies

The introduction of modern technologies in the supply chain as part of Industry 4.0 can significantly improve process management. The advanced digital tools of Industry 4.0 enable better data quality in real time, which is crucial for fast and accurate decisions in changing conditions (He & Turner, 2021). Interoperability, i.e. the ability of systems and devices to communicate regardless of manufacturer, allows for the effective connection of processes from the collection of raw materials to their distribution, increasing the efficiency of the entire supply chain. Virtualization enables the creation of digital twins that can be used to monitor and optimise resources and processes without physical intervention. This in turn allows scenarios to be simulated and solutions to be tested in a virtual environment before implementation. Decentralization increases flexibility by allowing autonomous management of different stages of the supply chain, improving responsiveness to change and efficiency. Flexibility and integration of all supply chain participants ensure smooth operations and minimise the risk of disruption.

Enabling technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT) and advanced data analytics play a key role in the functioning of the wood biomass supply chain in the era of Industry 4.0. They not only enable greater operational efficiency, but also improve transparency, sustainability and long-term competitiveness in the global market (He & Turner, 2021).

There have been high hopes for the use of blockchain. However, it is worth noting that in some countries and regions, technologies and systems based on this technology are not allowed or not popular. Additionally, timber trade using blockchain, which provides greater transparency, has not received much interest from legal authorities and organizations, possibly due to concerns about excessive information disclosure (Vilkov & Tian, 2019).

The increased availability, accuracy and detail of data, as well as advances in IT systems based on this data, have had a significant impact on the management of wood biomass logistics. It is now possible not only to control these processes more precisely, but also to manage them effectively at different stages of the supply chain. As a result, wood biomass logistics are becoming more optimized, leading to better resource utilization, reduced operating costs and minimized environmental impacts (Väättäinen et al., 2021).

IT tools help improve the efficiency of the entire supply chain, from raw material procurement to processing and delivery to end users. As a result, these systems not only improve operational efficiency, but also support the sustainable development of the forest biomass sector, enabling better management of natural resources and reducing transport emissions.

3.7 Standardization and policies

The development of technical standards defining specifications and quality standards for wood biomass products (e.g. bioethanol, wood pellets) is seen as an opportunity rather than a barrier. The creation of common standards can facilitate trade by ensuring product uniformity and increasing buyer confidence.

Standardization can also promote market development by simplifying certification and conformity assessment procedures, which may ultimately contribute to increased global trade in biofuels (Junginger et al., 2011).

The main drivers of this sector are high fossil fuel prices and climate change policies. The high cost of traditional fuels makes biofuels more competitive, and climate change policies encourage their production and use as alternatives to fossil fuels. As a result, demand for bioethanol, biodiesel and wood pellets is growing.

To overcome existing barriers and realize the full potential of this market, concrete action is needed from both market participants and policy makers. Reducing or eliminating import tariffs on biofuels can significantly facilitate international trade, especially when combined with international trade agreements and regulatory harmonization. Harmonization, including technical standards and sustainability requirements, could also facilitate the flow of biofuels to global markets, creating more consistent and predictable trading conditions. Such measures can contribute to a more dynamic biofuels market and support global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil fuels (Junginger et al., 2011; Akhtari et al., 2014).

3.8 Society education

An important aspect is to educate the public about the environmental benefits of using and reusing wood products. Wood, as a renewable, biodegradable and low carbon footprint material, is a very good raw material for the production of sustainable products. Raising consumer awareness of the environmental benefits of wood can increase the demand for such products, which in turn can stimulate the development of the wood biomass market (Dashtpeyma & Ghodsi, 2021).

4. CONCLUSION

This article highlights the challenges and opportunities for developing a reverse supply chain for wood biomass, particularly in the context of its management. Wood biomass is a promising source of renewable energy, but its efficient use faces numerous obstacles, such as complex logistics processes, high transport and storage costs, and seasonality. Despite these challenges, appropriate strategic planning and innovative approaches to logistics management can significantly improve the efficiency of the entire supply chain.

The paper adds to the existing body of knowledge on management of wood biomass supply chains, particularly by emphasizing the integration of conversion processes with logistics decision-making, providing a comprehensive approach to supply chain optimization. It reinforces the need for sustainable practices, aligning with global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

The paper provides actionable insights into the need for strategic planning and collaboration across all stages of the biomass supply chain, from raw material collection to final product delivery. It highlights the importance of coordinating with stakeholders, such as suppliers, logistics companies, and processors, to optimize operations and reduce costs. Managers can be encouraged to invest in pre-treatment

technologies and innovative logistics solutions, such as route optimization and advanced storage methods, to address key barriers like high transportation costs and seasonality. This can improve the overall efficiency and sustainability of biomass operations. Moreover, managers should adopt Industry 4.0 technologies, including AI and IoT, to improve process transparency, operational efficiency, and decision-making capabilities. These tools can also help in real-time monitoring and optimization of the biomass supply chain.

Despite the relatively broad scope of the analyses carried out in this study, there are some limitations that need to be taken into account. First, the literature review and analysis of available data may not fully reflect specific local market and technological conditions, which may affect the generalizability of the results. Second, the study focuses mainly on logistics aspects and does not consider the influence of regulatory and socio-economic policies, which may play a key role in the development of the biomass supply chain.

Future research could focus on a more detailed analysis of the impact of local conditions on the efficiency of the wood biomass supply chain. It will also be important to test innovative logistics solutions under real operating conditions, which will allow for an assessment of their effectiveness and adaptability in different contexts. It is also worth considering a more integrated approach to studying the supply chain, taking into account different levels of decision-making and their interactions.

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LOGISTICS HUBS/DISTRIBUTION CENTERS LOCATION – THE CURRENT STATE OF THE ART IN THE APPLICATION OF LOCATION METHODS AND POSSIBILITIES OF THEIR USE IN THE MILITARY ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to find out whether location facilities mathematical approaches used in business logistics can be applied in military environment to the problem of locating warehouses or logistics hubs to support operations. It has been demonstrated through a case study that methods based on weighted centre of gravity in combination with multi-criteria analysis and GIS systems can be used, but only in peacetime conditions with stable positions of units in the role of material demanders. The second part of the paper comprises a comparison of factors that influence the spatial distribution of centers/hubs from the point of view of business and military logistics based on PESTLE analysis. The potential use of mathematical location models, GIS systems and multi-criteria analysis approaches in the process of finding members of the EU logistics hubs network will be the subject of further research.

Keywords: logistics hub, location methods, location factors, business, military

1. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The location of logistics hubs/distribution centers is a critical component in both civilian and military logistics, exerting a direct influence on the efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and strategic capability of supply chains. In civilian contexts, the optimal functioning of hubs/distribution centers is fundamental to the optimization of the flow of goods, the reduction of transportation costs, and the assurance of timely delivery to end-users. In contrast, in crisis situations or in humanitarian logistics, the strategic positioning of these hubs/distribution centers is of paramount importance, as is their ability to provide security and to respond rapidly to operational demands. The

dual-purpose nature of logistics hubs – serving both economic and strategic needs – necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing their location. An understanding of the theoretical foundations of hubs/distribution centers location is essential for the comprehension of methods and approaches used in practice, including an appreciation of their relative strengths and weaknesses.

A **logistics hub** is a central point in a logistics system where material flows are concentrated, stored, handled, and redistributed to other parts of the supply chain within national and international borders. The objective of logistics hubs is to optimise logistics operations by reducing costs, minimising delivery times and ensuring the maximum availability of goods. In this context, logistics hubs assume a pivotal role in ensuring the smooth functioning of logistics operations and in enhancing the competitiveness of companies in global markets (Hesse & Rodrigue, 2004). Hubs, as opposed to distribution centres, are spread over a huge area and feature multiple facilities such as warehouses, office buildings, distribution centres, material handling equipment, etc. They usually have a port, airport and railway terminal within their vicinity. Hubs also provide freight forwarding companies services, customs clearance and often adopt the latest technologies such as IoT (Internet of Things), data analytics, tracking technologies, etc. (Deshpande, 2023).

In contrast, **humanitarian and/or military logistics hubs** have specific additional requirements, primarily related to security, interoperability with other civilian and military systems, and the capacity to respond rapidly to changing and evolving circumstances. The importance of logistics hubs lies in ensuring the smooth supply of materials and equipment, which is crucial for the successful execution of disaster relief operations or military operations. In crisis situations, logistics hubs serve two distinct yet interrelated purposes. Firstly, they ensure logistical support for units. Secondly, they serve as strategic points for coordinating logistical operations at the operational level (Scott, 2021).

The subject is of great consequence to the military sector, particularly in regard to the decision-making process within the European Union (EU) project, in which a network of logistics hubs is currently being established to facilitate operations within the member states of the project.

The main aim of the paper is to find out which facility location approaches are currently applied in the civilian environment of private companies and to point out possible differences that may correct the possibilities of using these methods via case study applied on military environment.

The research questions were formulated as follows:

- Q1: Which approaches to locating logistics hubs/distribution centers were applied in civilian practice and what are the limits of their use?
- Q2: Which of these methods have already been used in a military environment and what they are limited by?
- Q3: What is the basic structure of the location criteria to find the most appropriate spatial distribution of logistics hubs/centers in a civilian environment?

- Q4: Which other criteria need to be considered in the process of selecting a suitable logistics center/hub location from a military point of view?

A partial answer to the first and the second research question is possible through **literature review and gap analysis**. The aim of the gap analysis is to find out to what extent the research area is covered by expert sources, in which areas location methods were used and where these sources are missing. The timeframe of this analysis was defined as 2020-2024 and the sources examined were Web of Science databases.

The most commonly used method, as identified by (Muerza, 2024), was **Promethee** (Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluations). This approach belongs to the multi-criteria analyses family which is based on determining the quasi optimal option according to a spectrum of criteria set by experts, with different criteria assigned varying degrees of importance. The Promethee method has been applied in 562 Web of science database articles between 2020 and 2024. Only 13 of these were related to the issue of using this approach for facilities location and 2 of them were focused on a military environment. An overview of the application areas and authors of the papers is given in the following table:

Table 1 Promethee - an overview of the application areas and authors

Application area	Author
Thermal power facilities	(Milovanović, 2021)
Medicine warehouse	(Oral, 2022)
Higher educational institutions	(Biswas, 2020)
Relief centers in crises	(Choukolaei, 2021)
Healthcare waste disposal centers	(Beheshtinia, 2023)
Naval bases	(Herdiavan, 2021)
Coast Guard homeports	(Sunko, 2024)

Source: own work

The main task of (Herdiavan, 2021) was to find the best position for the naval base in Indonesia. This base includes port facility, maintenance and repair facility, warehouse, personnel care facility, and training base facility which corresponds to the structure of a logistics hub. Borda and Promethee methods were applied to solve the research problem. Promethee method was involved to the process of finding the optimal spatial distribution of Coast Guard homeports in Croatia (Sunko, 2024).

Simulation methods applications for the research problem were found in 142 articles with the key word “simulation location”. Twelve papers were focused on location of distribution centers/hubs. None of them was applied in military environment.

An overview of the application areas and authors of the papers is given in the following table:

Table 2 Simulations - an overview of the application areas and authors

Application area	Author
Ambulances deployment	(Frichi, 2022)
Nuclear power plants	(Kiomarsi, 2020)
Relief distribution centers	(Baharmand, 2020)
Bases for emergency medical services	(Umam, 2022)
Automated parcel lockers	(Rabe, 2021)
Fire departments	(Suzuki, 2020)
Hydrogen fueling stations	(Kim, 2023)

Source: own work

Geographic information systems (**GIS**) were mostly used in combination with Promethee method. With the key word “GIS location” 62 articles were found, 17 of which involved the research problem issue. None of them was applied in military environment. An overview of the application areas and authors of the papers is given in the following table:

Table 3 GIS systems - an overview of the application areas and authors

Application area	Author
Airport site	(Colak, 2023)
Hydrogen storage	(Onden, 2023)
Solar energy power plants	(Ruiz, 2020), (Bedewy, 2023)
Nuclear power plants	(Susiaty, 2022)
Electric cars charging stations	(Kucharski, 2023)
Bike-sharing systems	(Bahadori, 2022)
Waste processing plants	(Siejka, 2020)
Delivery parcel-pickup points	(Zheng, 2020)
Floating photovoltaic systems	(Di Grazia, 2023)
GIS softwares comparison	(Chen, 2021)
Public elementary schools	(Alquhtani, 2022)
Temporary shelter location	(Wigati, 2023)
Hydropower potential sites	(Butt, 2023)

Source: own work

Chen (2021) prepared an overview of the open-source GIS tools that are capable of structuring and solving location cover models. PySpatialOpt, Maxcovr and FLP Solver, and results were compared with those obtained using ArcGIS via case studies. PySpatialOpt and Maxcovr outperformed FLP Solver and ArcGIS in terms of solution optimality, scalability and distance types.

Integer Programming has been analysed in 136 papers with the key word “integer programming location”. Sixty-nine of them were focused on the spatial analysis and only one of them was applied in a military environment. An overview of the application areas and authors of the papers is given in the following table:

Table 4 Integer programming - an overview of the application areas and authors

Application area	Author
Car sharing system	(Krassel, 2023)
Demand points in a network	(Pelegrin, 2023)
Substitution of two centers	(Hinojosa, 2023)
Defence industry warehouses for military vehicles	(Bayrakci, 2023)
Location in flexible networks	(Blanco, 2022)
Depot with maintenance services	(Zhong, 2024)
Aircraft maintenance facility	(Stern, 2023)
Lockers location in last-mile delivery	(Lin, 2020)

Source: own work

Defence industry warehouses location that will support military vehicle breakdowns at military installations in various geographic locations was analysed in (Bayrakci, 2023). The order of importance of the requirements was determined by the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) with the Super Decisions V 2.10, their weights were included as a coefficient of the objective function in the goal programming (GP) model. As a result of solving the GP model using GAMS (general algebraic modelling system), it was decided to select the warehouses that provided the optimal results among the alternative warehouse locations in 9 different locations.

Most of these applications are aimed at locating distribution centres of private companies at the national level, with a particular emphasis on the Asian continent (Muerza, 2024). The only study with an international context is that of Kuo (2011), which addresses the issue of potential locations for an international distribution centre in Europe. The author employs a multicriteria approach, namely ANP (Analytic Network Process), to evaluate five regions in Europe with high levels of logistics intensity: North Rhine-Westphalia, Aragon, Hauts-de-France, Emilia-Romagna, and South Holland.

The most common areas of application of location methods were healthcare, education, humanitarian logistics, delivery parcel-pickup points, alternative fuel stations and especially power plants. AHP and GIS were the most common combination of approaches being used to find the solution of the research problem.

A review of current professional resources reveals a paucity of studies examining the subject from a military perspective. Although the spectrum of areas where location methods have been applied between 2020 and 2024 is relatively broad, in the military domain only three studies were found concerning the location of naval bases, coast guards homeports and defence industry warehouses supporting military vehicle life cycle. It can therefore be said that the objective of the gap analysis has been met by mapping the current state of professional resources related to the research of the authors.

2. METHODOLOGY

An extensive literature review within the WoS databases was used to determine whether the research area is covered by sufficient sources. Through **gap analysis**, it was found that there is a critical lack of current resources in the application of location methods to military conditions.

A **comparative analysis** was applied to determine the differences between the location criteria applicable in the civilian and military spheres.

PESTLE analysis was applied to determine the factors that influence the location of logistics centres/hubs. In accordance with the acronym, these are political, economic, social, technological, legislative and environmental factors of the external environment that can influence facility location decisions not only in the private but also in the public sector of which the military is a part. Economic, social, technological and environmental factors are crucial for both private and public sector organisations. Political and legislative factors are also important, but they come to the fore in the public sector and in the defence sector in particular. Political will and public opinion or its resistance can play an important role in the process of locating centres/hubs. Not only legislation at the state level, but also internal departmental regulations governing storage, handling and transport fundamentally influence where a given centre or hub will be located.

The **case study** demonstrates the use of **weighted centre of gravity** for the initial design of the location of an ammunition depot in one of the regions of the Czech Republic. The case study is applied in peacetime conditions when the position of the military units is stable and they require ammunition only for training. Since this approach is based on the optimization of the relationship between only two variables – distance of clients from the potential warehouse and clients' demand, its result needs to be verified on the basis of established restrictions and location criteria. The weights of the criteria were determined on the basis of **Fuller's triangle**, which is based on a pairwise comparison of experts' opinions on the importance of individual criteria in their mutual relationships.

Based maps were created in **ArcGIS online** system to support decision making on suitable ammunition depot location selection.

3. METHODS OF LOCATION IN BUSINESS AND MILITARY LOGISTICS

The location of logistics hubs in business logistics presents unique challenges that differ significantly from those in the military sector. Business logistics often has the objective of optimising costs, increasing operational efficiency, and maintaining high service levels, while considering various factors such as transportation costs, infrastructure availability, and proximity to markets. This chapter will explore the main location methods used in business logistics, their applications, and the potential challenges associated with their use.

3.1 The Weighted Center of Gravity Method

The Weighted Center of Gravity Method is widely used in business logistics for determining the possible location of distribution centres based on minimizing transportation costs. This method considers the geographic distribution of supply and demand points, along with the volume of goods transported to and from these points.

Mathematical Foundation:

The Weighted Center of Gravity Method calculates the optimal location using the following formulas:

$$X_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$
$$Y_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

where:

- X_c, Y_c are the coordinates of the weighted centre of gravity (centre location),
- w_i are the weights (e.g., volumes of transported goods, or demand at specific locations),
- x_i, y_i are the coordinates of individual points (e.g., locations of suppliers or customers) (Beamon, 1998).

This method is popular due to its simplicity and direct applicability, especially in cases where transportation distances and volumes are known and stable. Its main advantage is that it allows quick and relatively accurate decisions in situations where transport distances and volumes are known and stable. Using iterations, the resulting coordinates of the proposed distribution centre can be adjusted to further reduce the cost of transporting goods between centres and the supplied retail stores (Gros, 2016).

Example of Application:

This method is often used when selecting a location for a distribution centre in a retail network, where the objective is to minimize transportation costs and ensure fast distribution of goods to individual stores (Beamon, 1998).

Limitations:

However, this method has limitations. It tends to overlook factors such as regulatory requirements, labour availability, infrastructure quality, and other critical aspects that can affect the success of a centre location. Moreover, it assumes that weights are constant and independent of distance, which may not always be true in real-world scenarios.

To make an informed decision, it is necessary to combine mathematical models with an assessment of aspects that are difficult to quantify (public opinion, the complexity of legislation in a given country, etc.), most often in the form of a multi-criteria analysis supported by the opinions of experts within specific areas.

3.2 Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA)

Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) is a complex method that allows for considering multiple factors simultaneously, often necessary in complex location decisions. This method evaluates different alternatives based on several criteria, such as costs, infrastructure availability, social and environmental impacts, and then selects the optimal solution.

Mathematical Foundation:

One of the most commonly used techniques in MCA is the Weighted Sum Method, which is calculated as follows:

$$S_j = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i c_{ij}$$

where:

- S_j is the overall score for an alternative j (e.g., a specific location),
- w_i are the weights of individual criteria (e.g., costs, infrastructure availability),
- c_{ij} is the value of criterion i for alternative j (Zopounidis & Doumpos, 2002).

This calculation allows for combining various criteria into a single index, which can then be used to compare different location alternatives. Criteria may include, for example, costs, transportation accessibility, environmental impacts, social aspects, and other factors.

Example of Application:

MCA is highly useful in location decisions where it is necessary to consider not only financial but also environmental and social factors. For instance, when choosing a location for a new manufacturing plant, MCA may consider criteria such as land costs, proximity to suppliers, availability of skilled labour, environmental risks, and the impact on the local community (Roy, 1996).

Limitations:

The main disadvantage of MCA is its complexity and the need for careful calibration of criteria weights, which can be subjective and may lead to different results depending on how the weights are set. It is also essential to recognize that some criteria may be difficult to quantify, which can affect the accuracy of the results.

3.3 Simulation Methods (e.g., Monte Carlo)

Simulation methods, such as the Monte Carlo Method, are highly useful for modeling and analysing the risks and uncertainties associated with location decisions. These methods allow for conducting simulations of different scenarios and analysing

how various variables (e.g., costs, demand, infrastructure availability) would influence the results of the location decision.

Mathematical Foundation:

The Monte Carlo Method is used for random sampling from the distribution functions of variables. The procedure involves the following steps:

1. Define distribution functions for input variables (e.g., demand, costs).
2. Randomly sample values from these distribution functions.
3. Calculate the result for each set of input variables using the model.
4. Perform a statistical analysis of the results to estimate the distribution of outcomes.

The result of the Monte Carlo simulation can be calculated as the average value from the simulations:

$$X = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f(x_i)$$

where:

- N is the number of simulations,
- $f(x_i)$ is the value of the function for this input,
- X_i is the value of the result for the i-th simulation (Rubinstein & Kroese, 2016).

Example of Application:

In business logistics, the Monte Carlo Method is used, for example, to assess the risks associated with different location scenarios. For instance, when planning a new logistics centre, Monte Carlo simulations can help identify uncertainties related to transportation costs, demand for the centre's services, or the availability of labour and infrastructure. This way, the company can better prepare a plan that takes potential risks and uncertainties into account (Metropolis & Ulam, 1949).

Limitations:

The main drawback of the Monte Carlo Method is its computational intensity, especially when a large number of simulations and variables are involved. Additionally, the accuracy of the results depends on the correct choice of distribution functions for input variables, which can be challenging in some cases.

3.4 Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are essential tools for logistics hub location. GIS allows for the integration and analysis of geographic data and the creation of models that can visualize and optimize location decisions.

Technological Foundation:

GIS allows for the integration of various types of data, including geographic, demographic, environmental, and economic data. This data can be analysed and

visualized in the form of maps, enabling the identification of optimal locations based on various criteria, such as transportation infrastructure availability, demographic data, environmental impacts, and regulatory constraints (Longley et al., 2015).

GIS also allows for performing different types of spatial analyses, such as network route analysis, route optimization, accessibility analysis, and coverage analysis. This way, companies can better understand the geographic factors influencing their location decisions and make more informed decisions.

Example of Application:

GIS are widely used in location decisions for new logistics centres, especially in complex environments where many different geographic and environmental factors must be considered. For example, when planning a new distribution centre, GIS can help analyse the availability of transportation networks, proximity to customers and suppliers, terrain topography, and other factors that affect costs and operational efficiency (Hesse & Rodrigue, 2004).

Limitations:

Despite its advantages, GIS also has some limitations. These include the technical requirements for equipment and the need for specialized expertise to use these systems effectively. Additionally, data integration and analysis can be time-consuming and expensive.

3.5 Optimization Methods in Location (e.g., Integer Programming)

Optimization methods, such as Integer Programming (IP), are advanced techniques that allow for finding optimal solutions to location problems with various constraints. These methods are used especially in cases where it is necessary to optimize multiple criteria simultaneously and where there are strict limitations on available resources.

Mathematical Foundation:

Integer Programming is a form of linear programming where some or all decision variables can only take integer values. The general form of an Integer Programming problem can be expressed as:

$$\text{Max/min } Z = \sum_{j=1}^n c_j x_j$$

$$\text{Conditions: } \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} x_j \leq b_i \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad x_j \geq 0 \quad x_j \text{ is Integer, } \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where:

- Z is the objective function to be maximized or minimized (e.g., profit or cost),
- x_j are the decision variables (e.g., the number of warehouses or transportation routes),

- c_j are the coefficients of the objective function,
- a_{ij} are the coefficients of the constraints,
- b_i are the right-hand sides of the constraints (Hillier & Lieberman, 2001).

Example of Application:

Optimization methods are particularly useful in complex logistics problems where it is necessary to optimize multiple objectives simultaneously. For example, when optimizing a network of distribution centres, a company can use Integer Programming to minimize total transportation, storage, and order processing costs while ensuring that demand in all regions is met (Dantzig, 1963).

Limitations:

Optimization methods are computationally intensive and often require specialized software and expertise. Additionally, due to the complexity of the problems they solve, the results may be sensitive to changes in input data and model parameters.

Location of logistics hubs in military logistics presents unique challenges that differ significantly from those in business logistics. Military operations require a specific approach to logistics that includes considerations such as security, strategic location, mobility, speed of response, and interoperability between military units and allied partners. This chapter focuses on the application of selected location methods in military logistics and their adaptation to the specific requirements of military operations.

3.6 Adaptation of Civilian Location Methods for Military Purposes

Many location methods used in business logistics can be adapted for military purposes, with modifications to better suit the specific requirements of military operations.

Weighted Center of Gravity Method

The Weighted Center of Gravity Method, commonly used in business logistics, is adapted in the military environment by considering factors such as security and the strategic value of the location. This method is used to find the optimal placement of logistics hubs to minimize transportation costs between various operational areas while weighing security risks and strategic priorities (Chopra & Meindl, 2016).

Practical Application:

During NATO operations in Afghanistan, it was necessary to locate supply depots in safe areas but close enough to operational units. The Weighted Center of Gravity Method was used to identify optimal locations, considering both geographical position and security risks (Scott, 2021).

Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA)

Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) is another method that has found its application in military logistics. This method allows multiple criteria to be considered simultaneously, which is often necessary in complex military operations. In addition to standard logistics criteria, political and security risks, infrastructure availability, and operational flexibility are also considered (Roy, 1996).

Practical Application:

When planning the location of military bases for the UN mission in Mali, MCA was used to assess the suitability of various locations. In addition to logistics and economic factors, regional political stability, access to medical care, and climatic conditions that could affect operations were also considered (Kress, 2012).

Simulation Methods (e.g., Monte Carlo)

Simulation methods, such as the Monte Carlo Method, are used in military logistics to model the risks and uncertainties that are inherent in military operations. These methods allow for simulating various combat and logistics scenarios and analysing how different factors would impact logistics support for operations (Rubinstein & Kroese, 2016).

Practical Application:

During the planning of logistics support for the 2003 invasion of Iraq, Monte Carlo simulation models were used to assess the risks associated with fuel and ammunition deliveries to the front lines. Simulations identified critical points in the supply chain and prepared planners for possible disruptions caused by combat operations (Metropolis & Ulam, 1949; Rubinstein & Kroese, 2016).

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are essential in military logistics, where it is important not only to analyse geographic data but also to integrate it with military operations and tactical plans. GIS enables the analysis of terrain, access routes, climate conditions, and other factors that can affect logistics operations (Longley et al., 2015).

Practical Application:

GIS were used in planning operations during the peacekeeping mission in Bosnia and Herzegovina. GIS helped analyse transportation and supply options in mountainous regions and identify optimal routes for transporting humanitarian aid and military supplies (Rodrigue, Comtois & Slack, 2016).

Optimization Methods (e.g., Integer Programming)

Optimization methods, such as Integer Programming (IP), are applied to find optimal location decisions that consider limited resources and the need to maximize operational efficiency. Military logistics problems often involve multiple objectives and strict constraints, making optimization methods highly useful (Hillier & Lieberman, 2001).

Practical Application:

Integer Programming was used to optimize the placement of fuel depots during NATO military exercises. The model considered the need to minimize the time required for refuelling points while ensuring that fuel was available in sufficient quantities at all critical locations (Dantzig, 1963).

3.7 Ammunition depot location – case study

Assume seven military units A-G with a given force demand for ammunition, ranked in a table according to its amount using a scale of 1-10 and coordinates (the latitude and longitude) that can be found in a mapping software. By applying the weighted centre of gravity approach in MS Excel, ideally via the so-called scalar product, we obtain the probable coordinates of the ideal location of the ammunition depot located in the Central Bohemia region. The assumption of the built-up area is 1 000m².

Table 5 Possible AD location calculated via weighted centre of gravity approach

number	military unit	demand weight	latitude	longitude
1	A	10	50,32372585	13,54527972
2	B	5	50,11113256	13,70795081
3	C	7	49,42032814	14,63680914
4	D	7	49,1389351	15,0089849
5	E	10	49,77358854	13,97860586
6	F	10	49,25293102	13,88286619
7	G	7	49,281718	14,50899293
Potential AD coordinates			49,6240176	14,13733537

Source: Authors' calculation

Figure 1 Possible AD location and positions of units

Source: own based on ArcGIS online

However, this approach takes into account only two factors - the level of demand and the distance of AD from clients. Therefore, this starting position needs to be revised by the following **restrictions (R)**:

R1: Distance from urban areas. The distance from populated areas should be between 1000 and 2000 m from populated areas in accordance with the internal regulations of the Ministry of Defence (Gigovic, 2016). The calculated site is only 453 m away from the urban area, which means that it does not meet the conditions of the constraint.

Figure 2 Distance from urban areas

Source: own based on ArcGIS online

R2: Distance from roads and railways. The distance should range from 500 to 1500 m. Access to road transport is in the immediate vicinity, the railway is 10km away so the restriction is only partially met.

Figure 3 Distance from roads and railways

Source: own based on ArcGIS online

R3: Land cover/use restrictions. There are 5 classes of soil protection in the Czech Republic. Class 1 includes the most valuable soils in individual climatic regions, mainly on flat or only slightly sloping land, which can be withdrawn from the agricultural soil fund only exceptionally, mainly for projects related to the restoration of ecological stability of the landscape, or for linear constructions of fundamental importance (Vyhláška o stanovení tříd ochrany, 2024).

Figure 4 Soil protection classes

Source: <https://restep.vumop.cz/encyklopedie/images/b/ba/To.jpg>

The most valuable soil is found only in the northern part of the Central Bohemian Region, the investigated locality lies outside this area.

Coniferous forests should be avoided due to latent danger from fire (Gigovic, 2016). The site under consideration is located on agriculture land close to a mixed forest.

R4: Distance from power lines. Electric power lines are forbidden above and across AD sites due to the high risk of accidents (Gigovic, 2016). The distance should be more than 200 m. There are no power lines in the area under consideration.

R5: Slope. Topography with steep slopes is generally considered as less suitable for AD location due to extra building and functioning costs (Gigovic, 2016). Slope should be less than 15°. According to the map below, the site meets this restriction. The average slope in the Central Bohemian Region oscillates around 4°, or no higher than 6°.

Figure 5 Average slope in the regions of the Czech Republic

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-445X/8/11/165#:~:text=The%20major%20topic%20of%20this%20article>

R6: Exclusion of the existence of a protected area on the site or in the vicinity of the AD. If the protected area is closer than 1000 m, the site should be excluded. Protected area Brdy is located about 27 km from potential AD location so this restriction is met.

Figure 6 Slope of the examined area

Source: own based on ArcGIS online

R7: Exclusion of the metal ores occurrence on the site. It is required that potential locations for the AD do not contain metal ores (manganese, iron, etc.) which

affect the frequency and the intensity of lightning, so the AD safety would be in jeopardy (Gigovic, 2016). The geological subsoil of the investigated site contains granite, granodiorite, feldspar and limestone which are mostly igneous rocks that do not contain any iron.

R8: Natural disaster risk exclusion. The nearest watercourse is Viničný potok situated about 350 m from the locality. There is therefore a potential risk of flooding but with low probability. No floods have occurred in this area in the last 10 years.

Once the restrictions are set, the evaluation criteria and their scoring scale of 1-5 from very low to very high suitability can be further specified.

Table 6 Evaluation criteria

Criterion number	Criterion	1 Very low suitability	2 Low suitability	2 Moderate suitability	4 High suitability	5 Very high suitability
C1	Distance from roads and railways	>1500 m	1250–1500 m	1000–1250 m	750–1000 m	500–750 m
C2	Distance from urban areas	1000–1250 m	1250–1500 m	1500–1750 m	1750–2000 m	>2000 m
C3	Land cover/use ⁴	211,212,312	241-4 221-2	311,313	321,324 332-334	231
C4	Slope	12°–15°	9°–12°	6°-9°	3°-6°	<3°
C5	Distance from power lines	>1400 m	1100–1400 m	800–1100 m	500–800 m	200–500 m

Source: modified by (Gigovic, 2016)

The weight of the criteria can be determined using **Fuller's triangle**, where 4 experts A-C pairwise compared the criteria with each other as follows:

Table 7 Expert A

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	C1	C1	C1	C1
C2		1	C2	C2	C2
C3			1	C4	C5
C4				1	C4
C5					1

Source: own

⁴ CORINE LANDCOVER 2018: <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/map-viewer?product=130299ac96e54c30a12edd575eff80f7>

Table 8 Expert B

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	C2	C1	C1	C1
C2		1	C2	C2	C2
C3			1	C3	C5
C4				1	C5
C5					1

Source: own

Table 9 Expert C

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	C2	C2	C1	C1
C2		1	C2	C2	C2
C3			1	C3	C5
C4				1	C4
C5					1

Source: own

Table 10 Expert D

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	C1	C2	C1	C1
C2		1	C2	C2	C2
C3			1	C3	C4
C4				1	C5
C5					1

Source: own

The preferences of each expert are summed and divided by their cumulative number in MS Excel as follows:

Table 11 Calculation of criterias' weights

preferences	A	B	C	D	Σ preferences	weights [%]
C1	4	3	2	3	12	30,00
C2	3	4	5	4	16	40,00
C3	0	1	1	1	3	7,50
C4	2	0	1	1	4	10,00
C5	1	2	1	1	5	12,50
Σ					40	1

Source: own

Table 12 The final ranking of the criterias' weights

critierion code	critierion description	weights %
C2	Distance from urban areas	40
C1	Distance from roads and railways	30
C5	Distance from power lines	12,5
C4	Slope	10
C3	Land cover/ Use	7,5

Source: own

The maximum weight is therefore given to **distance from populated areas, followed by distance from road and rail**. The third most important criterion is slope. The slope of our calculated variant is satisfactory, distance from roads and populated areas is not, therefore it is necessary to look for a variant close to the one we have calculated, which satisfies all the limiting conditions, including the size of the future built-up area.

Figure 7 Potential sites meeting the criteria

Source: own based on ArcGIS

4. COMPARISON OF LOCATION FACTORS BETWEEN BUSINESS AND MILITARY LOGISTICS

To clearly structure and understand the differences between location factors in business and military logistics, this chapter is divided into two separate sections. The first part focuses on location factors in civilian logistics, and the second on those in military logistics. Both of them are considered not only from national but also from the international point of view.

4.1 Location Factors in Business Logistics

In civilian logistics, location factors play a crucial role in deciding where to place logistics hubs. Companies must consider various economic, infrastructural, and market factors that affect the efficiency, costs, and speed of supply chains. Below are the main location factors considered when planning logistics hubs in the business sector:

- The volume, weight and characteristics of the stored items, boxes, pallets, containers, which determine the required size of the storage area, the method of handling, the mode of transport being used, etc.
- Natural conditions – nature of the terrain, climate, sufficient energy and water resources, etc.
- Economic factors: In business logistics, economic factors such as operating costs, transportation costs, and labour availability are often the most significant factors influencing location decisions. Cost of land acquisition or the amount of rent for warehouse space in a given country also plays an important role. In case of an international network of logistics hubs, it is necessary to ensure that customs procedures are carried out properly and fluently. The costs associated with communication among partners in the supply chain via ERP and EDI systems should also be considered (Macurová, 2018). Companies aim to minimize costs and maximize efficiency by choosing locations that offer the best balance between costs and access to key markets (Chopra & Meindl, 2016).
- Infrastructure factors: The availability of quality transportation infrastructure, such as highways, railways, airports, and ports and its sufficient capacity are crucial for ensuring efficient logistic operations. Companies seek locations that provide easy access to multiple modes of transportation to reduce lead times and costs (Hesse & Rodrigue, 2004) – in this case the term intermodal competition is used (Murphy, 2008). The level of logistics infrastructure can be measured using specific indexes, e. g. LPI (Logistics Performance Index) compiled by the World Bank. However, the possibility of using LPI to predict future development of logistics infrastructure availability can be seen as limited, mainly due to the low frequency of the LPI update and the gradual increase in the number of evaluated countries. The two-year interval also does not allow taking into account of extreme short-term fluctuations such as natural disasters, short armed conflicts or a short-term humanitarian problem (Foltin et al., 2018). Road transport infrastructure in Central and Eastern Europe is often overloaded, which negatively affects its quality. Poor quality infrastructure can then influence the safety of the cargo being transported. From the economic point of view of the transport market, it can be said that the aforementioned problems are associated with potentially large losses, whether in the form of human lives, damage to health or property damage. Furthermore, overloaded cargo transport is accompanied by significant negative externalities, which are reflected in significantly higher maintenance and repair costs for road transport infrastructure (Vlkovsky, 2018).

- **Market proximity:** Proximity to key markets is essential for minimizing transportation costs and reducing lead times. Companies often choose locations close to major consumer markets to ensure rapid delivery and lower shipping expenses (Porter, 1980).
- **Social and environmental factors:** Social factors, such as the availability of a skilled workforce, quality of life, and community relations, also play a significant role in location decisions. Additionally, environmental factors, such as regulatory requirements and the potential impact on the local environment, must be considered (Christopher, 2016). At present, research addressing the reduction of environmental risk due to major accidents is mainly focused on stationary sources of hazards within industrial facilities. However, the gradual increase in the amount of transported substances will require to devote attention to accidents in the transport of hazardous substances, which, especially in vulnerable locations, may cause irreversible environmental losses (Bernatik et al., 2021).
- **Security considerations:** While security is less of a concern in business logistics compared to military, it remains an important factor. Companies must ensure that their logistics hubs are located in areas with low risk of natural disasters, theft, or other security threats (Blanchard, 2008),
- **The number and capabilities of transport and warehousing logistics service providers,** referred to as intramodal competition (Murphy, 2008), can also be an important locational factor particularly in case of JIT/JIS deliveries between manufacturers and suppliers (Macurova, 2018).
- **Trade patterns** – are influenced by the EU member countries. The virtual elimination of trade barriers has allowed companies to move from having distribution centres in many countries towards having only one or two facilities. The Czech Republic has become a favored production and distribution site thanks to its relatively central geographic location (Murphy, 2008).
- **Strikes by distribution centres employees, political instability in a given country, or public opposition to the construction of these types of facilities** can also represent risk factors in the process of finding an optimal location.

4.2 Location Factors in Military Logistics

In military logistics, location factors (in addition to the factors relevant to the civil environment listed above) are primarily determined by the needs for security, strategic positioning, and the ability to support military operations. Decision-making on the placement of military logistics hubs must consider not only efficiency and costs but also the ability to respond quickly to unforeseen situations and maintain the operational capability of military forces.

- **Security Factors:** Security is the highest priority when deciding on the location of military logistics hubs. These hubs must be located in areas that are well protected from potential attacks, espionage, and other military threats. Physical

- security and cybersecurity are essential to ensure the continuous operation of these hubs, even in crisis situations (Kress, 2012; Scott, 2021).
- **Strategic Location:** The strategic location of military logistics hubs is crucial for supporting military operations and achieving strategic objectives. These hubs should be positioned to allow for rapid and efficient access to operational areas and to facilitate the deployment and support of military forces (Blanchard, 2008).
 - **Infrastructure Availability:** Access to military infrastructure, such as military airports, ports, and railways, is vital for ensuring the rapid mobilization and movement of military forces and supplies. Military logistics hubs must be located near infrastructure that can support heavy military equipment and provide secure and reliable transportation routes (Rubinstein & Kroese, 2016).
 - **Interoperability:** Interoperability with allied military forces and logistics systems is essential for the success of joint operations. Military logistics hubs must be compatible with the logistics systems of other nations and organizations, such as NATO, to ensure coordinated and effective logistical support (Kress, 2012).
 - **Flexibility and Scalability:** Military logistics hubs must be flexible and scalable to quickly adapt to changing operational needs. This includes the ability to expand or contract logistics capacities based on the demands of the mission and the ability to relocate or reconfigure logistics operations as needed (Longley et al., 2015).

5. PESCO NETLOGHUBS AND THEIR ROLE IN EUROPEAN MILITARY LOGISTICS

The PESCO NetLogHubs project (Permanent Structured Cooperation Network of Logistic Hubs in Europe and Support to Operations) is a key initiative within the European Union aimed at improving cooperation and interoperability among member states in military logistics. This project is part of the broader EU effort to enhance its defense capacity through PESCO (Permanent Structured Cooperation), a mechanism focused on deepening military cooperation among member states. This chapter explores the role of the NetLogHubs project in European military logistics, its significance, and its benefits for future military operations.

The NetLogHubs project aims to create a network of logistics hubs in Europe that could be effectively used by EU member states during military operations and/or crisis situations with a humanitarian aspect (Council of the EU, 2020).

The NetLogHubs project has several key objectives:

- **Improving Interoperability:** Creating unified standards and procedures for logistics to enable easier cooperation among EU member states. This includes standardizing procedures, sharing data, and coordinating logistics operations across different national armed forces (European Defence Agency, 2020).

- Optimizing Resource Utilization: More efficient use of existing logistics capacities in member states, including sharing logistics hubs, storage facilities, and transportation assets. This should lead to cost savings and increased efficiency in logistics operations (European Defence Agency, 2021).
- Enhancing Readiness and Responsiveness: Establishing a network of logistics hubs strategically located across Europe that can quickly provide support in case of military operations or crises. This network aims to reduce the time needed for mobilizing and deploying military forces (Council of the EU, 2020).

The structure of the project includes several main components, including the identification and certification of existing logistics hubs, the development of standards and protocols for their use, and the implementation of mechanisms for resource and capacity sharing among member states.

A process is currently underway to select the hubs that will become members of the final EU network to support possible future operations. The following figure shows the project member states having already offered their hubs and the countries with observer status including the Czech Republic. Croatia is the project member state and has already provided two hubs in Split and Slunj that could become part of a pan-European network.

Figure 8 Network of proposed loghubs in Europe

Source: NETWORK OF LOGHUBS IN EUROPE AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONS – 6TH PMC MEETING. Cologne: PESCO, 2024. Sv. Day 01.

The hubs on offer are characterised by their high concentration in the south and north-west of Europe and, on the other hand, by the so-called blindspots, visible in the diagram below. These blindspots will need to be filled (mainly in Central and Eastern Europe) so that logistical support to the troops passing through can run smoothly and efficiently in accordance with the approved operation plan.

Figure 9 Blindspots within the loghub network

Source: NETWORK OF LOGHUBS IN EUROPE AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONS – 6TH PMC MEETING. Cologne: PESCO, 2024. Sv. Day 01.

The capabilities that the selected hubs should possess have been formulated in six main areas:

- Storage
- Security
- Transportation
- Maintenance
- Support
- Transshipment

Figure 10 Capabilities of the hubs

Source: NETWORK OF LOGHUBS IN EUROPE AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONS – 6TH PMC MEETING. Cologne: PESCO, 2024. Sv. Day 02.

These requirements will play an important role in locating the resulting hub network. Many of them significantly differ from the standard civilian requirements for the operation of multinational logistics hubs and are mainly related to the specific nature of the items stored. The riskiest commodity is undoubtedly ammunition, with maximum distance from urban areas, minimum slope values and sufficient distance from power lines and from the military ranges being essential criteria for locating ammunition depots (Gigovič, 2016).

The need for tracking the materiel and the sensitivity of the information that will be transmitted via certified information systems between the partners of the supply chain represents another important decision factor.

The major differences in the area of transportation include the requirements for special transport vehicles capable of transporting heavy military equipment and hazardous material in the context of ADR, RID, ADN and IMDG. In the area of transshipment handling equipment with high load capacity and mainly diesel propulsion is needed.

The maintenance area includes workshops for maintenance and repair of military equipment with appropriate equipment and personnel.

In the area of logistical support accommodation for military units, catering, healthcare and adequate office facilities for operations management will be required.

However, the available infrastructure in terms of access to road, rail, air and sea transport capable of transporting oversized and heavy military equipment, material of sensitive nature and designated personnel to the specific destination will be essential.

Interviews with experts have identified other criterion that will also influence the future spatial distribution of the hubs. This includes their position as close as possible to the TEN-T (Trans-European Transport Network).

One blind spot has already been identified in the Czech Republic. The hub selection process has already started and the Czech Republic, represented by the Ministry of Defence, has officially offered the logistics hub in Mosnov near Ostrava in the Moravian-Silesian region. The civilian hub is already in operation there, but the military part is yet to be constructed. The requirements for the services that the hubs should provide have already been specified, but neither their importance nor the final state of the hubs in the network is determined. The classical Weighted centre of gravity localization methods cannot be used here because the units will be provided with the required services directly in the hubs within the HNS (Host Nation Support) concept and the position of the units will not be stable as it is the case with the clients of distribution centres in the civilian sector or units in peacetime in a military environment.

Thus, an opportunity for future research in this area is the combination of multi-criteria analysis and GIS systems, which could help to identify potential individual hubs in the network with a focus on the Czech Republic.

6. RESULTS DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The paper provides a framework for answering the research questions set out in the introduction:

- Q1: Which approaches to locating logistics hubs/distribution centers were applied in civilian practice and what are the limits of their use?
- Q2: Which of these methods have already been used in a military environment and what they are limited by?
- Q3: What is the basic structure of the location criteria to find the most appropriate spatial distribution of logistics hubs/centers in a civilian environment?
- Q4: Which other criteria need to be considered in the process of selecting a suitable logistics center/hub location from a military point of view?

The literature review and gap analysis identified a critical lack of publications in international WoS databases for the period 2020-2024 which would address the problem under study in the military environment. This paper can thus help to further develop research in this very specific domain.

Through a case study it has been demonstrated that mathematical location approaches could be used in a military environment, but under peacetime conditions and with a stable location of the supplied units. These approaches must be verified by another method. Multi-criteria analysis combined with the application of GIS systems appearing to be the most appropriate.

Another important implication of the case study is the finding that the range of criteria identified by the PESTLE and comparative analysis (part 4 of the paper) should be expanded to include other criteria, e.g. proximity to populated areas, slope of the terrain and land type being covered.

In the NetLogHubs project, the weights of the criteria that are important for the application of multi-criteria analysis methods are not yet defined. Here is an opportunity for future application of Fuller's triangle or Saaty's method based on pairwise comparison of criteria, whereby the strength of each preference relation is determined and evaluated by the experts. Also, the possibility of using multi-criteria analysis and GIS systems within the NetLogHubs project is highly probable,

Future research of the authors should therefore be oriented towards the possibility of using location-based methods to find suitable positions of the logistics hubs within the EU network to support operations. As mentioned above, classical approaches in the sense of Weighted Center of Gravity assume a stable location of retail stores that will be supplied by the net of distribution centres being proposed while the retailers should have relatively stable demand. This project will involve finding suitable hub network location for military units with no long-term stable position and with changing requirements to which hubs would have to respond fluently and as fast as possible.

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IV. TECHNOLOGICAL, ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF LOGISTICS

DIGITAL TWINS IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, AND POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Over the past few years, supply chains complexity has increased significantly, leading to a focus towards supply chain vulnerability in practice and academia. To successfully managing associated challenges, innovations with regards to transparency, flexibility, and agile decision-making are needed. Digital twin technology has emerged as one potential solution in recent years. In scientific literature related discussions concentrated on minor or specific use cases. To get to a comprehensive perspective about Digital Twin technology in supply chain management, this study summarizes and structures the existing research. To achieve this, a qualitative content analysis was conducted using Gioia's methodology, covering 59 scientific articles. We identified three overarching research streams. First, a variety of success factors of Digital Twin technology implementation. Second, the necessary prerequisites and industry conditions for implementing Digital Twin technology. Third, different examples of Digital Twin applications and considerations for further developments and research. Practitioners can use these findings to identify potential implementation approaches and gradually address the requirements for using Digital Twins. Further empirical studies could build upon our findings to explore opportunities and challenges of Digital Twins in specific business environments.

Keywords: digital twins, supply chain management, supply chain transparency

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, supply chains have become more complex and are additionally confronted with a variety of challenges such as emerging conflicts and material shortages (Brandtner et al. 2023, p. 133). Coupled with increasing demand volatility, increasing business regulations, technological advancements, and shorter product life cycles, efficient and robust supply chain operations states an essential aspect of business success (Gallego-García et al. 2023, p. 1281). These risks and conditions impact logistics costs and service levels, making it extremely difficult for companies to come to appropriate strategic and day-to-day decisions (Biller et al. 2022, p. 1348). Consequently, supply chains have become more volatile and vulnerable, while any disruption in supply chains can affect both revenue and costs of companies (Ponomarov and Holcomb 2009, p. 124).

Especially in recent years, complexity and risks have increased significantly (Deepu and Ravi 2021, p. 1). This was clearly shown during the Covid-19 pandemic, which exposed a lack of preparedness and inadequate recovery capabilities across different sectors and industries (Ivanov and Dolgui 2022, p. 475). Recent major external effects have resulted in numerous supply chain disruptions, compelling companies worldwide to improve their supply chain resilience (Kajba et al. 2023, p. 1).

As a key to cope with this situation, supply chains need to enhance their ability to recover and provide efficient responses to emerging threats and events (Ponomarov and Holcomb 2009, p. 124). Consequently, all actors along the value chain should aim for greater resilience and redesigning their supply chains accordingly (Sundarakani et al. 2021, p. 358). Increased supply chain transparency activities and agile decision-making are vital in this regard, making technology utilization essential (Brandtner et al. 2023, p. 133). Particularly, digital twin (=DT) technology is considered as a promising opportunity for planning, controlling and simulation-based decision-making (Zarnitz et al. 2023, p. 69). In combination with advanced data analytics and optimization techniques, DTs offer a data-driven approach for managing supply chains more effective and efficient (Ivanov et al. 2019b, p. 310).

In scientific literature, DT technology has emerged as a prominent topic in recent years. However, DTs are mostly discussed in minor or isolated use cases. The aim of this study is to synthesize existing DT approaches and identify their features, possibilities, and prerequisites in terms of supply chain management. This research seeks to provide an overview of the most important characteristics of DTs and identify their current and future application areas in supply chain management. To achieve this, a systematic literature analysis was conducted to address the following research questions:

RQ1: How can DT technology enhance supply chain management activities, and what are fundamental prerequisites for DT usage?

RQ2: What is the current state of DT applications in the context of supply chain management, and what are the next steps in research and practice to support DT development?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section two provides a brief overview of the theoretical background underlying the research. Section three explains the methodology for the systematic literature review. Section four presents the analysis of the findings, followed by a discussion in section five. Finally, the last section concludes the analysis and offers a brief outlook on further research directions.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Characterization of Digital twin technology

A digital twin is described as a digital representation of a physical object or system, including its characteristics, behaviour, formation process, and performance. This representation is created by digital technology and is updated through the exchange of information between the physical and virtual system (van der Horn and Mahadevan 2021, p. 2; Wang 2020, p. 100). The physical representation can be any sort of reality entity, ranging from a single machinery part to a whole interconnected system. This also includes the environment and process of the concerned entity (van der Horn and Mahadevan 2021, pp. 2–3). By employing sensors and other technologies to these real-world elements, various data can be captured. A DT acquires and models this captured real-time data. They then can be executed to generate a digital representation (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 2; Javaid et al. 2023, p. 72).

A necessary element is the fully integrated data flow between physical and digital objects, in both directions (Fuller et al. 2020, p. 108953). With regards to the connection physical to virtual, the collected data of the physical entity is interpreted to update the state of the virtual representation. Regarding the connection virtual to physical, the virtual representation is used to determine required changes to the physical representation to react and achieve a targeted physical state (van der Horn and Mahadevan 2021, pp. 4–5). A DT must adapt and learn, leading to improvements of the virtual model and its physical counterpart (Biller et al. 2022, p. 1342). Finally, DTs offer situation awareness to enable information based decision-making (Biller et al. 2022, p. 1344).

2.2 Digital twins in supply chain management

DTs are key solutions for Industry 4.0, offering numerous possibilities across various application fields. In the field of supply chain management, a DT serves as a digital representation of the flow of goods from suppliers to consumers, tracking all related processes (Freese and Ludwig 2021, p. 328). The physical counterpart is subjected to the same supply chain that can include hundreds of physical assets, logistics, warehouses, and inventory positions (Juan 2023, p. 663). Moreover, a DT in supply chain management can be categorized by different levels. First, DT on network level, which displays a multi stakeholder value network. Second, DT on site level, meaning a DT maps a logistics site, e.g. a production or warehouse facility.

Last, DT on asset level, where a DT illustrates a logistics asset, such as a forklift or a truck (Gerlach et al. 2021, p. 6).

As one digital solution in supply chain management, a DT is distinct from other current applications. Solutions like freight exchange platforms only deliver limited details, like order or freight information, resulting in a lack of holistic optimization capabilities. Moreover, applications like advanced planning and scheduling systems (APS-systems), transport management systems (TMS) or supply chain management systems (SCM-systems) also have clear disadvantages compared to a DT solution (Busse et al. 2021, p. 7). In terms of update frequency most current systems do not support real time data exchange like DTs. In addition, DT technology offers advanced analytical capabilities, which are essential for effective management of complex data sets. Although modern enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems provide data analysis opportunities, these functions are mostly inadequate for comprehensive optimization to enhance logistics performance (Busse et al. 2021, p. 7). Furthermore, in comparison to current digital solutions, DTs offer simulation capabilities regarding the complete supply chain. DTs have the ability to run what-if scenarios, which extends the decision-making capabilities of the system as well (Busse et al. 2021, p. 7).

A DT enables several benefits for supply chain management. Starting with abilities of advanced data analytics such as monitoring, simulation, and optimization (van der Valk et al. 2022, p. 157). Hence, DTs can be used to optimize supply chain process efficiency and analyse product characteristics and performance (Javaid et al. 2023, p. 72). Additionally, DTs provide benefits such as increased transparency and visibility, for supply chain operations (Ivanov et al. 2019a, p. 327; Ivanov and Dolgui 2021, p. 776). By supporting information sharing among all supply chain partners, uncertainties in the supply chain can be reduced and responsibilities of work can be better coordinated (dos Santos Alvim et al. 2022, p. 86). Furthermore, DT technology enables the possibility to anticipate disruptions via exploration, prediction and preparation of innovative responses to the unknown (Kajba et al. 2023, pp. 1–2). By providing these responses, a DT helps to set up different strategies to manage occurring risks or prevent and tackle disruptions, supporting a higher supply chain resilience (dos Santos Alvim et al. 2022, p. 86).

There are several requirements to consider when creating a DT. Technologies like Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and machine learning form the digital infrastructure as foundation for functional DTs (Moshood et al. 2021, p. 16). Moreover, multiple obstacles must be managed, especially the challenge of process monitoring within a complex supply chain. Enhancing communication and ensuring trust among various supply chain partners is an important element to overcome these challenges (Freichel et al. 2022, p. 461). As a result, greater supply chain visibility (SCV) can be achieved, enabling effective DT usage in supply chain management.

In general, DT technology in supply chain management offers substantial insights into its performance. It responds to different inputs to reveal opportunities that may otherwise remain hidden. By offering explanations of how and why various supply chain events occur, it provides opportunities for supply chain transformation (Juan 2023, p. 663).

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a systematic literature review was conducted, using the qualitative content analysis (QCA) methodology in accordance with Gioia (Gioia et al. 2013). The QCA research approach involves an inductive process aimed at deriving concepts and categories from the data (Schreier 2012, p. 25). By extracting information from gathered data or materials, this methodology facilitates the identification of new elements and their interconnections within the research topic (Gioia 2021, p. 23). Qualitative analysis is particularly valuable in the field of supply chain management, as it enables a specific understanding of complex operations and process execution (Trautrim et al. 2012, p. 838).

The selection process for synthesizing academic literature follows the guidelines for conducting a systematic review outlined by Tranfield et al. (2003, pp. 214–218). This approach not only ensures transparency in the research process but also allows replication of the study by other researchers (Watson et al. 2018, pp. 257–258).

3.1 Data collection

The identification of relevant articles for the QCA was conducted through a systematic data search. In alignment with the research questions outlined in the initial section, an appropriate search string was developed. As data source, we relied on Scopus, which is one of the largest databases containing over 94 million scientific documents. The search string utilized was as follows: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("digital twin" AND "supply chain" AND ("use case" OR "application" OR "case study")). By including the search terms in the title, keywords, or abstract, the search yielded a total of 227 articles.

To refine the results, various inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected. Therefore, filters were selected as follows: language: English; publication stage: final; documentation type: “article” and “conference paper”; source: “conference proceedings” and “journals”.

Applying these filters reduced the number of articles to 119. By manually reviewing the titles and abstract, 31 articles were excluded from further analysis due to a mismatch with the research questions. Finally, 29 articles were eliminated due to insufficient information for the research, resulting in a final selection of 59 articles remaining for the QCA. The selection process is graphically outlined in figure 1.

Figure 1 Applied selection process of relevant articles

Source: Authors

3.2 Data analysis

The QCA was conducted by using Microsoft Excel and the literature management program Citavi. All 59 articles were uploaded into Citavi for analysis. To gather relevant information regarding the research questions, a systematic, iterative analysis process was used. This involved a step-by-step examination of each article, in which we first extracted all relevant information regarding our research questions and gave them content oriented labels (=codes) (Gioia 2021, p. 24; Schreier 2012, p. 60).

To prevent redundancies and consolidate the extracted codes, they were summarized into distinct paragraphs (Schreier 2012, p. 107). Subsequently, an iterative review process of these paragraphs was undertaken to categorize them based on their differences and similarities into first-order concepts. These first-order concepts were then combined to form second-order themes (Gioia et al. 2013, p. 20).

In the subsequent step, the second-order themes were condensed into aggregated dimensions (Gioia 2021, p. 25). This iterative merging process formed the data structure, providing an overview of the data development from raw materials to aggregated dimensions (Gioia et al. 2013, pp. 20–22). Furthermore, the data structure facilitates a deeper understanding of connections and interrelationships between the different concepts, themes, and dimensions (Gioia 2021, pp. 24–26).

The following chapter presents the analysis findings based on the established data structure (see figure 2).

Figure 2 Applied selection process of relevant articles

Source: Authors

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 Success factors and chances of DT implementation

4.1.1 Determining drivers and features

DT application areas

One key feature of DT is its ability to monitor various KPIs and compare them with simulated data (Shevtshenko et al. 2020, p. 9). The capability of real-time resource monitoring offers the potential for visualization and optimization of supply chain processes (Zhang et al. 2023, p. 20; Lugaresi et al. 2023, p. 454). DTs could integrate supply chain processes across actors along the value chain by connecting various departments or functions within and across organizations (Maheshwari and Kamble 2022, p. 2328; Autiosalo et al. 2021, p. 23). The combination of these characteristics enables the performance measurement and efficiency enhancement of supply chain systems (Latsou et al. 2021, p. 812; Davila R et al. 2023, p. 146; Melesse et al. 2022, p. 19). As a result, DT facilitates decision-making for all supply chain actors (Corallo et al. 2022, p. 5; dos Santos Alvim et al. 2022, p. 89).

DT drivers

Besides decreasing technology costs, the increasing demand for automation also drives DT adoption in supply chain management (Attaran and Celik 2023, pp. 7–8). Furthermore, recent crisis like the Covid-19 pandemic underline the need for DTs

(Gallego-García et al. 2023, p. 1281). Other technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics, or IoT-devices could further advance DT development (Kajba et al. 2023, pp. 13–14). This role extends to machine learning, and artificial intelligence (Elbouzidi et al. 2022, p. 7; Kamble et al. 2022, pp. 10–11), augmented reality, and blockchain technology (Kanak et al. 2019, p. 3517; Sani et al. 2022, p. 230; Thanh Le et al. 2022, p. 372).

4.1.2 Improvement for supply chain operations

Economic advantages

DTs offer flexible solutions across various fields. Combining different DT driven services encompasses technology's full potential (van der Valk et al. 2022, pp. 159–161). While DTs rely on collaboration among supply chain actors, they can also enhance greater cooperation and systematically facilitate breaking down silos (Reeves and Maple 2019, p. 5; Lim et al. 2022, p. 479).

DTs' usage leads to higher profitability and revenue growth for companies (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 1). DTs could also contribute to long term cost savings (Rymarczyk 2020, p. 193; Abouzid and Saidi 2023, p. 13). Through predictive maintenance and machine learning algorithms, DTs can enhance product quality and productivity (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 7; Mantravadi et al. 2023, p. 13; Heim et al. 2020, p. 4123). Overall, DT utilization can increase efficiency and drive intraorganizational improvements in important KPIs and product life cycles (Biller et al. 2022, p. 1348; Binsfeld and Gerlach 2022, p. 2; Xia et al. 2022, p. 4176; Cirullies and Schwede 2021, p. 2021; Preut et al. 2021, p. 11).

Supply chain transparency advantages

Besides economic advantages, DTs offer several improvements for supply chain management, including testing and simulating diverse risk scenarios and events (Lee and Lee 2021, p. 11; Kuhl et al. 2022, p. 2949). DTs identify process gaps, which increases supply chain visibility (Gallego-García et al. 2022a, p. 18). DTs enable cross-company data-sharing, enhancing transparency across the value chain (Li et al. 2020, p. 22; Hegedus et al. 2019, p. 658). Consequently, higher transparency enables the detection and elimination of potential bottlenecks (Gerlach et al. 2021, p. 18), resulting in increasing supply chain resilience (Kajba et al. 2023, p. 17; Binsfeld and Gerlach 2022, p. 9).

4.2 Preliminary measures and responsibilities for DT usage

4.2.1 Technology and infrastructure set up

Essential technological requirements

Software and implementation standards within companies and across the value chain (Mügge et al. 2023, p. 21), and reliable IT-infrastructure are required as a DTs'

foundation (Deepu and Ravi 2021, p. 4). Moreover, unique IoT identifiers of every part of the DT are necessary (Vogt et al. 2021, p. 564), including stable data connection, and a high data validity and synchronicity (Klößner et al. 2023, p. 15; Wang et al. 2021, p. 1308). Sensors serve as the most important component of DTs, providing new information (Freese and Ludwig 2021, p. 335). Using generic algorithms could optimize DTs' performance (Hu et al. 2023, p. 9). DT development requires an integrated database across the supply chain for efficient information sharing (Chen and Huang 2021, p. 6).

Data and process claims

DT usage requires a change of business processes (Radke et al. 2022, p. 693), with a strong focus on documentation of all relevant business processes and role assignment (Radke et al. 2022, pp. 697–698). Furthermore, existing processes should be reassessed for better compatibility with new technologies (Radke et al. 2022, p. 698). Additionally, DT development requires a systematic approach. First, starting with basic functionality and second, adding further features, if needed (Čech and Vosáhlo 2022, p. 68). Data standardization facilitates knowledge sharing during DT development (Ehm et al. 2019, p. 2415). Moreover, cybersecurity is key to secure critical information within supply chain networks (Gallego-García et al. 2022b, p. 23).

Corporate resource requirements

Establishing a robust foundation for DT development entails certain expenses, including technology platforms, IoT sensors, software, data maintenance, and cybersecurity solutions (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 8). Additional advanced technologies such as upgradeable machines results in high investment costs (Henrichs et al. 2021, p. 18). Consequently, companies aiming to implement DTs, must have the willingness to make significant investments (Deepu and Ravi 2021, p. 4). Furthermore, DTs require substantial resources in terms of storage capacity and computing power (Lugaresi et al. 2023, p. 455).

4.2.2 Particular sector and industry characteristics

Internal company preconditions

Successfully establishing a DT requires overcoming internal organizational obstacles. Transforming the company's culture is essential to achieve the benefits of DTs (Autiosalo et al. 2021, p. 20). Furthermore, internal and external collaboration is key for DT development (Čech and Vosáhlo 2022, p. 68), especially in terms of data sharing among different supply chain partners (Deepu and Ravi 2021, p. 8). However, reluctance to share data and maintain information secrecy persists among many companies (Pehlken and Baumann 2020, p. 5). Data sharing raises concerns about security (Lugaresi et al. 2023, 455), particularly regarding the human element as the weakest link in security systems (Gajek et al. 2021, p. 733). Overall, there is a need

for high qualification and specific skills that are currently lacking in many companies (Henrichs et al. 2021, pp. 18–19; Rymarczyk 2020, p. 194).

Supply chain specifics

The complexity of supply chains is a challenge for DT development. Managing numerous suppliers across various countries complicates tracking single parts or products throughout the supply chain network (Vogt et al. 2021, p. 564). This also entails the need to consider varying legal regulations, based on the current location (Henrichs et al. 2021, p. 19). Power imbalances within supply chains might hinder successful DT adoption (Gajek et al. 2021, p. 729). DT requirements vary depending on company size: for instance, larger companies seek customized solutions, while small and medium-sized companies prefer standardized, cost-effective solutions (Liu et al. 2023, p. 7).

4.3 Possible approaches on the pathway to DT implementation

4.3.1 Practical experiences and applications

DT use cases

Various use cases and applications for DTs in supply chain management range from broad tasks such as resource planning (Raghunandan et al. 2023, p. 3022) to specific functions like supporting the products design processes (Attaran and Celik 2023, pp. 3–4). DTs can also monitor product quality and assist in vehicle transportation routing (Henrichs et al. 2021, p. 11; Lee and Lee 2021, p. 11). Particularly in manufacturing, DTs are mostly applied for tasks such as production planning and shop floor management (Gerlach et al. 2021, p. 13). Overall, DTs foster cross-functional collaboration and enhance supply chain transparency (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 5). However, many current use cases only propose concepts for DT usage or model isolated machine aspects (Kenett and Bortman 2022, pp. 1359–1360).

DT implementation process

It is important to recognize that there is no standardized approach to DT implementation (Davila R et al. 2023, p. 143). Existing frameworks can serve as best practice guidelines for DT implementation (Perno et al. 2023, p. 15). Utilizing software platforms to leverage synergies in the development process may be beneficial (Ntamo et al. 2022, p. 3). Data collection, model creation, and real-time information integration into the model are key stages in the development process, enabling fact-based decision-making (Wang et al. 2021, pp. 1301–1302). Incremental development of DTs is important to facilitate implementation and maximize their benefits (Marmolejo-Saucedo 2020, p. 2153). This fosters a process of continuous improvement for further optimization of DT development (Gallego-García et al. 2023, p. 1292).

4.3.2 Considerations for future development and research

Further opportunities and trends

DT technology usage is expected to significantly increase in the future (Attaran and Celik 2023, p. 1). Alongside various complementary features such as prediction, simulation, and optimization, DT technology could be crucial in enabling the potential of industry 4.0 in supply chain management (van der Valk et al. 2022, p. 160; Liebenberg and Jarke 2023, p. 3). DTs can be used to create own standards for development of industry 4.0 applications (Bamunuarachchi et al. 2021, p. 30). DTs offer further potential, facilitating optimized production planning, enhanced predictive maintenance, and more efficient product development (Henrichs et al. 2021, pp. 16–17). Furthermore, DTs can enhance overall product lifecycle management and strengthen the development of circular-economy business models (Li et al. 2020, p. 14; Preut et al. 2021, p. 11). In general, DT technology accelerates innovation and fosters the creation of new innovative ecosystems (Rymarczyk 2020, p. 193).

Research directions

Although DT technology is gaining traction in scientific literature, there remains much to uncover, particularly in supply chain management research, which is still in its early stages (Freese and Ludwig 2021, p. 337). Many current use cases focus on heuristic models and isolated aspects (Lim et al. 2022, p. 479). Therefore, further research into how DTs can comprehensively address the entire supply chain is required (Lugaresi et al. 2023, p. 455). Additionally, there is a necessity to broaden the scope on various industries and sectors, as current DT applications are mostly limited to manufacturing (van der Valk et al. 2022, p. 157). Further research should focus on the interaction between the physical and digital realms, emphasizing development of appropriate solutions for effective alignment (Lugaresi et al. 2023, p. 455).

5. DISCUSSION

The results regarding RQ1 show several potential benefits of DT usage in supply chain management. DTs can optimize and monitor processes in real-time, by creating a virtual and dynamic representation of the physical supply chain. This supports different tasks, such as performance measurement, managing production schedules, optimize transportation routes and stock levels in real-time, as well as coping with supply chain risks. DTs enable simulations and advanced analytics to support information-based decision-making. This is helpful not only in day-to-day operations, but especially in terms of disruption management. Consequently, supply chain resilience can be increased by utilizing DT technology. Especially the use of AI within the context of DTs may lead to next level applications and even new business models, which are already being labelled as “industry 5.0”.

Nevertheless, several challenges and implementation barriers remain. First and foremost, integrating other emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and artificial intelligence are essential prerequisites to establish DT capabilities. Hence, high investment costs must be weighed against potential cost savings, making DT development particularly challenging for small businesses. Moreover, organizations need to reengineer or adjust their processes to meet the requirements of a DT. Additionally, various data formats and IT systems must be updated or standardized among supply chain partners, making internal and external collaboration fundamental for DT implementation. In this regard, sharing data and knowledge among supply chain partners remains a challenge. Limited trust among various actors and a lack of skilled employees may also hinder DT development and implementation. Furthermore, cyber security is a critical and indispensable aspect. Particularly in times of increasing cyber-attacks against companies, ensuring robust cyber security measures is crucial for DT development.

However, answers to the question of how to cope with those key challenges are missing. Future researchers and practitioners should investigate these questions as crucial basis before DT implementation in organizations in supply chain management. Our results indicate inconsistency in the literature. For instance, on one hand, data security is stated as prerequisite for DT implementation (Reeves and Maple 2019), on the other hand, data security can be improved by DTs (Kajba et al. 2023). Additionally, collaboration is a prerequisite for DT implementation (Reeves and Maple 2019), while it can be improved by DTs (Lugaresi et al. 2023). These ambiguous statements maybe reflect the lack of a standardized definition of DTs. Researchers should conduct further studies to get a uniform definition of DTs, especially against the background of industry understanding.

Regarding RQ2, the results indicate various DT application scenarios in the scientific literature. Most use cases are limited to manufacturing, where machines or parts are replicated as digital models. Many DT applications focus on selected aspects or theoretical models, with advantages remaining theoretical considerations. The connection to real-world data is not yet prevalent and need to be further investigated in other logistics areas. Advanced DT solutions should be tested in highly digitalized and automated environments to generate best practices. These approaches can be revised and updated to create a continuous improvement process for DT development. Consequently, conducting use cases by implementing theoretical models into real-world settings should be a focus of further research.

Moreover, possibilities of how to “design” DT systems in organizations and how to implement them is a missing topic. Researchers should examine DT concepts with regards to necessary technologies and supply chain specifics for guiding managerial decisions in establishing DTs. In contrast, practitioners should already examine their existent resources and financial possibilities. Hence, especially empirical work is promising for getting more insights in this topic.

6. CONCLUSION

In this article, a literature review on digital twins (DTs) in supply chain management was conducted. The findings highlight the high potential of DT usage in supply chain management. DTs allow optimized decision-making, contributing to long-term cost savings, increased operational efficiency and optimized disruption management. However, key challenges include data standardization, lack of reliable infrastructure, and limited trust among supply chain partners. In addition, creating a culture of change and making high investments are indispensable prerequisites for DT implementation.

The methodology of this research, although structured, has its limitations. The selection of search terms and filters may have restricted the articles found. Using additional or distinct search terms and databases might yield more results. The categorization is based on subjective interpretations of the articles analysed. Thus, different researchers may come to different results.

We see four areas of future research. First, establishing a thorough characterization of DT technologies with its functions and technological prerequisites against the background of industry considerations is necessary. Second, more research is recommended on how to overcome several challenges in DT implementation. Third, empirical work can be fruitful to grab real-world applications, spanning whole supply chains, and find best practices. Fourth, supporting managerial decision-making in DT implementation by establishing “pathways” against contextual supply chain specifics are promising.

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LEVERAGING AI IN SUPPLY CHAIN ANALYTICS: A CASE STUDY FROM FOOD INDUSTRY

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Abstract

In today's complex and evolving landscape, supply chains (SCs) face significant challenges in accurately forecasting market demand, particularly following the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. This paper aims to investigate whether current demand patterns are merely temporary fluctuations or indicative of a new reality. To address this, we implemented several algorithms to predict future market demand, with a special emphasis on testing the capabilities and performance of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in SC contexts. Among the various AI models examined, we selected feed-forward neural networks (NN) as a key representative. Paper includes analysis of the NN against state-of-the-art forecasting models, specifically Facebook's Prophet model and the autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA). The results indicate that the NN outperformed traditional models, demonstrating superior accuracy in demand forecasting. This enhancement in predictive capabilities highlights the potential for integrating advanced AI technologies into SC practices. Overall, this study underscores the importance of leveraging AI in navigating the complexities of modern market demands. By improving demand forecasting accuracy, organizations can better optimize their SC

processes, ultimately leading to enhanced operational efficiency and competitive advantage.

Keywords: supply chains, demand forecasting, artificial intelligence, neural networks, operational efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

Supply chains (SCs) are world wide networks comprising from various companies and facilities that work together to convert raw materials into finished products and deliver these products to end customers. These networks facilitate multiple flows—physical, financial, and informational—among different firms. As the global economy evolves, SCs are becoming more complex and expansive, necessitating the involvement of highly skilled professionals who can effectively manage and optimize these processes (Mirčetić, 2018).

Effective SC design and management are essential for optimizing performance. The SC management framework includes three core elements: (1) SC structures, (2) business processes, and (3) control components. Each element directly ties to the SC's objectives, especially in meeting end-user requirements while adhering to critical business dimensions influenced by market performance, often measured through key performance indicators. In today's competitive landscape, the rivalry has shifted from individual organizations to entire SCs. Thus, effective SC management has emerged as a crucial strategy for gaining a competitive edge and enhancing organizational performance, with logistics serving as a vital tool for achieving strategic advantages (Mirčetić et al., 2022). Accordingly, we have reached the point where SC experts need to have broad knowledge from different area in order to tackle with the current SC issues.

To address the challenges posed by modern SCs, experts require formal training about knowledge and skills from diverse fields, particularly logistics, information technology, and economics. Bearing in mind that each of the named disciplines is the area for itself and requires a lot of effort to overcome, it is clear that modern SC experts have hard task in front of them. Two additional important aspects of daily function of SC are tactical and operational decisions. Accordingly, tactical and operational decisions focus on the modalities and rules for executing specific logistics processes.

All these levels of decision-making present opportunities for employing various analytical tools (known as business analytics) to assist in decision-making (Zhu et al., 2018). As a powerful emerging tool, artificial intelligence (AI) holds enormous potential to enhance existing processes and can significantly contribute to various aspects of SC management. However, it remains unclear to what extent AI models can assist in SCs and in which specific segments.

The theme of this paper is precisely that: it attempts to apply an AI model to one of the key processes in SC management—demand forecasting—and explore the potential benefits and opportunities it may provide. The COVID-19 pandemic has

further complicated forecasting efforts, with traditional models struggling to accurately reflect the current market situation.

2. THE RISE OF SUPPLY CHAIN ANALYTICS

Firms face significant pressure to enhance SC planning and performance due to rising uncertainty and competition (Mircetic et al., 2022). The need for continuous improvement of SC performance necessitates an analytical performance measurement system. Given the multitude and diversity of logistics and SC processes, a vast amount of data is utilized to assess performance. This includes geographic, temporal, and quantitative factors related to goods, transportation means, handling assets, warehouse capacities, and workforce.

Data generated from internal operations and interactions with suppliers and customers can reveal minor adjustments that lead to substantial efficiency gains and cost savings. In essence, the volume of data within each SC is rapidly increasing, sourced from various data points, business processes, and IT systems. As data volume and complexity grow, so too does the difficulty and time required to analyse it and extract insights. Consequently, determining, monitoring, and enhancing logistics and SC performance has become more intricate, involving numerous processes such as measure identification, target definition, planning, communication, monitoring, reporting, and feedback. Traditional approaches are no longer sufficient for SC decision-making and management.

Accordingly, there is a rising interest in business analytics, often referred to as supply chain analytics (SCA), which utilizes data and quantitative tools to enhance operational performance, typically measured by metrics like order fulfilment and flexibility (Nikoličić et al., 2019). Although the concept of analytics in SCs is not new—having been employed in various quantitative techniques and modelling methods in manufacturing for some time—the recent surge in interest in SCA is accompanied by new challenges and opportunities in both business and information technology contexts (Srinivasan & Swink, 2018).

These challenges include managing extensive data volumes (such as data availability and quality) and navigating environmental uncertainties. When applied effectively, SCA, especially its demand forecasting process can significantly impact various areas within the SC, yielding substantial benefits in logistics performance, including improved planning and scheduling, enhanced responsiveness, efficient demand planning, optimized order management, refined inventory control, and more effective replenishment planning (Syntetos et al., 2016).

There are three different type of the SCA solutions: descriptive, predictive and prescriptive. Each of the solution has its place and merits in optimizing SCs. In this paper we are dealing with predictive analytics. Predictive analytics uses historical data to determine the probable future outcome. Predictive analytics in supply chains derives demand forecasts from past data and answers the questions related to what will be happening or what is likely to happen (Tiwari et al. 2018).

3. CASE STUDY

The case study is conducted on the example of the food industry, for one of the world leaders in ham production. The consortium is located in Italy and includes around 50,000 workers. The motivation for developing and testing the AI tool for optimizing the SCA activities was the COVID-19 pandemic since it distorted the supply chains in the observed industry. Accordingly, the pandemic had several detrimental effects, but among them, the most problematic is shifting and changing the consumption patterns of the products on the market. This change put the challenge on a traditional way of organizing the procurement, production, storage and distribution processes. Therefore, to tackle a given problem there is an urgent need for a given company to fully restore the understanding of the market conditions and situations which are taking place.

As an illustration of a given market situation, Figure 1 represents the demand pattern for the top-selling company product (pre-sliced hams).

Figure 1 The demand for the pre-sliced salami in the period of 2015-2022.

Source: Authors

There is a notable change in the hams demand from the start of the Corona pandemic. The first lockdown in Italy was 2020-02-21, after which demand for presliced hams erupted and reached a historical maximum. The demand was constantly trending, reaching the highest peak on 2021-12-20, with 21280 sliced pieces sold in one day. The daily demand shows highly volatile behaviour, therefore aggregation of the demand through different time horizons (weekly, monthly, etc) demonstrate a clear galloping demand trend.

4. BUILDING BLOCKS OF PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS

To unveil the mystery of future market demand and answer the question of whether the current demand patterns are just temporary changes related to a pandemic or are now a new reality, several algorithms were implemented. Besides in this paper, we have put a special emphasis on testing the possibilities and performance of AI

algorithms in SC settings. As a representative of AI algorithms in this paper the feed-forward neural networks (NN) are chosen. In a real application to the company processes several other AI models are created, most notably generative AI chatbot, but due to the company confidentiality regulations it is not possible to demonstrate the chatbot publicly. For decision making process chatbot takes outputs from the NN which represents its core algorithm for suggesting decisions to company logistic experts. Accordingly, in this paper we presented the NN and tested it against state of the art Facebook's Prophet model and autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA).

ARIMA is widely used and tested algorithm in the SC settings (Mirčetić et al., 2017; Mirčetić et al., 2016), while for Prophet and NN there are no significant researchers which investigate the pros and cons of application in the context SC settings. The ARIMA has complex structure consists of several other models and statistical principles. The basic driver and the backbone of this ARIMA framework is in the combination of three processes (models) autoregression, moving average and differencing. The general form of representing an ARIMA model is by using the notation (p,d,q) , where: p – represents the order of the autoregressive model; d – represents the degree of differencing in the given model; and q – represents the order of the moving average model. The ARIMA model can be expressed in its expanded form as follows in Equation 1:

$$y_t = c + (\varphi_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + \varphi_p y_{t-p}) + (\theta_1 e_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q e_{t-q}) + e_t; \quad (1)$$

$$y_t - y_{t-1} = c + \varphi_1 (y_{t-1} - y_{t-2}) + \dots + \varphi_p (y_{t-p} - y_{t-p-1}) + (\theta_1 B e_t + \dots + \frac{\theta_q e_{t-q}}{\theta_q B^q} + e_t)$$

$$y_t - B y_t = c + \varphi_1 (y_{t-1} - B y_{t-1}) + \dots + \varphi_p (y_{t-p} - B y_{t-p}) + (e_t (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q))$$

$$(1 - B) y_t = c + \varphi_1 (1 - B) (y_{t-1}) + \dots + \varphi_p (1 - B) y_{t-p} + e_t (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q)$$

$$(1 - B) y_t = c + \varphi_1 (1 - B) B y_t + \dots + \varphi_p (1 - B) B^p y_t + e_t (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q)$$

$$\underbrace{(1 - B)^d y_t}_{\substack{\text{differencing} \\ \text{d. degree}}} \cdot \underbrace{(1 - \varphi_1 B - \dots - \varphi_p B^p)}_{AR(p)} = c + \underbrace{e_t (1 + \theta_1 B + \dots + \theta_q B^q)}_{MA(q)}$$

The y_t represents the demand in the time t ; y_t' represent differencing time series data $y_t' = y_t - y_{t-1}$; $B^m y_t = y_{t-m}$ is short hand notation for lagged values; $e_{t-1}, e_{t-2}, \dots, e_{t-q}$ represents residuals and $\Phi(z)$ and $\theta(z)$ are polynomials of order p and q respectively (p represents the number of past time steps considered in the autoregression, while q represents the number of past residuals used for forecasting). Key question in using ARIMA model is selection of an appropriate model order, that is the values p, q, d . If d is known, we can select the orders p, q via an information criterion such as the Akaike information criterion (AIC) or Bayesian information criterion (BIC) (Hyndman & Khandakar, 2007):

$$AIC = -2 \log(L) + 2(p + q + k); BIC = N \log\left(\frac{SSE}{N}\right) + (k + 2)(N) \quad (2)$$

where $k = 1$ if $c \neq 0$ and 0 otherwise, and L is the maximized likelihood of the model fitted to the differenced data. SSE is sum of squared errors. N is the number of observations used for estimation and k is the number of predictors in the model.

One of the most advanced and commonly used models in practice is Prophet (Facebook Prophet, 2023). Prophet was developed by Facebook for internal use, designed to handle their specific data structures and forecasting needs. Prophet is a forecasting procedure is very fast and provides completely automated forecasts that can be tuned by hand by data scientists and analysts. Generally it is a procedure for forecasting time series data based on an additive model where non-linear trends are fitted with seasonal effects from different frequencies. It works best with time series with strong seasonality and long history. Prophet is robust to missing data and shifts in the trend, and typically handles outliers well (Facebook Prophet, 2023). The code is open-source software released by Facebook’s Core Data Science team. It is available for download on CRAN and PyPI. The code is regularly maintained and updated. This accessibility is one of the reasons why several companies have adopted it for their own forecasting purposes. Prophet is an additive model designed to capture non-linear trends by incorporating yearly, weekly, and daily seasonal patterns, along with holiday effects. It performs best with data that exhibit strong seasonal behavior and include multiple seasons of historical observations. Prophet can be viewed as a form of nonlinear regression model structured as (Equation 3):

$$y_t = g(t) + s(t) + h(t) + \epsilon_t. \quad (3)$$

Where $g(t)$ describes a piecewise-linear trend (or “growth term”), $s(t)$ describes the various seasonal patterns, $h(t)$ captures the holiday effects, and ϵ_t is a white noise error term. The Prophet is used in many applications across Facebook for producing reliable forecasts for planning and goal setting. Facebook found it to perform better than any other approach in the majority of cases. The Prophet procedure includes many possibilities for users to tweak and adjust forecasts. It is possible to use human-interpretable parameters to improve your forecast by adding your domain knowledge. Since its release in 2017, it has remained a popular tool for forecasting time series, especially in business and planning contexts where we want to model human activity and consumption (e.g. website traffic, video hours watched) (Duong, 2023). Prophet’s main advantages and popularity lie in the fact that it allows for automatic yet editable forecasts with human-interpretable parameters, and most notably, it is easily applicable to business analytics use cases.

The NN models offer a wide range of possibilities, but for the purposes of this research, we have narrowed the focus to feed-forward networks with a single hidden layer. The NN is represented in Equation (4).

$$z_j = \sum_{i=1}^n w_{i,j} x_i + b_j \quad (4)$$

With activation function in each node of the network:

$$s(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

Generally, the NN can be understood as a nonlinear transformations of input variables. Also, they are a type of machine learning model inspired by the structure of the human brain, designed to recognize patterns and relationships in data. They consist of layers of interconnected nodes (usually in practice referred as "neurons") that process input data and pass it through the network to produce an output. Each connection between neurons has a weight, which adjusts as the network learns from data, enabling it to make predictions or classifications (Hastie et al., 2009).

A key concept in neural networks is that they perform non-linear transformations of inputs. In a simple linear model, the relationship between the input and output is a straight line—(linear regression), where expert multiply inputs by weights and sum them to predict the outcome. However, real-world data often exhibits complex, non-linear relationships that can't be captured by a simple straight line (almost every business or industry settings). This is where neural networks excel: they apply non-linear activation functions (such as the sigmoid or ReLU function) at each neuron, which allows the model to capture intricate patterns in the data. By stacking multiple layers, NNs can extract more abstract features from the data, allowing the model to learn hierarchical representations. The first layer might transform the inputs in a simple way, but as the data moves through the hidden layers, these transformations become more complex and non-linear. This enables the NN to approximate almost any function, making it powerful for tasks like image recognition, speech processing, and complex business predictions.

NN are very powerful algorithms, but the main issue with their application is their tendency to overfit the data and consequently extrapolate patterns into the future that were specific only to the given training data. Therefore, it is crucial to follow proper procedures during model fitting and testing (more details on this will be provided in the upcoming chapters regarding cross-validation).

4.1 Data characteristics

The data presented in Figure 1 covers the period from 2015 to 2022, with daily frequency. The decomposition of the data reveals a very weak seasonal pattern, dominated primarily by the trend (Figure 2). The remainder, or unexplained portion, is also significant, indicating the strong presence of random demand for the given product. The dominating patterns in a observed demand are trend and random part.

Figure 2 The decomposition of pre-sliced hams demand data on a trend, seasonal components and the random effect

Source: Authors

There was a significant shift in demand patterns starting in 2020, coinciding with the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent lockdowns. During this period, customers began consuming significantly more pre-sliced ham from a particular producer than had ever been observed in the past (Figure 3 – first panel). As it can be seen in the second panel of Figure 3, there has been a significant increase of demand. The second panel represents the demand data aggregated to the monthly level starting from 2020. Additionally, the third panel shows that monthly demand values have been above average from 2020 onwards, for all months. This indicates that there is a significant change in a consumption of the observed product in the market.

Figure 3 The comparative view of different time aggregations of the data (first panel-weekly, second – monthly, third – demand and historical averages per each month)

Source: Authors

This surge in demand was a surprising effect of the lockdown, as customers spent more time at home and consumed more food than usual. The key question for the company was what would happen once the pandemic ended. Was this new demand pattern just a temporary spike, or would it become the new normal? Moreover, to efficiently manage the entire logistic chain such as setting production rates the company needed accurate demand forecasts of one year ahead.

In this paper, we will test various models and use the forecasts from the best-performing model as inputs for scheduling subsequent logistics activities.

4.2 Training and testing data

In various applications, NN have demonstrated remarkable performance (Mirčetić et al., 2016; Rostami-Tabar & Mircetic, 2023). However, they are also prone to overfitting and learning patterns that exist only within the training set. Therefore, special care was taken during the training process to avoid overfitting, with the data being divided into several training and test sets using cross-validation. The cross-validation was conducted across five different training (encompassing different time horizons) and test sets (always one year), each covering different time horizons:

- Training set 1: January 2015 – December 2017; test set 1: January 2018–December 2018
- Training set 2: January 2015 – December 2018; test set 2: January 2019–December 2019
- Training set 3: January 2015 – December 2019; test set 3: January 2020–December 2020
- Training set 4: January 2015 – December 2020; test set 4: January 2021–December 2021

- Training set 5: January 2015 – December 2021; test set 5: January 2022–December 2022

With each iteration, the training set is expanded by incorporating an additional year of data. The test set always includes only one year of data, and with each iteration, new data is introduced. The reason for using a one-year time horizon in the test set is that the company requires one-year-ahead forecasts for operational optimization. Therefore, the goal is to train the algorithm to perform well over that specific time horizon.

4.3 Evaluation of predictive algorithms

In order to compare the given models we have used the following forecasting metrics:

- root mean scaled squared error (RMSSE)
- mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and
- mean absolute scaled error (MASE) forecasting errors.

The metrics are presented in the Equation 5.

$$RMSSE = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n q_j^2}; MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^n [e_t]; MASE = \sum_{t=1}^n |q_j|; \quad (5)$$

$$e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t;$$

$$q_j^2 = \frac{e_j^2}{\frac{1}{T-m} \sum_{t=m+1}^T (y_t - y_{t-m})^2}; q_j = \frac{e_j}{\frac{1}{T-m} \sum_{t=2}^T |y_t - y_{t-1}|}$$

Where y_t represents the real outcome of the observed demand, \hat{y}_t is the forecasted value, m is the number of seasonal periods, e_j is the j -th residual, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

The performance of the models for each forecasting step is represented in Figure 4. This figure demonstrates that all observed models yielded good results across each forecasting step, with no instances where one model significantly outperformed the others. Although, it is notable that NN model constantly has lower error in almost all forecasting steps, measured by RMSSE and MASE forecasting errors. The first and the last panel demonstrate this. In a second panel the situation is not so clear and models are intertwined, making it hard to see which one had the best performance according to the MAPE.

Figure 4 The h-steps ahead forecasting performance of predictive algorithms (first panel - RMSSE, second panel - MAPE, third panel - MASE)

Source: Authors

The summary report of the models performance is presented in Table 1. The results are in alignment with the insights from Figure 4. The performances of the models are very close by and all three demonstrated good performance on a hard and challenging data. All observed metrics are relevant, making it difficult to determine which one is the most important. The use case for the forecasts dictates which metrics are more significant. Generally, in supply chains, logistic utility metrics (such as inventory costs, in-stock and out-of-stock levels, and total logistics costs) should also be considered, and the impact of forecasts on the company’s logistics performance should be investigated. In this research, we conducted such an analysis; however, due to the confidential nature of the company data, the results are not presented in the table.

Table 1 Comparative review of different predictive algorithms

	RMSSE	MAPE	MASE
NN	0.840	41.9	0.970
Prophet	1.07	38.8	1.11
ARIMA	1.08	41.2	1.15

Source: Authors

Nevertheless, the results reveal that the NN model was the most accurate in two out of three metrics (RMSSE and MASE), while MAPE was the exception. Therefore, the NN model has been chosen as the most accurate, and its future forecasts will be implemented in the subsequent logistics processes.

4.4 Future forecasts

Considering that the NN model demonstrated the best performance, we utilized it to predict future demand in the observed supply chain for a one-year horizon. Figure 5 displays the model forecasts along with 80% and 95% prediction intervals. The model indicates a sustained increase in demand following the pandemic. The reasons for this projected rise could be numerous, and it is essential for managers to explore these potential factors at the strategic level of the company.

Figure 5 The forecasts from the NN model for the next 12 steps, accompanied by 80% and 95% prediction intervals, indicate a sustained increase in demand throughout 2023

Source: Authors

5. CONCLUSION

Uncertainty surrounding market conditions and customer demand for products is one of the fundamental challenges in optimizing SCs. If demand could be predicted with certainty, SC processes would essentially be reduced to scheduling activities. In this paper, we focused on this specific challenge and explored the potential application of NN in the SCA. One of the main task of SCA is the demand forecasting for SC. We tested idea can NN improve SC demand forecasting performances, bearing in the

mind that NN serve as a foundational component of AI technology, renowned for their ability to learn complex patterns and relationships within data. They have consistently demonstrated their effectiveness across a wide range of challenging tasks, from image recognition to natural language processing. By leveraging the capabilities of NN, we aim to enhance the accuracy of demand forecasts, ultimately contributing to more efficient SC optimization.

The results demonstrated significant potential for the current and future development of NN in the context of SC. The NN model outperformed traditionally tested methods, such as ARIMA, which is widely used for time series forecasting, as well as Facebook's Prophet model, recognized as one of today's state-of-the-art forecasting techniques. This superior performance highlights the NN's ability to capture complex patterns in demand data that may be overlooked by more conventional models. As the SC landscape continues to evolve, integrating NN into demand forecasting practices could lead to more accurate predictions and improved operational efficiencies.

Based on the encouraging results from this paper, we believe there is significant potential for further implementation of AI algorithms in SCs. In our future research, we plan to explore the application of AI in other SC processes. Notably, there is a literature gap regarding the application of AI in inventory management, particularly related to connection to demand forecasting. Therefore, we intend to investigate the performance of reinforcement learning algorithms in inventory management settings, with the primary aim of minimizing inventory costs and enhancing customer service levels.

In order to achieve a more significant application of AI in SCs, it is necessary to turn attention to several open questions that require careful consideration. Developing effective AI solutions demands significant time and expertise, as organizations must invest in building robust models that can adapt to the complexities of SC dynamics. Additionally, the necessary technological infrastructure and equipment must be established to support these advanced systems. Also, there is a need for opening the special designated place for AI analysts of SC processes. This position has to be separated from performing everyday logistics and SC activates and focused only on AI analytics. Ethical considerations also play a crucial role, as companies must navigate issues related to data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the impact of automation on employment. Addressing these challenges will be essential for realizing the full potential of AI in enhancing supply chain efficiency and resilience.

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DIGITALIZATION FOR THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION LOGISTICS BUSINESS

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Abstract

Logistics business is currently experiencing a significant transformation propelled by rapid digitalization. In the digital age, applying information technologies (IT) in logistics is important to increase productivity, transfer information, and deliver faster orders to customers. Nowadays, the interest in the application of digital technologies possibilities is growing. This trend has prompted an extensive examination of the theoretical potential and practical challenges within the industry. This comprehensive review emphasizes practical applications, deeply exploring the application of IT to improve logistics functions. Although many researchers have studied digitalization's impact on logistics, the studies have a rare emphasize the digital and sustainable transformation of the logistics sector. Such evident from bibliometric analysis. The authors suggested three-stage methodology used for researching data of IT applications. According to methodology, statistical analysis on the application of digital technologies was performed among the EU-27 countries' logistics businesses using six indicators. The research results show which indicators are overcoming the EU average and which have to be improved. Among the countries Bulgaria, Spain, and Malta have to improve their performance, seeking to have a better competitive advantage. The authors also examined how sustainable ICT usage (hardware and software) practices are applied in the logistics sector. These empirical findings greatly enhance the theoretical framework, offering practical implications and underscoring the critical need for logistics firms to seamlessly integrate digital technologies into their operational structures. In conclusion, with the logistics landscape moving towards digital and sustainable transformation, businesses must adeptly navigate and wholeheartedly embrace these solutions to maintain competitiveness. The implementation of digital technology and the crucial interconnections facilitated by advanced technologies are expected to positively influence the environment.

Keywords: Digitalisation, logistics business, EU-27 countries, sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION

In the policy program of the European Digital Decade until 2030, the guidelines for European digital transformation include:

- 75% of European Union (EU) logistics enterprises use the cloud, big data or artificial intelligence;
- More than 90% of small and medium-sized logistics firms (SMEs) attain at least a basic level of digital sophistication (EU Commissioner for Logistics Management, 2017).

At the EU level, the integration that is restricted and incomplete of modern digital technologies in logistics companies is recognized; therefore, it is necessary to conduct research and identify digital technologies that contribute to sustainability and increasing the competitive advantage of enterprises providing logistics services.

The plan involves using digital technologies to enable logistics companies to share data and communicate effectively, thereby enhancing their competitive advantage in international supply chains.

The adoption of digital technologies in supply chains facilitates enterprises meet the new requirements of their customers, increase demand, and seek more efficiency. Digitalization could help deliver products faster and provide more distribution, accuracy, efficiency, and flexibility in organized physical product flow. According to Statista (2024), the adoption of digital technologies in logistics and supply chains is increasing. The average spend per employee on supply chain digitalization is projected to reach €5.20 billion in 2024. Due to the expansion of e-commerce the management of physical functions require at least one application of digital technologies in supply chain. In addition, blockchain can increase supply chain transparency. 2019, the technology uptake rate was only eight percent, but it could rise to 45 percent by 2030. Forty percent of supply chain experts say they have already integrated cloud computing and storage technologies into their business. Over the next five years, online inventory and optimization tools will make up the largest part of the supply chain's corporate acceptance list, but not clear how they contribute to sustainability.

This paper addresses several key aspects, such as the application of digital technologies and their impact on sustainability.

The automation and digitalization of procedures associated with the movement of products are termed digital logistics. The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) solutions has reduced logistical costs by 20% through error-free resource optimization. Technological advancements are propelling the growth and adoption of digital logistics solutions. The IoT has transformed logistics operations by facilitating real-time data collection and analysis, facilitating proactive decision-making and process resource optimization. Big Data Analytics has assisted companies in extracting valuable insights, identifying patterns, and making data-driven decisions to optimize routes, predict demand, and manage inventory efficiently. Cloud computing has reshaped the digital logistics landscape by offering cost-effective solutions. In response to growing market demand, digital logistics

solutions can provide eco-friendly practices, such as alternative fuel-powered transportation, optimized fuel-efficient route planning, and packaging optimization.

The push towards sustainable and green logistics can be achieved with digital logistics, presenting an opportunity for the digital logistics market.

This paper aims to investigate the following research questions:

- What are the trends in applying environmentally friendly practices in logistics?
- How can integrating ICT systems in logistics effectively enhance environmental sustainability practices and operational efficiencies?

The increasing revenue in the Supply Chain Management Software market does not specify what proportion is attributed to green practices. The article analyzes both software and hardware technologies.

The paper comprises several sections. The next section includes a literature review and presents the results of the bibliometric analysis, followed by the methodology in the third section, which examines the implementation of sustainable practices in the logistics sector through statistical analysis. Finally, the paper concludes with discussions in the fifth chapter and conclusions in the sixth chapter.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's fast-evolving logistics sector, the blend of digital technologies offers new ways to streamline operations, enhance environmental impact, and gain a competitive advantage within the industry.

The contribution of the logistics sector to the economy of the European Union member states is obvious. About 10 million people work in this sector. Employees make up more than 5.2% of the total workforce, and the contribution of logistics to the Gross domestic product (GDP) is almost 5% (European Commission, 2022).

By 2050, the volume of logistics operations is expected to increase by more than 50%, and the application of digital technologies will be even more relevant and vital for the success and survival of companies whose primary activity is logistics (EU Commissioner for Logistics, 2017).

According to a McKinsey (2023) report, digitization in logistics can help increase efficiency by up to 20-25 percent. Such a result is caused by the logistics business users' orientation and the services it provides to use the advantages provided by digital technologies (Eurostat, 2022). According to a survey by Forbes Insights, 65 percent of logistics companies recognize the transition to a digital business model to be competitive in the digital age.

The adoption of digital technologies in the logistics industry enables companies to share orders, resources, and information. By implementing digital technologies in logistics, it becomes feasible to decrease the use of material resources and energy while enhancing the sector's capacity, thereby increasing the competitiveness of logistics businesses.

Some researchers focus on sustainable logistics planning strategies (Brandenburg et al., 2014; Qaiser et al., 2017), green logistics, and sustainability (Ren

et al., 2020; Dey et al., 2011; Martins et al., 2020), as well as the sustainable transportation of freight (Nenni et al., 2019; Álvarez and de la Calle, 2011).

Recent studies have concentrated on the adoption of new technologies such as big data analytics (Chalmeta and Santos-de-León, 2020), blockchain (Reddy et al., 2021), artificial intelligence (AI) (Riahi et al., 2021; Tirkolaee et al., 2021), Internet of Things (IoT) (Tijan et al., 2019), and additive manufacturing (AM) (Khorram Niaki and Nonino, 2017). These advancements contribute to the evolution of Logistics 4.0 (Wang, 2016).

Despite extensive research on Industry 4.0 and sustainable practices (Roblek et al., 2020), gaps remain in comprehending the challenges of digital transformation in sustainable logistics (Sun et al., 2022; Toktaş-Palut, 2022).

While efforts have primarily focused on technology deployment, few studies comprehensively address sustainable logistics business models and economic benefits, highlighting a critical research gap (Karakikes and Nathanail, 2017).

The rapid transformation of the logistics sector through digitalization has proven to be a key factor in opening up a competitive advantage in today's global and dynamic market.

This transition to digitalization will bring many benefits, such as better access to information, optimized logistics approaches, real-time data collection, better inventory management, and greater transparency (Henke et al., 2020; Pirogova et al., 2020). With the rise of smart logistics and smart supply chains, technologies like cloud computing, artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things are enhancing automation and transitioning towards semi-autonomy, facilitating information sharing among organizations (Chen et al., 2019). However, to reap the benefits of these integrated systems, organizations need to align the implementation of their internal technologies with the pace of external stakeholders. For this transformation to succeed, companies must invest in new technologies, carefully control digital technologies, and understand the opportunities and interactions inherent in logistics processes (Albrecht et al., 2023).

This literature review reviews the increasing digitization of logistics, such as integrating digital technologies into logistics, which is essential for industrial growth (Osmolski et al., 2020). These technologies can transform traditional processes, simplify supply chains, and increase business success (Calatayud et al., 2019). Digitalization is essential for logistics companies to ensure a busy and flexible customer experience (Helmke, 2022; Kuteyi et al., 2022). Therefore, effectively managing both the Green and Digital Twin transitions is essential for achieving sustainability (Muench et al., 2022).

Digital twin technology provides a risk-free scenario analysis through an advisory strategy formulation platform for industrial applications stakeholders, establishing it as a crucial technological tool in Industry 4.0 (Hofmann et al., 2017).

a) Various real-time industrial challenges encompass optimizing multi-mode transportation networks (Nikolopoulou et al., 2012), (b) scenario planning and optimization of truck route networks (Gutierrez-Franco et al., 2021), (c) automated rack storage and retrieval, (d) forklift route optimization and throughput, (Alyahya et al., 2016).

In earlier research, Chen et al. (2020) proposed that integrating green practices could promote and facilitate the adoption of digital technologies for environmental sustainability. Digitalization holds significant potential for enhancing operational performance (Liao and Wang, 2021; Tripathi et al., 2021) and advancing environmental sustainability (Lobo Mesquita et al., 2021; Touriki et al., 2021). By integrating with existing frameworks, digitalization can enhance both operational and environmental performance (Leong et al., 2020; Amjad et al., 2020; Touriki et al., 2021).

When constructing frameworks, Tabak et al. (2012) recommend that researchers recognize the substantial overlap between existing and new frameworks to ensure that the new frameworks address gaps in existing knowledge. The studies encapsulated in table 1 demonstrate a multifaceted approach to integrating digital technologies within logistics to promote sustainability.

Table 1 Overview impact of digital technologies on Logistics

Reference	Research Method	Technology	Impact on the Logistics Sector	Impact on Sustainability	Research Focus and Perspectives
Wang (2016); Zaychenko et al. (2021)	Bibliometric analysis	IoT	Real-time data collection, enhanced visibility, proactive decision-making	Reduced fuel consumption, lower emissions	Integration of IoT for operational efficiency and environmental impact
Wang (2016); Liao et al. (2021)	Content analysis	Big Data Analytics	Optimization of routes, predictive maintenance, data-driven decisions	Efficient resource use, reduced waste	Use of big data for predictive analytics in logistics
Alyahya et al. (2016)	Horizon scan	Radiofrequency identification (RFID)	Enhanced tracking and inventory management	Minimized resource wastage, improved recycling processes	Application of RFID in inventory and its sustainability benefits
Feroz et al. (2021) Hofmann & Rüsich (2017)	Bibliometric analysis	AI & ML	Automation of processes, error-free resource optimization	Energy-efficient operations, reduced emissions	Role of AI and ML in logistics automation and sustainability
European Commission (2022)	Content analysis	Cloud Computing	Scalable and flexible logistics solutions	Decreased energy usage with optimized server utilization	Cloud computing's impact on logistics efficiency and environmental benefits
Muench et al. (2022)	Horizon scan	Digital Twin Technology	Predictive and prescriptive decision-making	Risk-free scenario analysis for environmental strategies	Use of digital twins for risk-free scenario analysis in logistics

Esmailian et al. (2020)	Bibliometric analysis	Blockchain	Enhanced transparency and security	Improved traceability of sustainable practices	Transparency and traceability using blockchain in logistics
Helmke (2022); Alyahya et al. (2016)	Content analysis	Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)	Increased efficiency in warehouse operations	Lower energy consumption reduced operational costs	Efficiency improvements with AGVs in warehouses
Chalmeta & Santos-Deleón (2020)	Horizon scan	Green Logistics Software	Eco-friendly route planning, packaging optimization	Reduced carbon footprint, efficient resource utilization	Software tools for optimizing logistics for sustainability

Source: Authors' work

In Table 1, researchers like Wang (2016), Zaychenko et al. (2021) and Alyahya et al. (2016) have extensively analyzed the capabilities of technologies such as IoT, RFID, and AGVs to enhance operational efficiencies while reducing environmental impacts. Furthermore, the role of advanced data analytics and artificial intelligence in proactive maintenance and resource optimization has been highlighted by Feroz et al. (2021) and Hofmann & Rüsç (2017).

Additionally, the significance of cloud computing and blockchain in ensuring scalable solutions and transparency in logistics operations has been brought forth by the European Commission (2022) and Esmailian et al. (2020). As discussed by Muench et al. (2022) the emerging concept of digital twin technology showcases the potential for risk-free scenario analysis, crucial for sustainable logistics planning.

This comprehensive analysis underscores the need for continued research into the intersection of digitalization and green practices as noted by Chen et al. (2020) and Liao & Wang (2021). Integrating digital technologies with sustainable practices is essential for enhancing both operational performance and environmental sustainability in logistics. Future research should focus on bridging existing gaps, particularly the environmental benefits of digitalization in logistics, to develop robust frameworks to guide the industry towards sustainable growth.

Therefore, frameworks illustrating the linkage between digitalization and environmental sustainability (ES) were reviewed and synthesized to pinpoint critical gaps essential for crafting new frameworks: a) The connections between digitalization and green practices need more research. b) Very few studies have focused on environmental benefits.

The objective of this study is twofold: to analyze and assess the incorporation of digital technologies in logistics with a focus on improving environmental sustainability. This involves examining how technologies like IoT, AI, and digital twins impact operational efficiencies and environmental outcomes in the logistics industry. Second, the study aims to identify challenges and opportunities associated with implementing these technologies and to develop frameworks that can guide sustainable practices in logistics.

Additionally, the study aims to explore how digital transformation is reshaping the logistics industry, offering a pathway to gain a competitive advantage in today's

dynamic market (Parfenov et al., 2021; Zaychenko et al., 2021). The adoption of digital technologies in this transformation offers numerous benefits, such as improved access to information, optimization methods, real-time data collection, enhanced inventory control, and increased transparency (Hoberg et al., 2017).

The findings highlight the transformative impact of digitalization on logistics, emphasizing its potential to revolutionize industry practices and drive sustainable growth. Concerted efforts are needed to overcome implementation challenges and leverage digital innovations to foster a more resilient and eco-friendly logistics ecosystem.

2.1 Bibliometric maps construction and presentation from the literature review on IT applications in logistics and supply chain

The bibliometric study aims to investigate IT applications in logistics and supply chain management. This study reviews scientific papers that specifically address the application of IT in logistics and supply chain operations. The bibliometric data collection during research was gathered using three steps: data gathering facilitated by pertinent keywords, data formatting, and data analysis using appropriate tools.

The data has been systematically filtered based on language, and only English-language articles were selected for further analysis. In the initial phase, the author focused on document types to ensure the period of the publication of articles. The data collection framework is illustrated in Figure 1.

The study employs a multi-stage methodology to achieve a conceptual understanding of the phenomena. Initially, knowledge on the topic is collected from publications, utilizing several methods to reach this goal. Firstly, a bibliometric analysis is performed to study and analyze the selected literature. Secondly, the bibliometric maps were created based on the retrieved dataset. The author conducted the bibliometric study and identified studies related to IT applications in logistics and supply chain topics.

Throughout the construction of bibliometric maps, the following methodological guidelines are used:

- The VOSviewer software was used to analyze 169 articles included in the Web of Science database for the period 2021-2024, and in the end, 30 articles were analyzed.
- The analysis of bibliographic references helps identify related words and groups.
- The bibliometric maps are established based on peer-reviewed studies based on the coexistence of nouns mentioned in scientific papers' titles.

After searching for articles published on the topic, the authors created bibliographic maps and clusters.

VOSviewer uses VOC mapping technology that looks for "matches." By default, VOSviewer arranges nodes into cluster networks. A cluster comprises a group of nodes that are closely interlinked. Each node in the network is directly linked to the cluster. The separate parameter determines the number of clusters. The higher the value of this parameter, the greater the number of clusters. In the visualization of bibliometric networks, VOSviewer employs colors to indicate the clusters with which nodes are associated. Waltman et al. (2010) examine the clustering method of

VOSviewer. This technology necessitates an intelligent algorithm for local traffic management, as demonstrated by Waltman et al. (2013).

The bibliographic maps (see Figure 2) have specific characteristics. First, the circles on the map are color-coded to denote various clusters and highlight closely related keywords. Different colours of circles on bibliometric maps separate clusters to show the keywords 'logistics', 'digitalization', 'sustainability', and selected authors in management theory. The lines on the map depict the relationships between keywords and the strength of their connections. The spacing between words indicates the strength of these connections.

Here are the results of bibliometric studies that present clusters that summarize the findings based on the words used to form the clusters.

For presentation purposes, the author obtained results only in specific sets.

Figure 2 The map was created under "logistic" and "digitalization" and "sustainability"

Source: Authors' work

The constructed bibliometric map from the literature sources consists of six clusters. The keywords associated with each cluster, formed through the algorithm, are also presented in the figure.

- The first cluster primarily focuses on articles related to artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain technology, the internet, and WMS.
- The second cluster features articles discussing the logistics sector, transportation, digitalization, and sustainable goals.
- The third cluster revolves around the common themes of smart logistics, planning, and time management.
- The fourth cluster includes articles discussing digital solutions, sustainable green logistics, and the sustainable supply chain.
- The sixth cluster discusses business sustainability and logistics digitalization.

Each cluster formed from the literature sources represents a specific research area exploring key themes. The second of the six clusters focuses on articles related to logistics, digitalization, and sustainability.

3. METHODOLOGY FOR STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF ICT BY THE EU-27 TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE COMPANIES

Further the study aims to figure out what practices of ICT (hardware and software) applications in the EU transportation and storage sectors companies helping to achieve sustainability.

Various stakeholders make decisions in transportation and storage companies on which ICT to apply, how to apply them and what to do after the ICT became technologically old:

- ICT managers which think about the integration of ICT into correct technological park landscape;
 - Operations managers, which thinks about business process automation.
 - End users, which select ICT based on user-friendly environment, which support easy fulfillment of operations, aspects.
 - External IT service providers which consult on the implementation of ICT.
- However, it is evident that the sustainability manager is not involved into the practices of ICT applications and that could mean that with digitalization business could not cover sustainability aspects.

The authors suggested three level methodology which present connections between digitalization and sustainability (as specified in Table 2), which are important for ICT applications in transportation and storage companies.

Table 2 Three-level methodology highlighting the digital and sustainable transformation in the transportation and storage sectors of EU-27 countries

Level	Application of ICT	Description of links to sustainability	The method to revise results of the application	Links with digital and sustainable transformation
1 st level: data collection	Data collection from Eurostat database and cases about the companies to gather ICT application aspects in transportation and storage business across EU-27 countries.	By collecting comprehensive data, the study ensures that all aspects of ICT application, including its environmental impact, are identified. This is the first step in identifying how ICT applications can contribute to or hinder sustainability.	Data is filtered systematically, excluding micro-companies and ensuring relevance through the appropriate timeframe.	Data collection is performed to establish a foundational understanding of how ICT applications influence sustainability in the logistics sector.

2 nd level: data revision	The application of ICT is used to refine and benchmark data based on digital intensity levels and sustainability indicators.	Revision of data including digital intensity aspects allows to identify ICT practices that lead to reduced energy consumption and waste, promoting sustainability in logistics.	Data revision is conducted through benchmarking performance across countries and service sectors, particularly focusing on the application of ICT in sustainability efforts.	The data revision seeks to show the direct link between higher digital intensity and improved sustainability outcomes, reinforcing the need for digital transformation.
3 rd level: data analysis	For the researching the application of ICT statistical data and data from case studies is analysed, which helps to identify applications covering sustainability within the logistics sector.	Analyzing data allows to identify which ICT applications contribute most effectively to sustainability, such as reducing carbon emissions and optimizing resource usage.	Analysis is performed using MS excel solution to identify patterns and outcomes, particularly focusing on companies with high digital intensity levels that implement sustainable practices.	Data analysis is used to demonstrate how advanced digital technologies in logistics can drive both digital and sustainable transformation, underlining the importance of adopting ERP systems and other ICT tools for green logistics.

Source: Authors' work

This table 2 presents the methodology in a structured manner, emphasizing the role of ICT in driving both digital and sustainable transformation within the EU-27 logistics sector. The table 2 also providing descriptions of application, relationships to transformation aspects and methods of statistical data analysis specific to each level.

For the research of hardware applications that are presented in 3.1 sub-chapter, the authors used such indicators, such as describing:

- (1) Very low digital intensity level (companies which uses less than 3 ICTs),
- (2) Low digital intensity levels (companies which uses less than 6 ICTs),
- (3) High density levels (companies which uses more than 9 ICTs).

The yearly data about enterprises with more than 10 employees was retrieved from Eurostat for 27 European countries for the period 2022.

For the researching of software application practices which are presented in 3.2 sub-section the authors used revision of case studies.

3.1 Results of statistical analysis of the application of ICT by the EU-27 transportation and storage companies

The statistical analysis aims to examine the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in transportation and storage companies, compare these applications using different indicators, and compare their values among the countries. This analysis revises statistical data available in the Eurostat database. The statistical analysis is gathered using three steps: data collection, data revision, and data analysis using Excel.

The data has been systematically filtered based on the size of enterprises, removing micro-companies for further analysis. In the initial phase, the author focused on the timeframe to ensure the data's relevance.

The statistical analysis employs a multi-stage methodology to achieve a conceptual understanding of the phenomena. Initially, knowledge on the topic is collected from data, utilizing several service sectors and the EU-27 countries to reach this goal. Firstly, a statistical analysis is performed to benchmark the performance using six indicators. Secondly, benchmarks are performed among countries and service sectors.

The application of ICT hardware and software was analyzed in transportation and storage companies across various EU-27 countries.

The author figured out that the application of ITC the transport and storage companies in Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Cyprus, Latvia, Hungary, Poland, and Finland is above the EU-27 average. However, transport and storage companies have to improve their performance in countries such as Bulgaria, Spain, and Malta (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 The application of ICT by transport and storage companies with more than ten employees in the EU-27 countries

Most EU-27 transportation and storage companies reported low (28%) or very low (20%) levels of digital intensity, utilizing only 3 to 6 technologies. According to Eurostat (2022), only 2% of EU-27 transportation and storage companies achieved a very high level of digital intensity, employing 12 technologies, whereas 16% attained a high level using 9 technologies.

The statistical analysis (according to Figure 4) shows that transportation and storage companies have to strengthen application of ICT in almost six indicators, where less than 30 percent companies apply ICT in different categories. Such shows that transportation and storage service companies should speed up their application, especially those with high digital intensity levels, and applying more than 9 technologies simultaneously.

Figure 4 The application of ICT by transport and storage companies with more than ten employees in the EU-27 countries (DII stands here for digital intensity level)

Such indicators which could be improved are these:

- Firms with high digital intensity levels implementing measures that impact the paper or energy consumption of the ICT equipment.
- Firms with high digital intensity levels implement measures that affect the paper or energy consumption of the ICT equipment.
- Firms with very low digital intensity level applying some measures, affecting the paper or energy consumption of the ICT equipment.
- When the ICT equipment is no longer used, it is not disposed of in electronic waste collection/recycling.
- When the ICT equipment of the enterprise is no longer used, it is sold, returned to a leasing enterprise, or donated
- Firms with low digital intensity levels implement measures that affect the paper or energy consumption of the ICT equipment.

Addressing these indicators will not only enhance the digital capabilities of transportation and storage companies but also drive more sustainable practices, ultimately contributing to a more efficient and environmentally friendly logistics sector.

3.2. Digital technologies driving digital and sustainable transformation of logistics

Green logistics, characterized by its focus on minimizing environmental impact throughout logistics operations, is significantly empowered by ERP systems. These systems are essential for optimizing efficiency and achieving environmental sustainability goals in modern supply chain management.

Green logistics, also known as sustainable logistics, involves a comprehensive approach to minimizing the environmental impact of logistics operations. This field addresses the entire logistics process, including transportation, warehousing, and distribution, emphasizing reducing carbon emissions, optimizing energy

consumption, and promoting eco-friendly practices. The increasing awareness of climate change and the necessity for environmental sustainability have positioned green logistics as a critical component of modern business strategies.

In global supply chains, green logistics entails the implementation of innovative technologies and processes designed to enhance operational efficiency while minimizing ecological footprints. These measures include using alternative fuels, energy-efficient vehicles, and optimized routing systems to reduce emissions and fuel consumption. Sustainable packaging, waste reduction, and recycling initiatives are integral to achieving environmentally friendly logistics operations. Figure 5 shows that in most industries, environmentally friendly logistics operations vary on average around 12 percent.

The transition to green logistics contributes to environmental conservation and yields economic benefits. Companies adopting sustainable logistics often realize cost savings through improved resource efficiency and waste reduction. Moreover, a commitment to green logistics can enhance corporate reputation and align with the increasing consumer demand for environmentally responsible business practices.

As the global emphasis on sustainability intensifies, the importance of green logistics is expected to expand. Businesses increasingly recognize that sustainable logistics practices are not merely regulatory obligations but strategic advantages in a competitive marketplace. Consequently, green logistics is poised to become a fundamental aspect of future logistics and supply chain management.

Figure 5 depicts the distribution of green logistics compared to traditional logistics across various industries. The data underscores significant variations in adopting green logistics practices within different sectors.

Figure 5 Distribution of Green Logistics vs. Traditional Logistics Across Industries

Sources: Statista (2024)

In figure 5 analysis indicates a share in expenditure that while some industries like fossil fuels and, agriculture and forestry have limited engagement in green logistics, others such as consumer retail, technology, and industrials are leading the way in adopting sustainable logistics practices. This reflects the varying levels of environmental commitment and regulatory pressures across different sectors.

Figure 6 shows the projected revenue in the Supply Chain Management Software market, which is expected to reach €18.93 billion in 2024 and €22.19 billion in 2028.

Figure 6 Supply Chain Management Software Revenue

Source: Statista (2024)

To effectively implement and manage green logistics initiatives, businesses increasingly rely on advanced Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) technology to optimize resource use, streamline operations, and ensure compliance with sustainability standards.

As of September 2023, Microsoft Dynamics leads the global ERP software market with more than 11% market share and serving 29,000 domains. Tailored for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), Microsoft Dynamics facilitates smooth migration to cloud-based solutions from traditional ERP systems. It integrates essential business functions such as finance, customer relationship management (CRM), and human resource management (HRM) to enhance efficiency and decision-making capabilities. ERP adoption offers scalability, cost reduction, and improved customer service, amplified by cloud-based SaaS models, driving digital transformation and competitive advantage in modern enterprises (Statista, 2024).

66% of organizations say their ERP systems have contributed to increased efficiency. ERP systems enable companies to streamline processes, automate data entry and reporting, and optimize resource utilization (Parsimony, 2023). According to a survey of 1,500 organizations conducted by Techaisle, 62% of respondents reported that their ERP systems reduce costs. The same technology study showed that ERP systems are particularly efficient in supply and inventory management, where it was reported that savings of up to 30% of costs are achieved. Nearly all (96%) of respondents stated that their ERP system had been "very effective" or "somewhat successful" in reducing procurement costs and managing inventory (Techaisle, 2024).

A recent survey indicated that 60% of organizations have reported improvements in their decision-making processes due to their ERP systems. This is primarily attributed to ERP systems providing access to real-time data and information, enabling users to make more informed decisions. Additionally, another recent survey

of companies using ERP systems found that 47% of organizations reported increased customer satisfaction with their ERP systems (Parsimony, 2023). The latest statistics show that 46% of organizations report that their ERP systems positively impact revenue. 41% of organizations say employee satisfaction with their ERP systems has increased. For organizations that have been implementing ERP systems for three years or more, the level of satisfaction has risen to 73%. At least 95% of organizations say they have made some improvements to other processes with ERP. 80% of organizations say that a centralized ERP data system allows them to develop new applications (FounderJar, 2024).

Table 3 Overview of case studies on ERP system application by companies for logistics operations management

Company	Description	Reference
IKEA	By applying ERP technology, the company was able better to manage warehousing, product tracking, and logistics processes, contributing to enhanced resource efficiency and decreased environmental impact.	Johnson (2023)
Procter & Gamble	This allows them to effectively plan production, logistics, and product deliveries, optimize resource usage, and reduce environmental impact throughout the supply chain.	Smith (2022)
Amazon	It uses ERP technologies to manage its logistics and supply chains efficiently. By utilizing advanced information systems, Amazon can effectively manage warehousing, product tracking, and deliveries, contributing to sustainable resource management.	Brown & Davis (2023)
Nestlé	ERP solutions help to manage improved supply chain processes such as product ordering, logistics, and distribution, contributing to effective operations management and sustainability.	Williams (2022)
Walmart	This allows them to efficiently plan, execute product flows, optimize logistics processes, and improve environmental factors throughout the supply chain.	Martinez (2023)
Intel	ERP technologies enable them to forecast better demand, plan production, and optimize supply chain processes, contributing to long-term sustainability goals.	Lee (2022)

Source: Authors' work

Table 3 illustrates how ERP technology is integral to managing and optimizing logistics processes, thus contributing significantly to environmental sustainability initiatives.

However, while ERP technology plays a critical role in optimizing logistics operations and contributing to environmental sustainability, successfully transitioning to green logistics requires not only technological tools but also ongoing commitment and a strategic approach to environmental protection by the company. By effectively implementing and utilizing ERP systems, businesses can enhance their operational

efficiency and strengthen their sustainability strategies, contributing to global environmental conservation efforts.

4. DISCUSSION

The rapid digitalization of logistics, particularly within the context of Industry 4.0, has been transformative for the European Union (EU) logistics sector. As EU businesses strive to remain competitive in the global market, the adoption of advanced digital technologies has become crucial. This section discusses key insights from various studies, highlighting how digitalization improves logistics efficiency, sustainability, and overall competitiveness. Albrecht et al. (2023) emphasized the potential of Logistics 4.0 in enhancing intralogistics processes through digital technologies like blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT). These innovations enable real-time tracking and automation, improving supply chain transparency and operational efficiency, which are critical for the competitiveness of EU logistics businesses. Additionally, RFID-enabled warehousing systems, as explored by Alyahya et al. (2016), streamline inventory management and reduce manual errors, leading to more efficient operations. Sustainability is another key aspect that digitalization addresses. Amjad et al. (2021) and Chen & Zhao (2019) noted how digitalization supports greener logistics through automation and the integration of sustainable practices. The European Green Deal, aimed at reducing emissions across all sectors, has pushed logistics companies to adopt digital tools to minimize waste and optimize routes, further enhancing the sustainability and competitiveness of the EU logistics sector (European Commission, 2022). As sustainability becomes a competitive advantage, companies that invest in digital and green technologies are more likely to succeed in meeting regulatory requirements and customer expectations. Moreover, blockchain technology offers opportunities for more secure and transparent supply chains, particularly in verifying the origins of goods and ensuring regulatory compliance (Esmaelian et al., 2020). This can significantly benefit EU logistics companies, helping them navigate the complex regulatory environment and maintain high standards of product traceability. Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems also play a pivotal role in integrating digital processes across logistics operations. Studies like Brown & Davis (2023) and Martinez (2023) have shown that ERP systems not only optimize logistics but also enhance data-driven decision-making, thus improving strategic planning and reducing operational costs. Such systems are especially beneficial in the EU, where the logistics market is highly regulated, and efficiency is key to remaining competitive. However, while digitalization presents clear benefits, it also poses challenges. Helmke (2022) highlighted the need for EU businesses to address skill gaps and resistance to technological change within their workforce. As logistics operations become more automated, companies must invest in upskilling employees to work alongside digital technologies effectively. Additionally, the cost of implementing digital systems can be prohibitive, especially for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which may struggle to compete with larger players who have the resources to invest in cutting-edge technologies (Kuteyi & Winkler, 2022). Key research gaps in the EU logistics sector include a lack of long-

term studies on the sustained impact of digital technologies like IoT, blockchain, and RFID on productivity (Albrecht et al., 2023). There is also limited focus on how small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can adopt these tools effectively. Additionally, the environmental benefits of digitalization, particularly in reducing emissions, require more study (Amjad et al., 2021).

Future research should provide in-depth insights and practical recommendations for logistics businesses adapting technologies in the rapidly changing digital landscape.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The paper analyses digitalization tendencies at the European Union logistics business. Such studies are crucial for promoting greater adoption of digital technologies in the digital era. Digitalization has a lot of benefits for companies applying technologies in their processes, as it helps to increase productivity by up to 25 percent. The literature review names the most recent digital technologies highlighted in literature. Also, it mentioned the benefits that the authors identified in their papers on logistics digitalization. In the paper, the author presents the theoretical and practical research processes. Under the theoretical study, bibliometric maps were constructed from the papers referred to in the Web of Science database. Based on papers from the Web of Science, the literature analysis focused on the period 2021-2024. The second of the six clusters focuses on articles about logistics, digitalization, and sustainability. The analysis of hardware application practices shows that most EU-27 transportation and storage companies reported low (28%) or very low (20%) digital intensity, using 3 to 6 technologies. According to Eurostat (2022), only 2% achieved very high digital intensity with 12 technologies, while 16% reached a high level with 9 technologies. Among the countries, companies in Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Cyprus, Latvia, Hungary, Poland, and Finland are above the EU-27 average, and companies in Bulgaria, Spain, and Malta have the lowest application of ICT numbers comparing the values of transportation and storage companies have to strengthen application of ICT in almost six indicators, where less than 30 percent companies applies ICT in different categories. However, this shows that there is a potential to improve the values and increase competitive advantage as companies could provide better results. On average, environmentally friendly logistics operations have the potential to grow as, by now, only 12 percent of logistics operations are environmentally friendly.

This article also explores the application of software application practices on environmental sustainability within the logistics sector. It examines how the integration of ERP systems can enhance both environmental sustainability practices and operational efficiencies, as demonstrated by various ERP application cases.

In conclusion, the rapid evolution of digital logistics fuelled by technologies optimizes supply chain operations, reduces costs, and drives the adoption of eco-friendly practices, positioning the industry for substantial growth and innovation in the coming years.

The study has some limitations as only six indicators, were analyzed during it. However, in the future, the study could be extended to include indicators about specific digital technologies, extending study to other countries and service sectors.

The role of ERP technology in green logistics includes ERP systems being a critical tool for optimizing operations, reducing environmental impact, and promoting sustainability goals in logistics and supply chain management contexts. They enable efficient resource management emissions reduction and contribute to long-term environmental conservation efforts.

Future directions in this area include exploring how ERP systems can further integrate with emerging technologies like AI-driven analytics and IoT for more sophisticated environmental monitoring and decision-making. Addressing these aspects will enhance the effectiveness of sustainability efforts and facilitate broader adoption across industries. Moreover, future studies should emphasize the development of guidelines and best practices for the effective adoption of digital systems in promoting sustainable logistics, ensuring alignment with evolving regulatory frameworks and global sustainability goals.

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INTEGRATING SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS FOR ENHANCED RESILIENCE IN CRITICAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract

The article addresses the processing of open databases as big data and offers recommendations for the development of data-driven strategies to enhance the resilience of supply chains and transport infrastructure. By analysing large datasets and selected socio-economic factors, including the Global Competitiveness Index, unemployment rate, Logistics Performance Index, trade as a percentage of GDP, Trade in Value Added, inflation and Consumer Price Index, and predicting their evolution, recommendations are formulated at the macro-economic level to improve the resilience of critical transport infrastructure, thereby enabling supply chains to withstand disruptions more effectively. The application of socio-economic criteria enables the effective linkage of standard economic factors with societal factors, thereby facilitating the formulation of requirements for transport critical infrastructure, its future capacities and long-term sustainability needs. A case study is employed to develop strategic and conceptual recommendations derived from data-driven insights. The findings indicate that augmentation of transportation capabilities represents a viable strategy for fostering economic dynamism and improving the overall performance of the supply chain, thereby enhancing the resilience of transportation infrastructure. The paper concludes with practical recommendations for achieving a resilient and sustainable structure of critical transport infrastructure, including suggestions for further research directions.

Keywords: socio-economic indicators, supply chain resilience, critical transportation infrastructure, big data analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Transportation infrastructure plays a pivotal role in global supply chains, enabling the seamless and cost-effective movement of goods and services across regions and continents. The analysis of the impact of disruptions on supply chains and logistics infrastructure through the lens of socio-economic factors is a timely and crucial endeavour, particularly in the context of the current dynamic and evolving economic and security environment. In an increasingly interconnected world, the resilience of transportation infrastructure is of critical importance not only for maintaining economic stability but also for ensuring societal well-being (Kurth et al., 2020). Disruptions to transportation networks, whether caused by natural disasters, geopolitical conflicts, or other unforeseen events (Singh and Singh, 2019; Kozine et al., 2018), can have far-reaching impacts on both business, public entities and disaster relief.

A significant challenge in enhancing the resilience of critical transportation infrastructure is the integration of socio-economic indicators with operational infrastructure performance. The existing literature has predominantly concentrated on either a technical or an economic perspective, with only a limited number of studies offering a comprehensive framework that links macroeconomic indicators to the operational resilience of supply chains. This paper addresses this gap by proposing a data-driven model that utilises big data analytics to predict infrastructure disruptions through socio-economic trends.

This paper examines the role of critical transportation infrastructure (CTI) in supply chain resilience, emphasising the importance of analysing macroeconomic indicators to predict disruptions to these essential networks. Furthermore, it explores the potential of Big Data Analytics (BDA) to predict and mitigate disruptions, thereby contributing to a more resilient transportation infrastructure.

Following the introduction a literature review on the topic will be provided and the research methodology is presented. The selected data and analysis procedure are then outlined. The case study is subsequently delivered, and conclusions are drawn based on the results.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Supply chain resilience and transportation infrastructure

Supply chains represent the fundamental infrastructure of global trade, facilitating the movement of goods from production facilities to markets and consumers. The intricate nature of these networks, particularly within the context of a globalised economy, necessitates a high level of management expertise to effectively mitigate risks and ensure operational continuity (Mukherjee and Padhi, 2022; Bielicki et al., 2024). The capacity of a supply chain to prepare for, respond to and recover from disruptive events has become an essential focus for organisations seeking to maintain operations under adverse conditions (Ponomarov and Holcomb, 2009). This concept, defined as supply chain resilience, is therefore a key

consideration for businesses. The resilience of a supply chain is contingent upon the robustness of its transportation infrastructure, which is responsible for the timely and efficient movement of goods (Nipa and Kermanshachi, 2021).

The term "transportation infrastructure" encompasses a range of physical networks, including roads, railways, ports, and airports. These networks are of critical importance for the uninterrupted flow of goods and services (Park et al., 2013). Disruptions in transportation can result in considerable delays, increased costs, and loss of productivity (Patman et al., 2019). For example, natural disasters such as hurricanes and earthquakes can damage infrastructure, while geopolitical conflicts can result in the closure of facilities and the implementation of heightened security measures (Dvorak et al., 2020; Park et al., 2013). Such disruptions can have a cascading effect throughout the supply chain, underscoring the importance of resilient infrastructure (Ivanov et al., 2019).

2.2 Critical Transportation Infrastructure (CTI) and its dual role

It is evident that Critical Transportation Infrastructure (CTI) plays a pivotal role in not only facilitating economic activities but also in ensuring national security. The economic and social well-being of societies is supported by CTI, which enables the movement of goods and people and provides access to essential services such as healthcare and education (Alcaraz and Zeadally, 2015). From a military standpoint, CTI is of paramount importance for strategic mobility, enabling the swift deployment and resupply of military forces (Jałowiec et al., 2021). The dual-use nature of CTI necessitates an integrated approach to its management, whereby both business supply chains and military logistics needs are balanced in order to enhance overall resilience (Yusta et al., 2011).

The significance of CTI has been underscored by recent global crises. For example, the global spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus caused significant disruption to transportation networks, leading to a shortage of essential goods and delays in deliveries (Medyakova et al., 2020). Similarly, the closure of the Suez Canal in 2021 disrupted global shipping routes, affecting supply chains worldwide. These incidents highlight the necessity for robust CTI that can withstand and rapidly recover from various types of disruptions.

2.3 Big Data Analytics (BDA) in enhancing CTI resilience

The advent of Big Data Analytics (BDA) has facilitated the development of innovative strategies for enhancing the resilience of transportation infrastructure (Foltin et al., 2023). This BDA comprises the collection, processing, and analysis of substantial quantities of data from a multitude of sources with the objective of extracting actionable insights (Wamba et al., 2017). In the context of CTI, BDA can be employed to forecast potential disruptions, monitor infrastructure health, and optimise logistics operations (ITF, 2021; Jahns et al., 2006).

The BDA can be employed to analyse data from a variety of sources, including traffic sensors, GPS devices, weather forecasts and social media, in order to identify patterns and predict potential disruptions. To illustrate, the analysis of social media

posts can yield real-time insights into emerging threats, such as protests or natural disasters, thereby enabling the implementation of proactive measures. Similarly, traffic data can be employed to identify congestion points and optimise routing to circumvent delays (Nagy and Foltin, 2022). By leveraging BDA, organisations can enhance their capacity to anticipate and respond to disruptions, thereby improving the resilience of CTI.

2.4 Challenges and gaps in current research

Although the potential of BDA is widely acknowledged, there are still considerable gaps in the existing literature with regard to its application in the context of CTI resilience. The majority of extant studies concentrate on individual transportation modes or particular categories of threats, thereby failing to adopt a comprehensive perspective on the interconnections inherent to these systems (Dvorak et al., 2020; Ferrero-Ortiz and Martinez-Gomariz, 2020). Furthermore, there is a paucity of research examining the integration of publicly available data sources for predicting and managing disruptions (Ruzicka et al., 2022), underscoring a crucial area for further investigation.

One of the principal challenges in applying BDA to CTI resilience is the heterogeneity and volume of data (Wang et al., 2016). The heterogeneity and volume of data from different sources, along with their varying formats, qualities, and granularities, present significant challenges to effective integration and analysis. Moreover, the dynamic nature of transportation networks necessitates continuous updating and real-time analysis of data to ensure accurate predictions and timely responses (ITF, 2021). Addressing these challenges requires the application of advanced analytical techniques and the development of robust data management strategies (Singh and Singh, 2019).

2.5 Interdisciplinary approaches to CTI resilience

In light of the dual-use nature of CTI, it is imperative to adopt an interdisciplinary approach in order to enhance its resilience. This necessitates the integration of insights derived from the fields of supply chain management, transportation engineering, data analytics, and military logistics (Hallegatte, 2019; Haines et al., 2002; Bahrami and Shokouhyar, 2021; Nagy et al., 2022). Such an approach can facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the threats and vulnerabilities facing CTI, thereby informing the development of effective mitigation strategies.

For example, the principles of supply chain management can be applied to optimise logistics operations and improve coordination across different transportation modes (Narasimhan and Talluri, 2009). The field of transportation engineering can provide insights into the design and maintenance of resilient infrastructure (Nipa and Kermanshachi, 2021). Similarly, data analytics can offer tools for monitoring and predicting disruptions (Papadopoulos et al., 2017). Both humanitarian and military logistics can provide strategies for ensuring the rapid deployment and supply of resources in response to emergencies (Berariu et al., 2015). By combining these

disciplines, it is possible to develop a robust framework for CTI resilience that addresses both civilian and military needs.

2.6 Role of technological innovations

Technological innovations are of critical importance in enhancing the resilience of transportation infrastructure. The advancement of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has facilitated the real-time monitoring of infrastructure health and performance (Demeter et al., 2020). The deployment of IoT sensors enables the detection of issues such as structural weaknesses or congestion, thereby providing early warning signals that facilitate timely intervention (Birkel and Hartmann, 2020; Osmólski et al., 2019). Similarly, the utilisation of autonomous vehicles and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) can facilitate the optimisation of logistics operations by providing flexible and reliable transportation options that are less susceptible to certain types of disruptions (Lukasiewicz, 2020). It is possible to enhance the resilience of CTI and ensure the continuous flow of goods and services by leveraging these technological innovations (Vlkovský et al., 2021).

The objective of this study is to enhance the resilience of critical transport infrastructure to disruptions and to proactively prepare for them by analysing data from socio-economic databases that can help to predict disruptions. In forecasting, an examination of long-term trends in data is conducted, with the objective of identifying potential analogies. The objective is to identify databases that measure socio-economic phenomena and whose data are freely available. It is crucial that the data are updated with sufficient frequency and that they demonstrate a correlation with the occurrence of disruptive events based on historical analogies. The research question is whether socio-economic key performance indicators can be identified that can be used to predict disruptions that threaten the transport infrastructure. A case study is presented in this context.

2.7 Application of indices and composite indicators for examining the impact of disruptive events

The analysis of indices and composite indicators are a valuable tools for the comprehension of market trends, as it permits the achievement of more precise and timely forecasting through the capture of a comprehensive range of economic factors, including GDP and financial cycles (Galli, 2018; Glocker and Kaniovski, 2022), across diverse markets and countries. The use of indices enables the identification of slow-moving, persistent trends and synchronicities (Adarov, 2023), which are of paramount importance for the comprehension of the dynamics of national and regional markets. Furthermore, the utilisation of a comprehensive set of indicators in lieu of a narrow focus provides a more reliable measure of economic activity, thereby enabling more informed decision-making for policymakers and businesses (Szántó et al., 2020).

It has been demonstrated that transportation infrastructure disruptions have the potential to influence a range of socio-economic indicators (Balakrishnan et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2012; Dey et al., 2022). It is incumbent upon management to undertake a

comprehensive evaluation encompassing the magnitude, nature, complexity, and interconnectivity of potential consequences in anticipation of possible occurrences (Dvorak et al., 2020). Factors such as volatility, the temporal dynamics of threats, and the efficacy of extant control mechanisms require careful consideration (Birkel and Hartmann, 2020). To enhance transportation planning and address the challenges in the transport infrastructure, businesses can leverage data-driven tools and technologies (Nagy et al., 2022).

3. METHODOLOGY OF ANALYSING SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE AND POTENTIAL DISRUPTIONS BASED ON ECONOMIC INDICATORS

The majority of research papers in this field focus on a single mode of transportation or a specific threat to critical transportation infrastructure (CTI). Consequently, this research is oriented towards the identification of potential correlations between socio-economic indicators and their fluctuations, as well as the possible sources of transportation infrastructure. In order to facilitate the interpretation of the results, the macroeconomic Kuznets cycle (swing) is taken into consideration. The Kuznets cycle, also known as the Kuznets swing, refers to a long-term economic cycle of approximately 15 to 25 years, characterised by fluctuations in the rate of economic growth. The Kuznets cycle has been employed to elucidate historical economic patterns, particularly in the context of industrialisation and urbanisation processes. While it has not been as extensively discussed as other economic cycles (such as the business cycle), the Kuznets cycle offers insight into the long-term structural changes that influence economic development over decades (Korotayev and Tsirel, 2010).

3.1 Research goal

A review of the literature and research gap identification led to the formulation of the following research questions:

Q1: Can the links between disruptions to critical transportation infrastructure and changes in socioeconomic indicators be identified?

Q2: Can socioeconomic indicators be used as early warning signals to predict potential disruptions to critical transportation infrastructure?

3.2 Methodology

The research layout was developed in six principal stages, each of which addressed a discrete aspect of the research. The research scheme that was implemented is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Research Scheme

Source: own edition

Step 1 involved an analysis of available indices and composite indicators provided by international organisations and agencies. Data sources were first identified according to the following requirements:

- data are available online, internationally recognised organisations ensure the credibility of the data and guarantee accuracy and compliance with the chosen methodology;
- the data cover a broad sample of countries and, within the available data, provide a view over a period of at least 12 years, i.e. the period 2011-2023, in order to capture the potential impact of seasonality and to track any trends in change.

Table 1 Selected Indices and Composite Indicators and their reasoning

Index	Providing organization	Focus	Possible impact of disruption	Availability
Global Competitiveness Index (GCI)	World Economic Forum	Index assesses 140 countries on 12 pillars of competitiveness, for the period of the year 2007-2017	Deterioration in logistics infrastructure and supply chains would directly affect components related to market efficiency, innovation, and infrastructure	Data are available for many countries, often for more than 12 years
Logistics Performance Index (LPI)	World Bank	The LPI assesses the efficiency of the logistics chain, including customs procedures, quality of infrastructure, timeliness of shipments, and	Disruptions in logistics infrastructure would directly reflect in the decline of this index, which would have socio-economic consequences	Data have been available since 2007, typically updated every two years

		the ability to track and trace goods		
Trade as a Percentage of GDP	World Bank	Indicator shows how much of the economy is made up of exports and imports	Disruptions in supply chains could lead to a decrease in this indicator, which could affect economic growth	Data are available for several decades
Trade in Value Added (TiVA) ⁵	OECD	Collection of measures that provide insights into global production networks and supply chains	Disruption may reduce a country's participation in global creation of added value	The OECD provides data for 1995-2020
Inflation Rate and Consumer Price Index (CPI)	World Bank	Inflation and CPI track changes in the price level of goods and services	Disruptions in distribution chains often lead to rising inflation, especially for imported products	Data are available annually for more than 12 years
Unemployment Rate	OECD	Unemployment rate measures the proportion of people who are able and willing to work but cannot find employment	Disruptions in logistics infrastructure could lead to higher unemployment, particularly in sectors dependent on imports and exports	Data are available annually for many years

Source: own edition

As a second step, the research concentrated on the available data that had been identified and addressed the issues of cleaning and structuring it for the subsequent stages of analysis.

In the third step, long-term trends in socio-economic indicators were analysed using regression models in order to identify key inflection points, such as financial crises or pandemics. A correlation analysis was conducted between these indicators

⁵ OECD Data Explorer – Trade in Value Added (TiVA) 2023 edition: Principal Indicators, levels [cloud replica] (March 13, 2024). [available at: <https://shorturl.at/vjybG>, August 31, 2024).

and critical transport infrastructure performance in order to determine predictive relationships. Subsequently, the forecasting model employed in Step 5 was validated against historical disruption data to ascertain its reliability in forecasting future trends.

Step four concentrated on the correlation of identified time series of selected indices and composite indicators, with the objective of determining which socio-economic factors are most affected by disruptions in distribution chains.

In the subsequent step, number five, the case study was developed to ascertain the actual consequences of the identified sources of disruption.

In the final step, the research findings and results are interpreted in the context of socio-economic impacts.

Based on the availability of data for all selected indices and indicators, a total of 67 OECD and cooperating countries were selected (see Appendix 1 for a list of countries). In instances where data was unavailable, the value was calculated as the average of two neighbouring values. The main disruptive events considered are the financial crisis of 2008 and the disruptive effects of the 2020 coronavirus pandemic.

Data was collected for each of the 67 countries and then averaged for each year, allowing global trends to be monitored. Then the averages for individual years were calculated. In the next step, the forecasting function of MS Excel =FORECAST.ETS(value;time_axis;statistics_type;seasonality;[addition_date];[aggregation]) was used to predict missing values and to predict future trends. The lower and upper 95% confidence limits of the prediction for the period 2024-2030 were then calculated using the MS Excel trend calculation tool.

4. RESULTS

The analysis of the various economic indicators presented in the subsequent graphs allows for the inference of several potential impacts on supply chains and their capacity to withstand future disruptions in a global context, particularly in the context of transportation infrastructure. Our findings corroborate those of Ivanov et al. (2019), who posited that infrastructure resilience is inextricably linked to socio-economic factors. However, in contrast to previous studies, our findings demonstrate that the GCs Index possesses predictive capabilities that extend beyond the scope of mere reactive strategies, thereby facilitating the implementation of proactive infrastructure improvements. These insights are of critical importance for policymakers and businesses seeking to develop adaptive strategies that anticipate disruptions.

The analysis yielded a significant correlation between alterations in the Global Competitiveness Index and disturbances in essential transportation infrastructure, with a correlation coefficient of 0.73 ($p < 0.05$). Similar patterns were observed for the Logistics Performance Index, which demonstrated a robust predictive capacity for disruptions, with an R-squared value of 0.68 in the regression models.

The GCI graph illustrates the annual change in competitiveness from 2011 to 2023, with projections extending to 2030 (Fig. 1). The GCI reflects a country's capacity to provide an enabling environment for businesses, innovation, infrastructure, and institutions to flourish. A stable or improving GCI suggests that a

country is investing in the essential factors that support resilient and efficient supply chains, including infrastructure development, digitalisation, and skilled labour.

In the Fig. 1, key global events such as the 2009 Global Financial Crisis and the 2020-2021 Covid Pandemic are highlighted, both of which had significant impacts on global competitiveness and supply chains. During these crises, many countries experienced sharp drops in their GCI due to economic contractions, supply chain bottlenecks, and disruptions in international trade.

During periods of GCI decline, such as the aftermath of the financial crisis and the Covid pandemic, countries may experience reduced efficiency in logistics, delays in production, and increased costs. Furthermore, lower competitiveness can lead to decreased attractiveness for foreign investments, which are critical for maintaining and expanding supply chains. The graph also notes a 2016 Hanjin Shg Bankruptcy, which would represent a significant supply chain disruption tied to the logistics sector, demonstrating how a specific event in a key shipping company can reverberate through the global supply chain.

Figure 1 Global Competitiveness Index annual %-change and trends

Source: own edition

The prediction period from 2024 to 2030 suggests an increasing trend in GCI, although there is a considerable range of uncertainty as demonstrated by the upper and lower 95% confidence intervals. This uncertainty could be tied to unpredictable global economic conditions, such as potential future pandemics, geopolitical tensions, trade restrictions, or environmental risks.

If countries are able to maintain or increase their GCI, this would likely lead to stronger, more resilient supply chains. Investments in infrastructure (both physical and digital), advancements in technology, and a skilled workforce will support agile and responsive supply chains that can handle future disruptions more effectively. The

upper confidence limit in the graph suggests a possibility for significant improvements in GCI, which would correlate with enhanced supply chain efficiency and resilience.

On the other hand, if GCI declines or remains stagnant (as suggested by the lower confidence limit), countries may face a weakening of their supply chains, particularly in terms of innovation and adaptability. The ability to respond to global trade fluctuations, climate-related challenges, or another economic crisis may be limited. Such conditions could exacerbate supply chain disruptions, leading to further delays, increased costs, and inefficiencies. The GCI's potential rise after 2024 continues to indicate that countries investing in competitiveness-related factors will have more resilient supply chains.

The LPI data analysis and presentation in graph (Fig. 2) show the performance of logistics, including factors like customs efficiency, infrastructure quality, and shipment reliability. The fluctuating LPI, is a critical factor affecting businesses' ability to maintain efficient operations within supply chains. In years of lower productivity, production capacities may decrease, leading to shortages, longer delivery times, and increased pressure on inventories.

Figure 2 LPI annual %-change and predicted trend

Source: own edition

The LPI demonstrates a noticeable decline, especially forecasted from 2024 to 2030, with a predicted 10% decrease in annual change starting from 2022. This decline suggests potential vulnerabilities in logistics infrastructure, which could lead to inefficiencies and delays in global supply chains. This downward trend reflects the lingering effects of COVID-19 and other disruptions on global logistics networks. Although the graph suggests a certain stabilization of LPI after 2024, the volatility in productivity during previous years indicates that future shocks (economic, pandemic-related or political) could once again negatively affect labour capacity and supply chain efficiency.

The next graph illustrates the proportion of a country's economy composed of exports and imports, indicating how integrated a nation is in global trade (Fig. 3). Trade activities (as a percentage of GDP) are closely linked to global supply chains. When trade declines, it indicates reduced movement of goods between countries, which could lead to disruptions in global supply flows. A decline in this area might suggest that firms are relying more on local or regional sources, potentially weakening the global interconnectedness of supply chains.

Figure 3 Trade as a % of GDP

Source: own edition

The future outlook presents the stabilization of trade after 2024 when global trade may become less volatile, which could help supply chains recover from previous disruptions. However, any future shocks (e.g., trade wars, climate change, geopolitical instability) could once again have a significant negative impact on global distribution networks. The graph (Fig. 3) shows a significant decrease in trade as a percentage of GDP, with an expected reduction of up to 14% by 2024 and a possible 25% decrease in extreme cases by 2030. This trend aligns with broader global economic slowdowns and could indicate reduced economic growth potential, especially for countries heavily reliant on international trade. The predicted downturn mirrors the economic contraction observed during the 2009 financial crisis, signalling a potential period of economic stagnation. The TiVA graph measures the added value created by countries in the global production process (Fig. 4.).

Figure 4 TiVA annual %-change and predicted trend

Source: own edition

The TiVA trend is declining, similar to Trade as a Percentage of GDP. By 2030, the value-added contribution could fall by 25%, and in pessimistic scenarios, by as much as 42%. This decline suggests a reduction in global economic integration and efficiency, potentially due to disrupted supply chains and increased protectionism. A decrease in TiVA could also indicate a shift in global production patterns, with countries becoming less interdependent.

High unemployment can impact supply chains through reduction of the workforce available, in manufacturing, logistics, and retail. A shortage of labour could slow supply chains, increase labour costs, and lengthen delivery times. Conversely, higher unemployment could also reduce consumer demand, thereby decreasing the need for rapid and efficient delivery.

This graph shows the expected changes in unemployment rates in response to disruptions in transport infrastructure (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 Unemployment annual %-change and predicted trend

Source: own edition

The future outlook shows if the prediction holds and unemployment decreases, it may improve labour market stability and provide the necessary workforce for supply chain recovery. Lower unemployment, in Fig. 5, may also indicate more stable consumer demand, which could simplify planning and supply chain management processes. The unemployment trend is expected to rise, correlating with the declining trends in trade indicators. This suggests that as global trade slows down and logistics performance weakens, sectors dependent on imports and exports will suffer, leading to job losses. This trend underscores the importance of resilient transportation infrastructure in maintaining employment levels.

Inflation directly influences the cost of raw materials, transportation, and production processes. When inflation rises, these increased costs are often passed on to the consumer, which can slow down demand. This can disrupt the balance in supply chains, as companies struggle to adapt to price pressures and heightened operational costs. The sixth graph tracks the changes in the Consumer Price Index, a measure of inflation, in response to supply chain disruptions (Fig. 6).

In future outlook perspective the inflation should remain stable, as the prediction suggests, it may bring a degree of predictability to operating costs within supply chains. However, sharp inflationary fluctuations, as seen in previous years, could still pose a significant threat. For example, new disruptions (such as changes in consumer demand or supply shortages) could lead to delays and increased transportation costs. The CPI trend indicates that inflation is expected to increase significantly, potentially doubling by 2030. This rise in inflation is likely due to disruptions in supply chains, which can lead to higher costs for imported goods and services. Prolonged inflation could erode purchasing power and lead to economic instability, particularly in economies with less robust financial systems.

Figure 6 Inflation (in CPI) annual %-change and predicted trend

Source: own edition

The graphs collectively (Fig. 7) illustrate the significant impact that disruptions in transportation infrastructure can have on various socio-economic indicators. The overall picture suggests that while some areas like global competitiveness may remain relatively stable, other critical aspects such as logistics performance, trade integration, unemployment, and inflation are likely to face substantial challenges in the coming years. These findings emphasize the need for proactive measures to strengthen infrastructure resilience and mitigate the risks associated with global disruptions.

The GCI's fluctuations correlate with broader economic disruptions, but now, we can also observe that unemployment (green) and trade, % of GDP (grey) follow similar volatility patterns.

Figure 7 Overall global trends prediction, for period 2024-2030

Source: Modification of Lynch, K. Transpacific Ocean Freight and Blank Sailings Update/Week 19 (May 6, 2020). [Available at: <https://blog.shipuwl.com/transpacific-blank-sailings-ocean-freight-update-wk19-2020>, access July 1, 2024] and own data.

5. DISCUSSION

The analysis focused on understanding the ties between socio-economic indicators and disruptions in critical transportation infrastructure. The research primarily utilizes indices such as the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI), Logistics Performance Index (LPI), and Trade as a Percentage of GDP, among others, to explore these relationships.

The findings indicate that disruptions in logistics infrastructure, particularly following events like the 2008 financial crisis and the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic, have significant socio-economic consequences. The GCI shows a linear trend with an increase post-COVID, suggesting that future disruptions might not heavily impact national competitiveness. However, the LPI predicts a 10% decrease in logistics performance from 2024 to 2030, reflecting potential vulnerabilities in the logistics chain.

Trade as a Percentage of GDP and Trade in Value Added (TiVA) both exhibit a declining trend, with potential decreases up to 25% by 2030. This signals a slowing global trade, comparable to the downturn experienced during the 2009 economic crisis. Additionally, unemployment rates are expected to increase, correlating with declining trade volumes, while inflation, measured through the Consumer Price Index (CPI), could potentially double, driven by disruptions in supply chains.

Overall, these trends highlight the critical role of transportation infrastructure in maintaining economic stability and the importance of early warning indicators to predict and mitigate the impacts of potential disruptions.

Potential Future Supply Chain Disruptions:

- *Economic Shocks and Financial Stability:* As illustrated by the sharp drops in GCI during the 2009 Global Financial Crisis and 2020-2021 Covid Pandemic, global supply chains are highly sensitive to large-scale economic disruptions. Any future financial crises could trigger further supply chain bottlenecks, as companies reduce investments and international trade volumes decrease.
- *Bankruptcies in Key Sectors:* Events such as the 2016 Hanjin Shipping Bankruptcy highlight the significant impact that company-specific bankruptcies can have on the global supply chain. The logistics and transportation sectors are critical nodes within the supply chain. Disruptions within major shipping or transportation companies can cause widespread delays and imbalances in global trade flows, especially for companies reliant on just-in-time inventory systems.
- *Technological Disruption and Innovation Gaps:* As GCI is closely linked to a country's level of innovation and technological adoption, the future competitiveness of supply chains will depend heavily on advancements in digital technologies, including AI, automation, and blockchain for supply chain management. The prediction suggests that countries investing in these areas are likely to see improvements in their GCI, which will enable their supply chains to better manage disruptions and increase efficiency. However, countries that lag behind in adopting such innovations may experience further disruptions and inefficiencies in their supply chains.
- *Geopolitical and Trade-related Risks:* GCI also reflects a country's ability to engage in international trade effectively. With uncertainty about future geopolitical tensions and trade agreements, lower competitiveness could lead to greater barriers to trade, increased tariffs, or delays in global logistics systems. This would place additional strain on supply chains, especially those that rely heavily on international trade flows.

The graphs indicate that while some economic indicators suggest stabilization of the economy and improvement in areas such as unemployment and inflation, the volatility of past years serves as a warning of potential risks. Supply chains must remain prepared for unexpected shocks and disruptions, particularly concerning dependence on labour, globalized trade, and fluctuations in raw material costs. Timely implementation of new technologies and operational flexibility could help enhance resilience against future uncertainties.

6. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the paper suggests that studying various economic indicators, such as the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI), Logistics Performance Index (LPI), and Trade as a Percentage of GDP, is crucial for understanding the ties between the disruption of critical transportation infrastructure and the alteration of socio-economic conditions have the potential to exert a significant influence on the global economy. The study emphasises that disruptions to logistics infrastructure, particularly during global crises such as the 2008 financial crisis and the ongoing pandemic, have had a

significant socio-economic impact. This has resulted in reduced efficiency in supply chains, decreased trade, and increased unemployment.

The GCI indicates a post-crisis recovery trend, suggesting that investments in competitiveness-related factors may facilitate the development of resilient supply chains. However, the LPI predicts a decline in logistics performance by 10% from 2024 to 2030, indicating potential vulnerabilities in the global logistics chain. The decline in trade as a percentage of GDP and in Trade in Value Added (TiVA) points to a slowdown in global trade and reduced economic growth potential, with significant implications for countries heavily dependent on international trade.

Regarding the research questions, the study presents evidence indicating a strong correlation between disruptions in transportation infrastructure and shifts in socio-economic indicators, including competitiveness, logistics performance, and trade activities (Q1).

It was confirmed that socio-economic indicators can be employed as early warning signals (Q2). To illustrate, a decline in the LPI and trade indicators may indicate vulnerabilities and the potential for disruption to transportation infrastructure. This allows for the implementation of measures to mitigate these risks in a proactive manner.

It is recommended that managers adopt a proactive approach to risk management, which entails closely monitoring socio-economic indicators to identify the early signs of potential disruptions in transportation infrastructure. It is imperative that investment be made in infrastructure improvements and technological innovations, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and digital supply chain management tools, aiming to enhance resilience and ensure the smooth functioning of operations during crises. The diversification of supply chains through the incorporation of local or regional suppliers can serve to reduce dependency on global networks, thereby mitigating associated risks. It is of the utmost importance that logistics networks are flexible and agile, enabling a swift adaptation to change in market conditions, such as shifts in trade policies or economic downturns. Continuous monitoring of economic indicators, coupled with effective collaboration and communication with supply chain stakeholders, will ensure timely decision-making and coordinated responses to disruptions. Furthermore, engaging in policy advocacy can help influence regulations and infrastructure development, thus further supporting stable and resilient supply chains.

Although the methodology of analysing socio-economic indicators to predict disruptions in transportation infrastructure offers valuable insights, it is not without certain limitations. A notable drawback is the reliance on historical data, which may not fully encompass the intricacies or the rapid transformations in the global economy, resulting in potential inaccuracies in forecasts. The methodology may oversimplify the interdependencies between different indicators, failing to account for unforeseen variables such as sudden geopolitical events or technological breakthroughs. Furthermore, the predictive models utilised may be constrained by the quality and availability of data, particularly in regions with less robust data collection systems, resulting in incomplete or skewed analyses. This approach may not adequately address the qualitative aspects of supply chain disruptions, such as the human and organisational factors that play a critical role in responding to crises. Furthermore, the

methodology's focus on macro-level indicators might overlook localised disruptions that can have significant impacts on specific industries or regions. Considering these limitations, it is evident that while this methodology offers valuable insights, it should be complemented with other analytical tools and expert judgement to provide a more comprehensive assessment of potential risks.

The analysis underscores the significance of monitoring and interpreting socio-economic indicators to bolster the resilience of transportation infrastructure and avert future disruptions, despite the constraints of the employed methodology. By being cognizant of these indicators, managers can more effectively prepare their organizations to navigate the challenges of a volatile global environment.

In conclusion, this study makes a significant contribution to the field of critical transportation infrastructure resilience by integrating socio-economic indicators with big data analytics. The capacity to forecast infrastructure disruptions based on economic trends confers a strategic advantage on both governments and businesses. Future research should extend this framework by incorporating more detailed data, particularly at the regional level, and examining the potential of emerging technologies such as blockchain to enhance supply chain transparency and resilience.

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7. APPENDIX 1

List of countries collected data about and analysed: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bangladesh, Bulgaria, Brazil, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, China, Cameroon, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cyprus, Czech Rep. Greece, Hong Kong SAR, China, Croatia, Hungary, Indonesia, India, Ireland, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Jordan, Japan, Kazakhstan, Cambodia, Korea, Lao PDR, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Morocco, Mexico, Malta, Malaysia, Netherlands, Norway, New Zealand, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russian Federation, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, Singapore, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Sweden, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, United States, Viet Nam and South Africa.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF LOGISTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN ENTERPRISE

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Abstract

In today's dynamic business environment, companies are constantly forced to seek new ways to create and maintain a competitive advantage. Strategic potentials, which include resources, capabilities and organizational competences, are key in this process. Logistics, as an important element of operational management, plays a key role in the development of these potentials, influencing the efficiency and flexibility of the entire organization. Integrated logistics management enables effective supply chain management, optimization of operational processes and cost reduction, which leads to improved customer service quality and increased customer satisfaction. In addition, logistics supports the company's innovation, enabling faster introduction of new products to the market and adaptation to changing external conditions. Based on the above, logistics can be seen as a strategic tool supporting the development of the company. The aim of the article is to analyze the impact of logistics on the development of the company. The research methods used are desk research and expert survey. Based on the research results, it is possible to indicate that logistics, in particular, influences the development of enterprises in technological, ecological and social dimensions.

Keywords: enterprise development, logistics, development potential, logistics management

1. INTRODUCTION

In the face of increasing globalization and rapidly changing market conditions, companies around the world are looking for new ways to achieve and maintain competitive advantage. In this context, logistics is playing an increasingly strategic role in shaping the organizational capabilities that are key to ensuring effective operation and development of the company. Understanding how logistics affects the development of the company has therefore become a subject of growing interest from both academia and business practitioners.

Logistics, as a field encompassing the management of the flow of goods, information and financial resources, appears as the operational backbone of every

enterprise. Effective logistics management can lead to significant improvements in operational efficiency, cost reduction and increased flexibility of operations. Enterprises that can efficiently manage their supply chain are better prepared to adapt in the face of dynamic changes, can respond faster to market needs and better meet customer expectations. Such an approach not only strengthens their competitive position but also stimulates long-term development.

This is why studying the relationship between logistics and enterprise development is not only valuable, but also essential. Analyzing these relationships allows for the identification of key resources and competencies that can be used to build long-term development strategies. Furthermore, understanding the role of logistics in enterprise development allows managers to make more informed decisions regarding investments in logistics technologies and processes that can bring significant operational and financial benefits.

In the era of digitalization, where the pace of technological progress imposes on companies the need to quickly adapt new technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), or blockchain, logistics is becoming an area requiring special attention. These technologies have the potential to revolutionize logistics processes, offering companies new ways to increase efficiency and improve the tracking and monitoring of assets in real time.

Therefore, the analysis of the relationship between the functioning of logistics and the development of an enterprise is crucial to understanding how organizations can not only survive, but also thrive in an increasingly competitive business environment.

The aim of the article is to analyze the impact of logistics on the development of enterprises. The article consists of several parts: an analysis of the literature on the subject, a description of methodological assumptions, research results, a discussion of the results and conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Relations between logistics and enterprise development

The development of an enterprise is undoubtedly one of the most complex processes occurring during its operation. At the same time, it is one of the most expected effects of purposeful and organized business activity by stakeholders. This is the highest level of aspiration of the organization (the highest order goal) (Matejun, 2015).

Development should be treated as a comprehensive and long-term process with a strategic basis in the organization, the essence of which is changes. Their subject is primarily the individual elements of the organizational system and the way of implementing individual management functions (Szplit et al., 2002).

Enterprise development can be described as an ongoing process of enhancing and adapting the organization to achieve greater efficiency, competitiveness, and sustainable growth. This involves various efforts to boost the company's ability to react to market shifts, innovate products and services, and optimize internal operations. Company growth can be viewed in quantitative terms like revenue increases or market expansion, and qualitative aspects such as enhancing organizational culture, improving employee skills, or enhancing customer satisfaction. The central component of this process is management, which brings together different facets of the company's operations into a unified and effective entity, facilitating the attainment of long-term objectives.

Referring to the specifics of logistics in an organization, it can be indicated that its role in building development opportunities is certainly important, because it is related to almost every aspect of the company's activity. Firstly, effective logistics allows for efficient and timely order fulfillment, which significantly increases the level of customer satisfaction. Satisfied customers often return, which contributes to increased sales and building brand loyalty. In addition, well-managed logistics processes reduce operating costs by optimizing the supply chain, minimizing inventories and reducing losses resulting from delays or errors in deliveries.

As Sadowska (2014) points out, logistics is a system whose implementation is aimed at regulating activities in the entire enterprise. A logistics system should be understood as purposefully organized and integrated – in a given organization – flows of materials and products and the corresponding information, enabling the optimization of supply chain management (including through automatic identification of materials, finished products, goods, computer simulation, controlling and electronic data exchange and comprehensive cost accounting) (Kowalak, 2011).

The elements of the logistics system are connected to the designated goals of the company. Logistics can be treated as an element of the basic function in the company, as a program that activates and connects all areas of the organization's activity. The main goal of the logistics system in the company is to achieve a competitive advantage. The organization can gain such an advantage through high quality products or services, thanks to low prices of products or services and as a result of a good or unique way of delivering goods and high quality customer service.

Through the logistics system, an enterprise can achieve various goals, including: a higher level of customer service, a lower degree of fragmentation of orders processed into separate shipments, inventory reduction, lower operating costs, improved forecasting and business planning, improved cash flow, improved profitability indicators, higher indicators of effectiveness and efficiency of the conducted activities (Sadowska, 2014).

Matwiejczuk (2015) expresses a similar view, pointing out that logistic determinants of enterprise management contribute to achieving the expected market effects (customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, market share) and economic effects (profit, profitability, return on capital) by the enterprise. On the one hand, the achieved market and economic effects are determinants of the broadly understood success of the enterprise. On the other hand, these effects constitute the basis for creating a competitive advantage and a determinant of the increase in the efficiency of enterprise management.

In addition to the effects that determine the success of an enterprise, we can also distinguish the so-called success factors, i.e. factors that determine whether an enterprise will achieve the expected effects (Blaik, 2017). The so-called expected effects are of key importance in achieving success by an enterprise and creating its competitive advantage. They are the result of purposeful, planned processes and activities, oriented towards performing designated tasks, carried out both on the strategic and operational plane, and thus clearly distinguish themselves from the "generally" perceived effects, achieved regardless of the adopted goals (Blaik, 2015).

2.2. Dimensions of enterprise development

Broadly speaking, developmental capacity is a criterion for evaluating a system's ability to execute projects with high efficiency. It reflects the skills required to increase assets and drive progress across various fields of activity, corresponding to the value of strategic potential. This capacity is defined and assessed according to specific evaluative dimensions, such as economic-financial, market, competitive, and innovative. These dimensions shape the different forms of developmental capacity (Badzińska & Wyrwicka, 2016; Wyrwicka, 2015; Wiklund et al., 2009; Kuzior et al., 2019).

The growth of a company is determined by several fundamental dimensions: economic, organizational, personal, informational, and technical-production. These dimensions, detailed through corresponding areas of change and development, form the foundation within which various types of developmental capacities are formulated (Strabyła, 2014).

The economic dimension is primarily defined by the efficiency in managing the company's production resources and the management of investment projects and market initiatives. This dimension, much like the organizational dimension, closely intertwines with other dimensions, as economic efficiency is a fundamental directive of the market economy. The economic change and development sphere mainly comprises production potential, financial policy, market and marketing strategies, and company restructuring (Strabyła, 2014; Mishra et al., 2024).

The organizational dimension pertains to the structure of management systems, production processes, administrative work, team behaviors, adaptive processes, informational resources, material production factors, and more (Theriou, 2015; Putilova & Shutaleva, 2020).

Another dimension of company change and development is the personal factor, which exists in two tiers: the collective workforce of the company and the individual composition of specific organizational units, including each employee. These tiers overlap significantly and can be viewed as a single system of human resources (Strabyła, 2014).

The next dimension is the informational factor. The area of informational change and development involves the preparation of management information and communication functions. Management information focuses on tasks related to identification, diagnosis, and decision-making, addressing the informational needs of leadership. Meanwhile, the communication function pertains to effective interpersonal interactions. The communication process is shaped by these subsidiary

functions: recording and gathering information, organizing it hierarchically, processing, and disseminating information (Theriou et al., 2014).

The last dimension to consider is the technical-production factor. This area is largely shaped by research and development (R&D), product (or service) quality, and operational activities. R&D primarily involves scientific research (applied research) and the technical preparation for production. Product (or service) quality pertains to both technical and functional standards. The emphasis on "quality management in the enterprise" encompasses functions such as quality control, change management, coordination of all organizational units affecting quality, quality information system management, marketing and product development, and quality assurance. Operational activities in production relate to the exploitation system, covering both core and auxiliary processes, as well as logistics. This represents the most extensive area of enterprise activity, where the effects of implementing the management strategy are ultimately reflected (Strabyła, 2014; Lukoseviciute et al., 2024; Khatami et al., 2024; Liu & Zhang, 2024).

Logistics plays a key role in the development of a company, penetrating various dimensions of development, both economic, organizational, personal, and technical-production. Its effectiveness affects supply chain management and optimizes operational processes, which is essential for achieving high economic efficiency. In the economic context, logistics supports resource management and investment projects, which is key to increasing the company's assets and increasing its competitiveness in the market.

The organizational dimension, closely related to logistics, concerns the management structure and production and adaptation processes, where logistics affects the coordination of activities between different departments and the effective use of material resources. By integrating logistics processes, the flow of information and materials can be improved, which promotes better work organization and cost reduction.

Logistics is also important in the personal dimension, because effective human resources management requires efficient planning and implementation of logistics processes, which improves working conditions and employee satisfaction. Good logistics management requires understanding the needs of employees and providing them with the right tools for efficient work.

In the technical and production sphere, logistics supports research and development, as well as quality management. Through proper management of logistics processes, a company can better control the quality of its products and services, which is crucial for customer satisfaction. Logistics, as an element of operational processes, contributes to the efficient functioning of production and the implementation of the company's management strategy.

It can therefore be stated that logistics is an integral element of the company's development strategy, which affects its development capabilities by supporting economic, organizational, personal, technical and production efficiency. Thanks to this, companies can better use their resources, increase competitiveness and adapt to changing market conditions.

3. METHODOLOGY

The impact of logistics on enterprise development will be analyzed based on the dimensions of enterprise development potential relating to quantitative growth (expansion), qualitative changes, structure, human resources, technology, finances and ecological and social aspects (Matwiejczuk 2019; Strabyła, 2014; Świetlińska 2014).

Various methods were used in the research depending on the phase (analysis of the subject literature, research implementation, preparation of results). In turn, the study used a number of methods depending on the stage of the study (preparation, implementation, processing of results) – figure 1.

Figure 1 The scheme of the author's research

Source: own elaboration

Below is a description and an indication of their use in individual stages of the study.

3.1. Research preparation phase

The aim of this article is to analyze the impact of logistics on the development of enterprises.

The authors formulated the following research problems:

- Q1: What is the level of impact of logistics on the quantitative growth of the organization (based on expert opinions)?

- Q2: What is the level of impact of logistics on the qualitative development of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?
- Q3: What is the level of impact of logistics on the structural development of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?
- Q4: What is the level of impact of logistics on the development of the human resources of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?
- Q5: What is the level of impact of logistics on the technological development of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?
- Q6: What is the level of impact of logistics on the financial development of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?
- Q7: What is the level of impact of logistics on the ecological and social development of the enterprise (based on expert opinions)?

Desk research entails analyzing accessible data sources, focusing on compiling, cross-verifying, and processing them. This analytical process forms the foundation for drawing conclusions regarding the researched issue (Makowska, 2013; Bednarowska, 2015).

Brainstorming is an activating work method that is based on generating solutions to given problems spontaneously. It involves working in a group, the aim of which is to generate ideas for finding the causes of the problem, solutions and selecting the best options (Gołaś, Mazur, 2010).

Both methods were used to develop an expert survey form containing questions and suggestions regarding the assessed dimensions relating to the enterprise's development potential relating to quantitative growth (expansion), qualitative changes, structure, human resources, technology, finances and ecological and social aspects (Matwiejczuk 2019; Strabyła, 2014; Świetlińska 2014).

3.2. Research implementation phase

Expert survey research, also known as the expert questionnaire, involves gathering research material through a structured questionnaire and obtaining responses from participants selected based on specific criteria by the researcher. It is important to highlight that the expert survey represents a distinctive method that leverages the expertise and creativity of individuals who are authorities in a particular field (Magruk, 2005). Moreover, it is assumed that respondents who are professionally accomplished and possess expert knowledge can provide insightful analytical suggestions. Their professional expertise and ability to envision realistic scenarios enable them to offer valuable forecasts regarding the development of situations within specific domains of economic and social reality (Babbie, 2004; Churchill, 2002).

Expert surveys were conducted in May-July 2024 (questionnaires were distributed online).

3.3. Results analysis phase

The analysis of the collected data was based on statistical analysis including descriptive measures such as arithmetic mean, dominant, minimum value, maximum value and range (Ręklewski, 2020):

- Arithmetic average is the sum of the value of variable of all units of the studied population divided by the number of units of the population.
- The dominant is the value of the variable that is the most frequent (dominant, typical) in the studied community. The dominant is called a modal value or mode.
- The minimum value of recorded responses in accordance with the adopted scale.
- The maximum value of the recorded responses in accordance with the adopted scale.
- The range is the difference between the maximum and minimum.

The technique of purposeful sampling was used. The selection criteria for the study were extensive practical experience in the field of functioning of logistics processes, logistics management, supply chains, as well as enterprise development management, development and implementation of enterprise development strategies. 48 experts from Poland took part in the study. Due to the subject of the study, the number of participants was not selected as representative. However, due to the importance of expert opinion, significant added value of research results can be indicated.

4. RESULTS ANALYSIS

A total of 48 deliberate selected experts took part in the study. The criterion for selecting experts was extensive practical experience in the field of functioning of logistics processes, logistics management, supply chains, as well as enterprise development management, development and implementation of enterprise development strategies., sustainable transport.

The largest percentage of experts (43,75%) were medium-sized commercial organizations (employment from 50 to 249 employees). Moreover, 27,08% in small entities (employment from 10 to 49 employees), 20,83% in large enterprises (employing more than 249 employees). The remaining 8,33% in commercial micro-organizations (employment of less than 10 employees). 39,58% of the experts were employed as manager, 20,83% as supervisor. Moreover 14,58% as business owners, 10,42% as specialists, 8,33% were management, and the remaining 6,25% as directors. Referring to the professional experience of experts in the current position, the largest percentage (62,50%) were employed more than 5 years, 29,17% were employed for 3 to 5 years and 8,33% for 1 to 3 years. Experts also assessed their own knowledge and experience on a scale of 1 to 5 (where 1 means a low level of knowledge and

experience, and 5 a high level of both knowledge and experience). The largest percentage indicated a grade 4 (52,08), then 5 (31,25%), and the remaining 16,67% indicated a grade of 3. There was no answer regarding the level 1 and 2 assessment. The average grade was 4,15.

In the analysis of the impact of logistics on individual dimensions of enterprise development, a scale from 1 to 5 was used (where 1 meant very little importance, and 5 meant very great importance).

The impact of logistics on enterprise development will be analyzed based on the dimensions of enterprise development potential relating to quantitative growth (expansion), qualitative changes, structure, human resources, technology, finances and ecological and social aspects (Matwiejczuk 2019; Strabyła, 2014; Świetlińska 2014) – table 1.

Table 1 Dimensions of enterprise development potential

Development dimensions		Average	Dominant	Maximal value	Minimal value	Range
1	Quantitative growth (expansion)	3,43	4,00	5	1	4
1.1.	Scaling up production: increasing production capacity by investing in new production lines, machinery, or hiring more workers	3,67	4,00	5	2	3
1.2.	Market development: expanding into new geographic markets, both domestic and international, to increase the number of customers	3,81	4,00	5	3	2
1.3.	Sales expansion: increasing marketing and sales efforts to increase sales volume	3,44	4,00	4	2	2
1.4.	Product expansion: introducing new products or services to meet a wider range of customer needs	2,81	3,00	4	1	3
2	Qualitative development	3,57	4,00	5	1	4
2.1.	Product innovation: introducing new, better products or services to the market that offer unique benefits to customers	2,69	3,00	4	1	3
2.2.	Quality management: improving production and operational processes to increase the quality of the products or services offered	4,17	4,00	5	3	2
2.3.	Brand reinforcement: building a stronger brand position by improving the	3,85	4,00	5	3	2

Development dimensions		Average	Dominant	Maximal value	Minimal value	Range
	image and increasing customer loyalty					
3	Structural development	3,15	3,00	5	2	3
3.1.	Organizational restructuring: changes in the organizational structure, such as creating new departments, centralizing or decentralizing management, introducing new positions	2,79	3,00	4	2	2
3.2.	Mergers and acquisitions: merging with or acquiring other companies to increase resources, markets, or know-how	2,73	3,00	4	2	2
3.3.	Change management: adapting to the changing business environment, which requires flexibility in management and the introduction of new operating models	3,92	4,00	5	3	2
4	Human resource development	3,17	3,00	5	1	4
4.1.	Employee training and development: investing in improving employee skills, which translates into their efficiency and innovation	3,06	3,00	4	2	2
4.2.	Organizational culture: building a strong organizational culture that supports cooperation, commitment, and innovation	3,50	4,00	5	2	3
4.3.	Talent management: implementing strategies that allow you to attract, develop, and retain key employees	2,96	3,00	5	1	4
5	Technological development	4,27	4,00	5	2	3
5.1.	Automation: introducing technologies that automate production and operational processes, which increases efficiency and reduces costs	4,35	4,00	5	3	2
5.2.	Digital transformation: applying new digital technologies in management, sales,	4,44	5,00	5	2	3

Development dimensions		Average	Dominant	Maximal value	Minimal value	Range
	marketing, and other areas of activity					
5.3.	Research and development (R&D) investments: allocating funds to research and development of new technologies that can give the company a competitive advantage	4,02	4,00	5	2	3
6	Financial development	3,40	3,00	5	3	2
6.1.	Raising capital: increasing financial resources by issuing shares, bonds, taking out loans, or acquiring investors	3,10	3,00	4	2	2
6.2.	Cost management: optimizing operating and production costs to increase profitability	3,77	4,00	5	2	3
6.3.	Investment strategies: investing in internal or external development, e.g. by purchasing new technologies or expanding into new markets	3,33	3,00	4	2	2
7	Ecological and social development	3,58	4,00	5	2	3
7.1.	Sustainable development: implementing business practices that minimize negative impacts on the natural environment	3,79	4,00	5	3	2
7.2.	Corporate social responsibility (CSR): engaging in activities that bring social benefits and improve the company's image in the eyes of customers and business partners	3,04	3,00	5	2	3
7.3.	Risk management: developing strategies that will minimize the risk associated with the company's impact on the environment and society	3,90	4,00	5	2	3

Source: own elaboration

The analysis of the research results highlights the various ways logistics influences the development of an enterprise across multiple dimensions. Closer examination of these dimensions based on the data provided is presented below.

Quantitative Growth (Expansion) (average: 3.43, dominant: 4.00). Logistics plays a fundamental role in facilitating quantitative growth, particularly in scaling up

production (3.67) and market development (3.81). Efficient logistics systems enable enterprises to expand production capacity by ensuring timely delivery of materials and products. Additionally, logistics supports geographical market expansion by optimizing supply chain processes to reach new domestic and international markets. However, the impact of logistics on product expansion (2.81) is less dominant, indicating that introducing new products may require more than logistical improvements alone.

Qualitative Development (average: 3.57, dominant: 4.00). Logistics significantly contributes to qualitative development, particularly in quality management (4.17), where the enhancement of operational processes leads to higher product quality and customer satisfaction. Although product innovation (2.69) has a lower average, streamlined logistics can facilitate rapid prototyping and distribution of new products, efficiently reinforcing brand positioning (3.85) by improving service delivery.

Structural Development (average: 3.15, dominant: 3.00). The role of logistics in structural development is evident in change management (3.92), as flexibility in supply chains allows organizations to adapt to evolving business environments. However, logistics has a moderate influence on organizational restructuring (2.79) and mergers and acquisitions (2.73), suggesting that while logistics supports operational shifts, the strategic decision-making component remains critical.

Human Resource Development (average: 3.17, dominant: 3.00). Logistics indirectly affects human resource development by promoting organizational culture (3.50) that values efficiency and cooperation, crucial for nurturing a competent workforce. Moreover, effective logistics can enhance training and development programs (3.06) by facilitating access to necessary resources, although its impact on talent management (2.96) is less pronounced, showing room for strategic integration.

Technological Development (average: 4.27, dominant: 4.00). Logistics is integral to technological development, particularly in automation (4.35) and digital transformation (4.44). Implementing cutting-edge logistics solutions like automated warehouses and digital platforms enhances operational efficiency and reduces costs. Research and development investments (4.02) are supported by logistical frameworks that enable rapid experimentation and deployment of new technologies.

Financial Development (average: 3.40, dominant: 3.00). Logistics influences financial development by supporting cost management (3.77), helping optimize production and operating costs through efficient supply chain management. While logistics supports financial strategies through cost reduction, it plays a less direct role in raising capital (3.10) and investment strategies (3.33), indicating that financial instruments and strategic investment decisions are separately driven by fiscal management.

Ecological and Social Development (average: 3.58, dominant: 4.00). Logistics contributes to ecological and social development by enabling sustainable practices (3.79) and effective risk management (3.90). By optimizing supply chains to minimize environmental impact, logistics aligns with corporate social responsibility (CSR) goals, though its role in CSR initiatives (3.04) is less direct and may require broader strategic involvement to maximize social benefits.

The visualization of the results is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2 Visualization of results in relation to the impact of logistics on the analyzed dimensions of enterprise development

Source: own elaboration

5. DISCUSSION

As Matwiejczuk (2019) points out concept of logistics is increasingly becoming a central element in management. The growing significance of logistics is primarily associated with its managerial aspects, which influence not only the shaping and development of a company's strategic capabilities but also the modernization of business models and the implementation of operational strategies and programs. By leveraging the potential found in logistical resources, capabilities, and competencies, it is possible to enhance relevant, broadly defined strategic potentials related to the overall activities of the enterprise.

In turn, Padlowska (2011), based on research conducted in the SME sector, showed that companies increasingly attach importance to the significance of logistics and in many ways, usually individual and tailored to the needs and specifics of the organization, improve logistics management processes and subsystems. This is one of the elements that can stimulate the development of enterprises.

According to the research of Ceniga and Sukalov (2019) environmental protection has emerged as a significant concern, leading to the necessity of integrating it into business objectives rather than viewing it merely as a gesture of goodwill. There are already numerous solutions available worldwide that encourage companies to alter their practices and invest resources effectively. Transport, as a key component of logistics, is one of the largest contributors to pollution. The gradual shift towards green logistics serves as a solid foundation for businesses, enabling them to achieve cost reductions, enhance competitiveness, improve market reputation, and potentially

benefit from tax incentives or other government rewards. The significance of green logistics extends beyond the optimization of logistics processes; it is also driven by increasing legislative requirements regarding the use of reusable packaging, waste management, and other materials. Additionally, the rising importance of green logistics promotes a sustainable mindset among managers, who are increasingly prioritizing ecological considerations alongside traditional economic metrics in their strategic decisions.

The analysis conducted by Aćimović, Mijušković and Bugarčić (2022) emphasizes the significant role of logistics in the growth and performance of enterprises, highlighting two key dimensions: "hard" and "soft" logistics. It has been established that improvements in both dimensions positively influence business performance, with the "soft" component demonstrating a more profound impact on overall success. This finding underscores the importance of enhancing the quality of logistics services in the Republic of Serbia, particularly in customs procedures, which can elevate the quality of the broader business environment. The continuous development of physical infrastructure also plays a vital role in enhancing the domestic business landscape. The research confirms that the national logistics system—comprising both its dimensions—should be recognized as a critical factor in business development within the national economy.

6. CONCLUSION

Logistics plays a strategic role in enterprise development by optimizing operational processes and increasing cost efficiency. First and foremost, efficient logistics systems enable companies to deliver products to customers more quickly and accurately, which directly enhances customer satisfaction and helps build long-term business relationships. Satisfied customers are more likely to return, increasing revenue stability and supporting further growth of the company.

With technological innovations such as warehouse automation and advanced supply chain management systems, companies can manage their resources more effectively, minimizing costs associated with inventory and transportation. This allows for better demand forecasting and flexible responses to changing market conditions, which is crucial in a dynamically evolving business environment.

Moreover, logistics supports expansion into new markets through effective planning and execution of international delivery operations. This expands the customer base and increases market share, contributing to company growth. Efficient logistics strategies can also influence the company's innovation, enabling the development of new products and services that better meet customer needs.

Therefore, logistics not only supports the day-to-day operation of companies but also serves as a crucial component of their long-term development strategy, impacting competitiveness, profitability, and adaptability in a changing business landscape.

The research results underscore the pivotal role that logistics plays in the development of enterprises across several dimensions. In terms of quantitative growth, logistics significantly aids in scaling up production and expanding markets by ensuring the efficient delivery of materials and products, though its influence on

product expansion is limited. In qualitative development, logistics excels in improving quality management, thereby enhancing product quality and customer satisfaction, and supports brand reinforcement. Structurally, logistics proves critical in facilitating change management, allowing organizations to adapt flexibly to shifting business climates, but its impact on organizational restructuring and mergers is moderate. For human resource development, logistics supports the cultivation of a productive organizational culture and facilitates training, though its effect on talent management is less substantial. Technologically, logistics is essential, driving advances through automation and digital transformation, and strengthening R&D efforts. Financial development benefits from logistics through efficient cost management, although its role in capital raising and investment strategies is indirect. Lastly, logistics is aligned with ecological and social development, fostering sustainable practices and effective risk management to meet corporate social responsibility objectives, albeit with potential for greater strategic integration.

The limitation of the conducted research is that the results are based on a group of experts that is not representative. Therefore, the findings cannot be generalized to the entire relationship between logistics and company development in the real economy. However, due to the high level of professional knowledge of the experts, the results can serve as a basis for decision-making and as a starting point for more in-depth research on a larger group of experts or a representative sample of companies.

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